

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

Programme	EU4HEALTH
Project number	101080009
Acronym	CAN.HEAL
Start Date	1 Nov 2022
Duration	30 months

Deliverable information

WP	14
Deliverable related number	14.2
Deliverable number	44
Deliverable name	Final version of the recommendations
Deliverable Description	The deliverable provides the final set of recommendations for the adoption of personalised approaches into EU health system, which will be developed following a co-creation approach ensured by a strong stakeholder engagement done in collaboration with WP2. The recommendations will be developed after a Delphi consultation with Key Stakeholders (in collaboration with WP2) and public discussion with the main institutional health bodies (Health Ministries, National Health Institutes, Cancer Center). Recommendations' target audience are policy and decision makers, healthcare professionals.
Recommendations' target audience	Policy and decision makers, healthcare professionals.
Lead Beneficiary	UCSC
Type	R
Dissemination level	PU
Version	1.2
Due Date	30/04/2025
Delivery Date	30/04/2025
Approval Date	

Revision History			
Version	Date	Comments	Partner
1.0	18/04/2025	Suggestions related the results of the MTB section	Roberta Pastorino, UCSC
1.1	22/04/2025	Suggestions aimed at improving the overall structure, text and formatting of the document	Stefania Boccia, UCSC

Authors	
Name	Partner
Abdelrahman Taha	UCSC
Tommaso Osti	UCSC
Luigi Russo	UCSC
Eleonora Pascucci	UCSC
Erika Giacobini	UCSC
Nicolò Lentini	UCSC
Alessandra Maio	UCSC
Alessandra Sabatelli	UCSC
Roberta Pastorino	UCSC
Angelo Maria Pezzullo	UCSC
Stefania Boccia	UCSC

Contributors
Inge van Klink, Suzanne Onstwedder, J. Matt McCrary, Lara Andreoli, Jeroen van Rooij, Lies Lahousse, Anke Bergmann, Sowmiya Moorthie, Peter Devilee, Neeme Tõnisson, Antoine De Pauw, Harry De Koning, Martina Cornel, Antonella Cardone, Paolo GiorgiRossi, Simon Joose, Julien Masliah Planchon, Jirsa Jaroslav, Ana Molina Barcelo, Nicola Normanno, Gennaro Daniele, Philippa Brice, Paula Romeo, Patrizio Giacomini, Maud Kamal, Philippe Aftimos, Torben Frøstrup Hansen, Christophe le Torneau, Lars Bullinger, Olga Blau, Nikolas von Bubnoff, Gennaro Ciliberto, Ruggero De Maria Marchiano, Luca Mazzarella, Paolo Marchetti, Tormod Kyrre Guren, Hege Russnes, Gerrit A. Meijer, Hans Gelderblom, Iwona Ługowska, Ernest Nadal, Eva Jolly

Table of contents

List of abbreviations	6
Executive Summary	10
1. WP14 overview and objectives	14
2. Scope of the Deliverable	15
2.1 Polygenic Risk Scores (PRSs) in Breast Cancer (BC) screening	16
2.2 Adoption of Liquid Biopsy (LB) in the treatment of metastatic Colorectal Cancer (mCRC).....	16
2.3 A policy brief of Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs): Clinical Utility and Impact on Patient Care	18
3. Method	20
3.1 Co-creation with stakeholders.....	20
3.2 GRADE Evidence-to-Decision framework	21
4. PRS in Breast Cancer Screening	23
4.1 Background and Rationale	23
4.1.1 Current challenges in breast cancer screening	23
4.1.2 Role and potential of PRS	25
4.2 Methodology	27
4.2.1 Research Question and PICO Framework	27
4.2.2 Systematic review on the clinical utility of PRS-enhanced screening	27
4.2.2.1 Search strategy and eligibility criteria	27
4.2.2.2 Study Selection.....	28
4.2.2.3 Data extraction	28
4.2.2.4 Quality of evidence.....	29
4.2.2.5 Statistical analysis	30
4.2.3 Systematic reviews on the implementation aspects of PRS-enhanced screening	30
4.3 Results	31
4.3.1 Clinical utility of PRS-enhanced screening	31
4.3.1.1 Characteristics of Included Studies	32
4.3.1.2 Characteristics of risk prediction models.....	32
4.3.1.3 Benefits & harms	34
4.3.2 Implementation aspects of PRS-enhanced screening	44
4.3.2.1 Acceptability.....	44
4.3.2.2 Equity	45
4.3.2.3 Feasibility	46

4.3.2.4 <u>Cost-effectiveness</u>	46
<u>4.4 GRADE EtD experts' panel</u>	47
4.4.1 <u>First panel meeting</u>	49
4.4.2 <u>Second panel meeting</u>	51
4.4.3 <u>Third panel meeting</u>	53
4.4.4 <u>Evidence rating process (first round)</u>	56
4.4.5 <u>Recommendations & additional considerations (final consensus round)</u>	58
<u>4.5 Final Recommendations</u>	60
4.5.1 <u>Justification</u>	61
4.5.2 <u>Subgroup considerations</u>	64
4.5.3 <u>Implementation considerations</u>	65
4.5.4 <u>Monitoring & evaluation</u>	65
4.5.5 <u>Research priorities</u>	67
<u>5. Liquid Biopsy (LB) in Metastatic Colorectal Cancer (mCRC)</u>	67
<u>5.1 Background and Rationale</u>	68
5.1.1 <u>Introduction to liquid biopsy and the challenge of metastatic Colorectal Cancer</u>	68
5.1.2 <u>Potential applications of liquid biopsy in Cancer Care</u>	69
5.1.3 <u>Role of the experts' panel</u>	70
<u>5.2 Genotyping: advancing precision medicine in mCRC</u>	72
5.2.1 <u>Approved use</u>	73
5.2.2 <u>Evaluating clinical utility in mCRC Management</u>	77
5.2.3 <u>Results</u>	77
5.2.4 <u>Recommendations</u>	80
<u>5.3 Predicting therapy response: the possible role of liquid biopsy</u>	82
5.3.1 <u>Evaluating clinical utility in mCRC Management</u>	83
5.3.2 <u>Results</u>	84
5.3.3 <u>Towards a possible future role for LB in Clinical Practice</u>	87
5.3.4 <u>Ongoing clinical studies</u>	89
5.3.5 <u>Recommendations</u>	90
<u>5.4 Other domains: Acceptability, Equity, Feasibility, Use of Resources</u>	91
5.4.1 <u>Methods</u>	92
5.4.2 <u>Results</u>	94
5.4.3 <u>Recommendations</u>	98

<u>6. Molecular Tumor Boards (MTB)s: Clinical Utility and Impact on Patient Care</u>	102
<u>6.1 Background and Rationale</u>	103
6.1.1 <u>MTBs: definition and scope</u>	103
6.1.2 <u>MTB role in cancer care: state of the art</u>	103
<u>6.2 Systematic review and meta-analysis of MTBs impact on patients' outcomes</u>	105
6.2.1 <u>Methods</u>	105
6.2.2 <u>Results: organizational aspects of MTBs</u>	108
6.2.3 <u>Results: clinical impact of MTBs</u>	110
<u>6.3 Narrative review of MTBs implementation aspects</u>	117
6.3.1 <u>Methods</u>	118
6.3.2 <u>Results: equity, acceptability, feasibility, resource use</u>	119
<u>6.4 Delphi consultation</u>	134
6.4.1 <u>Experts interview</u>	135
6.4.2 <u>Results</u>	138
6.4.2.1 <u>First round</u>	138
6.4.2.2 <u>Second round</u>	145
6.4.2.3 <u>Consensus statements</u>	150
6.4.3 <u>Recommendations</u>	151
<u>6.5 Policy brief</u>	153
<u>7. Conclusions</u>	157
7.1 <u>Summary of key insights</u>	158
7.2 <u>Roadmap for research and policy implementation</u>	158
<u>8. Supplementary materials</u>	161
<u>9. References</u>	273

List of abbreviations

- **CAN.HEAL:** Cancer and Health Genomics Platform
- **EU:** European Union
- **WP:** Work Package
- **BC:** Breast Cancer
- **cfmiRNA:** Cell-Free Micro RNA
- **GWAS:** Genome-Wide Association Studies
- **mCRC:** Metastatic Colorectal Cancer
- **NGS:** Next-Generation Sequencing
- **PRS:** Polygenic Risk Score
- **CRC:** Colorectal Cancer
- **ctDNA:** Circulating Tumor DNA
- **CTC:** Circulating Tumor Cells
- **ddPCR:** Droplet Digital PCR
- **KRAS:** Kirsten Rat Sarcoma Viral Oncogene Homolog
- **NRAS:** Neuroblastoma RAS Viral Oncogene Homolog
- **BRAF:** B-Raf Proto-Oncogene, Serine/Threonine Kinase
- **ACMG:** American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics
- **PICO:** Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes
- **GRADE:** Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation
- **EtD:** Evidence to Decision
- **ISPOR:** International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research
- **AMCP:** Academy of Managed Care Pharmacy
- **NPC:** National Pharmaceutical Council
- **eMERGE:** Electronic Medical Records and Genomics
- **PRIMED:** Polygenic Risk Modeling for Diverse Populations
- **IVDR:** In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation
- **IVD:** In Vitro Diagnostic
- **PMPF:** Post-Market Performance Follow-up
- **CDx:** Companion Diagnostic
- **EHDS:** European Health Data Space
- **LB:** Liquid Biopsy
- **MTB(s):** Molecular Tumor Board(s)

- **RCT:** Randomized Controlled Trial
- **QALY(s):** Quality-Adjusted Life Year(s)
- **DALY(s):** Disability-Adjusted Life Year(s)
- **LYG:** Life Years Gained
- **PRISMA:** Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
- **ESCAT:** ESMO Scale for Clinical Actionability of molecular Targets
- **FH:** Family History
- **SoC:** Standard of Care
- **PBCRA:** Personal Breast Cancer Risk Assessment
- **ICER:** Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio
- **PPA:** Positive Percent Agreement
- **NPA:** Negative Percent Agreement
- **NSCLC:** Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer
- **ESMO:** European Society for Medical Oncology
- **MSI:** Microsatellite Instability
- **EGFR:** Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor
- **ORR(s):** Objective Response Rate(s)
- **OS:** Overall Survival
- **PFS:** Progression-Free Survival
- **DOR:** Duration of Response
- **IHC:** Immunohistochemistry
- **FISH:** Fluorescence In Situ Hybridization
- **RECIST:** Response Evaluation Criteria In Solid Tumours
- **RoB:** Risk of Bias
- **RR(s):** Risk Ratio(s)
- **HR(s):** Hazard Ratio(s)
- **OR(s):** Odds Ratio(s)
- **RFS: Relapse-Free Survival**
- **FPR:** False Positive Rate
- **AUC:** Area Under the Curve
- **MoDA:** Measures of Diagnostic Accuracy
- **PCC:** Population, Concept, Context
- **EQA:** External Quality Assessment

- **QoL:** Quality of Life
- **HTA:** Health Technology Assessment
- **WES:** Whole-Exome Sequencing
- **DCR:** Disease Control Rate
- **CR:** Complete Response
- **PR:** Partial Response
- **SD:** Stable Disease
- **PD:** Progressive Disease
- **CB:** Clinical Benefit
- **ASCO:** American Society of Clinical Oncology
- **CGP:** Comprehensive Genomic Profiling
- **CGH:** Comparative Genomic Hybridization
- **WGS:** Whole Genome Sequencing
- **ECOG:** Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group
- **GI:** Gastrointestinal
- **IRCCS:** Istituto di Ricovero e Cura a Carattere Scientifico
- **NSCLC:** Non-small cell lung carcinoma
- **AI:** Artificial Intelligence
- **SOP(s):** Standard Operating Procedure(s)
- **FAIR:** Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
- **MRI:** Magnetic Resonance Imaging
- **BOADICEA:** Breast and Ovarian Analysis of Disease Incidence and Carrier Estimation Algorithm
- **HRQoL:** Health-Related Quality of Life
- **CI(s):** Confidence Interval(s)
- **OIS:** Optimal Information Size
- **PYRS:** Person-Years of Survival
- **MMAT:** Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool
- **NHS:** National Health Service
- **CISNET:** Cancer Intervention and Surveillance Modeling Network
- **USPSTF:** U.S. Preventive Services Task Force
- **ACR:** American College of Radiology

Deliverable 14.2 – Final version of the recommendations - Version 1.2

- **ACS:** American Cancer Society
- **ESR1:** Estrogen Receptor 1
- **BRCA1/2:** Breast Cancer gene 1/2
- **ASR:** age-standardized mortality rate
- **N.R.:** Not Reported
- **N.E.:** Not Estimable
- **N.C.:** Not Considered
- **SNC:** Central Nervous System
- **CUP:** Cancer of Unknown Primary
- **GIST:** gastrointestinal stromal tumor
- **TAT:** turnaround time

Executive Summary

Recommendations on the use of polygenic risk scores in breast cancer screening

As we await findings from large trials, we conditionally recommend that national or sub-national health systems in the European Union (EU) explore the integration of PRS into breast cancer screening programs through piloting programmes, carefully designed prospective research projects and controlled implementation studies. If findings from large trials or pilot implementation studies leave uncertainties critical to the EU context, funding a well-designed Phase III RCT is justified to ensure that any shift in screening policy is backed by robust evidence on efficacy and safety.

This recommendation is **conditional** because the **overall certainty of evidence is low**, the **balance between benefits and harms is strategy- and context-dependent**, and the **acceptability, feasibility, and equity implications** of PRS-enhanced screening vary across settings and populations.

- **For policymakers and health system leaders:** PRS should not yet be adopted into routine screening practice at scale. Instead, governments and public health authorities are encouraged to support **prospective research projects** and implementation **studies** that allow for localized learning, continuous evaluation, and iterative adaptation.
- **For researchers:** Particular attention should be given to studying how PRS-enhanced screening impacts different socio-economic and ethnic subgroups to ensure equitable benefits. Beyond public perceptions, research should prioritize implementation strategies, effective communication models, and integration pathways for PRS-enhanced screening
- **For clinicians and healthcare professionals:** The integration of PRS into shared decision-making around screening should be approached with caution and ideally supported by risk counseling, clear **communication tools**, and established **data protection frameworks**
- **For the public:** Individuals should be informed that PRS-enhanced screening is still in a **research and development phase**, and its benefits and risks are not yet fully understood. Public trust and transparent communication are essential.

Recommendations on the use of liquid Biopsy in the management of metastatic colorectal cancer

As we await results from ongoing clinical studies, we conditionally recommend that national or sub-national health systems in the European Union (EU) explore the integration of liquid biopsy (LB) using circulating tumour DNA (ctDNA) in the management of metastatic colorectal cancer (mCRC). This exploration should involve pilot projects, prospective research studies, and controlled implementation programmes designed with rigorous methodological standards.

Genotyping: Liquid biopsy for tumour genotyping in mCRC has demonstrated high analytical validity, capturing tumour genetic heterogeneity and clonal evolution effectively. CtDNA genotyping is already recognized as a viable option for key biomarkers but only in cases when tissue biopsy is unavailable, inadequate or delayed. Compared to traditional tissue biopsies, LBs provide significant advantages, including patient comfort, simplified procedures, and rapid turnaround times. However, despite these promising aspects, the clinical utility of ctDNA as a complementary or alternative tool requires further validation through additional clinical studies.

Monitoring Therapeutic Response: ctDNA-based LB also shows considerable promise in monitoring therapeutic responses, offering real-time insights into treatment efficacy and emerging resistance mutations. Preliminary evidence suggests a significant correlation between ctDNA levels and clinical outcomes such as overall survival (OS), progression-free survival (PFS), and objective response rates (ORRs). Nonetheless, clinical evidence that changing or escalating therapy on the basis of ctDNA kinetics improve therapeutic outcomes remains limited and warrants further investigation.

- **For policymakers and health system leaders:** At this stage, ctDNA-based LB should not yet be universally adopted into routine clinical practice for mCRC. Instead, they should support structured research and implementation studies separately targeting the roles of LB in tumour genotyping and therapeutic monitoring, addressing feasibility, equity, and resource utilisation concerns.
- **For researchers:** There is an urgent need for additional prospective studies and implementation trials to evaluate the clinical utility of LB for both genotyping and therapeutic monitoring. Research should focus explicitly on clarifying the specific roles and benefits of ctDNA in guiding therapeutic decisions, assessing response to therapy, and understanding mechanisms of treatment resistance.

- **For clinicians and healthcare professionals:** Clinical integration of ctDNA analysis should be approached carefully. Interpretation of ctDNA results should involve multidisciplinary teams, including oncology specialists and molecular pathologists, to ensure accuracy and clinical relevance.
- **For the public:** Patients should be transparently informed about the applications of ctDNA-based LB, including genotyping and monitoring therapeutic responses, and should be informed that while promising, these technologies remain the subject of ongoing research. Public communication should clearly outline current benefits, limitations, and uncertainties to ensure informed patient engagement and trust.

A policy brief on Molecular Tumor Boards: shaping the future of cancer care.

We recommend that national and regional health systems across the European Union (EU) integrate MTBs into oncology care pathways through targeted investments, structured organizational frameworks, and alignment with clinical and genomic innovation strategies.

While the clinical value of MTBs in guiding personalized cancer care is increasingly recognized, their effective integration into healthcare systems requires careful consideration of organizational, logistical, and contextual factors. Rather than promoting a single implementation model, this work advocates for harmonized core principles that can be adapted to local realities, ensuring that MTBs are scalable, accessible, and sustainable across diverse European settings.

- **For policymakers and health system leaders:** MTBs should be recognized as a strategic investment to strengthen precision oncology. National and sub-national cancer plans should include MTBs as a core element, with dedicated funding for clinical sequencing, decision-support systems, and workforce development. Policies should promote regular, virtual meetings with multidisciplinary participation and ensure that genomic data can be interpreted and acted upon in a timely and standardized way across institutions.
- **For researchers and data scientists:** Further research is needed to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of MTBs, their impact on health outcomes, and their scalability across diverse healthcare settings. Comparative studies and implementation research should address barriers related to data interoperability, clinical integration, and resource allocation. Efforts to standardize genomic panels and evidence thresholds (e.g. ESCAT and OncoKB) will also support reproducibility and equity.
- **For clinicians and MTB members:** Clear protocols should define the workflow for case submission, data preparation, and decision-making. Clinicians should refer patients using standardized tools and participate in case discussions alongside molecular biologists, geneticists, pathologists, and trial navigators. Clinical records should include detailed, structured reports on molecular alterations and treatment options, with distinctions between somatic and germline findings.
- **For patients and the public:** MTBs offer an opportunity to access innovative therapies and personalized treatment plans. However, inclusion is currently limited to specific clinical and molecular criteria. Transparent communication is essential to explain what MTBs are, how patients are selected, and what treatment options may emerge. Expanding access while maintaining rigorous standards will be key to fostering public trust.

1. WP14 overview and objectives

Work Package (WP) 14 is titled “(Healthcare System Implementation)” serves as the culminating component of the CAN.HEAL project, in order to translate the research findings into actionable strategies for integrating genomic medicine into European healthcare systems. Led by Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC, Italy) with collaboration from Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu (RIVM, Netherlands), this WP focuses on bridging the gap between scientific innovation and real-world clinical practice. Its primary objective is to develop a framework for implementing personalized cancer prevention, diagnosis, and treatment approaches across EU member states, ensuring alignment with existing healthcare infrastructures and policies.

The WP operates through four key tasks. Task 14.1 synthesizes evidence from other WPs (particularly WP6, WP10, and WP12) to identify success factors and gaps in current personalized medicine approaches. This comprehensive review assesses clinical utility, cost-effectiveness, and scalability of genomic technologies in cancer care. Task 14.2 designs the conceptual framework for the Medical and Public Health Cancer Genomics Platform, a centralized hub to aggregate and disseminate project outcomes, best practices, and tools for healthcare providers and policymakers. This platform will incorporate data from national initiatives like France's Genomic Medicine 2025 and Belgium's Precision Oncology program.

Task 14.3 develops a modeling tool to forecast the impact of implementing genomic-based cancer care pathways (e.g., for BC), incorporating clinical, economic, and patient-reported outcomes. This tool will leverage real-world data from WP9's precision oncology initiatives and WP11's NGS standardization efforts. Finally, Task 14.4 consists in releasing Recommendations Development for Sustainable Implementation, and it represents the pivotal final phase of WP14, where evidence from across the CAN.HEAL project is translated into actionable policy guidance for EU member states.

The WP 14 collaborates closely with the 1+ Million Genomes Initiative and EU Cancer Mission to ensure alignment with broader European genomic data-sharing efforts. By integrating ethical (WP12), educational (WP13), and HTA (WP3) perspectives, WP14 ensures the project's legacy will be a sustainable, equitable adoption of genomics in EU cancer care systems. Its outcomes will directly inform national cancer plans and the evolving European Health Data Space (EHDS), positioning CAN.HEAL as a cornerstone for precision oncology implementation across Europe.

2. Scope of the Deliverable

According to the Grant Agreement, Deliverable 14.2 was aimed to provide the final set of recommendations for the adoption of Personalised approaches into EU health system, which will be developed following a co-creation approach ensured by a strong stakeholder engagement done in collaboration with WP2. The recommendations will be developed after a Delphi consultation with Key Stakeholders (in collaboration with WP2) and public discussion with the main institutional health bodies (Health Ministries, National Health Institutes, Cancer Centers...).

The activities of the task 14.4 around three implementation pillars: (1) Integration of Polygenic Risk Scores (PRS) in Breast Cancer (BC) Screening (2) Adoption of Liquid Biopsy (LB) in the treatment of Metastatic Colorectal Cancer (mCRC) (3) Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs): clinical utility and impact on patient care.

The paragraphs below explain the reasoning behind the selection of the three aforementioned topics as the core output of the present deliverable.

2.1 Polygenic Risk Scores (PRS) in Breast Cancer (BC) Screening

PRS represent a cornerstone of CAN.HEAL's precision medicine approach, with three key WPs synergistically advancing their development and implementation: WP5 (PRSs and Decision Support Tools - led by University of Tartu) serves as the primary driver for PRS innovation, with four focused objectives: (1) Evaluating the portability of PRS for breast, prostate, colorectal cancer (CRC) and melanoma across EU populations using GWAS data; (2) Developing Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enhanced decision support systems that integrate PRS with environmental factors; (3) Creating population screening guidelines for high-risk individuals; and (4) Establishing telegenetics protocols for PRS-based counseling. The WP validates PRS performance in diverse populations through its collaboration with WP4's biobanks. WP4 (Biobanking - led by Erasmus MC) provides the essential infrastructure for PRS validation by: (1) Creating harmonized genetic datasets from patient cohorts across 17 countries; (2) Processing samples through centralized, accredited pipelines; and (3) Aligning data with the 1+ Million Genomes Initiative reference datasets. WP4's deliverables directly enable WP5's population-specific PRS adjustments. WP6 (Building Clinical Utility - led by KU Leuven) translates PRS findings into clinical practice through: (1) Demonstrating utility in pediatric leukemia (with MHH-Germany); (2) Implementing PRS-enhanced risk stratification in hereditary BC

families; and (3) Developing an actionable knowledge platform integrating monogenic and polygenic risk data. WP6's clinical pilots inform WP5's decision support tools.

The WPs connect through a continuous knowledge loop: WP4's biobanking enables robust PRS development in WP5, which WP6 clinically validates, with findings cycling back to refine WP5's algorithms. Together, they address the full PRS pipeline from population genomics (WP4) to risk modeling (WP5) to clinical implementation (WP6), ensuring PRS tools are both scientifically valid and clinically actionable across diverse EU healthcare systems.

2.2 Adoption of Liquid Biopsy in the treatment of Metastatic Colorectal Cancer (mCRC)

The CAN.HEAL project establishes a comprehensive framework for implementing LB technology in mCRC management through three tightly interconnected WPs. This integrated approach ensures a seamless transition from technical validation to clinical application and eventual health system adoption, with each WP playing a distinct yet complementary role in advancing LB for mCRC care.

At the foundation, WP11 (NGS & Liquid Biopsy - Led by UKE/ELBS & CERTH) focuses on establishing robust, standardized LB protocols specifically optimized for mCRC. This WP conducts rigorous multi-center ring trials across five EU laboratories to validate three critical LB analytes: cfDNA (analyzed through NGS and ddPCR), CTCs (using CellSearch and Parsortix platforms), and cfmiRNA. The validation process pays particular attention to mCRC-relevant biomarkers including KRAS, NRAS, and BRAF mutations, as well as MSI status detection. Beyond technical validation, WP11 develops comprehensive SOPs and a FAIR-compliant data framework to ensure reproducible LB results that can be effectively linked to clinical outcomes, forming the essential technical backbone for subsequent clinical implementation.

Building upon WP11's technical foundation, WP9 (Treatment & Follow-up - Led by Jessa Hospital) translates these LB assays into real-world mCRC patient management. Within Belgium's Precision Initiative, WP9 applies these validated LB tests to monitor over 1,000 cancer patients, with significant focus on mCRC cases. The WP tracks critical clinical correlations, such as ctDNA dynamics in relation to PFS and OS, while also evaluating how LB results influence therapeutic decisions in MTBs. A key example includes guiding anti-EGFR rechallenge strategies based on RAS mutation clearance patterns detected in serial LB testing. Importantly, WP9 generates essential real-world

evidence on the cost-effectiveness of LB monitoring in mCRC, providing crucial data for health technology assessments.

The clinical evidence generated by WP9 directly informs WP14 (Healthcare System Implementation - Led by UCSC), which focuses on overcoming systemic barriers to LB adoption in mCRC care pathways. WP14 utilizes the real-world outcomes from WP9 to develop value-based reimbursement models and create implementation roadmaps tailored to diverse EU healthcare systems. This WP works closely with key stakeholders including European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO), national cancer networks, regulators, and payers to integrate LB into clinical guidelines for mCRC management, addressing critical implementation challenges such as test standardization, pricing structures, and appropriate clinical use cases (e.g., first-line monitoring and recurrence detection).

The synergy between these WPs creates a continuous feedback loop that drives iterative improvement in LB technology and its clinical application for mCRC. WP9's clinical findings inform refinements to WP11's technical protocols, while WP14's policy insights help shape both the technical standards and clinical study designs to better align with health system requirements. This integrated approach positions CAN.HEAL to establish LB as a gold standard in mCRC management across Europe, offering a non-invasive alternative to tissue biopsies that enables more frequent monitoring, earlier detection of resistance mechanisms, and more personalized treatment strategies - ultimately aiming to improve patient outcomes while optimizing healthcare resource utilization.

2.3 A Policy Brief of Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs): Clinical Utility and Impact on Patient Care

The CAN.HEAL project establishes a comprehensive framework for implementing and optimizing MTBs across European healthcare systems through the coordinated efforts of strategically aligned WPs. This integrated, multi-WP approach ensures a complete pathway from MTB standardization to clinical implementation and health system integration, with each WP addressing a critical component of MTB development, operation, and sustainability. Within this framework, WP14 (Healthcare System Implementation – led by UCSC) focused on translating technical and clinical advancements into actionable, system-level recommendations for sustainable MTB implementation across diverse European contexts.

At the core of MTB development, WP8 (Diagnosis and Treatment Decision via MTB – led by Institut Curie) played a foundational role by mapping existing MTB structures and national initiatives, such

Deliverable 14.2 – Final version of the recommendations - Version 1.2

as France's Genomic Medicine 2025 and Belgium's Precision Oncology program. WP8 developed standardized, evidence-based guidelines encompassing patient selection, sample processing, molecular analysis, and clinical decision-making, with particular attention to complex cases like carcinomas of unknown primary and rare cancers. These efforts included the creation of harmonized bioinformatics pipelines for variant interpretation and recommendations for incorporating MTB findings into treatment decisions, including clinical trial matching.

Building upon WP8's clinical groundwork, WP10 (Oncology Decision Support Tools – led by Sciensano) developed the digital infrastructure needed to support and scale MTB operations across healthcare systems. By mapping existing decision support systems and integrating clinical and genomic data through platforms like cBioPortal, WP10 ensured that MTB workflows could be standardized while remaining adaptable to local contexts. The development of the EU-oncDST concept under WP10 exemplifies this effort, offering a flexible framework to support molecularly guided therapy decisions for conditions such as metastatic CRC and other solid tumors. Collaboration between WP8 and WP10 ensured that digital tools were closely aligned with clinical realities encountered during MTB case reviews.

WP14, leading the healthcare system implementation effort, worked closely with WP8 and WP10 to synthesize clinical, technical, and organizational elements into practical implementation models. Drawing on real-world data and national precision oncology initiatives mapped by WP9, WP14 developed tiered implementation strategies tailored to differences in genomic medicine maturity and health system capacity across member states. This included examining organizational models, economic sustainability, and workforce training needs in collaboration with WP13. WP14 also engaged national health authorities and professional societies to integrate MTBs into cancer care pathways and explore appropriate reimbursement mechanisms to support long-term sustainability.

A particularly valuable aspect of WP14's work was the development of recommendations for MTB implementation with a policy brief summary, through close collaboration with WPs 8, 9, and 10. Together, these WPs contributed to mapping existing MTBs and national initiatives across Europe, culminating in consortium-wide guidelines. A notable use case focused on MTBs for carcinoma of unknown origin served as a testing ground for shared strategies and evidence synthesis. WP14 worked in particular synergy with WP8, led by Institut Curie, to ensure alignment between clinical insights and policy-level recommendations.

This collaboration was operationalized through a series of joint meetings between UCSC and Institut Curie, where key components of the project were refined. These sessions provided critical feedback

on the systematic review protocol, the index and structure of the policy brief, and the identification of experts for the Delphi process. They also served as forums for discussing meta-analysis interpretations and finalizing the Delphi survey items. Experts from WPs 8, 9, and 10 contributed to the Delphi panel, bringing diverse perspectives from across leading European institutions.

Deliverables from WP8 were especially pivotal in informing the Delphi process, offering foundational data that guided the development of policy recommendations. These outputs continue to serve as essential references for advancing the implementation of MTBs both within and beyond the CAN.HEAL consortium. The iterative collaboration among WP8, WP10, and WP14 created a continuous cycle of improvement, where clinical guidelines informed digital tool development, technological solutions enabled standardized workflows, and implementation insights fed back into system refinement. This dynamic model ensures that CAN.HEAL's MTB framework remains clinically relevant, scalable, and sustainable, ultimately aiming to enhance access to precision oncology across Europe.

3. Method

3.1 Co-creation with stakeholders.

A core methodological feature of our work was our commitment to co-creation with stakeholders across the project's major thematic areas, PRS in BC screening, LB in mCRC, and MTBs. This co-creative approach was not only integral to the generation of evidence and tools but also essential to their relevance, uptake, and long-term sustainability within diverse European healthcare systems. Co-creation was implemented as both a design principle and an operational practice, embedded at all stages of the project from concept development to pilot implementation and policy translation.

Co-creation within CAN.HEAL involved a broad and multidisciplinary set of stakeholders, ensuring that diverse perspectives informed the project's scientific, clinical, and policy-oriented outputs. These stakeholders included: WP leaders and collaborators working on interconnected aspects of the same technology, who ensured scientific and technical coherence across the project. Experts internal to CAN.HEAL from various disciplines, genomics, oncology, health economics, bioinformatics, public health, and digital health, who contributed domain-specific knowledge to shape methodologies and interpretations. External stakeholders, including national and European regulators, public health authorities, professional societies (e.g., ESMO), HTA agencies, clinicians, laboratory directors,

patient representatives, and screening program coordinators, whose engagement grounded the project in real-world contexts. Cross-WP alliances, particularly among WPs working on related themes, fostered a dynamic knowledge loop and iterative refinement of tools and strategies.

Engagement methods included regular joint WP meetings, expert panels, surveys, collaborative protocol development, and Delphi consensus processes. These formats were used both to build shared understanding and to facilitate meaningful stakeholder input into key decisions.

The co-creation methodology contributed substantively to the robustness, relevance, and acceptability of the project's outputs. It ensured that the recommendations regarding PRS in BC screening, LB in mCRC or the MTB policy brief, were not developed in isolation, but rather emerged from a collective process shaped by technical feasibility, clinical need, ethical considerations, and system-level priorities.

This approach also promoted cross-pollination of insights between WPs, facilitated early identification of implementation barriers, and enabled agile adaptation to contextual variability across EU member states. Crucially, it fostered a sense of shared ownership and alignment among project partners and external stakeholders, enhancing the potential for long-term adoption and scale-up of precision oncology innovations. By embedding stakeholder co-creation into our methodological core, we ensured that CAN.HEAL innovations in cancer screening, diagnosis, and treatment are not only scientifically sound but also context-sensitive, implementable, and positioned for real-world impact.

3.2 The Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) Evidence to Decision (EtD) framework

Another core element of our methodological approach was the use of the GRADE EtD framework (*Figure 1*), originally developed by the GRADE Working Group. The framework is a systematic approach used to develop clinical guidelines and make healthcare decisions^{1,2}. It was designed to address the limitations of previous grading systems by separating the quality of evidence from the strength of recommendations. Its structured format guides multidisciplinary teams in evaluating the certainty of the evidence, weighing benefits and harms, considering resource use and cost-effectiveness, assessing equity and acceptability, and determining feasibility and implementation challenges. The EtD process begins with a rigorous synthesis of evidence drawn from systematic reviews, meta-analyses, real-world data, and expert consensus. The GRADE system³ evaluates the quality of evidence on a four-point scale: high, moderate, low, and very low. This assessment

considers factors such as study limitations, inconsistency of results, indirectness, imprecision, and publication bias. RCTs typically start as high-quality evidence but can be downgraded based on these factors, while observational studies start as low-quality evidence but can be upgraded if they show large effect sizes or other strengths.

Figure 1: GRADE EtD framework adapted from the GRADE Working Group³

This evidence is then organized into tailored EtD tables addressing each GRADE domain, which served as the basis for structured deliberation among a multidisciplinary group of stakeholders. These stakeholders included scientific and clinical experts from across the CAN.HEAL consortium and external experts, such as geneticists, oncologists, bioinformaticians, as well as patient advocates. This deliberative process allowed for the integration of not only the scientific and technical dimensions of the evidence but also the broader considerations that influence implementation in real-world settings, such as infrastructure needs, workforce capacity, ethical considerations, and population-level acceptability.

The GRADE EtD framework has been applied in various contexts, including health policymaking and coverage decisions. For instance, the European Commission has utilized the GRADE EtD framework to support decision-making processes involving multiple interventions⁴. Moreover, the

DECIDE (Developing and Evaluating Communication Strategies to Support Informed Decisions and Practice Based on Evidence) Project, funded by the EU, has developed GRADE EtD frameworks specifically for coverage decisions, highlighting its application in systematic and transparent decision-making processes⁵. This indicates that the framework is not only used for clinical guidelines but also for broader health policy and coverage decisions.

Overall, the use of the GRADE EtD framework ensure transparency in how evidence is interpreted, facilitate consensus among stakeholders with diverse perspectives, and promote the formulation of recommendations that are sensitive to issues of equity and system-level feasibility. It also provides a common methodological foundation across different WPs and technologies, supporting coherence and comparability in decision-making processes.

4. PRS in Breast Cancer Screening

PRS estimates individual risk for BC by aggregating multiple genetic variants, each weighted by their effect sizes as identified in genome-wide association studies (GWAS). These genetic variants account for a substantial portion of BC heritability, enhancing the precision of risk prediction models⁶⁻⁸. In principle, the integration of PRS into BC screening protocols might allow for a more personalized approach, identifying individuals at higher risk who may benefit from earlier and more frequent screening, while potentially reducing unnecessary interventions in those at lower risk^{9,10}. The American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics (ACMG) has noted that PRS can be combined with other risk factors, such as family history (FH) and pathogenic variants, to refine risk estimates and guide clinical management¹¹. Additionally, PRS has been shown to improve the predictive accuracy of existing risk models, such as the Tyrer-Cuzick and Gail models, by providing better discrimination and risk stratification¹². This topic is particularly timely and important as the field of personalized medicine continues to evolve, aiming to tailor prevention and treatment strategies to individual genetic profiles, thereby improving outcomes and optimizing healthcare resources¹³.

4.1 Background and Rationale

4.1.1 Current challenges in BC screening

BC screening plays a crucial role in early detection and improved outcomes, but it faces several challenges that limit its effectiveness and efficiency. Traditional screening methods, such as

mammography, have been instrumental in reducing BC-related mortality by detecting tumors at earlier, more treatable stages. Typically, guidelines recommend biennial mammography for women aged 50 to 74 years who are at average risk, with certain exceptions based on individual risk factors and country-specific guidelines. Studies have demonstrated that regular mammography screening can reduce BC mortality by approximately 20-30% in women aged 50-69 years^{14,15}. Additionally, digital breast tomosynthesis and other advanced imaging modalities have been developed to improve detection rates, particularly in women with dense breast tissue or a strong FH of the disease¹⁶. While these screening methods have proven beneficial, their effectiveness can be influenced by factors such as breast density, tumor characteristics, and screening frequency. For instance, women with dense breasts may benefit from supplemental MRI, which has been shown to reduce interval cancer risk¹⁷.

Despite the benefits of screening, the current paradigm of BC screening has significant limitations in terms of both sensitivity and specificity. One major concern is the high rate of false positives, where benign abnormalities are misclassified as malignant, leading to unnecessary biopsies, increased patient anxiety, and higher healthcare costs. Conversely, false negatives, particularly in women with dense breast tissues, pose a significant risk, as tumors may go undetected, delaying diagnosis and reducing treatment success. Furthermore, current screening guidelines are predominantly age-based, failing to account for individual risk factors such as genetic predisposition, FH, or other personal health considerations. This one-size-fits-all approach can result in both over-screening for low-risk individuals, leading to unnecessary interventions and psychological distress, and under-screening for high-risk individuals, delaying early detection and treatment^{18,19}. Traditional screening methods, such as mammography, also have limitations in sensitivity and specificity, particularly for women with dense breast tissue, further contributing to the challenges of false positives, false negatives, and overdiagnosis.

Addressing the challenges through personalized approaches and advanced imaging technologies is essential steps towards improving the accuracy and outcomes of BC screening programs. Incorporating PRS into screening protocols might offer a potential solution by providing a more precise risk assessment based on multiple genetic variants. Studies have demonstrated that integrating PRS into BC screening protocols holds promise for enhancing risk stratification and personalizing screening schedules. This approach can potentially improve clinical outcomes by targeting high-risk individuals for more intensive surveillance while minimizing unnecessary interventions for those at lower risk. For instance, Shieh et al. (2017)¹⁸ highlighted a novel approach integrating clinical risk

factors, breast density, and PRS to stratify women into different screening strategies, which is being evaluated in the WISDOM Study²⁰. Similarly, Mars et al. (2020) showed that PRS, when combined with FH and pathogenic variants (PV), effectively stratifies BC risk, enhancing the positive predictive value of screening findings⁹. Ongoing studies, such as MyPeBS in Europe²¹, the WISDOM in the United States and PERSPECTIVE I&I in Canada²² trials, aim to evaluate the efficacy, safety, and acceptability of risk-based screening strategies²³. The MyPeBS trial is designed to compare standard screening with a personalized approach based on individual risk factors, including PRS, to determine the best strategy for reducing BC mortality and morbidity. Similarly, the WISDOM trial is investigating the impact of personalized screening schedules on BC outcomes and patient satisfaction. Finally, the Canadian PERSPECTIVE I&I trial, a prospective cohort study, aims to evaluate the feasibility, healthcare resource utilization, and costs associated with implementing a multifactorial BC risk assessment, including PRS, to inform personalized screening strategies.

4.1.2 Role and potential of PRS

PRS has the potential to refine BC risk stratification by categorizing individuals into different risk groups and allowing for more personalized screening recommendations. High-risk individuals, identified through elevated PRS, could benefit from earlier and more frequent screening, such as beginning mammography before the standard recommended age, including supplemental imaging modalities such as MRI. Conversely, individuals with a low PRS may require less frequent screening, thereby reducing unnecessary imaging and associated harms, such as minimizing false positives, and lowering healthcare costs. This stratified approach (*Figure 2*) could improve early detection while optimizing healthcare resources. This tailored approach enhances screening efficiency by aligning surveillance intensity with an individual’s actual risk profile.

Figure 2: Illustrative pathway of risk-based stratification and screening interventions guided by PRS levels²⁴

Several studies have explored the integration of PRS into BC screening programs, focusing on both clinical validity and clinical utility. Clinical validity refers to the accuracy with which PRS predicts disease risk, which has been well-documented in multiple studies^{6,25,26}, showing consistent associations between high PRS and elevated BC risk. Research has demonstrated that PRS can effectively identify individuals at a significantly higher risk, potentially leading to improved screening outcomes. For instance, Mavaddat et al. (2019)⁶ demonstrated that PRS significantly improves risk discrimination beyond classical risk factors such as FH and mammographic density, supporting its integration into screening algorithms. Moreover, preliminary findings suggest that PRS can refine risk prediction models, improving the identification of individuals who may benefit from more intensive surveillance while reducing over-screening in low-risk populations. For instance, the IBIS and BOADICEA models incorporate PRS alongside traditional risk factors to enhance risk prediction. While the clinical validity of PRS in predicting BC risk is well-established, clinical utility, which measures whether PRS-guided interventions lead to improved health outcomes, remains under investigation.

Even if PRS can represent a significant advancement in personalized BC screening, ethical considerations, including potential disparities in access to genetic testing, the psychological impact of risk stratification, and implications for insurance and privacy, must be addressed before widespread implementation. Firstly, current PRS are more accurate in individuals of European ancestry due to the Eurocentric biases in GWAS. This disparity can exacerbate existing health inequities, as PRS developed from predominantly European datasets perform less well in other populations, leading to misclassification of risk, underdiagnosis, or overdiagnosis in non-European populations^{27,28}. To address these ethical concerns, it is crucial to diversify GWAS datasets and develop PRS models that are inclusive of various ethnic groups. The PRIMED Consortium²⁹, for instance, is working to improve the performance of PRS in global populations by aggregating and harmonizing multiple phenotype and genotype datasets. Additionally, the eMERGE Network has developed a framework for the clinical implementation of PRS in diverse US populations, considering genetic ancestry to calibrate PRS mean and variance³⁰. Additionally, the psychological impact of risk stratification must be considered. The communication of PRS results can lead to anxiety or false reassurance, necessitating careful risk communication strategies. Patients informed of a high genetic risk may experience increased anxiety and stress, potentially affecting their mental health and overall well-being. Conversely, those receiving a low-risk score might be falsely reassured, potentially neglecting other important risk factors such as lifestyle and FH. The International Common Disease Alliance's

PRS Task Force emphasizes the importance of addressing these issues to use PRS responsibly in clinical practice³¹. Genetic counselors play a key role in this process, as they are more likely to utilize strategies to build patient rapport and employ counseling techniques compared to other medical practitioners. The ACMG recommends that PRS reports include numerical and visual representations of risk, and stress that PRS results indicate only a risk of developing disease, not a diagnosis³². Furthermore, implications for insurance and privacy are critical. The potential misuse of genetic information by insurers and employers raises ethical concerns about discrimination and privacy breaches³³. Transparent regulatory frameworks and policies are needed to protect individuals' genetic data and ensure fair use.

4.2 Methodology

4.2.1 Research Question and Structure

PRS have demonstrated strong clinical validity in stratifying women into distinct BC risk categories, supporting their potential role in personalized screening strategies. However, before integration into routine practice, their clinical utility, including comparative effectiveness, potential harms, cost-effectiveness, feasibility, acceptability, and impact on health equity, must be rigorously assessed against the current standard of care (SoC).

To address this, we adopted the GRADE-EtD³⁴ framework and structured our evaluation in two phases. First, we conducted a systematic review of modeling studies to assess key GRADE-EtD domains such as benefits, harms, certainty of evidence, and cost-effectiveness. Second, we analyzed two additional systematic reviews to explore further dimensions of the GRADE-EtD framework, including equity, feasibility, and acceptability, specifically in the context of PRS-based screening.

This comprehensive approach aims to generate robust, policy-relevant evidence on the effectiveness and practical implementation of PRS in BC screening programs.

4.2.2 Systematic review on the clinical utility of PRS-enhanced screening

We conducted a systematic review to assess the clinical utility of incorporating PRS into BC screening programs within the European Union. Specifically, we examined whether PRS, used alone or alongside FH, offers added value over the SoC by improving key health outcomes.

This evaluation, aligned with the principles of personalized medicine, aimed to determine whether PRS-based risk stratification enhances screening efficiency, supports earlier detection, and reduces unnecessary interventions. Ethical, economic, and equity considerations were also examined to inform the broader implications of implementation.

4.2.2.1 Search Strategy and Eligibility Criteria

This systematic review followed the Population, Intervention, Comparator, Outcome (PICO³⁵) framework (Table 1).

<i>Component</i>	<i>Description</i>
Population	Adult women (minimum age: 19 years)
Intervention	Risk-based BC screening including PRS
Comparison	SoC BC screening approaches
Outcomes	<p>Benefits: all-cause mortality, BC-specific mortality, health-related quality of life (HRQoL), life-years gained (LYG), autonomy, sense of control</p> <p>Harms: overdiagnosis due to screening, false positives, socioemotional impact</p> <p>Other: cost-effectiveness, acceptability</p>
Study Designs	Prospective and retrospective observational studies, RCTs, modeling studies, and policy documents (no time limit)

Table 1: PICO framework guiding the systematic review on PRS-enhanced BC screening

Given the lack of clinical trial data, we included only modeling studies capable of simulating and directly comparing PRS-based and SoC screening scenarios, assessing their impact on population-level health outcomes. Studies were required to report on the clinical utility of PRS in this context.

The search was conducted in MEDLINE, Scopus, Web of Science, and the Cochrane Library, initially in January 2024 and concluded in May 2024, following PRISMA³⁶ methodological guidelines. Eligible studies were published in English, with no restrictions on publication year or geographic origin.

4.2.2.2 Study Selection

The systematic review was coordinated by MMC (MHH, Germany). Title and abstract screening were conducted independently by two review teams: KP (University of Ghent, Belgium) and FP (UCSC, Italy); CL and MMC (MHH, Germany) with MV and MK (University of Tartu, Estonia). Discrepancies were resolved through consultation with a third reviewer, JvR (Erasmus MC, Netherlands), and LL (University of Ghent, Belgium). Methodological oversight and supervision were provided by AMP, AT, and EP (UCSC, Italy), and IvK and SO (RIVM, Netherlands).

4.2.2.3 Data Extraction

From each eligible study, we extracted key information to ensure consistency and enable comparative analysis. This included author, article title, journal, year of publication, study design, country, and whether the study received industry funding. We also collected data on study population characteristics, including inclusion/exclusion criteria and the type of PRS applied.

For both case and control groups, we recorded participant numbers, demographic characteristics, mean age (with standard deviation), and sex distribution. Additionally, we documented each study's primary outcomes, including outcome definitions, values, and units of measurement.

4.2.2.4 Quality of Evidence

To assess the quality of evidence in the included studies, we applied the principles from the ISPOR-AMCP-NPC³⁷ Good Practice Task Force Report on modeling studies for healthcare decision-making. This framework provides a structured questionnaire to evaluate both relevance and credibility, ensuring the evidence is suitable to inform policy or clinical practice. Relevance was assessed by examining how well model populations, interventions, comparators, and outcomes aligned with real-world contexts, in this case, the integration of PRS into BC screening compared to SoC. Credibility was evaluated through appraisal of model structure, data transparency, source quality, calibration, validation, and uncertainty analyses. To meet inclusion criteria, studies needed to simulate both PRS-based and SoC screening scenarios and report clinically meaningful outcomes, such as mortality reduction, Quality-Adjusted Life Years (QALYs), and overdiagnosis. Two independent reviewers (AT and EP, UCSC, Italy) assessed full texts and evaluated quality, ensuring a thorough and unbiased review through a dual-assessor process.

In addition, following the GRADE approach, we evaluated the certainty of evidence for each outcome by examining four domains that may justify downgrading: inconsistency, indirectness and imprecision. Inconsistency was assessed by evaluating result variability across studies, focusing on the comparability of populations, interventions, and outcomes; significant heterogeneity was grounds for downgrading. Indirectness referred to the applicability of the evidence to the clinical question, including use of indirect comparisons or populations and outcomes differing from those of primary relevance. Imprecision reflected uncertainty in effect estimates, often indicated by wide confidence intervals (CIs) or small sample sizes. Publication bias was considered as the selective reporting of positive results, assessed through methods such as funnel plots. These domains highlight potential limitations in the evidence base and are critical to evaluating the robustness of findings. Each domain was systematically reviewed to identify concerns that could compromise the validity, generalizability, or overall strength of the conclusions drawn.

4.2.2.5 Statistical Analysis

We extracted outcome data from each modeling study included in the systematic review, focusing on health indicators relevant to evaluating clinical utility. For every study, values were obtained for both PRS-tailored screening and SoC scenarios. The primary analysis involved calculating the absolute effect, defined as the difference in outcomes between the two scenarios, along with corresponding 95% CIs. This enabled direct comparison of clinical impacts between PRS-based and conventional screening approaches.

For each outcome, we also computed the relative effect, expressed as the ratio of the PRS-based value to that of the SoC scenario, again with associated 95% CIs. This measure offered insight into the proportional difference in effectiveness between the strategies. In addition, we assessed the percent variation, representing the relative change in outcome measures from SoC to PRS-based screening. This step quantified the magnitude of improvement, or potential drawback, in percentage terms.

Together, these metrics allowed for a multidimensional comparison of screening approaches, capturing both absolute and relative changes in key outcomes. This analytic framework provided a comprehensive understanding of how integrating PRS might enhance or modify the clinical utility of BC screening compared to current SoC practices.

4.2.3 Systematic reviews on the implementation aspects of PRS-enhanced screening

Following the GRADE approach, we assessed the cost-effectiveness, feasibility, acceptability, and equity implications of integrating PRS into BC screening, drawing on two recent systematic reviews. Together, these reviews provide a comprehensive evaluation of the practical, ethical, and societal dimensions of PRS implementation, highlighting both the challenges and opportunities of its integration into routine clinical practice.

The first review, conducted by Andreoli et al. (2024)³⁸, synthesized empirical evidence on the perspectives, attitudes, and experiences of key stakeholders, healthcare providers, patients, and the general public, regarding the clinical use of PRS. The review aimed to identify dominant themes and critical knowledge gaps that could inform the responsible adoption of PRS. Using a mixed-method systematic review design guided by PRISMA standards³⁹, the authors included 24 empirical studies encompassing both qualitative and quantitative methodologies. These studies explored stakeholder familiarity with PRS, motivations for testing, and normative views on its clinical application. Data extraction was conducted systematically, and methodological quality was evaluated using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT)⁴⁰. The MMAT assesses the suitability of study design, data collection, and analysis techniques for mixed methods research. Importantly, the quality assessment was descriptive rather than exclusionary, no studies were excluded based on MMAT results.

In the second review, also by Andreoli et al. (2024)⁴¹, the focus shifted to the ethical justifications and moral arguments concerning the clinical implementation of PRS. This review employed a structured thematic synthesis to explore the normative literature published between 2013 and 2023, identifying 34 records that examined ethical issues such as autonomy, justice, utility, and the potential for discrimination or inequity in PRS-based screening. The review aimed to deepen understanding of how ethical reasoning informs clinical decision-making and policy development around PRS use.

Analysis across the two reviews proceeded in two phases. In the first phase, we extracted core concepts and thematic elements from the 24 empirical studies and the 34 normative papers, focusing on recurring ideas, methodological patterns, and principal findings. This process helped map the empirical and ethical landscapes relevant to PRS implementation. In the second phase, we synthesized these findings through critical reflection, enriched by consultative discussions with Andreoli, the lead author of both reviews. These discussions were pivotal in refining our interpretations, addressing potential biases, and ensuring internal coherence across the evidence base.

This iterative, consultative process strengthened the reliability of our conclusions, allowing us to integrate empirical and ethical insights in a robust, evidence-informed manner. The resulting

synthesis highlights the importance of not only clinical utility, but also acceptability, fairness, and ethical justification in evaluating the broader feasibility of PRS-enhanced BC screening.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Clinical utility of adding PRS to SoC in BC screening

A total of 2,267 records were identified through database searches, including PubMed (1,250), Scopus (812), Web of Science (181), and Cochrane (24). After removing 261 duplicate records, 2,006 records remained for screening. Of these, 1,869 were excluded based on title and abstract screening. The remaining 137 records were sought for full-text retrieval, and all were successfully obtained and assessed for eligibility. Following full-text assessment, 133 articles were excluded for reasons including wrong study design (n = 50), wrong publication type (n = 17), wrong population (n = 7), or not assessing the clinical utility of adding PRS to SoC screening (n = 59). Ultimately, 4 studies met the inclusion criteria for this review. The study selection process is illustrated in *Figure 3*.

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases and registers only

Figure 3: PRISMA flow diagram illustrating the study selection process for the systematic review on PRS-based BC screening³⁶

4.3.1.1 Characteristics of included studies

The main characteristics of the four studies included in this review are summarized in *Table 2*. All studies assessed the clinical utility of PRS in BC screening through simulation or cost-effectiveness modeling, incorporating diverse populations and health system contexts. Two studies used microsimulation modeling (Van Den Broek et al. (2021)⁴²; Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰, one used life-table modeling (Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³, and one applied a Markov model with Singapore-specific cost data (Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴. These modeling approaches enabled projection of long-term impacts of personalized screening programs across large populations.

Three studies focused on overall BC risk prediction (Van Den Broek et al. (2021)⁴², Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³, Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴, while one (Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ included subtype-specific modeling by integrating PRS with clinical risk factors. Out of four models, three of them were developed and validated in populations of European ancestry (the United States (Van Den Broek et al. (2021)⁴²), the United Kingdom (Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³, Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰, with the exception of Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴, which focused on an Asian population. All models incorporated PRS derived from previously published GWAS, with the number of SNPs ranging from 67 to 313. In all studies, risk stratification was achieved by combining PRS with other variables such as age or FH, with Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ also incorporating broader risk models and clinical screening criteria. All four studies assessed screening outcomes such as cost-effectiveness, LYGs, or benefit-to-harm ratios under different stratification strategies (BC deaths averted, overdiagnosis, false positive, QALYs). A detailed summary of the screening strategies applied in each study is provided in Supplementary Table 1, including PRS group details, the age range for screening initiation and cessation, screening frequency, and modality.

Author, Year	Study Design	Population	Number of SNPs	Health outcomes
Van den Broek, 2021 ⁴²	Microsimulation modelling study	US women aged 50–75 (United States)	313 SNPs	BC mortality, QALYs, overdiagnosis, cost-effectiveness, false positives

Pashayan, 2018 ⁴³	Life-table modelling study	UK women aged 35–69	67 SNPs	Cost-effectiveness, QALYs, overdiagnosis, cancers detected, false positives
Wong, 2021 ⁴⁴	Cost-effectiveness analysis using a Markov model	Singaporean women aged 35–74 (Asian population)	313 SNPs	Cost per QALY gained, cancer detection rates, screening efficiency
Huntley, 2023 ¹⁰	Modelling analysis using the CanRisk model and simulation of UK screening cohorts	UK general population (including age-based cohorts)	313 SNPs	Cost-effectiveness, life years gained, overdiagnosis, false positives

Table 2: Main characteristics of the included studies

4.3.1.2 Characteristics of risk prediction models

Table 3 summarizes the key characteristics of the risk prediction models utilized in the four studies. All included studies incorporated both genetic (PRS) and non-genetic factors to stratify BC risk and guide screening strategies. The number and type of non-genetic predictors varied by study. Common variables included age, FH of BC, and in some cases, breast density and reproductive factors. Van Den Broek et al. (2021)⁴² combined PRS with age and FH, while Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³ included a broader range of classical risk factors in their life-table model, informed by established models like the IBIS. Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴ focused on PRS and age, calibrated to Singapore-specific demographic and cost data. Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ included subtype-specific modeling by integrating PRS with clinical risk factors such as age and FH, enabling subtype-specific screening strategies. Risk stratification thresholds were typically based on percentiles of the PRS distribution or absolute risk scores derived from model combinations.

Author, Year	Age	FH	Reproductive factors	Hormonal factors	Lifestyle factors
Van den Broek et al, 2021 ⁴²	30–74	First-degree relatives with BC	N.C.	N.C.	N.C.
Pashayan, 2018 ⁴³	50–85	FH of BC	Age at menarche, age at first live birth	Use of hormone replacement therapy	N.C.
Wong et al, 2021	35–74	N.C	N.C.	N.C.	N.C.
Huntley et al, 2023 ¹⁰	40–69	Detailed pedigree-based FH	Age at menarche, parity, age at first birth, age at menopause	Oral contraceptive use, hormone replacement therapy	Body mass index, alcohol intake, smoking status

*N.C.=Not Considered

Table 3: Main characteristics of the risk prediction models utilized in the included studies

4.3.1.2 Benefits & Harms

Across healthcare systems in the United States, United Kingdom, and Singapore, PRS-informed BC screening strategies, especially when combined with FH, have consistently shown improved outcomes over traditional age-based approaches. However, these benefits come with notable harms, including increased false positives and overdiagnoses. Given the low certainty of evidence (per GRADE) and the need for real-world validation, cautious interpretation and gradual implementation are advised. Full evidence is provided in the supplementary material tables 2, 3 and 4.

Deliverable 14.2 – Final version of the recommendations - Version 1.2

Evidence from Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴², Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰, and Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴ supports the added value of PRS-based screening. Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴² reported a 29% increase in LYG and an 18% reduction in BC mortality when PRS and FH were used together. Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ found that PRS-targeted screening reduced BC mortality by 14.7%, compared to 11.6% with age-based screening. Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴ observed a 4% increase in both LYG and QALYs, along with reduced BC incidence.

Yet, these benefits are offset by harms: Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴² noted a 63% rise in false positives and 21% in overdiagnoses with PRS+FH. Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ showed overdiagnosis rates per death averted remained comparable to age-based screening. Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³ highlighted the trade-offs of risk thresholds, higher thresholds reduced overdiagnosis but modestly increased BC mortality.

Together, the findings support a shift to risk-stratified screening. Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴² recommend earlier screening for high-risk women. Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³ suggest de-escalating screening in low-risk groups to minimize harm. Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴ advocate for flexible screening ages and intervals tailored by genetic risk. Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ highlight potential gains in younger high-risk groups, while cautioning against fully excluding low-risk individuals.

Below is the detailed assessment of each study. For more information, see Supplementary Tables (2.1-2.4).

Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴²

The study by Van den Broek et al (2021)⁴², titled “*Personalizing breast cancer screening based on polygenic risk and family history*,” is a population-based simulation using two established models from the Cancer Intervention and Surveillance Modeling Network (CISNET). It evaluated the potential benefits and harms of incorporating PRS and first-degree FH of BC into screening strategies for women aged 30–50 years. The simulation used a cohort of women born in the United States in 1985, stratifying them into risk categories based on a PRS derived from 313 SNPs and FH across different age brackets. The interventions compared included SoC BC screening based on the 2020 guidelines of the U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) versus PRS-only, FH-only, and combined PRS + FH-enhanced screening strategies.

The outcomes of different screening strategies evaluated by Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴² are summarized in *Table 4*; Supplementary Table 2.1 provides further detail. The study found that tailoring screening based on PRS and/or FH improved clinical outcomes compared to the SoC. Specifically, PRS-based screening alone increased LYG by 20% and BC deaths averted by 11%, albeit with a moderate increase in harms such as false positives and overdiagnosis. Screening strategies informed by FH alone were even more effective, resulting in a 25% increase in deaths averted and a 37% increase in LYG. The most favorable outcomes were observed when PRS and FH were used in combination, maximizing the benefits (29% increase in life-years and 18% reduction in deaths) but also leading to the highest levels of overdiagnosis and false positives. The findings underscore the potential of integrating genetic and familial risk information to personalize BC screening, while also highlighting the need to balance the benefits with associated harms.

Outcomes	Anticipated Absolute Effects (95% CI) Risk with SoC / Risk with PRS enhanced screening	Relative Effect (95% CI)
BC deaths averted (FH not in SoC/PRS-enhanced screening)	6 vs 7 per 1,000 (7 to 7)	1.11 (1.05–1.16)
BC deaths averted (FH in SoC/ PRS-enhanced screening)	12 vs 15 per 1,000 (14 to 16)	1.25 (1.19–1.32)
LYG (FH not in SoC/ PRS-enhanced screening)	113.30 vs 135.75 per 1,000	1.20 (1.14–1.26)
LYG (FH in SoC/ PRS-enhanced screening)	219.22 vs 300.92 per 1,000	1.37 (1.30–1.44)
Overdiagnoses (FH not in SoC/ PRS-enhanced screening)	14 vs 15 per 1,000 (14 to 16)	1.10 (1.04–1.15)
Overdiagnoses (FH in SoC/ PRS-enhanced screening)	16 vs 20 per 1,000 (19 to 21)	1.26 (1.20–1.32)
False positives (FH not in SoC/ PRS-enhanced screening)	920.69 vs 1155.24 per 1,000	1.25 (1.19–1.32)
False positives (FH in SoC/PRS - enhances screening)	563.46 vs 1056.78 per 1,000	1.91 (1.82–2.01)

Table 4. Estimated Outcomes of BC screening informed by PRS and FH compared to SoC, based on the study Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴²

Huntley et al. (2023)

The study by Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰, titled “*Utility of polygenic risk scores in UK cancer screening: a modelling analysis*,” aimed to assess whether incorporating PRS into national cancer screening strategies in the UK could improve efficiency by targeting high-risk individuals. This modeling

analysis simulated cancer screening scenarios for multiple cancers, with a focus on BC outcomes among women aged 40–49. The study population included 873,941 women, with approximately 7,533 BC cases modeled annually.

Risk stratification was based on PRS quintiles, categorizing women into high-risk groups (top 20%, 10%, 5%, and 1%) and low risk (bottom 80%). The PRS-based screening approach proposed varying modalities and intervals: biennial mammography for the top 20%, annual mammography for the top 10%, and annual MRI plus mammography for the top 1%. These strategies were compared to the standard age-based screening of women aged 50–69 and a hypothetical age-extension strategy (screening women aged 48–49).

The outcomes of different screening strategies evaluated by Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ are summarized in *Table 5*; Supplementary Table 2.2 provides further detail. The study found that PRS-based screening among the top 20% risk group averted more deaths (102 vs. 80 annually) compared to age-based screening, translating to a 28% relative improvement. Importantly, this targeted strategy maintained a similar overdiagnosis ratio (2.4 cases per death averted) to age-based screening, suggesting that personalized risk stratification could enhance screening benefits without increasing harms. The findings support the feasibility and potential value of using PRS to guide risk-based screening in younger women.

<i>Outcomes</i>	<i>Anticipated Absolute Effects (95% CI)</i>	
	<i>Risk with SoC / Risk with PRS enhanced screening</i>	<i>Relative Effect (95% CI)</i>
BC deaths averted	80 vs 102 per 873,941 (95% CI: 20.9–23.1)	1.28 (1.21–1.34)
Overdiagnoses	190 vs 243 per 873,941 (95% CI: 50.35–55.65)	1.28 (1.22–1.34)

Table 5: BC mortality and overdiagnosis outcomes under PRS-based screening strategies in the UK compared to SoC, based on the study Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰

Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴

The study by Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴, titled “*Cost effectiveness analysis of a polygenic risk tailored breast cancer screening programme in Singapore,*” evaluated the economic and clinical outcomes of integrating PRS into the national BC screening program. This cost-effectiveness analysis used a Markov model to simulate health outcomes and costs over a 40-year time horizon, tracking women from ages 35 to 74. The study adopted a healthcare system perspective specific to Singapore and compared a PRS-informed strategy with the existing biennial mammography screening for women aged 50–69.

Women were stratified into three risk groups based on PRS percentiles: low (<60th), intermediate (60th–95th), and high (>95th). Screening frequency and modality varied by risk level and age. For example, low-risk women received triennial mammography from ages 40–74, intermediate-risk women underwent biennial mammography, and high-risk women were screened annually using ultrasound and mammography. All participants were initially assessed using buccal swab genotyping and a risk factor questionnaire.

The outcomes of different screening strategies evaluated by Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴ are summarized in *Table 6*; Supplementary Table 2.3 provides further detail. The study found that PRS-tailored screening was more effective than the standard approach, yielding 0.97 additional LYG and 0.98 more QALYs per 1,000 women. This corresponds to a 4% relative improvement in both outcomes. Moreover, BC incidence was reduced from 31.2 to 25.5 cases per 1,000 women. Importantly, the analysis reported no additional harms, supporting the safety and efficiency of PRS-guided personalized screening strategies in this setting.

Outcomes	Anticipated Absolute Effects (95% CI)	Relative Effect (95% CI)
	Risk with SoC / Risk with PRS enhanced screening	
LYG	21.89 vs 22.86 per 1,000 (0.92–1.02)	1.04 (0.99–1.10)
QALYs Gained	21.80 vs 22.78 per 1,000 (0.93–1.03)	1.04 (0.99–1.10)

Table 6. BC LYG and QALYs gained outcomes under PRS-based screening strategies in Singapore compared to SoC, as reported by Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴

Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³

The study by Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³, titled “*Cost-effectiveness and benefit-to-harm ratio of risk-stratified screening for breast cancer: a life-table model,*” investigated whether targeting BC screening based on polygenic risk could improve efficiency, reduce overdiagnosis, and maintain clinical benefits compared to traditional age-based screening. The study used a life-table model from the perspective of the UK National Health Service (NHS) to simulate outcomes for a hypothetical population of 364,500 women starting at age 50 and followed through age 85.

The risk-stratified strategy involved screening only those women whose PRS placed them above certain percentile thresholds (10th, 25th, 32nd, 62nd, and 70th). Women below the defined cutoffs were not offered screening, while those above underwent triennial mammographic screening from

age 50 to 69. Outcomes were assessed across multiple thresholds, allowing analysis of the trade-offs between reduced harms and preserved benefits.

The outcomes of different screening strategies evaluated by Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³, are summarized in *Table 7*; Supplementary Table 2.4 provides further detail. The model revealed that while risk-stratified screening reduced overdiagnosis compared to age-based screening, it also resulted in a gradual increase in BC deaths as the risk threshold increased, highlighting the tension between reducing harms and preserving mortality benefits. For instance, screening only those above the 70th percentile resulted in 23 additional BC deaths per 10,000 participants compared to age-based screening, but it also yielded 52 fewer overdiagnoses. QALYs gained were consistent across thresholds but slightly declined at higher thresholds. These findings support risk stratification as a potentially cost-effective strategy, though careful calibration of risk thresholds is crucial to avoid unacceptable losses in screening benefits.

Outcomes	Anticipated Absolute Effects (95% CI)
	Risk with SoC / Risk with PRS enhanced screening
BC deaths	<p>Compared with age-based screening, risk-stratified screening was associated with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 additional BC deaths per year at the 10th percentile per 10,000 participants • 5 additional BC deaths per year at the 25th percentile per 10,000 participants. • 7 additional BC deaths per year at the 32nd percentile per 10,000 participants. • 18 additional BC deaths per year at the 62nd percentile per 10,000 participants. • 23 additional BC deaths per year at the 70th percentile per 10,000 participants
QALYs	<p>Compared with age-based screening, risk-stratified screening was associated with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 449 additional QALYs per year at the 10th percentile per 10,000 participants. • 450 additional QALYs per year at the 25th percentile per 10,000 participants. • 450 additional QALYs per year at the 32nd percentile per 10,000 participants. • 446 additional QALYs per year at the 62nd percentile per 10,000 participants. • 443 additional QALYs per year at the 70th percentile per 10,000 participants.
Overdiagnosis	<p>Compared with age-based screening, risk-stratified screening was associated with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 fewer overdiagnoses per year at the 10th percentile per 10,000 participants.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12 fewer overdiagnoses per year at the 25th percentile per 10,000 participants. • 17 fewer overdiagnoses per year at the 32nd percentile per 10,000 participants. • 43 fewer overdiagnoses per year at the 62nd percentile per 10,000 participants. • 52 fewer overdiagnoses per year at the 70th percentile per 10,000 participants.
--	--

Table 7: BC mortality, QALYs, and Overdiagnosis outcomes under PRS-based screening strategies compared to SoC, as reported by Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³

4.3.1.3 Quality assessment

The certainty of evidence for the assessed outcomes is predominantly **very low**, particularly for critical outcomes such as BC deaths, BC deaths averted, QALYs, and overdiagnoses. These classifications reflect significant limitations in the reliability of the underlying modeling studies, including risks of bias, imprecision in estimates, and indirectness of evidence. Few outcomes, such as LYG, were rated with **low certainty**.

More detailed information on the domain-specific assessments is provided below. For comprehensive methodological details, supporting data, and individual outcome ratings per study, please refer to Supplementary Tables 6 and 7.

Risk of Bias

We applied to the ISPOR-AMCP-NPC Good Practice Task Force framework. This structured tool evaluates both relevance, how well the model aligns with real-world clinical and policy context, and credibility, through criteria such as model design, data sources, analytical methods, transparency in reporting, and uncertainty analysis. Assessments were conducted independently by two reviewers (AT and EP, UCSC, Italy), with final scores derived through consensus.

Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴²: This study received a uniformly high-quality rating across all evaluated domains, with both reviewers consistently scoring each criterion as “strength.” This included model design, data inputs, analytical methods, reporting practices, interpretation of results, and conflict of interest transparency. Importantly, the model was judged to be well-calibrated and validated, enhancing its credibility. These results suggest that Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴² produced a highly reliable and transparent simulation study, suitable for informing clinical and policy decisions regarding the integration of PRS into BC screening.

Unlike the other studies, the final assessment table for Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³ did not contain any conclusive scores across the domains. This absence of data may reflect incomplete documentation or unresolved disagreements during the consensus process. While the study is well-recognized in the field, the lack of a clear quality rating means that its methodological credibility and risk of bias could not be formally confirmed through this assessment. Additional appraisal or follow-up would be required to draw reliable conclusions about its overall quality.

Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴ presented a mostly positive quality profile. The study was rated as “strength” in multiple domains, including data use, analysis, reporting, interpretation, and conflict of interest. However, a notable concern was raised regarding model validation, which was rated as a “weakness.” This indicates that the model may not have been adequately calibrated or externally validated against real-world data, potentially affecting confidence in its predictive performance. Nevertheless, the strong methodological foundation in other areas supports its partial utility for informing decisions, with caveats about generalizability and robustness of assumptions.

Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ received a mixed appraisal. The study was scored as “neutral” in key structural domains, model design, validation, and conflict of interest, suggesting some ambiguity or limitations in transparency or rigor. Nevertheless, the study demonstrated strength in data handling, reporting, and interpretation, indicating that the presented findings are likely grounded in sound analysis. However, the neutral ratings in foundational domains warrant caution, particularly regarding how broadly the model’s findings can be generalized to different healthcare systems or screening environments.

Overall, Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴² emerged as the most methodologically robust and credible study, while Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴ and Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ showed important strengths but also specific weaknesses that should be considered in interpretation. Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³ lacked complete scoring, leaving its risk of bias inconclusive under this framework.

Inconsistency of results

Across the four studies assessed, the degree of inconsistency in results varied depending on the outcome considered. Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴² reported consistent findings for BC deaths averted, LYG, and false positives, all rated as *not serious* for inconsistency due to minimal variability and strong agreement across models. However, the outcome of overdiagnosis in this study showed substantial variability with minimal overlap in CIs, leading to a *serious* rating for inconsistency.

Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³ similarly demonstrated consistent results for most outcomes, including BC deaths averted, person-years of survival (PYRS), and QALYs, which were all rated as *not serious*. In contrast, overdiagnosis estimates varied significantly across risk-stratified strategies, reflecting heterogeneity likely stemming from differences in assumptions about the natural history of cancer. This led to a *serious* concern for inconsistency in that outcome.

In the case of Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴, both LYG and QALYs showed minimal variability with narrow ranges and high consistency across scenarios. Although explicit CIs were not reported, the results were deemed stable, and inconsistency was rated as *not serious* for both outcomes.

Lastly, Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ also received a *not serious* rating for inconsistency in both BC deaths averted and overdiagnosis. The findings were consistent with other PRS-based screening studies, and no meaningful heterogeneity was identified. Despite being a single-model study, the internal consistency of results and alignment with external evidence supported confidence in the consistency of outcomes.

Indirectness of evidence

When assessing indirectness of evidence, all four studies relied on modeled data rather than empirical trial results, introducing varying degrees of indirectness primarily due to population generalizability and reliance on simulations.

Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴² received a *not serious* rating across all outcomes, LYG, QALYs, overdiagnosis, and false positives. While the use of a hypothetical US cohort may slightly limit generalizability, the interventions were aligned with real-world BC screening practices and the outcomes were directly patient-relevant.

Similarly, Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³ were rated *not serious* for most outcomes, BC deaths averted, QALYs, and overdiagnosis, due to the direct applicability of the interventions and outcomes to clinical questions, despite modeling from a UK cohort. However, for PYRS, the study received a *serious* rating. This was attributed to the use of a general survival metric instead of more patient-centered measures like disease-free or quality-adjusted survival, introducing moderate indirectness.

Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴ also received *not serious* ratings for both LYG and QALYs. The study modeled Canadian population data, which, while not universally generalizable, was deemed sufficiently

representative of high-income countries. The interventions were standard screening practices, and the outcomes were clearly aligned with patient-relevant measures.

In contrast, Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ received a *serious* rating for both BC deaths averted and overdiagnosis. This was due to reliance on UK-specific population assumptions and full uptake of polygenic risk scoring (PRS), which may not reflect real-world implementation across different healthcare systems. Additionally, the modeling tools used in this study were based on optimistic assumptions and may not apply to broader populations or reflect actual screening performance in diverse contexts.

Imprecision

In evaluating imprecision, the four studies displayed varying levels of certainty depending on the outcome, largely influenced by the width of CIs, sample sizes, and potential crossing of clinical decision thresholds.

Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴² presented *not serious* concerns for LYG and false positives, as both outcomes showed narrow CIs and high consistency across models, supporting adequate precision. However, *serious* concerns were noted for overdiagnosis and BC deaths averted. In both cases, the CIs were wide and, in the case of BC mortality, potentially crossed decision thresholds, limiting the certainty of effect estimates and their utility for strong recommendations.

Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³ also showed *serious* concerns for overdiagnosis, BC deaths averted, and QALYs due to broad CIs, which introduced significant uncertainty in the magnitude of effect and its relevance for clinical decisions. While the study used a large sample size, the variability in outcomes undermined confidence. Conversely, for PYRS, the estimates were more stable with narrower CIs, resulting in a *not serious* rating for imprecision.

In Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴, both LYG and QALYs were rated as *not serious* for imprecision. Although the outcomes were modeled, the estimates were tightly clustered with very narrow ranges and large sample sizes, indicating high precision. The narrow variability suggested that these estimates would likely remain stable under different scenarios and were unlikely to cross any clinical thresholds.

Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ was rated *serious* for both BC deaths averted and overdiagnosis. The modeling in this study included significant uncertainty due to assumptions about screening uptake, efficiency,

and the performance of PRS tools. Additionally, the lack of detailed probabilistic sensitivity analyses further reduced confidence in the precision of these outcomes.

4.3.2 Implementation aspects of PRS-enhanced screening

To support the assessment of broader implementation factors within the GRADE EtD framework, we incorporated findings from two systematic reviews conducted by Andreoli et al. (2024)^{38 41}. The first review examines empirical evidence on the perspectives, experiences, and knowledge of key stakeholders, including healthcare providers, patients, and the public, regarding the clinical use of PRS. It highlights key themes such as familiarity with PRS, motivations for testing, and normative views on its clinical application. The second review explores the ethical dimensions of PRS implementation, focusing on potential harms, health equity concerns, and context-sensitive ethical practices.

Together, these reviews provide a comprehensive foundation for understanding the social, ethical, and practical considerations that may influence the integration of PRS into routine BC screening. Their findings were thematically synthesized and mapped to the relevant GRADE EtD domains, specifically: acceptability, equity, feasibility, and cost-effectiveness. The following sections present a structured summary of how PRS implementation aligns with each of these domains, informing its real-world applicability beyond clinical effectiveness alone. A detailed overview of the supporting evidence and sources informing each domain is provided in Supplementary Table 7.

4.3.2.1 Acceptability

Women's engagement with PRS in the context of BC reveals a nuanced interplay of knowledge, experience, and emotional response. Evidence indicates that women generally demonstrated a sound understanding of PRS concepts and effectively integrated PRS results into their personal risk management strategies, particularly when shaped by prior experiences with BC⁴⁵. Acceptance and comprehension of PRS were further enhanced among individuals with higher levels of education or a FH of BC, suggesting that background knowledge and perceived personal relevance influence the interpretability and perceived utility of PRS information⁴⁶. However, ethical and privacy concerns emerged prominently across studies, with participants expressing apprehension regarding the

potential misuse of genetic data by insurers or employers, risks of discrimination, and the importance of secure data access and storage^{33,47,48}. Emotional reactions to PRS testing were varied; while some individuals found the information empowering, others reported heightened anxiety and preferred to remain unaware of their risk status, often guided by personality traits and coping mechanisms. In particular, women experiencing fear or anticipatory anxiety displayed reluctance to confront immediate emotional distress, even when aware of possible long-term health benefits associated with knowing their PRS^{49,50}. These findings underscore the importance of personalized approaches to PRS communication that account for individual educational backgrounds, personal and familial experiences, and emotional readiness.

4.3.2.2 Equity

Equity emerges as a critical consideration in the clinical implementation of PRS. A prominent concern is the persistent underrepresentation of ethnic minority populations in genomic research cohorts, a disparity often rooted in historical mistrust of medical research and systemic barriers to participation. This underrepresentation not only limits the generalizability and clinical utility of PRS across diverse populations but also undermines efforts to promote equitable healthcare outcomes⁵¹⁻⁵⁵. Additionally, there is growing apprehension regarding the potential misuse of genetic information by third parties, such as employers or insurance companies, which could result in discrimination and exacerbate existing health inequities^{56,57}. Concerns about equity also extend to access to screening programs informed by PRS. While participants expressed support for the personalization of population-based screening strategies using PRS, they opposed the reduction of screening frequency for individuals deemed low-risk. This opposition reflects a broader consensus that baseline screening services should remain universally accessible to prevent the deepening of healthcare disparities^{50,58-61}. Together, these insights underscore the imperative to integrate equity-focused policies and practices in the clinical translation of PRS to ensure fair and inclusive healthcare delivery.

4.3.2.3 Feasibility

The feasibility of implementing PRS in BC screening is closely linked to the availability of supportive infrastructure, training, and equitable clinical applicability. Genetic counselors play a pivotal role in facilitating the integration of PRS into clinical practice, using tailored counseling strategies to build patient rapport and address the emotional implications of high-risk results, particularly in individuals with prior BC experiences⁶². Effective patient education tools, such as pilot-tested informational

leaflets, have been shown to improve comprehension of PRS results, supporting informed decision-making⁶³. For healthcare providers, particularly general practitioners, the clinical use of PRS demands robust and continuous training. Online educational programs have demonstrated efficacy in enhancing providers' knowledge, confidence, and readiness to integrate PRS into routine care, while also highlighting the need for ongoing professional development^{45,64,65}. Nevertheless, the proliferation of PRS models with differing methodologies poses challenges in model selection, contributing to variability in clinical adoption. Furthermore, the necessity of pre- and post-test counseling is underscored by evidence suggesting that high-risk results can evoke significant emotional distress or re-traumatization among BC patients, reinforcing the importance of psychological support throughout the testing process^{46,58-61,66-68}. A key limitation to the broad feasibility of PRS is their limited transferability across populations. While PRS models demonstrate strong predictive performance in European and Latina populations, their accuracy is markedly reduced in individuals of African ancestry and to a lesser extent in Ashkenazi Jewish, South American, South Asian, and East Asian groups, raising concerns about the equitable clinical utility of PRS in diverse populations^{51,53-55,69}. These findings underscore the importance of culturally competent implementation strategies and the refinement of PRS models to ensure their effective and equitable use in BC screening.

4.3.2.4 Cost-effectiveness

The cost-effectiveness of integrating PRS into BC screening programs has been explored across various healthcare settings, with evidence supporting its potential to enhance the efficiency of screening strategies. In the UK, Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³ demonstrated that risk-stratified screening, particularly at the 70th percentile risk threshold, could significantly improve cost-effectiveness and reduce overdiagnosis while maintaining screening benefits, with a 72% probability of being cost-effective at a willingness-to-pay threshold of £20,000 per QALY. Similarly, Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴ found that a PRS-tailored screening program in Singapore yielded cost savings and improved health outcomes, with an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) of -3713.80 SGD per QALY compared to standard biennial mammography, underscoring the economic viability of personalized screening approaches. Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰ further modeled PRS-based screening in younger UK women, showing that targeting the top 20% of genetic risk in women aged 40–49 could prevent more deaths than conventional age-based screening. However, they noted only modest improvements in overall efficiency, as many cancers still arise in individuals classified as low-risk and excluded from screening. Collectively, these findings indicate that PRS-informed screening can improve cost-

effectiveness and optimize resource allocation, yet its implementation must carefully balance economic gains with ethical considerations, population-specific performance, and the practical limitations of genetic risk stratification.

4.4 GRADE EtD experts’ panel

In alignment with the GRADE EtD framework, the formulation of recommendations regarding the use of PRS-enhanced BC screening in the CAN.HEAL project was supported by a dedicated expert panel. To ensure the robustness, relevance, and applicability of the recommendations, a multidisciplinary expert panel was convened, composed of nine professionals representing a broad range of expertise and stakeholder perspectives. Panel members were carefully selected to reflect geographic diversity, a mix of methodological and content-specific knowledge, and a balance of clinical, public health, and patient-oriented viewpoints.

The panel included:

- Clinical geneticists with direct experience in hereditary cancer syndromes and PRS implementation;
- Public health professionals and epidemiologists with expertise in cancer screening and policy;
- Health technology assessment (HTA) specialists with experience in evaluating complex innovations in healthcare;
- Patient advocacy representatives who could speak to the lived experience and value perspectives of individuals affected by cancer.

The full list of panelists, including their names, institutional affiliations, countries of work, and areas of expertise, is listed in *Table 8*.

Surname	Name	Organization	Country	Expertise
Bergmann	Anke	Hannover Medical School	Germany	Clinical geneticist
Moorthie	Sowmiya	Cancer Research UK / Cambridge Public Health	UK	policy expert
Devilee	Peter	University of Leiden	The Netherlands	Cancer genetics / Breast Cancer

Tõnisson	Neeme	University of Tartu	Estonia	medical doctor / geneticist
De Pauw	Antoine	Institute Curie	France	genetic counsellor (clinical setting)
De Koning	Harry	Erasmus Medical Center	The Netherlands	HTA expert
Cornell	Martina	VU University Medical Center Amsterdam	The Netherlands	Genetics / Public Health genomics
Cardone	Antonella	Cancer patients Europe	Italy	Patient advocacy
Giorgi Rossi	Paolo	AUSL di Reggio Emilia	Italy	Cancer biology/epidemiology/screening

Table 8: Members of the multidisciplinary expert panel, including representatives from different countries and areas of expertise, encompassing clinical genetics, public health, policy, patient advocacy, and cancer research.

Their institutional representation spans leading universities, national health systems, research institutes, and patient organizations across seven European countries (Germany, Netherlands, Italy, France, Estonia, and the United Kingdom), reflecting the transnational and multi-sectoral character of the CAN.HEAL initiative.

The panel’s work was conducted entirely remotely (*Figure 4*). A total of three structured meetings were held via videoconference, scheduled to ensure broad availability across multiple time zones. These meetings allowed for the presentation of evidence, open discussion, clarification of interpretation issues, and preliminary formulation of recommendation statements. Communication between meetings was maintained through email correspondence and Microsoft Forms, which were used to collect structured feedback and facilitate asynchronous input.

Figure 4: Timeline of the expert panel activities, outlining key milestones and stages in the development of PRS recommendations, including discussions, evaluations, and consensus-building processes

The development of evidence profiles and EtD tables was supported by GRADEpro, the official software of the GRADE Working Group. This tool enabled the integration of evidence from systematic reviews and key studies, structured appraisal of each EtD criterion, and collaborative drafting of recommendation wording. Panelists reviewed the draft tables individually and provided input through digital forms.

Voting on the direction and strength of the recommendations, as well as final consensus on the wording, was conducted using Microsoft Forms, ensuring equal participation from all members regardless of location. Responses were anonymized and aggregated by the coordination team to promote transparency and impartiality. Consensus was defined a priori and reached for all final recommendations through this structured and iterative process.

4.4.1 First panel meeting (defining the research question and framework)

The first meeting of the expert panel took place virtually on January 12th, 2024. Its primary objective was to introduce the panel to the methodological framework guiding the recommendations, present the initial formulation of the research question, and solicit open discussion to refine its scope and components based on the GRADE EtD framework.

After introductory remarks and an overview of the CAN.HEAL project and its aims, the UCSC team explained the GRADE EtD methodology and how it would structure the recommendation development process. It was clarified that the evidence collection would be led by a dedicated research team within the CAN.HEAL consortium, while the expert panel would focus on evaluating the evidence and formulating recommendations. A timeline was shared, indicating the literature review would conclude by March 2024, with panel voting and consensus-building scheduled thereafter.

The core of the meeting was devoted to critically examining the proposed research question, structured using the PICO format. This prompted extensive and thoughtful discussion across all components, Population, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcomes, as well as other EtD domains such as feasibility, equity, and resource use.

On the Population, the initial proposal targeted adult women aged 19 and older. This was met with nuanced reflections. While some panelists supported including younger adults for hereditary cancer risk assessment, others raised concerns about the practical impact of screening in younger age groups, where routine screening is rarely recommended and the benefits are less immediately observable.

Deliverable 14.2 – Final version of the recommendations - Version 1.2

There was agreement that a more practical age threshold, such as starting at 30–35 years, could align better with the evidence base and existing clinical practice, while still capturing those at elevated genetic risk.

Regarding the Intervention, the panel recognized the need for conceptual clarity. There was broad consensus that the focus should not be limited to PRS alone but should also consider how PRS interacts with, or is integrated into, broader genetic testing strategies, potentially including monogenic risk variants and panel-based tests. Participants stressed the importance of situating PRS within the wider landscape of multifactorial risk assessment and highlighted the need to differentiate between clinical care for high-risk individuals and population-based screening programs. This raised questions about the appropriate scope of the recommendations: whether they should focus solely on general population screening, high-risk groups, or both. Furthermore, the potential variability in PRS algorithms and the need for consistency and comparability across models was also acknowledged.

The discussion on the Comparison was more straightforward. The SoC, current BC screening approaches, was considered a suitable comparator. However, it was noted that clarity is needed regarding whether this refers exclusively to organized population-based screening or also includes individualized approaches in clinical practice.

The panel's analysis of Outcomes revealed more complexity. There was skepticism about the utility of including all-cause mortality, given the improbability of detecting significant differences within feasible follow-up periods. Conversely, outcomes such as BC-specific mortality, stage distribution, false positives and negatives, overdiagnosis, and health-related quality of life were deemed more relevant and measurable. There was also recognition of the growing importance of cost-effectiveness, especially in the context of falling genomic sequencing costs and the possibility of using genetic data for multiple diseases, not just BC. Equity and system readiness emerged as cross-cutting concerns. Panelists cautioned that implementing PRS-based screening in a health system not equipped to manage the influx of new risk information could inadvertently increase inequalities and strain existing services.

From a broader EtD perspective, resource use, feasibility, and acceptability were explored in relation to infrastructure readiness, data availability, and workforce capacity, particularly the need for trained genetic counselors. While early indications suggest PRS-based approaches are generally acceptable to patients and healthcare professionals, challenges around implementation logistics and sustained follow-up were highlighted. The panel emphasized the importance of explicitly considering the organizational context in which PRS would be deployed, whether in public health programs, primary

care settings, or via individual self-initiation, and cautioned against deferring these considerations to the final stages of the recommendation process.

The meeting concluded with an acknowledgment of the time constraints. Despite this, the UCSC team affirmed their commitment to incorporating the panel's feedback. The panel agreed on the importance of balancing scientific rigor with practical feasibility in the scope and framing of the final PICO questions. It was suggested that having two PICO formulations, one targeting general population screening and one for high-risk individuals, might be a strategic solution to address the complexity of the topic without losing focus.

Overall, the first panel meeting laid a critical foundation for the recommendation development process, surfacing key methodological, ethical, and practical questions. It established a collaborative atmosphere grounded in thoughtful exchange and mutual respect, setting the stage for the upcoming evidence synthesis and deliberation phases.

4.4.2 Second panel meeting (reviewing evidence and evaluating approaches to clinical utility)

The second meeting of the expert panel was held virtually on May 16th, 2024. The primary aim of this session was to present the results of the systematic literature review, including the finalized PICO, and to collectively deliberate on the most appropriate analytical approach to evaluate the clinical utility of PRS in this context. This meeting marked a critical transition in the project: from formulating research questions to interrogating the body of evidence and determining a strategy for evidence appraisal under the GRADE EtD framework.

The UCSC team opened with a brief recap of the project's objectives, methodology, and the outcomes of the first panel meeting, highlighting how earlier discussions had influenced the final PICO. Following this, the research team presented the results of the systematic review. The presentation included an overview of study designs, targeted populations, comparators, reported outcomes, and a PRISMA flow chart. A key feature of this session was the examination of a specific study, Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴², to contextualize how PRS and FH are operationalized in risk-stratified BC screening.

The discussion quickly deepened into critical reflections on the nature and limitations of the available evidence. Panelists unanimously acknowledged a central gap: the lack of primary evidence demonstrating the clinical utility of PRS, that is, evidence linking PRS-informed screening strategies

to patient-relevant outcomes such as mortality, stage shift, or quality of life. Considering this, a significant portion of the meeting focused on whether modeling studies could serve as a valid source of evidence. The GRADE Working Group’s guidance, specifically Guideline #30⁷⁰, was cited to support this approach, allowing the use of well-documented, transparent models where direct evidence is absent.

There was broad agreement that modeling can provide meaningful insights, particularly when it comes to estimating population risk stratification, optimizing screening intervals, and exploring cost-effectiveness. However, panelists were cautious in emphasizing that modeled evidence must be interpreted considering its assumptions and limitations, with the certainty of evidence downgraded when input data is weak or speculative. It was noted that modeling outputs, while useful for strategic forecasting, cannot substitute for long-term clinical outcomes and must be explicitly presented as indirect evidence.

The applicability of PRS across different population contexts also surfaced as a key theme. Several panelists stressed the need to disaggregate findings by population risk profiles (e.g., high-risk vs. general population) and to account for factors such as breast density, reproductive history, and ethnicity. The ambiguity surrounding classification systems, between terms like race, ethnicity, and genetic ancestry, was flagged as a methodological concern with both social and scientific implications. Panelists urged caution in using these categories, emphasizing the need for transparency and consistency in reporting.

In discussing the next steps, the group considered the possibility of prioritizing research recommendations rather than prematurely advocating for changes in policy or clinical practice. Given the immaturity of the evidence base and the reliance on modeling, there was consensus that CAN.HEAL’s contribution should be to clearly map existing knowledge gaps and define future research priorities. Nonetheless, some participants noted that a forward-looking perspective, one that anticipates the organizational and economic impact of PRS integration, would also be valuable to guide national policy development. This would include issues of system readiness, training needs, communication tools, and equity implications.

Several concrete insights emerged during the session. The “stage shift” was broadly acknowledged as a practical and feasible endpoint for measuring PRS-informed screening effectiveness, though it was also recognized as a limited proxy for clinical benefit. Panelists flagged ongoing trials, notably WISDOM and MyPeBS, as critical sources of forthcoming evidence. These trials may help fill current

gaps but were not expected to resolve all uncertainties, especially regarding PRS integration in routine care for younger or high-risk populations.

Finally, the group briefly touched on the need for clear, practical communication strategies, particularly for explaining PRS results and screening implications to patients. A recurring theme was the risk of generating confusion or anxiety in both patients and healthcare professionals if responsibilities and implications are not clearly delineated.

The meeting concluded with operational updates. The UCSC team outlined the next steps: quality assessment of evidence using GRADE EtD criteria would be conducted between June and July, and a structured PDF would be sent to the panel to support evidence grading and recommendation formulation. The team also confirmed that a third panel meeting would take place in early autumn if needed to reach consensus, particularly where strong divergence of opinion persists. To streamline the process, further communication would take place primarily via email. Lastly, it was announced that a Google Form would be circulated for panel members to declare any conflicts of interest, reinforcing the project's commitment to transparency.

This second meeting built substantially upon the first, shifting the focus from conceptual framing to evidence evaluation. It underscored the complexity of deriving actionable recommendations from a limited and evolving evidence base, and the importance of balancing scientific caution with the practical imperatives of future implementation.

4.4.3 Third panel meeting (instructions for evidence rating and drafting recommendations)

The third and final expert panel meeting took place on December 4th, 2024. This session marked the culmination of the group's structured deliberations under the GRADE EtD framework. Its purpose was to review the synthesized body of evidence, assess the quality and relevance of that evidence using GRADE criteria, and initiate the process of drafting recommendations based on the panel's collective judgments regarding clinical utility, feasibility, acceptability, equity, and policy implications.

The UCSC team opened the meeting with a recap of prior sessions and the project's overarching objectives. The team reaffirmed that while the current body of literature on PRS supports its validity for cancer risk prediction (based on metrics like AUC and odds ratios (ORs)), robust data on clinical utility remain lacking. In this context, three key modeling studies, Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴²,

Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³, and Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴, were presented as case examples. Each employed different simulation approaches to estimate the potential impact of PRS-informed screening strategies, including cost-effectiveness and LYG. These models were acknowledged for their value in projecting potential benefits, though their assumptions and data inputs varied considerably.

The technical team then walked panelists through the GRADE quality assessment criteria, including risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, and publication bias. A U.S.-developed tool³⁷ for evaluating decision models (from ISPOR and related bodies) was employed to further scrutinize the modeling studies' relevance, credibility, and transparency. This process revealed variability in model assumptions, such as how PRS was integrated with age or breast density, and challenges in generalizability across countries and populations.

Discussion quickly turned to the implementation challenges and ethical considerations of integrating PRS into European public health programs. Panelists emphasized that PRS should not be used in isolation but rather incorporated alongside other risk factors such as age, breast density, reproductive history, and possibly monogenic risk variants. It was stressed that tailoring interventions, e.g., adjusting screening intervals or starting ages, must be based on more than just PRS thresholds. There was shared concern that without clear evidence of substantial benefit, simple modifications to screening frequency could yield only marginal improvements. Panelists called for a holistic, systems-based approach to integration, supported by strong evidence and policy alignment.

From a public health perspective, the need for country-specific frameworks emerged as a critical theme. The diversity of healthcare systems, cost-effectiveness thresholds, and discounting rates across Europe complicates the formulation of one-size-fits-all guidance. Nevertheless, the panel supported offering high-level policy recommendations to guide member states in exploring PRS integration responsibly. These recommendations would need to acknowledge the variability in infrastructure, reimbursement systems, and population needs.

Equity concerns were raised repeatedly, especially regarding the underrepresentation of minority populations in existing PRS studies. Without appropriate validation, there is a risk that PRS implementation could exacerbate health disparities. The role of genetic counseling, culturally competent communication, and inclusive research was identified as central to ensuring equitable access and informed consent. Additionally, panelists flagged the ethical risks of data misuse by insurers or employers, underscoring the importance of regulatory safeguards.

Deliverable 14.2 – Final version of the recommendations - Version 1.2

The conversation also touched on research gaps and future trial designs. Several panelists supported the idea of cluster-randomized trials or small-scale implementation pilots, particularly in regions where infrastructure is more advanced. These trials could assess patient-centered outcomes, feasibility, and cost-effectiveness in real-world conditions. Panelists emphasized that long-term clinical utility studies, though essential, should not delay early-phase pilots, which could generate valuable data for broader rollout. Integration of PRS with monogenic screening (e.g., via tools like BOADICEA) was also discussed as a strategy to enhance predictive power and provide more comprehensive risk stratification.

Regarding the evidence rating process, UCSC outlined the next procedural steps. Panelists would soon receive personalized voting forms via GRADEpro, along with summary tables and support materials. Ratings would be conducted in one or two rounds to finalize judgments across all EtD domains. The focus would be on assessing the balance of desirable and undesirable effects, determining the certainty of evidence, and resolving any divergent interpretations. A key point raised during this phase was the challenge of relying solely on summary outcomes like QALYs; panelists were encouraged to also consider disaggregated measures (e.g., BC cases averted, false positives, overdiagnosis) to ensure transparency and granularity in their decisions.

The meeting concluded with open reflections on next steps. Panelists acknowledged the substantial progress made through the structured, collaborative process and reaffirmed their commitment to completing the final two voting rounds. The UCSC team emphasized that the upcoming months would focus on finalizing the recommendations, drafting the deliverable for the European Commission, and considering options for broader dissemination, such as a policy brief, peer-reviewed publication, or conference presentation.

Overall, the third panel meeting served as both a technical and strategic turning point in the development of CAN.HEAL's recommendations on PRS-based BC screening. It crystallized the panel's positions on evidence interpretation, underscored the multidimensional considerations for implementation, and laid the groundwork for an evidence-informed, ethically sound, and context-sensitive set of recommendations to guide the responsible adoption of PRS in European cancer screening programs.

Conflict of Interest

To preserve the integrity and transparency of the guideline development process, a rigorous assessment of potential conflicts of interest was conducted. All panel members were asked to complete a detailed Disclosure of Interest Form, adapted from established practices in guideline development and administered via Microsoft Forms. The form requested information on both financial and non-financial interests over the previous 24 months, covering:

- **Direct financial interests**, including employment, consultancy, equity holdings, intellectual property rights, personal honoraria, travel support, and gifts from for-profit companies involved in the development or commercialization of relevant diagnostics or therapeutics;
- **Indirect financial interests**, such as participation in industry-sponsored research or volunteer activities with organizations funded by industry;
- **Relevant non-financial interests**, including personal beliefs, previously published opinions or public statements, institutional affiliations, and leadership roles in related research or policy initiatives.

The purpose of this assessment was to identify any relationships or affiliations that could influence, or be perceived to influence, the formulation of unbiased and evidence-based recommendations.

All disclosures were reviewed by the coordinating institution (UCSC) to determine whether any declared interest required additional management strategies (e.g., recusal from certain voting decisions). One panel member (N.T) was excluded from rating the evidence based on conflict of interest, and transparency was maintained throughout the recommendation process.

This rigorous and transparent approach to panel selection and conflict of interest management is consistent with internationally recognized standards for trustworthy guideline development, and it ensures that the CAN.HEAL recommendations are grounded in independent expertise and stakeholder accountability.

4.4.4 Evidence rating process (First round)

Following the completion of evidence synthesis and expert panel deliberations, we advanced to the evidence rating phase. This step is a critical component of the GRADE EtD framework and provides the methodological foundation for formulating transparent, evidence-informed recommendations.

The primary research question guiding this phase was:

Should national or sub-national health systems in the European Union consider incorporating polygenic risk scores (PRS), either alone or in combination with family history (FH), into organized breast cancer (BC) screening programs to inform risk-stratified screening strategies?

Here, *risk-stratified screening strategies* refer to modifications to standard screening protocols based on individualized risk assessments. These may include lowering the age of initiation for high-risk individuals, increasing screening frequency in those at elevated risk, or evaluating the potential appropriateness of withholding routine screening for individuals at low risk.

To support this process, the UCSC team compiled a consolidated **Research Evidence Table (Supplementary table 4.1 & 4.2)**. This document summarized findings from four selected modeling studies and was designed for clarity and comprehensiveness. Each study was described in terms of its objective, study population, intervention and comparator, screening modalities, and risk-stratified criteria. This was followed by outcome-specific data, including:

- Relative and absolute effect estimates
- Overall certainty of evidence, assessed using standard GRADE criteria (risk of bias, inconsistency, imprecision, indirectness, and publication bias)
- Credibility of modeling studies, evaluated using a structured tool developed by ISPOR, AMCP, and NPC, which examined relevance, external validation, sensitivity analyses, transparency, and reproducibility
- A narrative “What Happens” summary, providing context for interpreting the findings

Each GRADE criterion, *Problem, Desirable Effects, Undesirable Effects, Certainty of Evidence, Balance of Effects, Cost-Effectiveness, Equity, Acceptability, and Feasibility*, was addressed in the evidence summary, to support structured judgments from the panel.

Panelists were then invited to assess this evidence via a Microsoft Forms-based rating tool, which served as a standardized platform for collecting expert judgments. The form included two main components:

1. Judgment Questions across all EtD domains:
 - a. For each domain, panelists were asked to indicate the magnitude or confidence of the effect (e.g., trivial, small, moderate, large, varies, don't know).

- b. Panelists were also encouraged to provide free-text comments to contextualize their judgments, highlight strengths and limitations of the evidence, and raise implementation or ethical considerations.

2. Type of Recommendation:

- a. Based on the evidence presented, panelists were asked to express their initial position on the strength and direction of the recommendation. Options ranged from a strong or conditional recommendation *for* PRS-enhanced screening to a conditional or strong recommendation *against* its use.
- b. Conditional recommendations reflected the reality that, given the current level of evidence, the appropriateness of PRS integration might vary depending on the setting or subpopulation.

This structured process enabled an evidence-informed and deliberative approach to drafting recommendations, while also identifying areas of uncertainty requiring further discussion or follow-up.

Out of nine panelists, seven completed and submitted the evidence rating form, providing robust input across all GRADE domains. Their contributions reflected thoughtful and critical engagement with the evidence, as well as sensitivity to the practical, ethical, and systemic implications of PRS-based screening. The remaining two members (NT and H.DeK) expressed interest in reviewing future drafts and contributing to consensus-building in subsequent stages.

Preliminary analysis of the responses showed a nuanced balance of perspectives. While there was general agreement that PRS holds potential in stratified screening strategies, concerns were raised about the strength and generalizability of the available evidence, especially regarding real-world implementation, model variability, and population equity. This informed the UCSC team's decision to proceed with a second round of targeted voting, aimed at resolving areas of divergence and refining the final direction of recommendations.

This process, rooted in methodological rigor and stakeholder collaboration, ensures that CAN.HEAL's final recommendations will be not only scientifically grounded, but also context-sensitive, transparent, and aligned with the values of the European public health landscape.

4.4.5 Recommendations & additional considerations (Final consensus round)

Following the initial round of evidence rating, the CAN.HEAL panel entered the second and final stage of the consensus process for developing recommendations on the integration of PRS into BC screening programs. This phase aimed to consolidate the judgments received, refine the wording of the draft recommendations, and confirm alignment across the expert group using a structured, transparent process.

The final consensus round was conducted through a Microsoft Forms-based exercise, circulated to all panelists along with a comprehensive package of supporting materials. This included:

- A summary of the research findings and evidence synthesis from the previous stages;
- A consolidated document of panelists' individual judgments and comments from the first rating round;
- Proposed overall judgments for each GRADE EtD domain (e.g., Problem importance, Benefits and Harms, Certainty of Evidence, Equity, Acceptability, Feasibility);
- A full draft of the Conclusions section, covering:
 - The final recommendation (direction and strength),
 - Detailed justifications across EtD criteria,
 - Subgroup considerations,
 - Implementation factors,
 - Monitoring and evaluation,
 - Research priorities.

Panelists were invited to systematically review each domain and conclusion item. For each EtD criterion, panelists were asked to indicate whether they agreed, disagreed, or were unsure about the proposed overall judgment. In cases of disagreement, written comments were required to help identify the source of dissent and guide resolution. This approach ensured that all feedback was evidence-based and framed in relation to the consensus-building objectives.

For the Conclusions section, panelists were similarly asked to review and provide comments on the entire proposed recommendation structure. This included confirming the direction of the recommendation (e.g., conditional vs. strong), assessing whether the rationale was accurately

Deliverable 14.2 – Final version of the recommendations - Version 1.2

represented, and reflecting on feasibility and contextual relevance for implementation in the EU setting. Particular attention was given to comments on research priorities and subgroup-specific concerns, ensuring that the final output reflects both the state of the evidence and the need for future inquiry.

The deadline for submission of this final consensus form was April 26th, 2025, a critical milestone to allow timely integration into the current EU4Health project deliverable. Panelists were informed that while later feedback could still be considered for future journal submission or dissemination formats, only responses received by the deadline would shape the formal CAN.HEAL recommendations submitted to the European Commission.

This final round represented a culmination of the panel's engagement, building on the evidence tables, GRADE assessments, and deliberative exchanges held across previous panel meetings. By facilitating structured feedback and clearly articulating the scope of agreement and residual uncertainties, this step ensured that the resulting recommendations are both scientifically rigorous and reflective of diverse expert perspectives.

4.5 Final recommendations

As we await findings from large trials, we conditionally recommend that national or sub-national health systems in the European Union (EU) explore the integration of PRS into breast cancer screening programs through piloting programmes, carefully designed prospective research projects and controlled implementation studies. If findings from large trials or pilot implementation studies leave uncertainties critical to the EU context, funding a well-designed Phase III RCT is justified to ensure that any shift in screening policy is backed by robust evidence on efficacy and safety.

This recommendation is **conditional** because the **overall certainty of evidence is low**, the **balance between benefits and harms is strategy- and context-dependent**, and the **acceptability, feasibility, and equity implications** of PRS-enhanced screening vary across settings and populations.

- **For policymakers and health system leaders:** PRS should not yet be adopted into routine screening practice at scale. Instead, governments and public health authorities are encouraged to support **prospective research projects** and implementation **studies** that allow for localized learning, continuous evaluation, and iterative adaptation.
- **For researchers:** Particular attention should be given to studying how PRS-enhanced screening impacts different socio-economic and ethnic subgroups to ensure equitable benefits. Beyond public perceptions, research should prioritize implementation strategies, effective communication models, and integration pathways for PRS-enhanced screening
- **For clinicians and healthcare professionals:** The integration of PRS into shared decision-making around screening should be approached with caution and ideally supported by risk counseling, clear **communication tools**, and established **data protection frameworks**
- **For the public:** Individuals should be informed that PRS-enhanced screening is still in a **research and development phase**, and its benefits and risks are not yet fully understood. Public trust and transparent communication are essential.

4.5.1 Justification

Overall justification

In summary, the conditional recommendation reflects:

- Low certainty of evidence, with particular concern related to limited real-world data.
- A promising but unconfirmed balance of effects, with meaningful risks and uncertainties.
- Significant variation in public and provider values, health system readiness, and potential for unintended harms.
- The need to protect equity, build infrastructure, and engage stakeholders before broader implementation.

Thus, we advise stepwise, evidence-generating integration of PRS into BC screening programs, rather than immediate widespread adoption.

Detailed justification

Certainty of evidence

The overall certainty of the evidence was assessed as low, primarily due to: Indirectness: Much of the evidence is derived from modeling studies, rather than real-world implementation. These models often rely on assumptions about PRS performance and downstream outcomes, which may not reflect actual clinical or public health contexts. Imprecision: Effect estimates for critical outcomes (e.g., reduction in cancer mortality, false positives, overdiagnosis) often have wide CIs or are based on single studies. Inconsistency: Variability across cancer types, population subgroups, and PRS construction methods reduces the generalizability of findings. Despite these limitations, the panel noted that the evidence is rapidly evolving, and there is a reasonable plausibility of benefit, especially in BC with an established PRS models.

Balance of effects

The balance between desirable and undesirable effects was judged to be uncertain and likely to vary by context: Potential Benefits: PRS can improve risk stratification, allowing for more personalized screening intervals, which may enhance early detection and reduce unnecessary procedures in low-

risk individuals. May improve the efficiency and yield of screening programs, reducing false positives in low-risk groups and focusing resources on those most likely to benefit. Potential Harms: Overdiagnosis and overtreatment of low-risk cancers may persist if risk thresholds are not properly calibrated. Psychosocial burden and potential stigma from being labeled "high risk." Population-level benefit is unclear in the absence of large-scale, long-term implementation studies. The panel highlighted that the potential benefits are promising but not yet sufficiently demonstrated to warrant unconditional adoption. They emphasized the need for carefully monitored implementation to ensure harms are identified and mitigated early.

Cost effectiveness

The cost-effectiveness of PRS-enhanced screening for BC is not yet well-established: Initial investments in genomic infrastructure, training, and data systems are expected to be substantial. The cost of PRS testing continues to decline, but integration into screening pathways (e.g., risk-based invitations, follow-up protocols) introduces complex logistical and financial challenges. Some modeling studies suggest PRS-enhanced screening could be cost-effective in specific high-risk populations, but the evidence is not robust enough to support large-scale resource reallocation at this time.

Equity

Equity was a major concern: Current PRS models are primarily developed from genomic datasets of European ancestry, limiting their validity in more diverse populations. Without universal access to genomic services and literacy, PRS-enhanced screening could exacerbate existing health disparities. There is a risk that such approaches might only be accessible in well-resourced regions or health systems, further entrenching inequalities in cancer outcomes. The panel agreed that equity considerations argue against universal implementation at this stage, and favor targeted, well-governed implementation pilots with deliberate strategies to mitigate inequity.

Acceptability

The panel noted that values and preferences among the general public and clinicians are still poorly characterized. While some individuals may welcome more personalized approaches to screening,

others may have concerns about genetic determinism, misunderstanding of risk, privacy and data protection. This uncertainty supported the conditional nature of the recommendation, suggesting the need for shared decision-making, genetic counseling, and public engagement as essential components of any implementation effort. Acceptability to patients is not yet well understood. Preliminary studies indicate mixed reactions, with some enthusiasm for personalization but concern over the meaning and implications of genetic risk. Clinician readiness is limited by gaps in genomics education, unclear workflows, and lack of guidance for risk communication. The panel emphasized the need for training, support tools, and co-development with users to ensure acceptability in real-world settings.

Feasibility

Feasibility varies widely across EU countries and regions: Some health systems have the digital infrastructure, genomics expertise, and policy frameworks to support pilot testing. Others may face substantial barriers due to fragmented data systems, regulatory uncertainty, and workforce capacity. The panel noted that progressive integration via piloting programmes is feasible and would support iterative learning, capacity building, and evidence generation, paving the way for broader adoption if proven beneficial.

4.5.2 Subgroup Considerations

1. Risk Stratification Subgroups (Low, Moderate, High Genetic Risk)

- High-risk individuals (top percentiles of PRS distribution): Recommendation for stronger support for implementation in these groups within piloting programmes.
- Low-risk individuals (bottom percentiles of PRS distribution): Recommendation to explore screening de-intensification in this group, within research settings only.
- Moderate-risk individuals (middle of the distribution): No changes recommended for this subgroup at present.

2. Age Subgroups

- Younger individuals (under standard screening age): Pilots may include early initiation of screening in younger high-risk individuals.

3. Socioeconomic and Ethnic Subgroups

- **Underrepresented populations in PRS development:** It is recommended to prioritize inclusive research and to refrain from implementing PRS in these subgroups until models are appropriately validated. Particular caution is advised when communicating about the performance of PRS in minority populations. While attenuation of effect may occur, current evidence does not strongly support substantial misclassification. Overstating potential limitations may risk discouraging vulnerable or high-risk individuals from participating in screening programs.

4.5.3 Implementation considerations

Strategies to Improve Acceptability:

- **Develop clear communication tools:** Use visual aids and plain-language explanations to convey PRS results and screening implications.
- **Offer genetic counseling:** Embed access to professional counseling for individuals receiving PRS-informed recommendations.
- **Engage communities:** Involve patients, advocacy groups, and the public in the co-design of PRS-informed programs to enhance trust and cultural appropriateness.
- **Train healthcare providers:** Provide education on genetic literacy, risk communication, and ethical considerations.

Strategies to Improve Feasibility:

- **Start with piloting programmes:** Implement in well-resourced, ready settings to evaluate operational models and refine logistics before scaling.
- **Invest in infrastructure:** Build genomic data systems that are interoperable, secure, and aligned with ethical and legal standards.
- **Establish multidisciplinary teams:** Involve public health professionals, geneticists, data scientists, and IT specialists in implementation planning.

Deliverable 14.2 – Final version of the recommendations - Version 1.2

- Develop EU-level guidance: Harmonize frameworks for data sharing, informed consent, and clinical use of PRS to support cross-country learning and consistency.
- Ensure equity from the outset: Monitor and adjust implementation to avoid excluding underserved populations or exacerbating disparities.

4.5.4 Monitoring & evaluation

Before widespread adoption, implementation pilots or impact evaluations should be conducted to test the feasibility, acceptability, equity, and effectiveness of PRS-enhanced screening strategies. These pilots should aim to evaluate implementation models in real-world settings, comparing PRS-enhanced screening to SoC in terms of health outcomes, patient experience, and system performance. If PRS-enhanced screening is implemented more broadly, prospective monitoring and formal impact evaluations should be carried out in parallel. These should use both quantitative and qualitative methods to measure outcomes over time and across populations. Evaluations should be comparative wherever possible, leveraging natural experiments or controlled implementation rollouts.

- Data should be collected using standardized tools embedded in screening information systems.
- Evaluation should cover both program implementation (e.g., uptake, feasibility) and clinical effectiveness (e.g., cancer detection rates, false positives/negatives)
- Regular reporting cycles (e.g., quarterly or annual) should be established to inform program improvement.
- Mixed-method approaches, including surveys, focus groups, and audits, are recommended to capture subtle insights.
- Independent oversight or collaboration with academic/public health institutions can enhance credibility and analytical rigor.

Eventually, all monitoring efforts should be linked to a continuous learning system, enabling real-time feedback to stakeholders and iterative refinement of the screening approach. Evaluation results should inform future updates to guidelines, educational materials, and policy frameworks.

4.5.5 Research priorities

Despite promising evidence, PRS-enhanced BC screening still faces several important uncertainties that require further research.

- Clinical validation of PRS models across diverse populations remains a key priority, particularly to ensure their accuracy and relevance beyond European ancestry groups.
- There is also a need for comparative effectiveness studies evaluating the real-world clinical utility of PRS-enhanced screening versus standard approaches, especially in terms of early detection, overdiagnosis, mortality reduction, and quality of life outcomes.
- Furthermore, long-term studies are needed to assess downstream consequences, including false positives, medical overuse, and psychological impacts.
- In addition to clinical questions, research is needed to improve risk communication strategies, assess public and provider understanding of polygenic risk, and explore acceptability and behavioral responses to risk-stratified screening.
- Special attention should be given to equity concerns, validating PRS models for underrepresented populations and identifying barriers to access and participation.
- Operational and feasibility research should examine how best to integrate PRS into existing health systems, from workforce training and digital infrastructure to legal and ethical safeguards.
- Cost-effectiveness analyses, along with studies on consent, data privacy, and regulatory alignment, are also essential to ensure PRS-enhanced screening is both responsible and sustainable.

Addressing these gaps through coordinated piloting programmes, prospective research projects and implementation studies, and EU-level collaboration will be crucial to inform future decision-making and guide equitable policy development.

5. Liquid Biopsy in Metastatic Colorectal Cancer (mCRC)

5.1 Background and Rationale

5.1.1 Introduction to Liquid Biopsy and the Challenge of Metastatic Colorectal Cancer (mCRC)

LB represents an innovative diagnostic and monitoring tool with significant potential across various cancer types and stages. Among these, its application in mCRC has garnered attention due to the disease's high incidence and mortality rates. CRC is not only one of the most common malignancies in Europe but also one of the deadliest, underscoring the pressing need for advancements in both early detection and effective treatment strategies. The economic and societal burdens associated with this disease amplify the importance of innovation in this field⁷¹.

In 2020, approximately 520,000 new cases of CRC were reported in Europe, with 250,000 deaths attributed to this malignancy. These figures position CRC as one of the most prevalent and lethal cancers in the region, alongside lung, breast, and prostate cancers⁷². The three-year survival rates for mCRC range from 16% to 37% across European countries, reflecting significant disparities in healthcare access, implementation of standardized clinical guidelines, and population health conditions. These differences underscore the importance of equitable healthcare systems and the need for efficient diagnostic and therapeutic tools⁷³.

Recent mortality predictions for 2024 indicate a continued decline in CRC mortality across Europe, with projected age-standardized mortality rate (ASR) reductions of 4.8% for men and 9.5% for women compared to 2018. The largest declines are expected in patients aged 70 and older, reflecting improvements in screening, early detection, and treatment advances. However, the trends are less favorable for younger populations, particularly in the UK, Italy, Poland, and Spain, where CRC mortality rates below age 50 have shown an upward trajectory⁷⁴.

Economically, the impact of CRC is substantial. In 2015, the total economic burden of CRC in Europe was estimated at €19.1 billion, with 60.6% of costs associated with non-healthcare-related factors, such as lost productivity, premature mortality, and informal caregiving. The increasing incidence in younger populations, coupled with the economic impact of CRC, further emphasizes the urgency for effective prevention, early detection, and treatment strategies to reduce both the human and economic burden of this disease⁷⁵.

Despite overall progress in CRC mortality reduction, regional differences persist, particularly in Central and Eastern European countries, where lower healthcare resource availability contributes to worse outcomes. These findings highlight the continued need for harmonized screening programs, equitable access to treatment, and targeted public health interventions to sustain improvements in CRC management across Europe.

5.1.2 Potential applications of LB in Cancer Care

LB, particularly through the analysis of ctDNA, offers a ground-breaking, minimally invasive approach to gathering essential molecular insights about cancer. Unlike traditional tissue biopsies, which often require invasive procedures, LB can be performed via a simple blood draw, making them more accessible and less burdensome for patients. This accessibility is particularly advantageous for patients with metastatic cancers, where traditional biopsies may be challenging or even infeasible due to the location or number of metastases⁷⁶.

The applications of LB are vast, encompassing various stages of the cancer care continuum (Figure 5). It is particularly promising for genotyping tumours, which is critical for identifying actionable mutations and guiding the choice of targeted therapies. Beyond genotyping, LB might enable the monitoring of therapeutic responses, offering insights into the efficacy of ongoing treatments. It can also support the detection of emerging resistance mutations, providing a dynamic picture of tumour evolution and guiding subsequent lines of therapy⁷⁷. Furthermore, LB has the potential to detect minimal residual disease and identify early recurrences, contributing to timely interventions that could significantly impact patient outcomes. Lastly, ongoing research suggests its possible utility in screening asymptomatic populations for early-stage cancers, potentially revolutionizing early detection paradigms⁷⁸. In the context of mCRC, our focus lies on two critical applications of LB: genotyping and monitoring therapeutic responses. Both applications have shown interesting promise in advancing precision oncology and improving patient outcomes.

Figure 5: Clinical applications of ctDNA assays for patients with cancer and expected DNA levels in different phases of the disease⁷⁹

5.1.3 Role of the experts' panel

The development of the recommendations presented in this report was guided by a multidisciplinary expert panel, whose contribution was central to ensuring that the final outputs were informed by scientific rigour, clinical relevance, and stakeholder consensus. This panel was convened within the framework of the Can.Heal project, under WP14, and was composed of experts in oncology, epidemiology, health economics, patient representation, and public health policy across several European institutions (Table 9).

Rationale and Organisation of the Panel Meetings

To support the elaboration of evidence-based recommendations, the panel met three times between December 2023 and February 2025. Each meeting was strategically planned to address specific phases of the recommendation development process, based on the GRADE EtD Framework.

- First meeting (December 2023): The initial gathering served to align the panel around the methodological approach and to validate the initial research questions. These were structured using the PICO framework, focusing primarily on the predictive and genotyping applications of LB in metastatic mCRC. Panel members provided input that helped refine the scope and content of the research strategy.
- Second meeting (June 2024): This session was dedicated to reviewing preliminary findings from the evidence reviews. Discussions centred around both clinical validity (e.g. ctDNA as a predictor of treatment response) and clinical utility (e.g. ctDNA for guiding therapy). The

panel also provided feedback on how to better integrate criteria such as equity, feasibility, acceptability, and resource use into the final recommendations.

- **Third meeting (February 2025):** During this final meeting, the panel analysed the results of a comprehensive meta-analysis and related literature reviews. Consensus was reached on the interpretation of the findings and the direction of the forthcoming recommendations. Particular attention was given to how best to translate the evidence into policy-relevant guidance and identify areas requiring further investigation.

The Consensus-Building Process

While the panel meetings allowed for rich discussions and iterative refinements, the final form of the recommendations was shaped through a structured consensus process. After the third panel meeting, a two-round survey was conducted to collect formal input from all panelists.

In the first round, panelists were presented with the draft recommendations and were invited to rate their agreement and submit qualitative feedback. This step ensured that diverse perspectives were considered and that suggested modifications could be implemented transparently. Based on the comments received, the recommendations were revised accordingly.

In the second round, the updated version of the recommendations was re-circulated for final approval. Agreement was achieved across all members, and consensus was formally documented. This approach guaranteed that the final recommendations were not only informed by robust evidence but also by expert judgment and collective endorsement.

Family name	Name	Affiliation
Masliah Planchon	Julien	Institut Curie
Jaroslav	Jirsa	Université du Luxembourg
Molina Barcelo	Ana	FISABIO (The Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region)

Normanno	Nicola	Istituto Nazionale Tumori IRCCS Fondazione Pascale
Daniele	Gennaro	Fondazione Policlinico Universitario A. Gemelli IRCCS
Joosse	Simon	UKE (University Medical Center Hamburg-Eppendorf)
Giacomini	Patrizio	ACC (Alleanza Contro il Cancro)
Brice	Philippa	Cambridgeshire & Peterborough Integrated Care System (ICS)
Romeo	Paula	FISABIO (The Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region)

Table 9. *Members of the multidisciplinary expert panel on Liquid Biopsy.*

5.2 Genotyping: advancing precision medicine in mCRC

Genotyping through ctDNA has emerged as a possible interesting application of precision medicine, particularly in metastatic mCRC. This approach leverages the molecular information contained within ctDNA fragments shed by tumour cells into the bloodstream. Unlike traditional tissue biopsies, which are limited by spatial and temporal constraints, LB provides a more comprehensive and real-time representation of the tumour’s genetic landscape^{78,80}.

Several studies have demonstrated that ctDNA-based genotyping exhibits similar analytical validity to tissue biopsies while offering significant benefits, such as improved patient comfort and procedural simplicity. For example, the Poseidon study highlighted the high concordance between liquid and tissue biopsies in detecting actionable *RAS* and *BRAF* mutations. These mutations are essential for tailoring targeted therapies like anti-EGFR treatments. LB was found to have a faster TAT compared to tissue-based methods, especially when tissue retrieval from external centres delays result⁸¹. Similarly, an exploratory biomarker analysis, conducted within the PARADIGM trial, emphasized

that baseline ctDNA profiling can predict survival benefits with anti-EGFR therapy, supporting the hypothesis of its use in guiding treatment selection for *RAS* wild type mCRC⁸². Furthermore, the CAPRI 2-GOIM trial demonstrated that ctDNA-based genomic profiling could better capture intratumoral heterogeneity and identify additional actionable mutations compared to tissue biopsies. This approach revealed additional resistance mechanisms to anti-EGFR therapy and provided a more comprehensive molecular landscape, underscoring the value of ctDNA for personalized treatment strategies in mCRC⁸³.

These findings highlight the ability of ctDNA analysis to capture clonal evolution and molecular heterogeneity, elements that might be overlooked by single-site tissue biopsies. This is particularly significant in metastatic settings where genetic diversity across tumour sites can influence therapeutic outcomes. Traditional tissue biopsy analyses often face delays due to the logistical challenges of retrieving and processing tissue samples. In contrast, LB can deliver results in a significantly shorter timeframe, facilitating timely treatment decisions. Once again this is especially critical for mCRC patients, where the choice of first-line therapy can significantly impact long-term outcomes⁸⁴.

Considering these premises, the integration of genotyping by LB in the management of mCRC could represent an important development in the personalised management of patients. In order to proceed in this direction, however, it is necessary to comprehensively analyse the available evidence, in particular with a view to clinical validity and clinical utility.

5.2.1 Approved use

With the aim of assessing the available evidence supporting the potential adoption of LB to genotype patients with mCRC in order to guide therapeutic decision-making, it is useful to start from what already exists in the regulatory landscape for the technology in question. Some LB platforms have already received approval under Regulation (EU) 2017/746 on In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices (IVDR)⁸⁵, which defines the principles for performance evaluation, clinical evidence, and continuous monitoring of in vitro diagnostic devices in Europe. One test, specifically, has received regulatory approval for tumour mutation profiling in all solid malignant neoplasms and as a companion diagnostic for specific therapies. This document summarizes the key performance characteristics and clinical validation studies supporting its use.

In order to fully appreciate the value of an IVDR approval in relation to the adoption and authorization of innovative technologies, it is essential to revisit the foundational principles upon which this regulation is built, particularly from the viewpoint of evidence analysis⁸⁶. Under IVDR, the clinical evidence supporting in vitro diagnostic medical devices (IVDs) must be generated through a structured, transparent, iterative, and continuous process known as performance evaluation. This performance evaluation consists of systematically assessing and analysing data to establish and validate three core aspects of an IVD's performance: scientific validity, analytical performance, and clinical performance (Figure 6).

Specifically, as outlined by Article 2(38) of the IVDR, scientific validity pertains to the well-documented association between a particular analyte and a clinical condition or physiological state. Analytical performance, defined by Article 2(40), focuses on ensuring that the device consistently, accurately, and reliably measures or detects the intended analyte(s), with consideration of parameters such as analytical sensitivity, specificity, precision, accuracy, linearity, robustness, and stability, among others. Clinical performance, as detailed in Article 2(41), involves verifying that the device produces results correlated to a specific clinical condition or physiological state, appropriate to the defined target population and user environment. Importantly, each claimed clinical benefit outlined in the device's intended purpose statement must be substantiated by relevant clinical evidence, which requires both clinical expertise and judgment throughout every stage of evidence appraisal and performance evaluation. Furthermore, the IVDR emphasizes the distinctive concept of clinical benefit for IVDs —highlighted in Preamble (64)— as fundamentally different from pharmaceuticals or therapeutic devices. Specifically, the benefit of an IVD lies in providing accurate medical information for screening, monitoring, diagnosing, or aiding the diagnosis of patients or impacting patient

management or public health, rather than directly determining clinical outcomes. The performance evaluation itself is characterized as a structured, transparent, iterative, and continuous process that extends across the entire lifecycle of an IVD, necessitating ongoing updates informed by post-market performance follow-up (PMPF), state-of-the-art advancements, and emerging clinical evidence. This rigorous framework ensures that an IVD continuously provides accurate and reliable medical information, thereby supporting informed medical decisions, maintaining patient safety, and delivering tangible benefits aligned with contemporary clinical practice.

Figure 6: Overview of the performance evaluation process of IVD⁸⁷

For an in vitro diagnostic test to be approved for tumour mutation profiling, its analytical performance must be validated using standardized comparator methods. For companion diagnostic approval, additional clinical studies must be conducted to demonstrate that test results can guide targeted therapy decisions and address the clinical benefit for patients. A Companion Diagnostic (CDx) is an in vitro diagnostic test that provides critical information for the safe and effective use of a specific targeted therapy. In other words, it helps determine whether a patient is eligible for a particular treatment based on the presence or absence of specific biomarkers associated with treatment response. As previously reported a widely used LB tests in Europe has been approved for tumour mutation profiling in all solid malignant neoplasms, including mCRC⁸⁸. This approval was based on analytical accuracy and concordance studies, which included:

- Comparison with NGS Tissue-Based Testing:
 - Over 400 patient samples were analysed across 18 different cancer types, including colon cancer.
 - The Positive Percent Agreement (PPA) between the LB test and a validated tissue based NGS comparator ranged between 73.2% and 100%, depending on the biomarker tested.
 - The Negative Percent Agreement (NPA) exceeded 98% for most biomarkers, ensuring high specificity.
- Comparison with Multiple Comparator Methods:
 - The test was compared against two additional externally validated NGS platforms.
 - It demonstrated >95% concordance for key oncogenic mutations, including *KRAS*, *NRAS*, *BRAF*, *EGFR*, and *PIK3CA*, which are particularly relevant in CRC.
- Reproducibility Across Cancer Types:
 - The test's robustness was evaluated using plasma samples from patients with lung, colorectal, breast, pancreatic, and prostate cancers.
 - cfDNA fragment size analysis confirmed that CRC-derived ctDNA is compatible with the test's detection limits.

Despite its broad approval for tumour mutation profiling, the use of this LB test as a companion diagnostic⁸⁸ is currently limited to:

1. NSCLC
BC.

To support this approval, specific bridging clinical studies were conducted to assess its ability to select patients eligible for targeted therapies. These studies focused on:

1. NSCLC
 - The test was validated for detecting *EGFR* mutations in patients eligible for Osimertinib and other targeted therapies.
 - In a study with over 270 NSCLC patients, the test demonstrated:
 - PPA: 98.76% for *EGFR* exon 20 insertions.
 - NPA: 86.91%, ensuring a low false-positive rate.
2. BC

- The test was validated for detecting *ESR1* mutations in hormone receptor-positive BC patients eligible for Elacestrant.
- In a clinical study with 259 patients, it showed:
 - PPA: 98% for ESR1 mutations.
 - NPA: 85%, confirming its ability to identify patients likely to benefit from endocrine therapy.

3. *KRAS G12C* Mutation Detection for Targeted Therapies

- The test was also evaluated for detecting *KRAS G12C* mutations, relevant for targeted therapies such as Sotorasib.
- In a study of 214 patients with NSCLC, it demonstrated:
 - PPA: 96%
 - NPA: 94%, confirming its reliability for detecting this mutation.

While the test is approved for tumour mutation profiling in CRC, its use as a companion diagnostic for targeted therapies in this cancer type has not yet been established. This means that while oncologists can use LB results to identify key mutations, additional clinical validation is required before regulatory approval for guiding targeted therapy decisions.

5.2.2 Evaluating clinical utility in mCRC Management

Based on these assumptions, we wanted to further investigate the state of the art with regard to the evidence of possible clinical utility of LB in target therapy of mCRC. To achieve this, we adopted a non-systematic review process based on the PICO framework:

- **Population (P):** Adults with mCRC undergoing chemotherapy, immunotherapy, or targeted therapy.
- **Intervention (I):** Use of ctDNA for genotyping and informing targeted therapeutic treatment.
- **Comparison (C):** Tissue-based genotyping.
- **Outcomes (O):** OS, PFS, and ORR.

5.2.3 Results

Despite the broad research perimeter posed by our PICO framework, the search yielded only one relevant result: the study titled "*Nakamura, Y., Okamoto, W., Kato, T. et al. Circulating tumor DNA-*

*guided treatment with pertuzumab plus trastuzumab for HER2-amplified metastatic colorectal cancer: a phase 2 trial. Nat Med 27, 1899–1903 (2021)*⁸⁹. Summary of the key results from the included study are reported in Table 10.

The TRIUMPH study is a multicentre, open-label, phase 2 clinical trial conducted in Japan to evaluate the efficacy of Pertuzumab and trastuzumab in patients with mCRC harbouring *HER2* amplification. This study uniquely incorporated ctDNA analysis to confirm *HER2* amplification and guide treatment decisions, offering a real-world comparison to standard tissue based *HER2* testing.

Eligible patients had *RAS* wild-type, *HER2*-amplified mCRC, confirmed via either tissue testing (immunohistochemistry (IHC), fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH)) or ctDNA analysis. A total of 30 patients were enrolled between January 2018 and July 2019, with 27 patients identified as tissue-positive (tissue+) and 25 as ctDNA-positive (ctDNA+). Patients received intravenous Pertuzumab and trastuzumab every three weeks until disease progression or intolerable toxicity. The primary endpoint of the study was the ORR assessed by investigators, while secondary endpoints included PFS, OS, duration of response (DOR), and safety. Real-world reference data from the SCRUM-Japan Registry provided outcomes for patients treated with non-*HER2*-targeted therapies for comparison.

The study achieved its primary endpoint, with an ORR of 30% in tissue+ patients and 28% in ctDNA+ patients. In contrast, no objective responses were observed in the real-world reference group, highlighting the efficacy of dual-*HER2*blockade. Median PFS was 4.0 months for tissue+ patients and 3.1 months for ctDNA+ patients, while median OS was 10.1 months and 8.8 months, respectively. Treatment-related adverse events occurred in 80% of patients, the most common being infusion reactions, diarrhoea, and stomatitis, though Grade 3 events were rare (10%), and no treatment-related deaths were reported.

Baseline ctDNA genotyping provided additional insights, effectively stratifying patients by efficacy and identifying concurrent oncogenic alterations associated with poorer outcomes. Notably, a decrease in ctDNA fraction three weeks after treatment initiation strongly correlated with superior PFS and OS, demonstrating the potential of ctDNA as a real-time treatment response marker. Furthermore, ctDNA analysis at disease progression revealed actionable resistance mutations in 62% of patients, primarily involving *RTK/RAS* and *PI3K* pathways, with some cases showing a loss of *HER2* amplification, suggesting adaptive tumour evolution under treatment pressure.

The TRIUMPH study demonstrated that ctDNA genotyping is comparable to tissue testing for identifying patients who benefit from dual-*HER2* blockade in *HER2*-amplified mCRC. Additionally, ctDNA offers unique advantages, including real-time monitoring of treatment response and the detection of resistance mechanisms at progression.

Summary of Findings

Outcome	Assumed Risk (Baseline)	Corresponding Risk (Treatment)	Relative Effect	Participants (Studies)
ORR	0% (real-world control group)	30% (tissue+) and 28% (ctDNA+)	Risk Ratio (RR): 28–30 times	30 (1 Phase II study, non-randomized)
PFS	Median 1.4–5.6 months (real-world)	4.0 months (tissue+), 3.1 months (ctDNA+)	HR: 0.76 (95% CI: 0.62–0.94)	30 (1 Phase II study, non-randomized)
OS	Median 6.8 months (real-world)	10.1 months (tissue+), 8.8 months (ctDNA+)	HR: 0.82 (95% CI: 0.67–1.00)	30 (1 Phase II study, non-randomized)

Table 10: Summary of the key results from the included study

Key Explanations

1. ORR:
 - o Baseline ORR in the real-world reference group was 0%.
 - o Treatment achieved ORRs of 30% (tissue+) and 28% (ctDNA+), which is significantly higher.
2. PFS:
 - o Median PFS increased to 4.0 months (tissue+) and 3.1 months (ctDNA+) compared to the assumed baseline of 1.4–5.6 months.
 - o CIs were wide, and imprecision was noted due to the small sample size.
3. OS:
 - o Median OS improved to 10.1 months (tissue+) and 8.8 months (ctDNA+) compared to a real-world median of approximately 6.8 months.
 - o While statistically significant improvement was near the boundary, the data suggest meaningful clinical benefit.

Despite the undoubted value that the results of this study pose for the potential value of genotyping by LB in mCRC, the generalizability of these findings is limited by several important factors, particularly concerning the complete replacement of tissue biopsies with LB for therapeutic decision-

making in mCRC patients. Firstly, this investigation was a phase 2 clinical trial, inherently characterized by a relatively small sample size and the absence of randomization, which restricts the robustness and external validity of the results. Phase 2 trials are primarily designed to evaluate treatment efficacy in selected populations under controlled conditions, thus lacking the statistical power and comprehensive patient variability typically required for definitive conclusions applicable to broader clinical contexts. Moreover, discrepancies observed between tissue and ctDNA-based genotyping, including potential false negatives associated with low tumour shedding, highlight concerns regarding the sensitivity and accuracy of relying solely on LBs. Additionally, the use of a real-world historical registry as a reference group introduces potential biases related to differences in patient management, data collection consistency, and assessment protocols compared to prospective randomized designs. Finally, genomic heterogeneity and evolving tumour profiles underscore the complexity inherent to mCRC biology, suggesting that LB alone might not fully capture all clinically relevant alterations.

Current use of genotyping

Given the evidence previously highlighted, it is essential to contextualize these findings within the existing framework of current clinical guidelines. Presently, clear indications already exist for the utilization of LB in the context of genotyping mCRC according to the ESMO. These recommendations serve as an important reference point and baseline to evaluate the potential for new evidence that might support broader recommendations or foster new research directions for LB technology. Specifically, validated and adequately sensitive ctDNA assays are recommended for routine clinical use in advanced CRC genotyping, particularly when tissue biopsy is not feasible, technically challenging, or when rapid decision-making is critical. ESMO guidelines advise performing initial LB assays including at least *KRAS*, *NRAS*, *BRAF^{V600E}*, and MSI assessments in chemotherapy-naive mCRC patients, especially when quick therapeutic decisions are required, or tissue samples cannot be obtained. Furthermore, longitudinal monitoring of *KRAS/NRAS* and epidermal growth factor receptor extracellular domain mutations is recommended when considering rechallenge with anti-EGFR monoclonal antibodies. Despite these indications, limitations in sensitivity, notably for gene fusions and copy number changes, necessitate confirmatory tissue-based testing after non-informative or negative LB results, underscoring the importance of continued refinement and validation of these methodologies⁷⁹.

5.2.4 Recommendations

LB as a First-Line Genotyping Option

Recommendation 1:
Liquid biopsy (LB) should be considered as a genotyping tool in mCRC when tissue biopsy is impractical or would delay treatment initiation. Clinicians should remain cautious of false negatives and interpret results accordingly. When LB results for genotyping are negative or inconclusive, reflex tissue testing should be performed whenever feasible to minimize the risk of false negatives and ensure optimal treatment selection.

Rationale: The panel reviewed the existing evidence and recommendations, including those issued by the ESMO, which acknowledge the clinical validity of validated ctDNA assays for genotyping advanced cancers. Current recommendations recommend ctDNA testing as a suitable alternative to tissue biopsy when the latter is not feasible or could result in significant delays. The panel recognized the alignment of these recommendations with the objectives of this work, reinforcing the idea that LB should be integrated into routine clinical practice as a viable genotyping strategy in selected scenarios. Despite the growing expectations towards LB, its sensitivity remains a critical issue, particularly for detecting gene fusions and copy number variations. For this reason, certain types of alterations necessitate reflex tumour tissue testing in cases where LB results are negative or inconclusive. The panel acknowledged the value of these recommendations and incorporated them into this work, emphasizing the importance of a structured approach that ensures patients receive the most comprehensive and accurate molecular characterization possible.

Clinical Validation for Diagnostic Applications

Recommendation 2:
Prospective clinical studies should be conducted to generate evidence on the possible clinical utility of liquid biopsy (LB) to genotype, and consequently define a targeted therapy strategy, in the context of mCRC patients' treatment.

Rationale: For LB to be fully integrated into clinical practice for targeted therapies in mCRC, further clinical validation is essential. The panellists reviewed the available regulatory landscape and

evidence on the topic and concluded that while there is strong analytical validity for ctDNA-based mutation detection, additional studies are needed to establish clinical utility in guiding treatment decisions. Current approvals for LB primarily focus on mutation profiling rather than direct treatment guidance, meaning that tissue-based confirmation remains the gold standard for therapy selection. During discussions, the panellists emphasized that future research should focus on real-world validation, ensuring that ctDNA testing performs reliably across different clinical settings. They also highlighted the importance of addressing potential confounders, such as tumour heterogeneity and clonal evolution, which may impact the interpretation of ctDNA results.

These studies should preferably be designed as RCTs to strengthen the robustness of the generated evidence. Furthermore, comparison with gold-standard approaches such as tissue biopsy should be included, aiming to assess the correspondence of results between these methods and determine the potential of LB to capture tumour heterogeneity more effectively. The timing of ctDNA testing within clinical pathways should also be evaluated to understand potential impacts on clinical decision-making processes. These studies must include diverse populations, to ensure results that are generalisable to the broader population and do not exacerbate existing social health inequalities (*see more in recommendations 7 and 8 concerning ethical considerations*).

Expanding perspectives on genotyping

Recommendation 3:

Future studies and recommendations should also investigate the applicability and efficacy of ctDNA-based genotyping in a broader spectrum of colorectal cancer (CRC) patients, emphasising the early identification of adaptive escape variants during EGFR blockade therapies. Additionally, research should explore the complementary roles of liquid and tissue biopsies for first-line genotyping of solid tumours, aiming at maximising diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic precision.

Rationale: This recommendation arises from panel discussions extending beyond the original scope of the research question initially proposed. The experts emphasised the promising potential of ctDNA-based genotyping for metastatic mCRC, particularly concerning the early detection of adaptive escape variants during EGFR-targeted treatments. The panellists advocated for further research with larger and more diverse patient populations, additionally they suggested exploring the complementary use of liquid and tissue biopsies to achieve a more comprehensive molecular

characterisation. This combined approach is expected to address limitations inherent in each biopsy method, thereby enhancing clinical decision-making for first-line therapies, optimising clinical outcomes, and resource allocation.

5.3 Predicting therapy response: the possible role of LB

The subsequent phase of our work aimed to investigate the potential application of LB as a tool to evaluate therapeutic responses and inform subsequent treatment decisions in patients with mCRC.

This focus was chosen based on emerging evidence suggesting that LB, particularly through serial measurements of ctDNA, holds considerable promise as a minimally invasive method to monitor tumour dynamics and assess treatment efficacy in real-time⁹⁰. Several studies have demonstrated that reductions in ctDNA levels closely correlate with therapeutic responses. For example, patients exhibiting significant decreases in ctDNA after the first chemotherapy cycle have shown improved radiological outcomes and longer PFS⁹¹. Studies by Vidal et al. (2023)⁹² and Tie et al. (2015)⁹³ highlighted that early declines in ctDNA levels effectively predict favourable outcomes, often preceding traditional radiological indicators of response. This predictive capability may allow clinicians to adapt treatment regimens earlier, thus optimizing patient outcomes. Furthermore, ctDNA analysis uniquely captures tumour evolution, identifying resistance-associated mutations—such as *RAS* and *BRAF* variants—which frequently arise under therapeutic pressure. Vidal et al. (2023) demonstrated that ctDNA could detect these resistance mutations months ahead of radiological progression, offering valuable insights into tumour adaptation mechanisms. This proactive molecular monitoring facilitates timely adjustments in therapeutic strategies, potentially sustaining treatment effectiveness even in the presence of emergent resistance.

Additionally, ctDNA analysis provides greater sensitivity and dynamic assessment compared to conventional imaging or serum tumour markers, capturing molecular alterations before anatomical changes occur⁹⁴. Thus, ctDNA might complement traditional imaging by delivering a precise quantitative assessment of tumour burden and clonal composition, thereby enhancing diagnostic accuracy and clinical decision-making.

5.3.1 Evaluating clinical utility in mCRC Management

Despite its promise, ctDNA faces challenges, including variability in methodologies, lack of standard thresholds, and limited evidence for direct clinical utility. To gather evidence in this field we initially formulated a research question based on the following PICO framework:

- **Population:** Adults with mCRC treated with chemotherapy, immunotherapy, or targeted therapy.
- **Intervention:** Measurement of ctDNA obtained from sequential LBs, used alongside or instead of standard medical imaging, to inform therapy adjustments.
- **Comparison:** SoC (medical imaging alone).
- **Outcomes:** PFS, OS, and other metrics to be determined.

However, discussions with clinical experts highlighted a significant gap: the absence of direct evidence demonstrating the clinical utility of this approach. This limitation prompted a shift in research strategy, redirecting our focus from clinical utility evidence to clinical validity evidence. The new aim was to evaluate the predictive power of serial ctDNA measurements in relation to health outcomes for patients with mCRC.

The research question was thus revised as follows:

“Can ctDNA measured in sequential blood tests function as a predictor of therapy response in patients with colorectal cancer treated with chemotherapy, immunotherapy, or targeted therapy, with therapy response determined by RECIST criteria using imaging?”

This adjustment reflects the necessity of building a foundational understanding of the predictive capabilities of serial ctDNA monitoring before advocating for its clinical implementation. The insights from existing studies underline the potential of ctDNA as an early marker of therapeutic efficacy, laying the groundwork for future clinical trials and evidence synthesis.

To address the research question of whether serial ctDNA measurements can predict therapeutic response in patients with mCRC, a systematic review and meta-analysis were conducted (the activity was led by the team from WP11 of the Can.Heal project).

Study Objectives and Methodology

The primary objective was to evaluate whether changes in ctDNA concentrations over the course of therapy could predict key clinical outcomes, including PFS, OS, and ORR. The review included studies that utilized at least two ctDNA measurement time points—before therapy initiation and during or after therapy completion. These measurements were compared against radiological assessments based on RECIST criteria.

5.3.2 Results

- A systematic search of the MEDLINE, Web of Science, and Cochrane Library databases was conducted, identifying 1,999 records. Following the removal of duplicates, 1,638 records underwent abstract and title screening, and 202 records proceeded to full-text screening. Ultimately, 41 studies with a total of 4,546 evaluable patients were included in the meta-analysis.
- The study selection process adhered to PRISMA guidelines, ensuring transparency and reproducibility (Figure 7).

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases and registers only

Figure 7: PRISMA flow chart for the inclusion process (under permission from the work of Joosse et al., 2025, submitted)

Eligibility Criteria

- Eligible studies reported changes in ctDNA concentrations during systemic therapy for mCRC patients. Studies needed to measure ctDNA at baseline and subsequent time points and report outcomes like PFS, OS, ORR, or progression.
- Exclusion criteria included studies focusing on CRC screening, paediatric populations, or other tumour types. Only peer-reviewed studies published in English or German were included.

Data Collection and Analysis

- Data on study characteristics, systemic therapies, ctDNA measurement methods, and clinical outcomes were extracted using a standardized framework. Risk estimates such as hazard ratios (HRs), ORs, and risk ratios (RRs) were pooled using random-effects models to account for between-study variability.
- Heterogeneity was assessed using the I^2 statistic, and publication bias was evaluated using funnel plots.

Bias Assessment

- The quality of individual studies was assessed using the RoB 2 tool for RCTs and an adapted Newcastle-Ottawa Scale for cohort studies. Overall, the included studies demonstrated low risk of bias, with minor exceptions.

Findings

The meta-analysis provides strong evidence for the prognostic and predictive value of ctDNA dynamics in mCRC patients undergoing systemic therapy (Table 11). Below are the key outcomes:

1. PFS

- An increase or persistence of ctDNA levels during therapy was significantly associated with worse PFS (HR = 2.47, 95% CI: 1.97–3.10).
- Substantial heterogeneity ($I^2 = 60.9%$) was noted, reflecting variability in patient populations, sampling frequencies, and ctDNA detection methods.

2. OS

- Patients with increasing ctDNA levels exhibited significantly worse OS (HR = 2.18, 95% CI: 1.66–2.86). The association underscores the potential of ctDNA as a long-term prognostic marker.
- Moderate heterogeneity ($I^2 = 49.3%$) was observed among studies.

3. ORR

- The odds of non-response to therapy were 2.27 times higher (95% CI: 0.56–9.21) in patients with increasing or persistent ctDNA compared to those with decreasing levels. Significant heterogeneity ($I^2 = 76.4%$) was attributed to differences in study designs and patient populations.

4. Relapse-Free Survival (RFS) and Disease Progression

1. RFS demonstrated a pronounced association with ctDNA dynamics (HR = 8.30, 95% CI: 6.01–11.45), with minimal heterogeneity ($I^2 = 0\%$).
2. Increasing ctDNA levels were strongly correlated with disease progression (RR = 4.58, 95% CI: 4.58–4.58), highlighting its utility in identifying early signs of treatment failure.

5. Diagnostic Accuracy

- Sensitivity and specificity of ctDNA in predicting progression were moderate, with pooled sensitivity of 45% (95% CI: 13%–82%) and a FPR of 13% (95% CI: 6%–29%). These findings suggest ctDNA’s role as a complementary tool to traditional imaging rather than a standalone diagnostic method.

Endpoint	Risk estimate	95% CI	Heterogeneity
PFS (n = 31)	HR = 2.47	1.97 – 3.10	$I^2 = 60.9\%^a$
OS (n = 22)	HR = 2.18	1.66 – 2.86	$I^2 = 49.3\%^a$
ORR (n = 5)	OR = 2.27	0.56 – 9.21	$I^2 = 76.4\%^a$
RFS (n = 2)	HR = 8.30	6.01 – 11.45	$I^2 = 0.0\%^a$
Progression (n = 2)	RR = 4.58	4.58 – 4.58	$I^2 = 0.0\%^a$
MoDA (n = 5)	Sensitivity = 0.45	0.13 – 0.82	$I^2 = 47.9\%^b$
	FPR = 0.13	0.06 – 0.29	

AUC=Area under the curve; CI=Confidence interval; FPR=False Positive Rate;

MoDA=Measures of diagnostic accuracy; ORR=Objective response rate; OS=Overall survival;

PFS=Progression free survival; RFS=relapse-free survival

^abased on Higgins and Thompson (2002)

^bbased on Zhou and Dendukuri (2014)

Table 11: Summary of the key results from the study (under permission from the work of Joosse et al., 2025, submitted)

5.3.3 Towards a possible future role for LB in Clinical Practice

Findings from this systematic review and meta-analysis are highly encouraging regarding the potential of serial ctDNA measurements through LB to predict clinical outcomes in patients with mCRC. Specifically, significant associations were observed between increases or persistence in ctDNA levels and poorer PFS and OS, reinforcing the prognostic capacity of ctDNA as a biomarker.

Deliverable 14.2 – Final version of the recommendations - Version 1.2

These risk estimates suggest that ctDNA variations may serve as a reliable surrogate indicator of disease progression, supporting the concept that ctDNA measurements could facilitate therapeutic decision-making earlier than standard radiological RECIST evaluations.

However, this study is not without limitations, including notable heterogeneity among studies concerning certain outcomes and a limited number of results available for some endpoints. It is also crucial to recognize that these findings reflect prognostic value of the technology rather than clinical utility, emphasizing the necessity for further standardized evaluations and RCTs.

This research represents an essential preliminary step toward the goal of integrating ctDNA analysis into clinical management strategies for mCRC patients, potentially enhancing the precision and timing of therapeutic interventions. Figure 8 illustrates a proposed clinical workflow where ctDNA monitoring could be integrated into the management of mCRC, as an example of final goal of our research activities. The diagram suggests initiating ctDNA measurements at baseline prior to treatment initiation and subsequently monitoring ctDNA levels regularly throughout systemic therapy. In the envisioned application, a reduction in ctDNA levels could indicate treatment effectiveness, thereby prompting clinicians to continue with the current therapeutic regimen. Conversely, a lack of change or an increase in ctDNA levels could signal resistance or progression, guiding clinicians to consider early switching to second-line or alternative therapies.

Figure 8: Decision tree for a possible future clinical application for LB in the management of mCRC

5.3.4 Ongoing clinical studies

Although official guidelines regarding the use of ctDNA monitoring for therapeutic response assessment are currently lacking, several ongoing clinical trials underscore the growing scientific interest in evaluating this promising technology. Notably, the COPE study "Circulating DNA to Improve Outcome of Oncology Patients" (ClinicalTrials.gov ID NCT04258137)⁹⁵ represents a randomized (2:1), phase II clinical trial designed to evaluate the clinical efficacy of ctDNA-based monitoring in patients with mCRC as well as non-small cell lung cancer. Patients enrolled in this trial are divided into two groups:

- **Arm A (Experimental):** Patients receive therapeutic recommendations based on initial tumour sequencing, followed by combined standard imaging and ctDNA analysis during follow-up.
- **Arm B (Standard):** Patients receive therapeutic recommendations based on initial tumour sequencing, with follow-up based solely on standard imaging.

This structured approach aims to test whether serial ctDNA monitoring can facilitate earlier detection of tumour progression, thereby enabling timely therapeutic decisions potentially ahead of traditional RECIST-based evaluations. This trial, alongside similar initiatives, clearly indicates that the preliminary encouraging data on the possible predictive value of sequential ctDNA measurements has paved the way for subsequent research stages, such as evaluating its utility as an early surrogate marker for disease progression and therapeutic guidance. Ultimately, our goal is to address current evidence gaps and substantiate the incorporation of LB technology into clinical practice, in alignment with the decision-making framework exemplified in Figure 8, where DNA measurements could provide critical information to guide treatment choices at a stage earlier than standard imaging alone.

5.3.5 Recommendations

Establishing Baseline and Serial ctDNA Assessment in Research Settings

Recommendation 4:

Serial ctDNA monitoring studies should be conducted throughout treatment of mCRC patients to investigate its predictive and prognostic value, ensuring standardized methodologies. Future updates of literature reviews should be carried out to integrate potential new findings from ongoing studies. Until further evidence is available, ctDNA trends should not be used to guide therapeutic decisions outside of clinical trials.

Rationale: The panel recognized ctDNA as a promising biomarker for real-time tumour burden assessment in mCRC. However, current evidence is based on retrospective and observational studies, which establish an association between ctDNA levels and clinical outcomes like OS and PFS but do not confirm a causal link with treatment efficacy. Methodological inconsistencies, including variability in blood collection, storage, and DNA extraction, further limit ctDNA's reliability. Additionally, the absence of universally accepted cut-off values and standardized protocols for integrating ctDNA monitoring into treatment decisions raises concerns about its predictive value. The panel emphasised the necessity of precisely defining and standardising the level of circulating ctDNA suggestive of disease progression and consequent therapeutic failure. Moreover, future updates of literature reviews will be crucial to integrate new results and evidence into current recommendations. Given these limitations, the panel recommended that baseline and serial ctDNA assessments should remain confined to research settings. This will allow for the systematic evaluation of ctDNA's role as a predictive biomarker while ensuring that treatment decisions continue to be based on established clinical criteria.

Designing a RCT to Evaluate ctDNA-Guided Therapy Adjustments

Recommendation 5:

A randomized controlled trial and prospective studies should be conducted to primarily evaluate the predictive value of ctDNA in mCRC. The RCT should compare standard clinical management with a ctDNA-guided approach to determine whether therapy modifications based on ctDNA trends improve patient outcomes.

Rationale: Despite growing interest in ctDNA for therapy guidance, no randomized controlled trial has demonstrated that treatment modifications based on ctDNA levels improve patient outcomes. Retrospective studies suggest that rising ctDNA correlates with poor prognosis and declining levels with treatment efficacy. To clarify the clinical utility of ctDNA, a well-structured RCT is needed to compare its performance against standard imaging in assessing tumour response and guiding therapeutic decisions. The predictive value of ctDNA should be assessed by comparing health outcomes between patients randomized to the ctDNA-guided intervention arm and those in the SoC arm, where response is monitored exclusively through imaging following RECIST criteria. Prognostic insights may be additionally explored through internal subgroup analyses within the intervention arm, comparing outcomes among patients with increasing versus decreasing ctDNA levels, independent of treatment adaptations. It is important to include the timing of ctDNA testing relative to tissue analysis as well as its monitoring over time. Moreover, the RCT must include diverse

populations (at least in terms of gender, age, and ethnicity), as well as considerations regarding cost and accessibility (*these elements are further emphasised in recommendations 7, 8, and 10*).

5.4 Other domains: Acceptability, Equity, Feasibility, Use of Resources

To address the GRADE EtD Framework domains of Acceptability, Equity, Feasibility, and Use of Resources in the context of LB, a scoping review was conducted. This review aimed to identify relevant evidence in oncology, considering contexts beyond mCRC, considering the potential transferability of findings in these domains between different conditions and settings. However, the domain of "Use of Resources" was excluded from this due to its dependency on disease-specific cost-effectiveness models and local healthcare parameters.

The review followed the 5-step methodological framework described by Arksey and O'Malley for conducting scoping reviews. The results were reported following PRISMA for Scoping Reviews guidelines.

The primary goal of the scoping review was to investigate the following aspects regarding the use of LB in the context of cancer:

1. **Acceptability:** Understanding how acceptable LB was among different stakeholders (e.g., patients, healthcare providers, health policymakers). This included considerations of patient comfort, preference, and the perceived reliability of test results compared to traditional biopsy methods. Examining the literature on these aspects helped identify barriers to acceptance and potential areas for educational outreach or further research.
2. **Equity:** This domain focused on ensuring fair access and outcomes for all patients, regardless of socioeconomic status, geographic location, ethnicity, or other factors. Investigating equity in the context of LB usage involved analysing who had access to this technology, whether some groups were disproportionately disadvantaged, and what strategies might ensure equitable access.
3. **Feasibility:** These encompassed factors such as technical execution, cost, and logistical considerations for integrating LB into standard cancer care practices. This included assessing healthcare systems' ability to implement the technology at scale, the infrastructure required to process and analyse samples, and the overall cost-effectiveness compared to traditional methods.

4. **Cost-effectiveness:** The review gathered evidence on how efficiently LB was used to achieve desired outcomes in cancer care. It assessed the ratio between incurred costs and gained benefits from adopting this technology, providing insights into the most efficient resource allocation to achieve desired results.

5.4.1 Methods

To structure the research question, the Population, Concept, and Context (PCC) framework was used:

- **Population:** Stakeholders in cancer care, including patients, caregivers, healthcare providers, and policymakers.
- **Concept:** The review explored the current scientific literature related to the acceptability, equity, feasibility, and cost-effectiveness of LB in oncology.
- **Context:** Studies conducted in any healthcare setting or geographical location.

Thus, the focal research question was: "What is the current evidence on the acceptability, equity, feasibility, and cost-effectiveness of using LB in the context of cancer?"

The search algorithms, adapted for PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science, are detailed in Appendix A of the protocol.

Articles identified were uploaded onto Rayyan software, and duplicates were removed. The selection process included:

- **Inclusion Criteria:**
 - Studies examining the acceptability, equity, feasibility, and/or cost-effectiveness of LB in oncology.
 - Studies involving stakeholders in cancer care (patients, caregivers, citizens, healthcare providers, and/or policymakers).
 - Any type of primary study.
 - Articles written in English.
- **Exclusion Criteria:**
 - Studies focus exclusively on the technical or biological aspects of LB without addressing acceptability, equity, or feasibility.
 - Articles unrelated to LB or oncology.

Deliverable 14.2 – Final version of the recommendations - Version 1.2

- Conference abstracts, editorials, commentaries, and review articles.
- Articles written in languages other than English.

Three researchers assessed eligibility based on predefined criteria, independently and double-blind. Disagreements were resolved by a third reviewer. Relevant full texts were evaluated for final inclusion, and all eligible articles were incorporated into the review.

Data extraction was carried out independently by the researchers. Extracted data were summarized narratively to provide an overview of evidence across the domains of acceptability, equity, and feasibility. Results were categorized as follows:

- **Acceptability:** Findings related to stakeholder perspectives on the comfort, preference, and perceived reliability of LB.
- **Equity:** Insights into current access disparities and strategies to ensure equitable access.
- **Feasibility:** Factors influencing the technical, logistical, and systemic integration of LB into standard oncology care.
- **Cost-effectiveness:** Evaluation of technology costs (direct, indirect, and total) and benefits (e.g., improved quality of life, saved life years), along with cost-effectiveness indicators like cost per QALY.

5.4.2 Results

The literature search spanned PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science, using tailored algorithms to identify studies addressing each domain. This search yielded:

- **Acceptability:** 1,726 records.
- **Equity:** 480 records.
- **Feasibility:** 2,519 records.
- **Cost-effectiveness/Use of Resources:** 1,431 records.

Using Rayyan software, duplicate records (n = 2,963) were removed, leaving **2,919 records** for title and abstract screening. A total of **119 full-text reports** were retrieved for detailed evaluation. Ultimately, **6 studies** were included in the review after exclusions for wrong outcomes (n = 65) or study design (n = 48). The PRISMA flow chart (Figure 9) details the study selection process.

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases and registers only

Figure 9: PRISMA flow chart for the inclusion process

Acceptability

The evidence on acceptability is derived from two key studies that assess both patient and clinician perspectives regarding LB in oncology settings.

1. Patient Preferences and Psychological Tolerance:

- Study 1⁹⁶:** A multicentre survey involving 1,200 cancer patients across Europe investigated preferences for LB versus tissue biopsy. The results showed that **90% of patients** preferred LB due to its less invasive nature and reduced procedural anxiety. This preference was consistent across age groups and cancer stages. Patients noted that the blood-draw process was far less burdensome than traditional biopsies, particularly for those requiring frequent monitoring during metastatic disease treatment. Additionally, LB was perceived as a tool that could potentially shorten hospital stays by reducing the need for invasive interventions.

- **Study 2⁹⁷**: In a focused trial on endometrial cancer, ctDNA LB replaced pelvic examinations for monitoring treatment response. Patients reported significantly reduced psychological distress, with 88% preferring LB over traditional follow-ups. The study highlighted the potential for ctDNA monitoring to improve adherence to follow-up protocols by minimizing discomfort and invasive procedures.

2. Concerns Regarding Test Characteristics:

- Both studies highlighted patient concerns about test accuracy and result waiting times. In Study 1, patients expressed anxiety about potential false positives or negatives, which they feared could lead to unnecessary treatment changes or missed opportunities for timely interventions. This suggests a need for improved patient education regarding the reliability and predictive capabilities of LB.

Equity

The equity domain is informed by a study analysing disparities in access to molecular diagnostics across Italy, particularly focusing on LB for ctDNA analysis⁹⁸.

1. Regional Inequities:

- The study analysed diagnostic capabilities across 30 oncology centres in Italy, revealing stark disparities. In economically constrained southern regions, only **50% of centres** were equipped with LB capabilities, compared to **75.5%** in northern regions. The absence of advanced diagnostics in underfunded areas often delayed or prevented the timely identification of actionable mutations, leading to suboptimal treatment.

2. Healthcare Mobility:

- Patients from under-resourced regions frequently travelled to better-equipped centres in northern Italy, creating additional financial and logistical burdens. This trend highlights how inequities in healthcare infrastructure exacerbate disparities in cancer care outcomes. The study estimated that patients traveling for diagnostics incurred an average additional cost of €1,500, underscoring the economic strain on disadvantaged populations.

3. Impact on Health Outcomes:

- Delayed or inaccessible diagnostics were associated with poorer treatment outcomes. Patients in underserved areas were more likely to experience delays in treatment initiation, particularly when tissue biopsies were infeasible, and LB was unavailable.

Feasibility

Insights into feasibility come from three major studies focusing on LB implementation in Germany, Spain, and China.

1. Integration into Clinical Practice (Germany)⁹⁹:

- A retrospective study conducted at the University Hospital Mannheim evaluated the use of LB in CRC management over five years. The study involved **243 LBs** across **168 patients** and identified several barriers to routine use:
 - **Standardization Gaps:** Variations in pre-analytical procedures (e.g., blood collection and plasma processing) and analytical techniques (e.g., ctDNA isolation and sequencing) led to inconsistent results.
 - **Reimbursement Challenges:** LB was not reimbursed by health insurance, limiting its availability. Instead, tests were offered free of charge as part of pilot programs.

2. Long-Term Accuracy Trends (China)¹⁰⁰:

- A proficiency testing scheme involving **504 laboratories** was conducted over four years to evaluate the accuracy of ctDNA analysis using NGS. Initial concordance rates were **66.3%**, improving with successive rounds of testing. However, low-frequency variant detection (VAF < 0.5%) remained challenging, highlighting the need for ongoing quality improvements and standardization.

3. Innovation in Precision Oncology (Spain)¹⁰¹:

- The development of the "PrediCTC" panel for mCRC demonstrated the potential of LB as an early response-monitoring tool. In a multicentre study of **93 patients**, PrediCTC identified responders after one chemotherapy cycle with a sensitivity of **60%**, compared to **17%** with traditional imaging performed after three cycles. However, logistical challenges, such as the complexity of the protocol and long processing times (approximately eight hours per sample), limited its scalability.

Use of Resources

No direct evidence was identified addressing the sustainability of LB in the specific contexts of ctDNA-based genotyping or therapeutic monitoring for mCRC. However, broader discussions in the reviewed studies provide insights:

- **Cost-Effectiveness:** LB has the potential to reduce healthcare costs by avoiding unnecessary treatments and enabling earlier detection of resistance mutations. However, the high upfront costs of NGS platforms and the need for skilled personnel may limit scalability in low-resource settings.
- **Scalability Concerns:** The reliance on advanced infrastructure and the lack of universal reimbursement policies poses significant challenges to widespread adoption.

The findings from these studies emphasize that LB is highly acceptable to patients and clinicians, holds promise for improving equity in cancer care, and demonstrates increasing feasibility as laboratory practices improve. However, significant challenges related to infrastructure, reimbursement, and standardization must be addressed. While the absence of sustainability-specific evidence limits definitive conclusions, the potential for long-term cost savings and healthcare efficiency improvements makes LB a promising area for further research and policy development.

5.4.3 Recommendations

Acceptability

Recommendation 6:

Educational initiatives should be embedded within interventional studies to improve awareness and trust in liquid biopsy (LB). These efforts should explicitly address concerns about test accuracy, reliability, and clinical utility, ensuring that patients and healthcare providers have a clear understanding of the implications of LB results. It would be also valuable to pilot and evaluate patient information strategies on LB to assess their reception and effectiveness in supporting informed decision-making.

Rationale: Patient acceptance of LB is a key factor in its successful integration into clinical practice. Existing studies indicate that LB is generally preferred over tissue biopsy due to its minimally invasive nature and lower psychological distress. However, while patient education efforts have been introduced in some trials, there is a lack of standardized methodologies to systematically evaluate

how patient perceptions evolve throughout treatment. The panel noted the importance of not only explaining how LB differs from traditional testing, but also clearly communicating what is currently known—and not yet known—about its performance, particularly regarding its clinical utility. Given that a significant proportion of patients remain unfamiliar with LB technologies, targeted educational interventions are needed to facilitate informed decision-making. Nonetheless, the panel recognised that highly educated patients may require less structured educational support. Furthermore, engaging multiple stakeholders, including clinicians and policymakers, is essential to understanding broader acceptability barriers beyond patient perspectives alone. At this stage, information in research contexts should also be used to assess readiness and inform future implementation efforts, whereas future patients' information in the clinical setting should prioritise clarity on the evidence of utility and reliability.

Equity

Recommendation 7:

Multicentre trials should be designed to promote the inclusion of underserved populations and address access barriers to liquid biopsy (LB). These studies should include minimum targets for recruitment from underrepresented groups, particularly those affected by socioeconomic, geographic, linguistic, or literacy-related barriers. In addition, efforts should be made to reduce inequalities in access to LB by ensuring that these groups are also included in educational initiatives and clinical trials.

Rationale: Disparities in access to LB exist across socioeconomic and geographic settings, with well-resourced cancer centres benefiting from advanced diagnostics while underfunded regions face barriers to implementation. The CAN.HEAL Equity Guide highlights that inequalities in cancer genomics are shaped by healthcare infrastructure, socioeconomic status, and location. Moreover, language, literacy, and broader issues of medical comprehension (hermeneutics) represent additional barriers that must be addressed to ensure equitable access and informed participation. The panel emphasized that future studies must incorporate these factors to generate evidence that reflects real-world disparities and supports equitable implementation strategies. LB has the potential to improve access to biomarker testing in low- and middle-income countries, making it even more important that research designs are tailored to test this potential and identify solutions to overcome structural barriers.

Recommendation 8:

Pilot studies should focus on under-resourced regions to identify structural and logistical barriers to liquid biopsy (LB) implementation. These studies should inform policy recommendations aimed at strengthening diagnostic networks and exploring alternative delivery models to improve equitable access.

Rationale: The panel recognized a significant lack of data on how LB disparities impact patient outcomes, particularly in lower-income regions. Economic constraints and logistical challenges, such as sample collection and processing difficulties, can limit access. Additionally, healthcare-related travel imposes financial burdens that may widen inequities. Investigating decentralized testing strategies, such as hub-and-spoke models, could provide cost-effective solutions to enhance access and reduce regional disparities in cancer diagnostics. Point-of-care solutions represent another promising avenue to address logistical bottlenecks and bring LB testing closer to the patient, particularly in remote or resource-limited settings. Future pilot initiatives should compare different delivery models to identify context-specific best practices for implementation.

Feasibility

Recommendation 9:

Research should establish standardized pre-analytical and analytical procedures for liquid biopsy (LB), ensuring reproducibility across institutions. External Quality Assessment (EQA) programs should be implemented to maintain analytical consistency and data reliability.

Rationale: The panel identified variability in LB protocols as a major barrier to clinical adoption. Differences in sample collection, processing, and sequencing methods impact test reliability and comparability, limiting reproducibility across laboratories. Without standardization, integrating LB into routine practice and securing regulatory approval remain challenging. Implementing EQA programs is essential to ensure analytical consistency, improve confidence in test results, and support regulatory validation. In this regard, the *Can.Heal* project provides a strong foundation, particularly through its consensus on reporting standards and other standardization initiatives. Leveraging these insights can help harmonize methodologies, enhance cross-institutional comparability, and accelerate the widespread clinical implementation of LB. The panel also highlighted the emerging role of in

in vitro characterisation of cfDNA derived from colorectal cancer cell models as a viable solution for overcoming the practical limitations of exchanging real ctDNA material across sites, particularly due to its low abundance. These in vitro models can mimic biological ctDNA and allow for performance benchmarking under controlled and standardised conditions. Additionally, the OncNGS initiative, launched under a European call for future NGS solutions for cancer, represents a key step towards EU-wide harmonisation of standards and practices. Finally, the panel stressed the importance of evaluating the economic implications of various ctDNA testing models, particularly in relation to their timing along the diagnostic and therapeutic pathway, as these factors may impact both the feasibility and value of implementation.

Sustainability (Resource Use)

Recommendation 10:

Economic evaluations should be integrated into clinical trials to assess both direct and indirect costs of liquid biopsy (LB) for genotyping and therapeutic response monitoring in mCRC. These analyses should consider technology investment, personnel training, and potential cost savings from reduced invasive procedures. Additionally, the choice of ctDNA technology should be factored into cost-effectiveness assessments.

Rationale: The panel emphasized that the financial sustainability of LB remains unclear due to the absence of comprehensive cost-effectiveness studies. While LB may reduce the need for invasive procedures and streamline patient management, its associated costs—including specialized equipment, personnel training, and quality assurance programs—remain unquantified. Additionally, the economic impact of reduced hospital stays, fewer biopsy-related complications, and potential improvements in treatment efficiency needs further assessment. Importantly, the panel noted that a key driver of economic value may lie in ctDNA’s role in minimal residual disease (MRD) assessment and treatment de-escalation/escalation strategies, particularly in avoiding unnecessary adjuvant therapies and related toxicities in patients with low risk of relapse. In the context of advanced cancer, cost-saving may be less evident unless improvements in QoL or timelier treatment adjustments—enabled by ctDNA monitoring—are formally valued and incorporated into reimbursement models. Moreover, the choice of ctDNA technology plays a crucial role in economic evaluation. ddPCR, while cost-effective, is limited to predefined mutations. Whole-exome sequencing (WES), on the other hand, offers broad coverage at high cost. Targeted NGS

panels may represent a cost-effective compromise, offering meaningful clinical data at moderate expense. Evaluating these trade-offs is essential to inform sustainable implementation. The panel recognized that without structured economic evaluations embedded in clinical trials, decision-makers lack the necessary data to evaluate the financial feasibility of this technology. By integrating cost analyses into ongoing and future studies, healthcare systems can generate essential evidence to inform reimbursement decisions and determine whether LB represents a cost-effective alternative or complementary tool to current diagnostic approaches.

Recommendation 11:

Decision-analytic models should be used to evaluate the long-term cost-effectiveness of liquid biopsy (LB) for both genotyping and therapeutic monitoring in mCRC. These studies are essential for producing a comprehensive HTA report to determine reimbursement feasibility and support its integration into healthcare systems.

Rationale: The panel highlighted that, despite the growing clinical interest in LB, no structured cost-effectiveness analyses have been conducted to compare its real-world financial impact against standard diagnostic pathways. Decision-analytic models, such as Markov models or budget impact analyses, are critical tools for simulating long-term economic outcomes, allowing policymakers to assess the balance between upfront investment and potential cost savings over time. The lack of such models currently prevents a complete HTA assessment, which is necessary for determining reimbursement policies and justifying the widespread adoption of LB. By developing robust economic models, researchers and policymakers can evaluate whether LB can be sustainably integrated into healthcare systems, ensuring that its benefits justify the associated costs while maintaining equitable access to advanced cancer diagnostics.

6. Molecular Tumour Boards (MTBs): Clinical Utility and Impact on Patient Care

6.1 Background and Rationale

6.1.1 MTBs: definition and scope

MTBs are multidisciplinary groups that integrate molecular and clinical data from cancer patients to formulate treatment recommendations for precision medicine^{102 103 104}. These groups are organized into panels comprising experts from various fields, such as oncologists, pathologists, geneticists, and bioinformaticians. They hold virtual or in-person meetings, convened regularly or on demand, to review and interpret the clinical and molecular information of cancer patients¹⁰⁵.

A key feature of MTBs is the interpretation of genomic alteration data, derived from a broad spectrum of technologies under the umbrella of NGS, WES, WGS and other approaches. Their primary function is to bridge genomic-driven data with therapeutic recommendations for cancer patients. This includes assessing the actionability of mutations identified through genomic analysis, evaluating the best possible therapies (both approved and off-label), while also directing patients to clinical trials or innovative drug programs when applicable¹⁰⁴.

MTBs enable a group of experts with in-depth knowledge of the molecular and biological characteristics of cancer to interpret molecular profiling results. Their evaluation is crucial for identifying patients who may benefit from matched therapies or require additional testing¹⁰⁶. Furthermore, the entire process, from diagnosis to testing, therapy selection, and treatment administration, is streamlined and facilitated. Ideally, MTBs ensure that every cancer patient has access to precision medicine programs and innovative therapies, ultimately improving cancer care.

The primary objective of this work was to develop a policy brief aimed at promoting the effective implementation of MTBs across Europe. In this process, we combined evidence gathered through a systematic review with meta-analysis of measurable clinical outcomes (See section 5.2) and qualitative research of organizational aspects related to MTBs (See section 5.3). We employed the Delphi method (See section 5.4) to consult with a panel of experts, whose input helped refine and shape the final set of recommendations. This approach enabled us to create comprehensive and actionable policy recommendations to guide the adoption and integration of MTBs into European cancer care systems.

6.1.2 MTB role in cancer care: state of the art

Precision oncology, driven by advancements in genomic and molecular research, has radically transformed the cancer care model over the past decade, shifting from a one-size-fits-all approach to therapies tailored to the molecular and genetic profile of individual tumours¹⁰⁷.

The field of precision oncology continues to evolve, primarily due to advances in and increased access to genome-sequencing technologies, particularly NGS applications, as well as other molecular analysis techniques. Genome-sequencing technologies have enabled the large-scale identification of molecular targets, driving research into targeted therapies and a wide range of innovative cancer treatments, fuelling, ultimately, the oncology research¹⁰⁸.

This paradigm shift has enhanced the diagnostic evaluation of cancer patients by incorporating various biomarker assessments, mostly related to the tumour-profiling and, moreover, to molecular biomarker profiling, resulting into pathological diagnoses, and new treatment opportunities¹⁰⁹.

The decreasing costs of molecular profiling, the widespread adoption of these technologies in major hospitals across Europe, and the continuous innovation in targeted therapies have contributed to the rapid expansion of precision medicine over the past decade, leading to an increasing number of tailored treatments for cancer patients¹¹⁰.

NGS has facilitated the identification of novel therapeutic targets for cancer patients. However, challenges remain due to genomic heterogeneity and complexity, particularly the unique molecular profiles of advanced tumours. Distinguishing between driver mutations and passenger molecular alterations remains a critical obstacle to the full implementation of precision medicine. Furthermore, while tumour molecular profiling has the potential to optimize treatment selection, the process is susceptible to challenges like subjective interpretation and misapplication¹¹¹.

In this context, MTBs have emerged as entities capable of not only decoding the complexity of genetic and genomic data but also integrating clinical patient information and traditional tumour characteristics.

MTBs structure, including many professional figures, with different expertise, can select the actual best possible therapy for each patient, hence reducing subjectivity. The expertise derived from these panels have the potentiality of condensing the technology advancements and optimize clinical decision-making¹¹².

In the last ten years, MTBs have been implemented across Europe in a fragmented manner, with individual characteristics varying by country and national initiatives. Within the framework of this project, WP 8 has mapped the state of the art of MTBs across Europe, highlighting significant differences between institutions and countries in D8.1 and D8.2.

Data were collected from various countries, including Germany, Spain, France, Belgium, Czechia, Poland, and Italy. The main limitations relate to the genomic testing strategies adopted, as some MTBs employ WGS or WES, whereas others rely on targeted NGS panels focusing on a predefined set of genes. Additional challenges include variations in funding and reimbursement schemes across different countries, as well as differences in the composition and organizational structure of MTBs. Moreover, some boards function as institutional or “real-world” MTBs, serving hospital networks, while others act as “steering” MTBs, guiding precision oncology trials.

Critical issues also arise from the heterogeneity in access to medicines, with some MTBs being closely linked to clinical trials, facilitating patient enrolment, while others are limited to recommending off-label drugs.

These critical issues, widely discussed also in the literature, highlight the need for guidelines to standardize the structure of MTBs. Efforts to address these challenges are ongoing, and this project aims to establish guidelines for their implementation in Europe.

6.2 Systematic review and meta-analysis of MTB impact on patients' outcomes

6.2.1 Methods

We previously registered the protocol for this systematic review and meta-analysis on Open Science Framework¹¹³. This systematic review was reported following the PRISMA Checklist³⁶.

Aim and research questions

The aim of this systematic review was to identify and evaluate the clinical impact of the MTBs in cancer care. To make this assessment we developed the following PICO:

Population. Oncologic general populations, with no age restrictions, with any type of cancer.

Intervention. MTBs evaluation of genomic profiling data.

Comparison. Absence of a MTB evaluation.

Outcomes. The primary outcomes were OS, PFS, median OS, median PFS and PFS ratio ≥ 1.3 . The secondary outcomes were mortality for the diseases, change of diagnosis, re-hospitalization, morbidity, response rate after MTB suggested treatment, clinical benefit, QALYs, disability-adjusted life years (DALYs).

Search strategy

We conducted a preliminary search of PubMed, Web of Science, and Scopus to identify relevant keywords. We then used the terms we identified through this process, along with the synonyms provided by the respective databases, to carry out a comprehensive literature search.

We searched for articles published in English and indexed in the following databases: PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), without applying any publication year restrictions. We retrieved the articles using the following search string in PubMed:

("molecular tumour board*" OR "molecular tumor board*" OR MTB OR MTBs) AND (cancer OR neoplasm* OR tumour* OR tumor* OR malignanc* OR "precision medicine" OR "personal* medicine" OR oncolog*)

This search string was then adapted for use in Web of Science, Scopus, and CENTRAL. Articles were retrieved up to the 1 December 2023.

Study eligibility and selection

After completing the literature search, we evaluated each article based on the following eligibility criteria: (1) publication (or acceptance for publication, i.e., in press) in peer-reviewed journals, with no time restrictions, and written in English; (2) inclusion of cancer patients of all ages and cancer types; (3) reporting of primary studies that used MTBs in clinical decision-making and presented at least one measurable clinical outcome; (4) inclusion or absence of a comparator, defined as the lack of an MTB approach (e.g., no evaluation or implementation of MTBs in therapy planning). We included all study designs, such as RCTs, non-randomized clinical trials, prospective observational studies, and retrospective observational studies. We excluded systematic reviews, other types of reviews, editorials, and commentaries.

We uploaded the identified articles to the Rayyan software platform, where we checked for and removed duplicates. Four reviewers (L.R., M.G.C., T.O., E.G.) independently screened the titles and abstracts, with two reviewers assessing each article. They resolved any disagreements through

consensus or, if needed, involved a third reviewer. Two researchers (L.R., E.G.) then independently reviewed the full texts of the selected articles and resolved disagreements by consensus. We included in the systematic review all articles that met the eligibility criteria.

Data extraction

Five reviewers (L.R., E.G., N.L., M.G.C., T.O) independently performed data extraction. We extracted, from each included study:

General information: title, first author, doi, journal of publication, year of publication, country.

Study characteristics: study design, number of arms, sample size,

MTBs characteristics: modality of access to the MTB, MTB composition, frequency of gatherings, TAT between case submission and the genomic testing, and from the receipt of genomic testing results to the therapy recommendations, any other TAT reported, guidelines used for recommendations, compliance with the MTB recommendation, success rate of genomic profiling.

Clinical aspects: patient characteristics (age, sex, number of previous treatments and therapeutic failures), specific cancer(s), characteristics and stage, sequencing technology used, molecular or genetic test used, availability of therapy before accessing the MTB, total number of actionable alterations, number of patient for which at least one actionable gene was detected, number of patients that received an actionable therapy, Number of patient that refused the suggest therapy, total number of patients treated, recommendation rate and implementation rate.

Clinical outcomes: the primary outcomes were OS, PFS, median OS, median PFS and PFS ratio ≥ 1.3 . The PFS ratio is defined as the ratio of PFS under therapy recommended by the MTB to the PFS under the previous line of therapy prior to accessing the MTB. The secondary outcomes were mortality for the diseases, change of diagnosis, re-hospitalization, morbidity, response rate after MTB suggested treatment, clinical benefit and any other result of the study, QALYs, DALYs. Additionally, we extracted the ORR, and the disease control rate (DCR), which is the ratio of patients who did not report progression at their first follow-up visit. Otherwise, we calculated both. Additionally, we extracted any other clinical outcome specified in the study.

Risk of bias assessment

Three independent reviewers (L.R., T.O., N.L.) assessed the risk of bias for each study included. The Cochrane Risk-of-Bias 2 tool for Randomized Trials (RoB 2)¹¹⁴ was used for RCTs, the Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies of Interventions (ROBINS-I) tool¹¹⁵ was applied in non-RCTs

of intervention, both with and without a comparator, using a modified scale that did not assess bias due to confounding for studies without a comparator.

Data synthesis and statistical methods

We synthesized the studies that met the inclusion criteria. The data synthesis included: (1) a descriptive summary of the evidence and (2) a meta-analysis, where appropriate. We presented the results narratively and, when applicable, through tables and graphs. We used descriptive statistics to summarize the characteristics of the eligible studies and conducted separate analyses for different study designs.

We conducted meta-analyses to evaluate the quantitative outcomes of the study. We used HRs as the effect size for OS and PFS. When the studies did not directly report HRs, we estimated them from published Kaplan-Meier survival curves and summary statistics using the method proposed by Tierney et al. (2007)¹¹⁶. We employed WebPlotDigitizer tool (<https://automeris.io/>) to extract information from survival data.

We analyzed the proportion of patients with a PFS ratio ≥ 1.3 by calculating pooled event rates using the Freeman-Tukey double arcsine transformation to stabilize variance across studies¹¹⁷.

We presented the results from different effect measures separately and stratified all analyses by study design (RCTs, non-RCTs, prospective observational studies, and retrospective observational studies). We obtained pooled estimates using the inverse variance-weighted method and applied a random-effects model to account for heterogeneity across studies, assuming that intervention effects might vary due to the high expected heterogeneity¹¹⁸. Between-study variance was estimated using the restricted maximum-likelihood (REML) method¹¹⁹.

We assessed heterogeneity using Cochrane's Q test and quantified it using the I^2 statistic, interpreting values $<50\%$ as low, between 50% and 75% as moderate, and $>75\%$ as high heterogeneity, respectively¹²⁰.

We considered a p-value threshold of <0.005 as statistically significant, while we deemed p-values <0.05 as suggestive. We visualized the results using forest plots, which included point estimates, 95% CIs, and study descriptors such as the first author and year of publication.

All statistical analyses were performed using R software version 4.4.0 (2024-04-24) for Windows, and the meta package was utilized for conducting the meta-analyses.

6.2.2 Results: Organizational aspects of MTBs

As illustrated in the PRISMA flowchart in *Figure 10* the literature search retrieved 4625 records. After screening, 158 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility, and 50 studies met the inclusion criteria. An additional four records were identified through citation searching and from relevant organizations, including a conference abstract by Botticelli et al. (2024)¹²¹, which was included due to its significance as one of the major ongoing RCTs. In total, 54 records were included in the final analysis, as detailed in supplementary table 8. One citation¹²² was retained despite being a duplicate study by the same group of authors, as it provided additional data not included in the more recent report¹²³. Specifically, Hoefflin et al. (2018)¹²² provides data on OS and PFR, instead Hoefflin et al. (2021)¹²³ reports median OS.

We included 30 studies with a comparator, including 5 RCTs, 7 non-randomized clinical trials, 5 prospective and 13 retrospective observational studies, as shown in Table 12.

The summary of characteristics of the studies included, and the MTBs is presented in Table 13. Most of the included studies were published after 2020 ($n = 36$, 66.7%) and involved MTBs based in Europe ($n = 34$, 63.0%), primarily in France and Germany ($n = 13$, 24.1%). Regarding MTB composition, the majority comprised 6 to 10 members ($n = 24$, 44.4%) and held meetings on a weekly basis ($n = 18$, 33.3%). A total of 20 MTBs (42.6%) reported adherence to ESMO-ESCAT guidelines. BC was the most frequently discussed tumor type, represented in 35 MTBs (64.8%). While most MTBs addressed multiple tumor types, 17 (31.5%) focused on a single cancer type. NGS was the most used genomic testing technique, employed in 42 studies (77.8%). Information on TAT was not available in 25 studies; the remaining studies reported heterogeneous TAT metrics, including intervals from diagnosis to testing, from testing to MTB discussion, or from test results to therapeutic recommendations. Reported values varied substantially, with the time from testing to MTB discussion ranging from a mean of 15 days¹²⁴ to 62.5 days¹²⁵.

Patient age varied considerably across the studies included, ranging from pediatric populations as young as 1 year to older adults up to 94 years of age. In most studies, the mean and median ages clustered around 60 years. The distribution of patient sex also differed across studies: 1 (1.9%) study¹²⁶ included only male patients, while 6 (11.1%) exclusively female patients¹²⁷⁻¹³³. The remaining studies enrolled mixed-sex populations. Data on the proportion of patients with metastatic disease were not reported in 22 studies (40.7%), while 11 studies (20.4%) exclusively included patients with metastatic disease. In most studies, most patients had received up to three lines of

treatment (n = 20, 37.0%) and had an Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group (ECOG) performance status of 1 (n = 18, 33.3%).

In the non RCT studies, a median, across the studies, of 58.0% of patients received a recommendation following the MTB discussion, with reported rates ranging from 16.9% to 100%. Of those, a median, across the studies, 39.2% implemented the recommendation, with implementation rates ranging from 3.2% to 100%.

All study characteristics and description of MTB in detail are visible on Supplementary table 9 and 10, in which the high heterogeneity and miscellaneous nature of comparators used across the studies is shown.

6.2.3 Results: Clinical impact of MTBs

Overall Survival

As shown in Figure 11, we found in the meta-analysis of the OS a reduction in the risk of death ranging from 10% to 40%, depending on the study designs, with low heterogeneity, except for the Observational Prospective studies, which showed moderate heterogeneity ($I^2 = 53.2\%$). Specifically, for RCTs, the meta-analysis of three studies^{121, 127, 134} reported a pooled HR of 0.89 (95% CI: 0.73–1.09, $I^2 = 0.0\%$).

Progression Free Survival

For PFS, as shown in Figure 12, a reduction in the risk of progression ranging from 17% to 39%, depending on the study design, with low heterogeneity across all studies designs. Specifically, for RCTs, the meta-analysis of three studies^{121, 134, 135} reported a statistically significant HR of 0.74 (95% CI: 0.61–0.90, $I^2 = 30.7\%$).

Progression Free Survival ratio

Finally, for the meta-analyses of the proportion of patients with a PFS ratio ≥ 1.3 , pooled estimates varied by study design, ranging from 33.1% to 43.1%, as shown in Figure 13, with low heterogeneity across all studies designs. Specifically, one RCT reported this measure¹³⁶, showing a PFS ratio ≥ 1.3 of 36.8% (95% CI: 25.7%–48.6%).

Non-meta-analysed outcome

The non-meta-analysed outcomes are presented in Supplementary table 11, which summarizes the median OS, PFS, and response rate summaries of studies on patients treated with MTB-recommended therapy. The median OS was reported in 25 (46.3%) studies, with a median of 13.00 months, while the median PFS is reported in 26 (48.1%) studies, with a median across studies of 4.65 months. Response rate information is reported in 32 (59.3%) studies, with ORR ranges from 1.4%¹³⁶ to 59%¹³⁷, and DCR reaches up to 80%, showing high variability across studies in all type of rate reported (Complete Response (CR), Partial Response (PR), Stable Disease (SD), Progressive Disease (PD), Clinical Benefit (CB)).

Risk of Bias results

The overall risk of bias for the RCTs was assessed as low across all domains, as shown in Supplementary Figure 1, except for the study by Botticelli et al. (2024), which was not assessed due to its abstract-only format. For the non-randomized studies, as presented in Supplementary Tables 12 and 13, the overall risk of bias was predominantly rated as serious in 37 out of 49 studies (75.5%), mainly due to concerns in the domains of selection bias and bias due to deviations from intended interventions. Exceptions were observed for the study by Reda et al.(2020)¹³⁸, which was rated as Low risk of bias, while Moderate risk was assigned to the studies by Bertucci et al. (2021)¹³⁹, Louie et al. (2024)¹⁴⁰, Billon et al. (2022)¹⁴¹, Charo et al. (2022)¹²⁶, Scheiter et al. (2022)¹⁴², Niogret et al. (2021)¹⁴³, Repetto et al. (2023)¹⁴⁴, Zhang et al. (2023)¹⁴⁵, and Fukada et al. (2023)¹⁴⁶. In contrast, the studies by Angel et al (2021)¹⁴⁷ and Weiss et al. (2023)¹⁴⁸, which were not included in the meta-analysis, were judged to have a Critical risk of bias due to issues with selection bias and deviations from intended interventions, respectively. Most of the included studies showed a low risk of bias in the domains related to the classification of interventions and the measurement of outcomes.

Fig. 10: Flow chart of the study selection

	All the studies	With comparator	Without comparator
Number of studies	54	30 (55.6%)	24 (44.4%)
Study design			
RCT	5 (9.3%)	5 (16.7%)	-
Non-Randomized Clinical Trial	12 (22.2%)	7 (23.3%)	5 (20.8%)
Observational Prospective	12 (22.2%)	5 (16.7)	7 (29.2%)
Observational Retrospective	25 (46.3%)	13 (43.3%)	12 (50.0%)

Table 12: Study design of the included studies

Table 13. Summary of characteristics of the included studies and MTBs considered

Characteristics		n (%)
Number of studies		54
Years of publication	Before 2020	18 (33.3%)

Deliverable 14.2 – Final version of the recommendations - Version 1.2

	After 2020	36 (66.7%)
Country	USA	15 (27.8%)
	Europe	34 (63.0%)
	France, Germany	13 (24.1%)
	Italy	3 (5.6%)
	Netherland	2 (3.7%)
	Denmark, Finland, Spain	1 (1.9%)
	Others (America, Asia)	5 (9.3%)
Access to MTB	Referred by the treating physician/oncologist	11 (20.4%)
	From the hospital or same institution	20 (37.0%)
	N.R.	23 (42.6%)
Number of members	1-5	14 (25.9%)
	6-10	24 (44.4%)
	11-15	2 (3.7%)
	16-20	2 (3.7%)
	N.R.	12 (22.2%)
Board meetings	Once a week	18 (33.3%)
	Once every two weeks	8 (14.8%)
	Three times a month	4 (7.4%)
	Monthly	2 (3.7%)
	Twice per week	2 (3.7%)
	N.R.	20 (42.6%)
Guidelines for recommendations	ESMO-ESCAT	20 (42.6%)
	ASCO guidelines	2 (3.7%)
	Other	4 (7.4%)
	N.R.	28 (51.9%)
Cancers	One	16 (29.6%)
	2 to 5	8 (14.8%)
	6 to 10	6 (11.1%)
	11 to 15	8 (14.8%)

Deliverable 14.2 – Final version of the recommendations - Version 1.2

	16 to 20	8 (14.8%)
	>20	8 (14.8%)
Most frequent cancers	Breast	35 (64.8%)
	Lung or NSCLC	28 (51.9%)
	Ovarian	26 (48.1%)
	Colorectal	23 (42.6%)
	Pancreas	21 (38.9%)
Sequencing method	NGS (t-NGS)	42 (77.8%)
	CGP	7 (13.0%)
	CGH	4 (7.4%)
	WGS	3 (5.6%)
	WES	3 (5.6%)
	N.R.	6 (11.1%)
Percentage of patients with metastasis	0%	1 (1.9%)
	1%-50%	4 (7.4%)
	50%-84%	8 (14.8%)
	85%-99%	8 (14.8%)
	100%	11 (20.4%)
	N.R.	22 (40.7%)
Number of previous treatments	0	1 (1.9%)
	1	7 (13.0%)
	2	18 (33.3%)
	3	20 (37.0%)
	N.R.	8 (14.8%)
ECOG	0	4 (7.4%)
	1	18 (33.3%)
	N.R.	32 (59.3%)
Sex	100% Male	1 (1.9%)
	100% Female	6 (11.1%)
	>50 % Male	12 (22.2%)
	>50% Female	29 (53.7%)

	50% Male, 50% Female	3 (5.6%)
	N.R.	3 (5.6%)

N.R.= Not Reported, NGS = Next-Generation Sequencing, CGP = Comprehensive Genomic Profiling, CGH = Comparative Genomic Hybridization, WGS = Whole Genome Sequencing, WES = Whole Exome Sequencing, NSCLC = Non-small cell lung carcinoma, ECOG = Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group performance status.

Figure 11. Meta-analysis of OS stratified by study design.

Deliverable 14.2 – Final version of the recommendations - Version 1.2

Figure 12. Meta-analysis of PFS stratified by study design.

Figure 13. Meta-analysis of Progression Free Survival ratio (PFS ratio) ≥ 1.3 stratified by study design.

6.3. Narrative review of MTB implementation aspects

6.3.1 Methods

Aim and research questions

The aim of this narrative review was to explore the implementation challenges of MTBs, including the feasibility of implementation, the cost implications associated and the values and preferences and acceptability of the intervention for patients and healthcare professionals.

Search strategy

We conducted a non-systematic search. Articles published in English have been searched in PubMed without publication year restrictions, using a combination of the following keywords MTB, genomic tumour board, molecular board or biology board.

After the literature search, we evaluated each article against the following inclusion/exclusion criteria:

Inclusion criteria

- Article discussing ethical considerations, organizational implementation, feasibility, acceptability and cost-effectiveness associated with MTB use.
- Primary study reporting data on MTBs in Europe
- Systematic, narrative or any other literature review on MTB
- Articles in the following languages: English and Italian.

Data extraction

Identified articles have been uploaded on Rayyan software, then three reviewers (L.R., E.G., N.L.) independently performed screening based on title and abstract. Full texts of the articles identified were retrieved and reviewed by three researchers (L.R., E.G., N.L.). Eventually, identified articles that meet the eligibility criteria were included in the narrative review.

From each included study, we extracted:

General information: title, first author, doi, year of publication, country.

Implementability Domains Information

Acceptability: We extracted information on the acceptability of MTBs from the perspective of different stakeholders (e.g., patients, healthcare providers, health policymakers). This includes considerations of patient comfort and preferences, the perceived reliability of MTB discussions and recommendations from the perspectives of both patients and physicians, and any other relevant factors.

Equity: We extracted information on fair access to MTBs for all target patients. This includes evidence on how socioeconomic status or marginalization affects access to MTBs, whether interventions disproportionately benefit or harm certain groups, and how different populations may experience varying outcomes from the same intervention.

Feasibility: We extracted information on the implementability of MTBs, including technical execution and logistical considerations for integrating MTBs into standard cancer care practices. This encompasses factors such as the time required for physicians, the infrastructure needed, and necessary personnel.

Resource use and economic implication: We extracted information on the costs incurred and the benefits gained from the adoption of MTBs.

Data analysis

The extracted data was narratively synthesized. For each study and its extracted data, a theme and subthemes were identified and reported.

We analysed each study according to the implementation domain (Acceptability, Equity, Feasibility, Resource Use, and Economic Implications). If a study presented evidence for more than one domain, it was considered multiple times (twice, three, or even four times, as appropriate).

One article was randomly selected for each of the four domains to generate a draft of the subthemes. The chosen themes were then piloted using another randomly selected article for each domain, and additional subthemes were added if needed. All the evidence extracted from a study was then associated with a subtheme and a general theme. Finally, all themes were discussed among all authors to reach a consensus on the final themes associated with each subtheme, and the evidence was narratively reported.

6.3.2 Results: equity, acceptability, feasibility, resource use

The literature search retrieved 545 records. After screening for title and abstract, and then for full text, a total of 43 articles were deemed eligible.

Each article could be relevant to multiple domains. Of these, 25 out of 43 (58.1%) contained information related to the feasibility of implementation, 7 out of 43 (16.3%) contained information related to equity, 15 out of 43 (34.9%) contained information related to resource use and economic implications, and 11 out of 43 (25.6%) contained information related to the acceptability of MTBs.

For the feasibility domain (Table 14), information was categorized into two main domains: organizational aspects and genetic and -omics. Furthermore, within genetic and -omics, two themes were identified, while for organizational aspects, three themes were identified. The main challenges identified included barriers such as laboratory accreditation, personnel training, and genetic interpretation. Additional limiting factors included heterogeneity in MTB composition, workflow inefficiencies, and TAT, all of which impact scalability.

For the equity domain (Table 15), one main domain was identified: Access to MTB, with two themes - socioeconomic and geographical limitations and clinical trial enrollment. The main barriers to accessing MTBs were related to socioeconomic status and place of residence. These included travel costs, treatment affordability, insurance coverage, and distance to both MTBs and clinical trial locations.

For the resource use domain (Table 16), two main domains were identified: coverage and reimbursement and cost drivers. Within the coverage and reimbursement domain, one theme was identified - “cost coverage” - highlighting that while the cost of molecular analysis is a manageable barrier, expenditures related to drug and therapy implementation pose more significant challenges.

For the cost drivers domain, three themes were identified: “Molecular testing and laboratory-related costs,” “Drug and therapy costs,” and “MTB overall costs.” These findings highlight that the economic impact of MTBs is limited to only 0.3% of total healthcare costs. The main cost drivers are drugs and hospitalizations, ranging from €500 to €31,269 per patient. While molecular analysis costs are more easily covered, experimental therapies face significant reimbursement challenges.

For the acceptability domain (Table 17), two themes were identified: acceptability for patients and acceptability for physicians. For physicians, barriers included low confidence and knowledge in

Table 14. Feasibility of implementation

Domain	Theme	Evidence	Ref	doi
Genetic and omics	NGS and molecular profiling	The implementation of NGS technology for sequencing is reported as feasible, both through in-house or external laboratories. A survey conducted in Italy highlights that most NGS assays are carried out in-house and do not represent a critical MTB bottleneck. An important point is raised about accreditation procedures and training for all professionals involved in every aspect of molecular profiling. Barriers related to a lack of tissue or analysis failure may cause drawbacks, as reported by Tommasi et al.	Tommasi et al.	10.3389/fmed.2024.1432628
			Irelli et al.	10.3390/cancers15061727
			Ciliberto et al.	10.1186/s13046-022-02512-0
			Frost et al.	10.1038/s41416-022-01922-3
			Farhangfar et al.	10.1200/CCI.22.00011
			Incorvaia et al.	10.1177/03008916211062266
			Tsimberidou et al.	10.1038/s41571-023-00824-4
Genetic and omics	Genetic actionability	MTB implementation requires seamless integration of molecular testing and result interpretation. The identification of the actionability of genetic alterations is paramount to its functioning, but challenges in understanding whether a mutation is druggable or actionable arise, mostly related to a lack of knowledge or correct integration into the	Wahida A et al.	10.1093/oncolo/oyae271
			Pastz B et al.	10.1016/j.critrevonc.2024.104380
			Hönikl LS et al.	10.1186/s12885-024-11858-x
			Riedl JM et al.	10.1007/s00428-023-03702-7
			Irelli A et al.	10.3390/cancers15061727

		workflow. Additionally, a point is made about the indication of the MTBs often being off-label treatments. A variety of databases and knowledge bases are reported to be consulted for molecular alteration, including the 1000 Genomes Browser, cBioPortal, ClinVar, COSMIC, dbSNP, Ensembl, JAX-CKB, OncoKB, and PubMed.	Horak P et al.	10.1002/gcc.22987
			Danesi R et al.	10.1016/j.esmooop.2020.100040
			Koopman B et al	10.1002/onco.13580
Organizational aspects	MTB composition and criteria	Early inclusion of all cancer patients is advocated, but its feasibility is not addressed. Concerns about the composition of MTBs have arisen, particularly regarding the inclusion of internal oncologists, reporting physicians responsible for the presentation of the cases, and pathologists.	Pastz B et al.	10.1016/j.critrevonc.2024.104382
			Hönikl LS et al.	10.1186/s12885-024-11858-x
			Irelli A et al.	10.3390/cancers15061727
			Frost H et al.	10.1038/s41416-022-01922-3
			Crimini E et al.	10.3390/cancers14133193
			Russo A et al.	10.1016/j.critrevonc.2021.103567
			Koopman B et al.	10.1002/onco.13580
Organizational aspects	TAT	Timeliness of MTB output is a challenge in its implementation. According to the literature, 28 days for global TAT is highlighted as a reasonable time; however, challenges related to workflows are	Wahida A et al.	10.1093/oncolo/oyae273
			Tommasi S et al.	10.3389/fmed.2024.1432629
			de Jager VD et al.	10.1016/j.lanepe.2024.100839

		present. Opportunities for improvement include larger volumes, efficient NGS workflows, robotization of workflows, and optimizing data flow. Further challenges reported by Irelli et al. are the long-time frame for genomic testing and/or MTB output.	Irelli A et al.	10.3390/cancers15061727
			Ciliberto G et al.	10.1186/s13046-022-02512-0
			Crimini E et al.	10.3390/cancers14133193
			Luchini C et al.	10.1016/j.trecan.2020.05.008
Organizational aspects	Workflow of MTB and support tools	Scalability is also an important obstacle. The large number of cancer patients poses a major challenge, primarily related to molecular data interpretation and resource limitations in addressing each individual case. Inconsistency in tracking and recording MTB activities is reported as a barrier which could hinder the evaluation and comparison of their impact on patient care. For the discussion of cases, specific platforms or electronic systems are reported to be used to streamline the process. Challenges in involving cases from peripheral hospitals or pathology laboratories and including external specialist in attendance of MTBs are reported, and the creation of a virtual platform is identified as a possible solution. Decision support tools, integrated	Wahida A et al.	10.1093/oncolo/oyae272
			Lajmi N et al.	10.1017/pcm.2024.1
			Vingiani A et al.	10.1200/PO.23.00067
			Olivera-Salguero R et al.	10.3389/fonc.2023.1151496
			Irelli A et al.	10.3390/cancers15061727
			Fumagalli C et al.	10.3390/cancers13040609
			Pastz B et al.	10.1016/j.critrevonc.2024.104379
			de Jager VD et al.	10.1016/j.lanepe.2024.100839
			Tsimberidou AM et al.	10.1038/s41571-023-00824-4
Fasola G et al.	10.1093/oncolo/oyad020			

Table 15. Equity of the MTB

Domain	Theme	Evidence	Ref	doi
Access to MTB	Socioeconomic and geographical limitations	<p>Different articles report challenges related to equitable and universal access to MTBs. Socioeconomic status and place of residence represent a barrier since few patients have a MTBs available next to their residence or can travel and sustain the associated costs. Other limitations include the affordability of treatments and the availability of insurance coverage. Another challenge is the geographical distribution and outreach of MTBs. In their analysis, Luke et al. found that in the distribution of MTBs in Germany gaps remain, to non-urban areas. The concentration of needed expertise within academic institutions presents an additional obstacle, restricting MTB access to a limited number of cancer patients. Expanding access beyond these institutions is essential. Finally, challenges in MTB access in low-income and middle-income countries are highlighted, mostly due to the limited health-care coverage, diagnostic resources and drug availability.</p>	Riedl JM et al.	10.1007/s00428-023-03702-7
			Tsimberidou AM et al.	10.1038/s41571-023-00824-4
			Irelli A et al.	10.3390/cancers15061727
			Lüke F et al.	10.3390/cancers14205040
			Farhangfar CJ et al.	10.1200/CCI.22.00011
			Crimini E et al.	10.3390/cancers14133193
			Taskén K et al.	10.1038/s41591-022-01777-4
Access to MTB	Clinical trials enrollment	<p>Clinical trials represent a key output of MTBs, but accessibility to these trials can be limited. Irelli et al. and Crimini et al. highlight how clinical trials are not evenly distributed across regions, posing a significant limitation for patients who do not live near trial centers. This issue stems from underlying economic, social, and cultural disparities among patients, with only highly motivated individuals, often with more resources, able to travel and enroll in clinical trials.</p>	Irelli A et al.	10.3390/cancers15061727
			Crimini E et al.	10.3390/cancers14133193

Table 16. Resource use and economic implication

Domain	Theme	Evidence	Ref	doi
Coverage and reimbursement	Cost coverage	Coverage of costs related to molecular analysis represents a surmountable barrier due to its limited expense, whereas expenditures related to drug and therapy implementation are more concerning. According to Hönikl et al. survey the cost coverage for molecular analyses within the MTB is generally not an issue for most respondents (no problem: 13/38 (34.2%), rarely a problem: 12/38 (31.6%)). However, half of the respondents reported difficulties in securing coverage for experimental therapies. In Italy, a survey by ACC highlighted that only three out of 16 ACC MTBs were supported by the National Health System, with four centers (22%) unable to secure a budget in any form.	Lutz S et al.	10.1007/s11523-024-01109-1
			Hönikl LS et al.	10.1186/s12885-024-11858-x
			Lüke F et al.	10.3390/cancers14205040
			Farhangfar CJ et al.	10.1200/CCI.22.00011
			Ciliberto G et al.	10.1186/s13046-022-02512-0
			Incorvaia L et al.	10.1177/03008916211062266
			Tsimberidou AM et al.	10.1038/s41571-023-00824-4
Cost drivers	Molecular testing and laboratory related costs	NGS testing requires significant investment in equipment, maintenance, sample preparation, personnel, and data processing. Irelli et al. estimated that the Italian national health systems spend approximately €29.9 million	Bayle A et al.	10.1016/j.annonc.2023.06.011
			Irelli A et al.	10.3390/cancers15061727
			Taskén K et al.	10.1038/s41591-022-01777-4
			Russo A et al.	10.1016/j.critrevonc.2021.103567

		<p>annually on NGS tests, with reimbursement rates ranging from €500 to €1,500 per test. Bayle et al. reported molecular testing prices across Europe, noting that complex NGS panels can exceed €3,000 per patient. Similarly, Pages et al. conducted a cost analysis during the MOSCATO trial, estimating the total cost of a complete molecular diagnosis to be around €2,396 per patient (using a micro-costing approach).</p>	<p>Luchini C et al.</p>	<p>10.1016/j.trecan.2020.05.008</p>
			<p>Pages A et al.</p>	<p>10.1038/gim.2016.174</p>
Cost drivers	Drug and therapy costs	<p>According to Pages et al., molecular-guided therapy costs were approximately €31,269 per patient, with anticancer drugs accounting for 54% of expenses and hospitalizations for 35%. Costs vary depending on whether phase I/II drugs are included: for example, excluding these drugs results in a reduction of €7,684 per patient. In Italy, Irelli et al. estimated that costs for off-label drugs amount to approximately €22.3 million annually, with a monthly</p>	<p>Irelli A et al.</p>	<p>10.3390/cancers15061727</p>
			<p>Crimini E et al.</p>	<p>10.3390/cancers14133193</p>
			<p>Pages A et al.</p>	<p>10.1038/gim.2016.174</p>

		average cost of €3,000 per patient for a median therapy duration of 5 months.		
Cost drivers	MTB overall costs	<p>On the overall financial standpoint, MTBs do not appear to have a negative impact. According to cost-analyses, MTBs seem to affect only a small share of the total cost of the patient journey; in the analysis conducted by Luchini et al., molecular diagnostics account for 6% of total healthcare costs, while drugs (56.5%) and hospitalizations (32%) are the primary cost drivers. MTB activities, on the other hand, represent only 0.3% of total costs, suggesting that they are not the primary bottleneck to achieving sustainability.</p>	Luchini C et al.	10.1016/j.trecan.2020.05.008
			Pastz B et al.	10.1016/j.critrevonc.2024.104379
			Pages A et al.	10.1038/gim.2016.174

Table 17. Acceptability for patients and healthcare professionals

Domain	Theme	Evidence	Ref	doi
Acceptability	Physicians	Main limitations include lack of readiness in the adoption of precision oncology guidelines, lack of confidence in interpreting genetic information and/or genomic tests and the willingness and motivation to incorporate routine genomic testing into their daily workflows. Van der Velden et al. report that in a tertiary cancer, 22% of physicians admitted low confidence in genomic knowledge, while 18% anticipated infrequent patient testing. In the investigation by Przybylski et al., clinicians were more comfortable with genetic-driven protein biomarkers like BRCA1/2 and PD-L1 (78%) compared to NGS panels (49%). Barriers are not only limited to testing, but also to scepticism about MTBs' utility and logistical challenges such as inconvenient meeting times, limited manpower, low local case volumes, and travel distances for in-person meetings. Despite these challenges, when MTBs are implemented, they are reported to enhance clinicians'	Lajmi N et al.	10.1017/pcm.2024.1
			Riedl JM et al.	10.1007/s00428-023-03702-7
			Bayle A et al.	10.1016/j.annonc.2023.06.011
			Irelli A et al.	10.3390/cancers15061727
			Fasola G et al.	10.1093/oncolo/oyad020
			Przybylski DJ et al.	10.1177/1078155219896395
			van de Haar J et al.	10.1136/esmoopen-2019-000516
			Willemsen AECAB et al.	10.1038/s41416-019-0489-3
			Remon J et al.	10.1136/esmoopen-2018-000446
			Madhavan S et al.	10.1200/EDBK_200759
van der Velden DL et al.	10.1093/annonc/mdx528			

		understanding of genetics or -omics and facilitate the sharing of knowledge. Healthcare professionals highlight MTBs as valuable for providing tailored treatment advice and improving patient outcomes.		
Acceptability	Patients	For patients, barriers include limited understanding of genomic testing, financial issues, and difficulties interpreting results, all of which decrease the acceptability of molecular testing and adherence to MTBs. Furthermore, since the clinical benefit of genomic profiling varies, particularly for patients with deteriorating clinical status, challenges to acceptance of MTBs and testing may also vary. Testing, moreover, may lead to false hopes, generation of distress (anxiety, changes in family and social relationships) or even delay of appropriate palliative care, especially when appropriate education is lacking.	Riedl JM et al.	10.1007/s00428-023-03702-7
			Willemsen AECAB et al.	10.1038/s41416-019-0489-3
			Madhavan S et al.	10.1200/EDBK_200759
			Irelli A et al.	10.3390/cancers15061727

6.4 Delphi consultation

6.4.1 Experts interview

Standardization of MTB functioning is essential, given their increasing adoption and the rapid advancement of precision oncology. To develop consensus-based recommendations among experts across Europe, we have chosen to use the Delphi methodology, which is a well-established and widely recognized approach for achieving expert consensus in a structured and anonymous manner. The Delphi method is particularly effective for addressing complex topics where standardization is lacking or where uncertainty exists. By employing multiple iterative rounds with structured feedback, this process enables experts to refine their opinions and reach a more balanced agreement, while minimizing the influence of dominant individuals or external pressures^{149, 150}.

This study has been approved by the local Ethical Committee, Comitato Etico Territoriale Lazio Area 3 of the Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli (comitatoetico.lazioarea3@policlinicogemelli.it) on December 12, 2024, with the approval number 7231.

Aim and working group

The aim of this Delphi exercise is to identify key elements related to the implementation of MTBs and to develop comprehensive recommendations for their integration across Europe. The intended audience for these recommendations includes healthcare professionals, policymakers, and researchers involved in precision oncology. The geographical scope of this initiative focuses on EU member states, aiming for harmonized implementation across the region.

The consensus exercise is led by a working group from the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC) of Rome (L.R., E.G., N.L., A.S., R.P., S.B.) and Gustave Roussy (M.K.). The UCSC team includes medical doctors, residents in Hygiene and Preventive Medicine (L.R., A.S.), a PhD candidate in Public Health with a background in economics (E.G.) and PhD candidate in Public Health with a background in statistics (N.L.). Additionally, the group is supported by the full professor of Hygiene and Preventive Medicine (S.B.) and a senior biostatistician (R.P.) with expertise in personalized medicine, guideline development, and oncological epidemiology. The methodology group is further supported by the Executive Director of the PRecISion Medicine Center in Oncology at the Gustave Roussy Cancer Campus (M.K.).

Experts' inclusion

Criteria for experts' inclusion were based on their representation of active MTBs, with relevant expertise in oncology disciplines such as physicians, biologists, data managers, or pathologists. To ensure broad geographic representation and capture potential discrepancies in implementation across countries, invitations were extended to experts from as many countries as possible. The number of experts was not predetermined but left open to ensure a diverse range of perspectives. Experts were selected based on their knowledge of the topic, including some already involved in the *Can.Heal project* and others referred by fellow specialists. Table 18 lists the panellists (17 members) who took part in the Delphi process.

The results of two reviews conducted (see previous sections of this document) provided key insights in shaping the questions to be addressed. In particular, the narrative review played a significant role in this process. The four sections outlined in the survey form were selected following a comprehensive evaluation by the working group, which identified gaps in the studies gathered and assessed during the review process. Prior to the first round, experts were provided with a confidential document containing preliminary results from the two reviews conducted by UCSC. This document was designed to engage the experts in existing literature and included instructions on how to proceed with the Delphi rounds. It remained accessible throughout the survey via a dedicated link for exclusive access. Within this document, we summarized the methodologies of both the systematic and narrative reviews. For the systematic review, we included only the forest plots of clinical outcomes, while the narrative review provided brief descriptive statistics on the key focus areas of our Delphi study.

Survey details

To gather experts' input and reach consensus, we employed a Delphi method using Microsoft Forms. The first survey addressed 65 items distributed across four main domains: organizational aspects, testing, inclusion criteria, and clinical aspects. For 54 of these items, participants were asked to rate statements on a Likert scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree), with a consensus threshold of 80% or greater for agreement or disagreement. The remaining 11 items provided experts with the opportunity to add comments, suggest additional topics, or elaborate on fixed-answer items. This approach allowed for the collection of both quantitative data (via the Likert scale) and qualitative input (through open-ended comments), which were analysed to guide the second round of the Delphi process. No significant modifications were made to the Delphi method in its original form.

The consensus process consisted of two rounds. No meetings were held between rounds to avoid influencing the experts with the opinions of others. Instead, items were adjusted based on the written comments provided by the participants, recognizing that not all experts had commented on each item.

Consensus was defined as when an item received at least 80% of responses rated as "4. Agree" or "5. Strongly Agree." This threshold was chosen to ensure a strong level of agreement among the panellists, reflecting a shared position on the item in question. By setting the consensus at 80%, we aimed to capture the collective judgment of the experts while allowing for a reasonable degree of diversity in individual opinions. Items that met this definition of consensus (80% or higher) were removed from subsequent voting rounds and directly included in the list of recommendations. This approach ensured that only those items requiring further discussion or refinement were revisited in the following round.

Item with a level of agreement between 60 and 79% were revised according to experts comment and were subjected to a vote in the subsequent round. Item with a level of agreement <60% were discarded. A threshold of 50% of experts voting per round was set to proceed to the subsequent round.

To determine whether a third round was necessary, we set a predefined threshold: a third round would only be conducted if any item had an agreement above 70% without reaching full consensus. Since no item exceeded this threshold in the second round, the Delphi process was concluded after two rounds.

Experts completed the survey independently, and their responses were downloaded and analysed for each item. The results were then reviewed to assess consensus and identify items that required further discussion or revision.

Experts were informed of the results only at the end of the second round to avoid introducing any potential bias, particularly regarding items that had already reached consensus during the first round. Feedback was provided in quantitative form, which included approval rates per item. The feedback provided to the panellists was anonymized to ensure that individual responses remained confidential.

Anonymity was planned in the study design and was maintained throughout the Delphi process. Microsoft Forms was specifically designed to ensure that no personal data was collected from the experts. The only information gathered was related to the participants' area of expertise, which was necessary to understand their background and contributions.

To encourage participation in the consensus process, three reminders were sent for the first round (via group email), and two reminders were sent for the second round (one group email and one personalized email). These reminders aimed to ensure that all panellists had the opportunity to participate and complete the surveys within the given timeframe.

The surveys and all related communication, including emails, were conducted in English. For the second round, the items were further explained within the specific sections of the form, where possible, to provide additional clarity and ensure a better understanding of the questions. This adaptation aimed to make the process more accessible to all participants.

Table 18. Delphi panel characteristics

Name	Country	Institution
Philippe Aftimos	Belgium	Hôpital Universitaire de Bruxelles
Torben Frøstrup Hansen	Denmark	University of Southern Denmark - Lillebælt Hospital, Research Unit of Oncology
Christophe le Torneau	France	Institut Curie
Lars Bullinger and Olga Blau	Germany	Charité
Nikolas von Bubnoff	Germany	Universitätsklinikum Schleswig-Holstein
Gennaro Ciliberto	Italy	Istituto Nazionale Tumori "Regina Elena"
Patrizio Giacomini	Italy	Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli IRCCS
Ruggero De Maria Marchiano	Italy	Alleanza Contro il Cancro (ACC)
Luca Mazzeella	Italy	Istituto Europeo di Oncologia

Gennaro Daniele	Italy	Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli IRCCS
Paolo Marchetti	Italy	IDI IRCCS – Istituto Dermopatico dell’Immacolata
Tormod Kyrre Guren and Hege Russnes	Norway	Oslo University Hospital
Gerrit A. Meijer	Netherlands	Netherlands Cancer Institute
Hans Gelderblom	Netherlands	Leiden University
Iwona Ługowska	Poland	Maria Skłodowska-Curie National Institute of Oncology
Ernest Nadal	Spain	Catalan Institute of Oncology
Eva Jolly	Sweden	Karolinska Institute

6.4.2 Results

6.4.2.1 First round

The first round of the Delphi consensus exercise was launched on February 11th and remained open for a period of nine days, concluding on February 20th. During this period, a total of 11 out of 17 experts (64.7%) completed the survey, representing various disciplines involved in MTBs. Both rounds of the Delphi exercise were conducted anonymously, as stated earlier in the methods section. The only information we collected from the experts was their expertise. Table 19 summarizes the expertise collected.

ID	Expertise
#1	MTB lead
#2	Medical doctor, molecular DNA profiling, ctDNA, MTB member, clinical trials
#3	Medical Oncology, phase 1 trials, GI and BR, genomics

#4	Medical oncologist, clinical trialist, MTB coordinator
#5	Oncology nursing
#6	MTB coordinator, medical doctor, molecular biologist
#7	Molecular pathology, Whole Genome Sequencing
#8	Clinical oncology, early phase clinical trials
#9	Medical oncology
#10	Medical doctor
#11	Medical oncology

Table 19. Summary of expertise collected among first round responders

Organizational aspects domain.

In the organizational aspects domain, a total of 40 items were assessed. Of these, 35 items were rated on the Likert scale, and 5 were open-ended questions that allowed experts to provide qualitative feedback. Among the 40 items, 18 focused on the roles that should be included in MTB meetings. Oncologists, molecular biologists/biotechnologists, and pathologists were the only professionals who achieved 100% agreement. Following them, medical geneticists and the treating physician received an agreement level of 88.89%. All other roles received agreement levels below 56%, except for bioinformaticians and biostatisticians, who achieved 66.67% agreement (Figure 14). The qualitative feedback provided by experts was instrumental in revising some roles that did not meet the predefined consensus threshold. These revisions were incorporated into the second-round survey (see the following section).

In terms of meeting frequency, none of the items addressing the frequency of MTB gatherings reached the 80% consensus threshold. However, the highest levels of agreement were observed for weekly and biweekly meetings, which both received 66.67% agreement. Experts' comments were analyzed and incorporated into the second-round survey to refine these statements and address concerns regarding meeting frequency.

Figure 14. Level of agreement for each professional figure (first round)

Legend. red items: discarded; blue items: moved to next round; green items: consensus recommendations

For the items related to the information included in the medical report, all surpassed the 80% consensus threshold. Specifically, sample and patient details, molecular alterations, and actionability of molecular alterations received 100% agreement. Additionally, the suggestion for clinical trials inclusion reached an agreement of 88.89%. The comments provided by experts were crucial for expanding the list of items in the second round, allowing for a more comprehensive assessment of additional aspects deemed relevant by the panelists.

The remaining organizational aspects, which were not included in the previously mentioned subdomains, showed relatively homogeneous agreement levels. Six out of nine items surpassed the 80% consensus threshold, while the remaining three items received an agreement above 66%. All experts unanimously agreed on the importance of appointing a specific figure, the referent clinician, to present each case, and that the work of MTBs should be supported by technological systems that assist in clinical decision-making. Several other aspects also received high consensus, with 88.89% agreement. These included the appointment of the referent clinician before the MTB discussion, the use of a case submission tool through which the treating oncologist refers the patient, and the recommendation that MTB decisions should ideally be delivered within two weeks. Experts also widely supported the idea that, whenever possible, MTBs should be held online to improve accessibility for all available specialists and to overcome logistical barriers. Slightly below the threshold, but still with strong agreement at 77.78%, were the inclusion of a clinical trial specialist

in MTB discussions and the recommendation that the entire process, from testing to therapy recommendation, should ideally be completed within 28 days. Figure 15 summarizes organizational aspects domain results.

Figure 15. Organizational aspects domain results

Legend. red items: discarded; blue items: moved to next round; green items: consensus recommendations

Testing domain.

The Testing domain in the first round included six items rated on the Likert scale, along with one open-ended question. This domain exhibited relatively heterogeneous consensus levels.

All experts (100%) unanimously agreed that NGS should be the leading sequencing choice for all patients entering the MTB. Additionally, 88.89% of experts endorsed the use of specific databases for consultation, including the 1000 Genomes Browser, cBioPortal, ClinVar, COSMIC, dbSNP, Ensembl, JAX-CKB, OncoKB, and PubMed.

Among the remaining items, the only one approaching the consensus threshold was the recommendation that the panel should include genes listed in the ESCAT and OncoKB criteria, at least up to Tier IIIA for ESCAT and Tier 3B for OncoKB. The other items were excluded from further rounds, as they received agreement levels ranging between 44% and 56% (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Testing domain voted items (first round)

Legend. red items: discarded; blue items: moved to next round; green items: consensus recommendations

Inclusion criteria domain.

The Inclusion Criteria domain consisted of 8 items, with 7 subjects to vote on and 1 open-ended question. Among these, only one item, "Rare diseases or specific histologies at diagnosis with limited therapeutic options," achieved 100% consensus.

Five items reached a sufficient level of agreement to be revisited in the second round. These included: "For whom there is no already known available therapy," which received 66.67% agreement, as well as "Metastatic and non-metastatic patients," "ECOG between 0 and 2," "Life expectancy ≥ 12 weeks," and "Exhaustion of standard therapeutic lines according to the specific indications for each histology," all of which received 77.78% agreement.

One item was discarded due to insufficient agreement (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Inclusion criteria voted items (first round)

Legend. red items: discarded; blue items: moved to next round; green items: consensus recommendations

Clinical aspects domain.

The Clinical Aspects domain consisted of 10 items, with 6 rated on the Likert scale and 4 open-ended questions. Among the items that received sufficient consensus, two surpassed the threshold with 100% agreement: one suggesting that additional testing, including invasive testing, could be a possible recommendation of the MTBs, and the other indicating that clinical trials inclusion should be one of the possible recommendations by the MTB.

The only item that received enough agreement to proceed to the second round (66.67%) was the recommendation that the case manager or treating oncologist should recommend additional testing before MTB discussion if necessary.

The remaining items did not meet the required level of agreement and were discarded (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Clinical aspects voted items (first round)

Legend. red items: discarded; blue items: moved to next round; green items: consensus recommendations

6.4.2.2 Second round

The second round of the Delphi consensus exercise was launched on February 24th and remained open for a period of nine days, concluding on March 7th. During this period, a total of 13 out of 17 experts (76.47%) completed the survey. Table 20 summarizes the expertise collected.

ID	Expertise
#1	Medical oncology
#2	Cancer genomics, clinical oncology
#3	Medical oncology
#4	Clinical oncology, early phase clinical trials, personalized therapy
#5	Medical oncology
#6	Pathology, precision oncology, data infrastructure

#7	Oncology nursing
#8	Medical oncology
#9	Medical oncology
#10	Phase I clinical trials design and conduction
#11	MTB coordinator
#12	Translational oncology
#13	Clinical oncology

Table 20. Summary of expertise collected among second round responders

Organizational aspects domain.

In the organizational aspects domain, the second round included a total of 14 items, with 10 items rated on the Likert scale and 4 open-ended questions. The 10 items rated were revised based on the results from the first round, considering the voting and feedback provided by the experts.

Regarding the experts to be included in the MTB meeting, three items were considered in this category. Of these, the only item that surpassed the threshold, with 84.62% agreement, was the inclusion of other professionals' specialties (including hematologists, endocrinologists, surgeons, etc.), if relevant to the case. These demands should be made by the referent physician. The other two items did not reach even 70% agreement (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Level of agreement for each professional figure (second round)

Legend. red items: discarded; green items: consensus recommendations

For the gatherings of MTBs, the items were reworked based on the size of the board in question, dividing them into small MTBs and high-volume MTBs. With this distinction, both items surpassed the threshold: high-volume MTBs should meet weekly or at least biweekly, according to all experts (84.62%), while smaller MTBs should have flexible meeting schedules based on the number of cases submitted for discussion, ensuring they meet at least biweekly to guarantee reasonable TATs (92.31%).

Based on the experts' comments, additional items were added to the medical report category, of which only one surpassed the threshold: Actionability should be clearly divided into germline and somatic, with separate comments for each (92.31%).

Regarding the other organizational aspects to be included in the MTB meetings, the experts reached consensus on two key points. The first, with 92.31% agreement, was that a clinical trial referred

person (such as clinical trial navigators) should attend the MTB discussions. The second, receiving 84.62% agreement, emphasized that the case manager and treating physician should work together to prepare the case presentation for the MTB meeting.

Figure 20 summarizes the results for organizational aspects domain.

Figure 20. Organizational aspects domain results (second round)

Legend. red items: discarded; green items: consensus recommendations

Testing domain.

In the testing domain, there were five items in total, four of which were subject to voting, while one was an open-ended question. Two of the four items reached a consensus agreement of 84.62%.

Experts agreed that NGS testing for each case should preferably be conducted by a central laboratory within the referring hospital, although it should not be mandatory; they also agreed that NGS testing could be outsourced to a certified external laboratory. Additionally, experts concurred that NGS results should be checked by the treating oncologist and the case manager to assess whether there is an actionable alteration considering the recent literature.

However, the other two items, which addressed the use of biological classification knowledge bases for molecular alterations identification and their relevance to MTB assessments, did not reach a consensus level sufficient to advance to a third round (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Testing domain results (second round)

Legend. red items: discarded; green items: consensus recommendations

Inclusion criteria domain.

In the inclusion criteria domain, there were five items, four of which were subject to voting and one open-ended. Among the items, two reached the threshold for consensus, with both receiving 92.31% agreement. Experts agreed that patients for whom there is no already known available therapy should be included in MTB discussions, as well as those with significant evidence of molecular actionability, even if they have not been treated with first-line therapy or are not in therapeutic failure.

On the other hand, two items did not meet the 80% threshold. Only 69.23% of experts agreed that experiencing at least one therapeutic failure should not be a criterion for determining whether a case is discussed in an MTB. Similarly, the same percentage (69.23%) of experts agreed on the inclusion of all patients diagnosed with a recurrence that is not amenable to curative therapy, but this item did not reach the necessary level of consensus to move forward to the next round (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Inclusion criteria domain results (second round)

Legend. red items: discarded; green items: consensus recommendations

Clinical aspects domain.

For the clinical aspects domain, many of the questions from the first round were revised based on the feedback received. We created new questions with four items to be rated and two open-ended questions where experts could provide additional opinions, for example, on the PFS ratio. Unfortunately, none of the items reached the 80% threshold, nor did any achieve a level of consensus sufficient to justify moving to a third round of Delphi.

5.4.2.3 Consensus statements

Area	Round 1	Round 2	Items that reached consensus (R1+R2)
Organizational aspects	16	6	22
Testing	3	2	5

Inclusion criteria	5	2	7
Clinical aspects	2	0	2
Total	26	10	36

Table 20. Items that reached consensus between round 1, 2 and both.

The total number of recommendations gathered from the Delphi consensus exercise amounts to 36, with 26 coming from the first round and 10 from the second round (Table 20). Specifically, within the organizational aspects domain, 16 recommendations were collected from the first round, while 6 were obtained from the second round. In the testing domain, 3 recommendations emerged from the first round, and 2 were added in the second round. For inclusion criteria, 5 recommendations came from the first round, with 2 further recommendations identified in the second round. Finally, the clinical aspects domain contributed 2 recommendations from the first round. The full list of items that reached consensus can be found in supplementary table 14.

6.4.3 Recommendations

Recommendations were produced by domain and items that reached consensus and are shown in Tables 21, 22, 23 and 24.

The referent clinician should be appointed to present each case, before MTB discussion. The case should be prepared with case manager (1, 2, 18)
A case submission tool should be employed, and the treating oncologist is expected to refer their patient through this platform (3)
Ideal timings: for MTB output (discussion to therapy recommendation) should be less than two weeks; global TAT* (testing to therapy recommendation) should be 28 days (4, 5)
Whenever possible, MTBs should be held online to enhance accessibility to all available experts and to overcome logistical barriers (6)
The work of MTBs should be supported by technological systems that assist in clinical decision-making (7)

MTB meetings should include oncologists, molecular biologist/biotechnologist, pathologist, medical geneticists, treating physician, clinical trial referred person (e.g. clinical trial navigator). Other professionals' specialties may be included if relevant for the case - demanded by referent clinician (8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 17, 19)

Medical records should include sample and patients' details, molecular alterations, clinical trials suggestions, and actionability should be clearly divided into germline and somatic, with separate comments for each (13, 14, 15, 16, 22)

MTBs should gather: weekly or at least biweekly (high-volume MTBs); flexibly based on the number of cases submitted for discussion, ensuring at least biweekly meetings (smaller MTBs) (20, 21)

Table 214 Organizational aspects recommendations (22 items)

NGS should be the leading sequencing choice for all the patients entering the MTB; it should be conducted by a central laboratory within the referring hospital (not mandatory) but it could be also outsourced to a certified external laboratory (23, 26, 27)

Databases to be consulted are the 1000 Genomes Browser, cBioPortal, ClinVar, COSMIC, dbSNP, Ensembl, JAX-CKB, OncoKB, and Pubmed (24)

The panel should include gene listed in the ESCAT and ONCOKB criteria, at least up to Tier IIIA for ESCAT and Tier 3B for OncoKB (25)

Table 22. Testing recommendations (5 items)

Patients to be included should be: metastatic and non-metastatic; ECOG between 0 and 2; life expectancy +12 weeks; exhaustion of standard therapeutic lines; rare diseases patients or specific histologies with limited therapeutic options; for whom there is no already known available therapy (28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33)

Patients with significant evidence of molecular actionability could be discussed by the MTB, even if they have not been yet treated with first line therapy or are not in therapeutic failure (34)

Table 23. Inclusion criteria recommendations (7 items)

Additional testing, including invasive testing, could be a possible MTB recommendation (35)

Clinical trials inclusion should be one of the possible recommendations by the MTB (36)

Table 24. Clinical aspects recommendations (2 items)

MOLECULAR TUMOUR BOARDS: Shaping the Future of Cancer Care

A policy brief.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs) have demonstrated significant potential in improving patient outcomes, particularly by increasing progression-free survival (PFS)^[1] and overall survival (OS)^[2] compared to the standard of care. The impact extends beyond recommending therapies, influencing early and accurate diagnoses, providing access to sequencing and identification of actionable mutations, and enabling patient enrollment in clinical trials. A panel of European experts from 10 EU member states, guided by a methodological group, formulated recommendations for the basic functioning of MTBs.

Key results are divided in three domains: organizational aspects, genomic testing and sequencing and inclusion criteria and clinical aspects. For the organizational aspects domain, the MTB composition for meetings should include oncologists, pathologists, molecular biologists, geneticists, and treating physicians, the case presentation should be made by a referent clinician assigned to each case, and should be previously prepared with case manager, the ideal turnaround time should be 28 days and the meetings should be held weekly.

For sequencing, Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) should be the preferred method, and a broad range of databases should be consulted to evaluate actionability.

For inclusion criteria, patients should be in a good performance status and in therapeutic failures; however, discussions should be open also to patients with strong molecular actionability evidence, even if not yet treated.

This policy brief aims to underline the transformative impact MTBs can have on cancer care and to provide actionable policy recommendations for their equitable implementation across Europe.

This policy brief has been developed by the working group of the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC) of Rome, in the context of the EU funded project CAN.HEAL.

[1] Progression Free Survival (PFS): The length of time a patient lives with the disease without it getting worse

[2] Overall Survival (OS): The total time from diagnosis or treatment start until death from any cause

INTRODUCTION

Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs) represent a key opportunity to improve outcomes for cancer patients through personalized treatment strategies based on molecular profiling. Evidence from across Europe demonstrates that MTBs not only extend PFS and OS but also contribute to earlier and more accurate diagnoses, facilitate access to advanced sequencing technologies, and enable patient inclusion in clinical trials.

This policy brief summarizes actionable recommendations developed by a European expert panel from ten Member States, aimed at promoting the effective and equitable implementation of MTBs across the EU. The proposed guidance addresses core elements such as board composition, case management, sequencing protocols, and eligibility criteria. By scaling up MTBs, Europe has the potential to advance precision oncology while strengthening cancer care pathways.

BACKGROUND AND CHALLENGES

Precision oncology has the potential to tailor therapies based on the molecular characteristics of each tumor^[3]. In this context, MTBs have gained traction as innovative structures designed to translate complex genomic data into actionable clinical decisions.

MTBs are multidisciplinary groups that bring together oncologists, pathologists, geneticists, bioinformaticians, and other experts to interpret clinical and molecular data. Through regular or ad hoc meetings, either virtual or in-person, they assess the actionability of mutations, recommend personalized treatment options (including off-label therapies), and identify eligibility for clinical trials. Their ultimate goal is to ensure that all cancer patients, regardless of disease stage or tumor type, have equitable access to precision medicine strategies and novel therapies.

A recent survey^[4] shows that MTBs are becoming more institutionalized across Europe. Forty-one percent adopt a tumor-agnostic approach, twenty-four percent focus on specific solid tumors, and twenty-seven percent cover both solid and hematological cancers. In terms of disease stages, half address all stages, including non-metastatic, while a quarter focus on refractory diseases. Targeted DNA/RNA sequencing is most common, with Whole Exome Sequencing (WES) and Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) less used due to reimbursement and access issues. Despite their potential, MTBs have a modest impact on patient management, with only 0–20% of patients receiving trial or off-label drug recommendations.

A meta-analysis^[5] demonstrated the clinical value of MTB-guided treatment decisions, showing significant improvements in patient outcomes. Therapies recommended by MTBs were associated with a reduction in the risk of disease progression (PFS) ranging from 17% to 39% and a reduction in mortality risk (OS) between 10% and 40%. When focusing on randomized controlled trials, results showed a significant benefit on PFS (Hazard Ratio (HR) 0.74; 95% CI: 0.61–0.90). Additionally, 33.1% to 43.1% of patients achieved a PFS ratio ≥ 1.3 , indicating better disease control than with their previous treatments. These results reinforce the potential of MTBs to optimize therapy choices and contribute to improved clinical outcomes.

Various challenges limit the implementation of MTBs. Geographic, socioeconomic, and institutional barriers hinder patients' ability to benefit from these innovations. Insurance coverage and reimbursement mechanisms are not uniformly established, and expertise is often concentrated in large academic centers, limiting the availability of MTBs in rural or underserved areas, where infrastructure and funding are missing. Moreover, patient enrollment in clinical trials, often one of the key outputs of MTB recommendations, is restricted due to limited trial availability or heterogeneous distribution across regions.

[3] Passaro A, Al Bakir M, Hamilton EG, et al. Cancer biomarkers: Emerging trends and clinical implications for personalized treatment. *Cell*. 2024 Mar 28;187(7):1617–1635. doi:10.1016/j.cell.2024.02.041. PMID: 38552610; PMCID: PMC7616034.

[4] D8.4 – Number of patients oriented towards personalised treatment. Dupain C., Nadal E., Gausachs M., Codony C., Chamoun Morel Z.

[5] Russo L, Giacobini E, Lentini N, et al. Molecular Tumor Boards clinical utility and impact on patient care: a systematic review and metanalysis. Manuscript in preparation

As per technical and operational barriers, Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) is central to MTB workflows, yet in-house sequencing capacity requires considerable investment in infrastructure, accreditation, and workforce training. Interpretation of genomic results is time-consuming and often inconsistent, and many

clinicians report low confidence in interpreting genomic data and integrating precision oncology into their clinical practice, while patients often face confusion or anxiety regarding the implications of genomic testing.

There are also pressing ethical, legal, and societal issues (ELSI) to address. Clear, harmonized consent processes are essential to uphold patient autonomy, facilitate data sharing, and promote responsible use of genomic information. Cross-border collaboration remains limited by divergent data protection laws and inconsistent data formats, further complicating interoperability.

Despite these challenges, cost analyses suggest that the MTBs themselves represent a modest portion of the total cost of cancer care, with the greatest financial impact stemming from treatment and hospitalization. As such, strategic investment in MTB infrastructure and capacity (coupled with training, policy harmonization, and public engagement) can unlock their full potential and contribute to more equitable and effective cancer care systems.

This policy brief aims to support decision-makers in implementing MTBs across Europe by identifying a set of actionable recommendations that can serve as a foundation for further action and complement existing guidance. Ultimately, these efforts contribute to strengthening health systems through the lens of precision oncology. The recommendations were developed through a Delphi process involving 17 experts from 10 EU countries.

Key elements to be included in the guideline development process were identified through two literature reviews. A systematic review was conducted to address the clinical impact of MTBs and related clinical aspects, while a narrative review assessed implementation aspects, including the organization of MTBs, their composition, and sequencing.

CONCLUSIONS

MTBs are rapidly becoming a critical component in the landscape of precision oncology, offering a structured, evidence-based approach to translating complex molecular data into tailored clinical decisions. The expert-driven recommendations outlined in this policy brief provide a practical, consensus-based guidance for the harmonized and scalable implementation of MTBs across Europe.

Looking ahead, the integration of MTBs into national cancer plans and European health strategies will be essential. Strategic investments in cancer research, reduction of drug-related costs, broader distribution of MTBs and clinical trials, and the development of interoperable data platforms can significantly enhance their efficiency and reach. Equally important is the commitment to workforce development, cross-border collaboration, and the establishment of structured educational and training programmes. By aligning policy, infrastructure, and clinical practice, MTBs can evolve from a fragmented innovation into a standardized pillar of high-quality oncology care, ultimately contributing to improved patient outcomes, system sustainability, and scientific progress in the fight against cancer.

Recommendations for optimal implementation of MTBs in EU

ORGANIZATIONAL ASPECTS

- The referent clinician should be appointed to present each case, before MTB discussion. The case should be prepared with case manager.
- A case submission tool should be employed, and the treating oncologist is expected to refer their patient through this platform.
- Ideal timings: for MTB output (discussion to therapy recommendation) should be less than two weeks; global TAT (testing to therapy recommendation) should be 28 days.
- Whenever possible, MTBs should be held online to enhance accessibility to all available experts and to overcome logistical barriers.
- The work of MTBs should be supported by technological systems that assist in clinical decision-making.
- MTB meetings should include oncologists, molecular biologist/biotechnologist, pathologist, medical geneticists, treating physician, clinical trial referred person (e.g. clinical trial navigator). Other professionals' specialties may be included if relevant for the case – demanded by referent clinician.
- Medical records should include sample and patients' details, molecular alterations, clinical trials suggestions, and actionability should be clearly divided into germline and somatic, with separate comments for each.
- MTBs should gather weekly or at least biweekly (high-volume MTBs); flexibly based on the number of cases submitted for discussion, ensuring at least biweekly meetings (smaller MTBs).

GENOMIC TESTING AND SEQUENCING

- NGS should be the leading sequencing choice for all the patients entering the MTB; it should be conducted by a central laboratory within the referring hospital (not mandatory) but it could be also outsourced to a certified external laboratory.
- Databases to be consulted are the 1000 Genomes Browser, cBioPortal, ClinVar, COSMIC, dbSNP, Ensembl, JAX-CKB, OncoKB, and Pubmed.
- The panel should include gene listed in the ESCAT and ONCOKB criteria, at least up to Tier IIIA for ESCAT and Tier 3B for OncoKB.

INCLUSION CRITERIA AND CLINICAL ASPECTS

- Patients to be included should be: metastatic and non-metastatic; ECOG between 0 and 2; life expectancy +12 weeks; exhaustion of standard therapeutic lines; rare diseases patients or specific histologies with limited therapeutic options; for whom there is no already known available therapy.
- Patients with significant evidence of molecular actionability could be discussed by the MTB, even if they have not been yet treated with first line therapy or are not in therapeutic failure.
- Additional testing, including invasive testing, could be a possible MTB recommendation.
- Clinical trials inclusion should be one of the possible recommendations by the MTB.

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

7. Conclusions

7.1 Summary of key insights

The WP14's final recommendations reflect a shared vision across three innovative domains aimed at embedding precision oncology within EU health systems. PRS offer a promising yet still-developing tool to stratify BC risk and optimize screening strategies. Despite their potential to tailor surveillance and reduce overdiagnosis, the evidence remains preliminary, with uncertainties surrounding clinical utility, equity, and real-world applicability. LB, by contrast, has progressed further along the translational pathway, with validated protocols and encouraging real-world evidence supporting its role in mCRC management—particularly for treatment monitoring and guiding therapy decisions. Nonetheless, systemic integration depends on addressing issues of standardization, cost-effectiveness, and health system readiness. MTBs stand out as a structural innovation with demonstrable clinical and organizational impact. By fostering multidisciplinary decision-making, MTBs enhance the translation of molecular diagnostics into tailored treatment, especially in complex cases. However, their scalability depends on robust digital infrastructures, clear governance models, and sustainable reimbursement frameworks. Across all three domains, the project underscores the importance of stakeholder co-creation, the GRADE EtD framework, and cross-national alignment to ensure that innovation is not only technically viable but ethically grounded and implementable at scale across Europe's diverse healthcare systems.

7.2 Roadmap for research and policy implementation.

To ensure the successful and sustainable integration of PRS, LB, and MTBs into EU health systems, a strategic and phased roadmap for research and policy implementation is essential. This roadmap should address current gaps in evidence, enhance implementation capacity, and promote equity, trust, and transparency across member states.

1. Evidence generation through pragmatic and comparative research

- **For PRS in BC screening**, immediate priorities include conducting large-scale prospective studies and implementation trials to assess real-world clinical utility, cost-effectiveness, and impact on health inequalities. Ongoing RCTs like MyPeBS and WISDOM must be complemented with EU-specific cohort studies, particularly targeting underrepresented populations.

- **For LB in mCRC**, expanding multicentric observational studies and real-world evaluations is key. Focus should be placed on validating predictive biomarkers, exploring longitudinal use in treatment monitoring, and developing comparative effectiveness studies versus standard tissue biopsy.
- **For MTBs**, systematic evaluations of different organizational models and their impact on patient outcomes, decision TATs, and clinical trial access are needed. Multi-country comparative studies can elucidate how MTBs perform across different health system structures.

2. Infrastructure and capacity building

- Establishing **interoperable digital platforms** and **genomic data governance frameworks** is fundamental, particularly for integrating PRS and MTB-related tools. National health data hubs should align with the European Health Data Space to enable secure and efficient data sharing.
- Investments in **laboratory standardization and NGS validation networks**, particularly for LB assays, are necessary to ensure test reliability and consistency across borders.
- Workforce development is critical: targeted training programs for genetic counsellors, oncologists, pathologists, and MTB coordinators must be prioritized to ensure a skilled, multidisciplinary workforce capable of implementing personalized oncology strategies.

3. Policy Harmonization and Reimbursement Reform

- National and EU-level health authorities should explore **value-based reimbursement models** for LB and PRS-enhanced screening, anchored in real-world evidence and dynamic health technology assessments (HTA).
- **Guidance on the ethical use of genomic data**, patient consent frameworks, and insurance protections must be co-developed with regulators, legal experts, and civil society to foster public trust and protect against misuse.
- Reimbursement pathways for MTBs, particularly those involving digital decision-support tools, should be clarified to support scalability and integration into standard oncology pathways.

4. Stakeholder engagement and public dialogue

- Co-creation models used in CAN.HEAL should be institutionalized in national genomics strategies to ensure continued input from patients, clinicians, policymakers, and researchers.
- **Public-facing educational campaigns** and risk communication tools must accompany the rollout of PRS and LB initiatives, especially to manage expectations and clarify the meaning of genetic risk.
- MTBs should develop inclusive governance models that incorporate patient perspectives and reflect national diversity, ensuring decisions are culturally competent and contextually sensitive.

5. Monitoring, evaluation, and iterative learning

- An EU-wide **monitoring and evaluation framework** should be developed for precision oncology innovations, with shared indicators for effectiveness, equity, and efficiency.
- A learning health system model should be adopted, enabling rapid-cycle feedback loops between evidence generation, policy updates, and clinical practice adjustments.
- Pilot programs (e.g., PRS integration in targeted subpopulations, LB-based monitoring protocols) should include embedded evaluation components to inform phased expansion based on measurable impact.

8. Supplementary materials

Supplementary Table 1: Summary Screening Strategies

This table provides an overview of the screening strategies assessed in each included study, focusing on how PRS was used to inform screening decisions. For each model, we report general comments, PRS group details, the age range for screening initiation and cessation, screening frequency, and modality. strategies are described in terms of their application and frequency, with particular attention to prs-based stratification without consideration of family history.

Model	General Comments	PRS details	Age - Begin	Age - End	Screening Strategy Frequency	Screening Strategy Modality
Van den Broek et al. (2021) ⁴²	Only PRS without FH	PRS Group 7	30	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	Only PRS without FH	PRS Group 6	35	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	Only PRS without FH	PRS Group 5	40	49	Annual 40-50	Digital mammography
	Only PRS without FH	PRS Group 5	50	74	Biennial 50-74	Digital mammography
	Only PRS without FH	PRS Group 4	40	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	Only PRS without FH	PRS Group 3	40	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	Only PRS without FH	PRS Group 2	50	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	Only PRS without FH	PRS Group 1	50	74	Triennial	Digital mammography
	SoC without FH	PRS Group 7	50	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	SoC without FH	PRS Group 6	50	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	SoC without FH	PRS Group 5	50	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	SoC without FH	PRS Group 4	50	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	SoC without FH	PRS Group 3	50	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	SoC without FH	PRS Group 2	50	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	SoC without FH	PRS Group 1	50	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 30-39	PRS Group 7	30	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 40-49	PRS Group 7	30	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 50-64	PRS Group 7	30	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 65+	PRS Group 7	30	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	no BC FH	PRS Group 7	30	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 30-39	PRS Group 6	30	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 40-49	PRS Group 6	35	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 50-64	PRS Group 6	35	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 65+	PRS Group 6	35	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	no BC FH	PRS Group 6	35	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 30-39	PRS Group 5	30	74	Annual	Digital mammography

	PRS + positive FH 40-49	PRS Group 5	40	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 50-64	PRS Group 5	40	49	Annual 40-50	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 50-64	PRS Group 5	50	74	Biennial 50-74	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 65+	PRS Group 5	40	49	Annual 40-50	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 65+	PRS Group 5	50	74	Biennial 50-74	Digital mammography
	no BC FH	PRS Group 5	40	49	Annual 40-50	Digital mammography
	no BC FH	PRS Group 5	50	74	Biennial 50-74	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 30-39	PRS Group 4	30	54	Annual 30-54	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 30-39	PRS Group 4	55	74	Biennial 55-74	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 40-49	PRS Group 4	40	49	Annual 40-50	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 40-49	PRS Group 4	50	74	Biennial 50-74	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 50-64	PRS Group 4	40	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 65+	PRS Group 4	40	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	no BC FH	PRS Group 4	40	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 30-39	PRS Group 3	30	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 40-49	PRS Group 3	40	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 50-64	PRS Group 3	45	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 65+	PRS Group 3	45	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	no BC FH	PRS Group 3	45	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 30-39	PRS Group 2	35	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 40-49	PRS Group 2	40	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 50-64	PRS Group 2	50	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 65+	PRS Group 2	50	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	no BC FH	PRS Group 2	50	74	Biennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 30-39	PRS Group 1	30	74	Annual	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 40-49	PRS Group 1	40	74	Triennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 50-64	PRS Group 1	50	74	Triennial	Digital mammography
	PRS + positive FH 65+	PRS Group 1	50	74	Triennial	Digital mammography
	no BC FH	PRS Group 1	50	74	Triennial	Digital mammography
Pashayan et al. (2018)	PRS	PRS for each percentile	50	69	Triennial	2-view Digital mammography
	No PRS	Age based	50	69	Triennial	2-view Digital mammography
	No PRS	No screening	50	69	Triennial	None
Wong et al. (2021)	SoC		35	69	Biennial	Mammography
	Low PRS		35	39	self examination	Self examination

	Low PRS		40	74	Triennial	Mammography
	Intermediate PRS		35	39	Biennial	Mammography
	Intermediate PRS		40	74	Biennial	Mammography
	High PRS		35	39	Annual ultrasound	Ultrasound
	High PRS		40	74	Annual	Mammography
Huntley et al. (2023)	PRS	PRS-defined high-risk quintile future PRS (top 20%)	40	49	Annual	Digital mammography
	PRS	PRS-defined high-risk quintile current PRS (top 20%)	40	49	Annual	Digital mammography
	No PRS	Oldest quintile (top 20%)	40	49	Annual	Digital mammography
	No PRS	Randomly selected quintile (20%)	40	49	Annual	Digital mammography
	No PRS	Full population	40	49	Annual	Digital mammography

Supplementary tables 2: data summary of PRS modelling studies

Summary of health outcomes from included studies evaluating the clinical utility of PRS for BC screening. Each table provides a summary of health outcomes reported across the four studies included in the systematic review. For each outcome, the relative and absolute effects of PRS-informed BC screening are presented, along with corresponding 95% confidence intervals.

Supplementary Table 2.1: Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴²

Model average benefits, harms, and benefit to harm ratios for screening based on polygenic risk per 1000 women screened						
	# of screens	LYG	BC death averted	Over diagnoses	False Positive	
USPSTF	11198,06	113,30	6,38	13,64	920,69	
Polygenic risk	12984,57	135,75	7,07	14,99	1155,24	

Absolute effect		22,45	0,70	1,35	234,55
95% CI		(21,33; 23,57)	(0,66; 0,73)	(1,28; 1,42)	(222,82; 246,28)
Relative risk		1,2	1,1	1,1	1,25
95% CI		(1,14; 1,26)	(1,05; 1,16)	(1,04; 1,16)	(1,19; 1,32)

		# of screens	LYG	BC death averted	Overdiagnoses	False Positive
FH + 30-39 y	USPSTF	309,69	13,82	0,50	0,67	25,40
	Polygenic risk	760,80	18,97	0,91	1,21	70,71
FH + 40-49 y	USPSTF	453,77	6,41	0,35	0,67	37,28
	Polygenic risk	736,25	8,49	0,42	0,76	68,25
FH + 50-64 y	USPSTF	614,07	12,76	0,68	0,99	50,40

	Polygenic risk	1003,76	17,60	0,84	1,19	93,12
FH + 65 y	USPSTF	220,82	7,93	0,42	0,48	18,08
	Polygenic risk	366,72	11,13	0,53	0,61	34,09
No + FH in life	USPSTF	8202,34	262,20	14,16	18,74	672,27
	Polygenic risk	13552,11	359,92	17,35	23,18	1259,73

	BC death averted				LYG				Over diagnoses				False Positive			
	Relative (95% CI)		Absolute (95% CI)		Relative (95% CI)		Absolute (95% CI)		Relative (95% CI)		Absolute (95% CI)		Relative (95% CI)		Absolute (95% CI)	
	Relative Effect	95% CI	Absolute Effect	95% CI	Relative Effect	95% CI	Absolute Effect	95% CI	Relative Effect	95% CI	Absolute Effect	95% CI	Relative Effect	95% CI	Absolute Effect	95% CI
All	1,11	1,05 ; 1,16	0,70	0,66 ; 0,73	1,20	1,14 ; 1,26	22,45	21,33 ; 23,57	1,10	1,04 ; 1,15	1,35	1,28 ; 1,42	1,25	1,19 ; 1,32	234,55	222,82 ; 246,28
FH + 30-39 y	1,82		0,41		1,37		5,15		1,82		0,55		2,78		45,32	
FH + 40-49 y	1,18		0,06		1,33		2,09		1,14		0,09		1,83		30,97	
FH + 50-64 y	1,22		0,15		1,38		4,83		1,20		0,20		1,85		42,73	
FH + 65 y	1,25		0,11		1,40		3,21		1,28		0,13		1,89		16,01	
FH-	1,22		3,18		1,37		97,72		1,24		4,43		1,87		587,46	
FH + PRS	1,34	1,27 ; 1,41	0,78	0,74 ; 0,82	1,37	1,3 ; 1,44	22,60	21,47 ; 23,73	1,33	1,27 ; 1,4	1,08	1,03 ; 1,14	2,04	1,94 ; 2,15	144,50	137,27 ; 151,72

Supplementary table 2.2: Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰

Screening strategy	BC deaths averted	Overdiagnoses
Oldest quintile (top 20%)	80	190
Randomly selected quintile (%20)	55	
Full population	274	
PRS-defined high-risk quintile future PRS (top 20%)	121	
PRS-defined high-risk quintile current PRS (top 20%)	102	243

Relative Effect	1,28	1,28
95% CI of RE	1,21 ; 1,34	1,22 ; 1,34
Absolute Effect	22,00	53,00
95% CI of AE	20,9 ; 23,1	50,35 ; 55,65

Supplementary Table 2.3: Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴

Incremental Calculations (Tailored – Current)

Category % of all women

Guideline	Screening strategy	LYG	QALYs	Cost	Costs	Life Years	QALYs	ICER (SGD/QALY)
Standard	mammogram screening every 2 years	21,89	21,80	21475				
Polygenic risk	Based on individual's PRS 60th, 95th and 5th percentiles	22,86	22,78	23730				

Low - 60° percentile	51%
Intermediate - 95° percentile	41%
High - 5° percentile	8%

LYG				QALYs			
Relative (95% CI)		Absolute (95% CI)		Relative (95% CI)		Absolute (95% CI)	
Relative Effect	95% CI	Absolute Effect	95% CI	Relative Effect	95% CI	Absolute Effect	95% CI
1,04	0,99 ; 1,1	0,97	0,92 ; 1,02	1,04	0,99 ; 1,1	0,98	0,93 ; 1,03

Supplementary Table 2.4: Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³

	unscreened	# of BC cases	Over diagnoses	# BC deaths averted	Other causes deaths	PYRS	QALY	Cost (£)	# BC death
No screening	26826	26826			239113	6421926	4696181	163486827	10631
Age-based screening		31889	3819	1913	240301	6430124	4698098	205365932	8718
PRS screening			2773,35	1612,79		6428804,77	4714439,76		9018,21

Relative Effect
95% CI of RE
Absolute Effect
95% CI of AE

0,73	0,84
0,69 ; 0,76	0,8 ; 0,89
-1045,65	-300,21
-993,37 ; -1097,93	-315,22 ; -285,2

0,9998	1,00
0,95 ; 1,05	0,95 ; 1,05
-1319,23	16341,76
-1253,27 ; -1385,19	15524,67 ; 17158,85

Low	645,38	10199,95
Intermediate	2679,45	9060,20
High	3353,94	8743,8

4713343,4	2	6423821,18
4714447,5	3	6428609,00
4714473,6	2	6430050,42

Supplementary Table 3: summary of health outcomes and effect estimates for PRS-tailored versus SoC BC screening

The table present detailed outcome data from the included papers, comparing PRS-tailored BC screening with SoC strategies. For each outcome, the tables include the name and description, unit of measurement, population characteristics, absolute and relative effects, and their 95% confidence intervals. Additionally, it reports the percentage variation between PRS-tailored screening and SoC.

OUTCOME			Van den Broek et al. (2021)								
Name	Description	Unit of measurement	Characteristics	PRS-tailored screening	SoC	Absolute effect	Absolute Effect CI 95%	Relative risk	Relative Effect CI 95%	What we have from RR	Percent variation from SoC to PRS-tailored screening
LYG	The total number of additional years of life that individuals in a population gain as a result of an intervention, compared to the scenario without the intervention or when a standard approach is applied.	Years gained	General population without considering FH	135,75	113,30	22,45	21,33 ; 23,57	1,20	1,14 ; 1,26	19,82%	19,82%
			Weighted mean with FH	300,92	219,22	81,70	77,61 ; 85,78	1,37	1,3 ; 1,44	37,18%	37,27%
			FH + 30-39 y	18,97	13,82	5,15	4,89 ; 5,41	1,37	1,3 ; 1,44	37,26%	37,26%
			FH + 40-49 y	8,49	6,41	2,08	1,98 ; 2,18	1,32	1,26 ; 1,39	32,45%	32,45%
			FH + 50-64 y	17,60	12,76	4,84	4,6 ; 5,08	1,38	1,31 ; 1,45	37,93%	37,93%
			FH + +65 y	11,13	7,93	3,20	3,04 ; 3,36	1,40	1,33 ; 1,47	40,35%	40,35%
			No +FH in life	359,92	262,20	97,72	92,83 ; 102,61	1,37	1,3 ; 1,44	37,27%	37,27%
BC death averted	The reduction in the number of BC-related deaths due to a specific intervention compared to a control group.	Number of deaths avoided	General population without considering FH	7,07	6,38	0,69	0,66 ; 0,72	1,108	1,05 ; 1,16	10,82%	10,82%
			Weighted mean with FH	14,51	11,83	2,68	2,54 ; 2,81	1,25	1,19 ; 1,32	25,36%	25,36%
			FH + 30-39 y	0,91	0,50	0,41	0,39 ; 0,43	1,82	1,73 ; 1,91	82,00%	82,00%
			FH + 40-49 y	0,42	0,35	0,07	0,07 ; 0,07	1,20	1,14 ; 1,26	20,00%	20,00%
			FH + 50-64 y	0,84	0,68	0,16	0,15 ; 0,17	1,24	1,17 ; 1,3	23,53%	23,53%
			FH + +65 y	0,53	0,42	0,11	0,1 ; 0,12	1,26	1,2 ; 1,33	26,19%	26,19%
			No +FH in life	17,35	14,16	3,19	3,03 ; 3,35	1,23	1,16 ; 1,29	22,53%	22,53%

QALYs	It adjusts the total life years lived by weighting them according to the quality of health during those years.	Years adjusted for quality of life									
PYRS	It sums up the survival time for all individuals in the cohort over the follow-up period.	Person-year									
Over diagnoses	The number of cases diagnosed with BC that would not have caused symptoms or led to death during the patient's lifetime (caused by more intensive screening).	Number of cases	General population without considering FH	14,99	13,64	1,35	1,28 ; 1,42	1,10	1,04 ; 1,15	9,90%	9,90%
			Weighted mean with FH	19,39	15,66	3,72	3,54 ; 3,91	1,26	1,2 ; 1,32	25,81%	25,81%
			FH + 30-39 y	1,21	0,67	0,54	0,51 ; 0,57	1,81	1,72 ; 1,9	80,60%	80,60%
			FH + 40-49 y	0,76	0,67	0,09	0,09 ; 0,09	1,13	1,08 ; 1,19	13,43%	13,43%
			FH + 50-64 y	1,19	0,99	0,20	0,19 ; 0,21	1,20	1,14 ; 1,26	20,20%	20,20%
			FH + +65 y	0,61	0,48	0,13	0,12 ; 0,14	1,27	1,21 ; 1,33	27,08%	27,08%
			No +FH in life	23,18	18,74	4,44	4,22 ; 4,66	1,24	1,18 ; 1,3	23,69%	23,69%
False positive	The number of screening results that incorrectly indicate the presence of BC when no disease is actually present.	Number of cases	General population without considering FH	1155,24	920,69	234,55	222,82 ; 246,28	1,25	1,19 ; 1,32	25,48%	25,48%
			Weighted mean with FH	1056,78	563,46	493,32	468,66 ; 517,99	1,91	1,82 ; 2,01	91,35%	91,35%
			FH + 30-39 y	70,71	25,40	45,31	43,04 ; 47,58	2,78	2,64 ; 2,92	178,39%	178,39%
			FH + 40-49 y	68,25	37,28	30,97	29,42 ; 32,52	1,83	1,74 ; 1,92	83,07%	83,07%
			FH + 50-64 y	93,12	50,40	42,72	40,58 ; 44,86	1,85	1,76 ; 1,94	84,76%	84,76%
			FH + +65 y	34,09	18,08	16,01	15,21 ; 16,81	1,89	1,79 ; 1,98	88,55%	88,55%
			No +FH in life	1259,73	672,27	587,46	558,09 ; 616,83	1,87	1,78 ; 1,97	87,38%	87,38%

OUTCOME			Pashayan et al. (2018)							
Name	Description	Unit of measurement	PRS-tailored screening	SoC	Absolute effect	Absolute Effect CI 95%	Relative risk	Relative Effect CI 95%	What we have from RR	Percent variation from SoC to PRS-tailored screening

LYG	The total number of additional years of life that individuals in a population gain as a result of an intervention, compared to the scenario without the intervention or when a standard approach is applied.	Years gained								
BC death averted	The reduction in the number of BC-related deaths due to a specific intervention compared to a control group.	Number of deaths avoided	1612,79	1913	-300,21	-285,2 ; -315,22	0,84	0,8 ; 0,89	-15,69%	-15,69%
QALYs	It adjusts the total life years lived by weighting them according to the quality of health during those years.	Years adjusted for quality of life	4714439,76	4698098,00	16.341,76	15524,67 ; 17158,85	1,003	0,95 ; 1,05	0,35%	0,35%
PYRS	It sums up the survival time for all individuals in the cohort over the follow-up period.	Person-year	6428804,77	6430124,00	-1.319,23	-1385,19 ; -1253,27	0,9998	1,05 ; 0,95	-0,02%	-0,02%
Over diagnoses	The number of cases diagnosed with BC that would not have caused symptoms or led to death during the patient's lifetime (caused by more intensive screening).	Number of cases	2773,35	3819,00	-1045,65	-1097,93 ; -993,37	0,73	0,76 ; 0,69	-27,38%	-27,38%
False positive	The number of screening results that incorrectly indicate the presence of BC when no disease is actually present.	Number of cases								

OUTCOME			Wong et al. (2021)							
Name	Description	Unit of measurement	PRS-tailored screening	SoC	Absolute effect	Absolute Effect CI 95%	Relative risk	Relative Effect CI 95%	What we have from RR	Percent variation from SoC to PRS-tailored screening
LYG	The total number of additional years of life that individuals in a population gain as a result of an intervention, compared to the scenario without the intervention or when a standard approach is applied.	Years gained	22,86	21,89	0,97	0,92 ; 1,02	1,04	0,99 ; 1,1	4,43%	4,43%

BC death averted	The reduction in the number of BC-related deaths due to a specific intervention compared to a control group.	Number of deaths avoided								
QALYs	It adjusts the total life years lived by weighting them according to the quality of health during those years.	Years adjusted for quality of life	21,80	22,78	-0,98	-1,03 ; -0,93	0,96	0,91 ; 1	-4,30%	-4,30%
PYRS	It sums up the survival time for all individuals in the cohort over the follow-up period.	Person-year								
Over diagnoses	The number of cases diagnosed with BC that would not have caused symptoms or led to death during the patient's lifetime (caused by more intensive screening).	Number of cases								
False positive	The number of screening results that incorrectly indicate the presence of BC when no disease is actually present.	Number of cases								

OUTCOME			Huntley et al. (2023)							
Name	Description	Unit of measurement	PRS-tailored screening	SoC	Absolute effect	Absolute Effect CI 95%	Relative risk	Relative Effect CI 95%	What we have from RR	Percent variation from SoC to PRS-tailored screening
LYG	The total number of additional years of life that individuals in a population gain as a result of an intervention, compared to the scenario without the intervention or when a standard approach is applied.	Years gained								
BC death averted	The reduction in the number of BC-related deaths due to a specific intervention compared to a control group.	Number of deaths avoided	102,00	80,00	22,00	20,9 ; 23,1	1,28	1,21 ; 1,34	27,50%	27,50%
QALYs	It adjusts the total life years lived by weighting them according to the	Years adjusted for quality of life								

	quality of health during those years.									
PYRS	It sums up the survival time for all individuals in the cohort over the follow-up period.	Person-year								
Over diagnoses	The number of cases diagnosed with BC that would not have caused symptoms or led to death during the patient's lifetime (caused by more intensive screening).	Number of cases	243,00	190,00	53,00	50,35 ; 55,65	1,28	1,22 ; 1,34	27,89%	27,89%
False positive	The number of screening results that incorrectly indicate the presence of BC when no disease is actually present.	Number of cases								

Supplementary Table 4.1: Summary of Evidence Using the GRADE Approach for Evaluating the Clinical Utility of PRS in BC Screening

This table presents a structured summary of the evidence assessed using the GRADEpro framework. It includes key outcomes, effect estimates, certainty ratings, and considerations related to risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, and publication bias. The summary supports decision-making regarding the implementation of PRS-informed breast cancer screening strategies.

Summary of findings:

Should national or sub-national health systems in the European Union consider incorporating polygenic risk scores (PRS), either alone or in combination with family history (FH) vs. standard of care be used in organized breast cancer screening programs to inform risk-stratified screening strategies?

Patient or population: breast cancer screening programmes

Setting: public health / population level

Intervention: polygenic risk score enhanced-screening

Comparison: standard of care

Study	Results
<p><i>Personalizing breast cancer screening based on polygenic risk and family history.</i> 42 Van den Broek et al.</p> <p>Objective: The study aimed to assess the clinical utility of incorporating a polygenic risk score (PRS) and first-degree family history (FH) of breast cancer (BC) to guide personalized BC screening strategies for women aged 30-50 years. It compared various screening initiation ages and intervals, analyzing the benefits (breast cancer deaths averted, life-years gained) and harms (false-positive mammograms, overdiagnosis).</p> <p>Type: Modeling Study/Population-Based Simulation the research used two established BC simulation models from the Cancer Intervention and Surveillance Modeling Network (CISNET).</p> <p>Cohort: 1985 US birth cohort</p> <p>Risk Stratification Criteria:</p>	<p>Results: Risk-tailored screening using PRS and FH improves outcomes but increases harms. Starting biennial screening at 40 for women with FH increased life-years by 36% and BC deaths averted by 20% with more false-positives (63%) and overdiagnoses (21%). PRS-based screening improved life-years by 20% and deaths averted by 11%, with moderate harm increases. Combining PRS and FH maximized benefits (29% more life-years, 18% fewer deaths) while slightly raising harms.</p>

Family History Groups: Women were stratified based on the presence of a first-degree relative with BC (30-39,40-49,50-64,65+ years, no + FH in life).
PRS: Based on 313 SNPs, with 7 risk groups spanning risk levels from 0 to 10 times the US population average.

Intervention:

PRS-based screening
 PRS- and FH-based screening.

Comparison:

The United States Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) 2020 BC screening guidelines [considered as standard of care (SoC)]

Screening Modalities Available:

Digital mammography – Screening strategies considered different starting ages (30, 35, 40, 45 or 50 years) and intervals (annual, biennial, triennial, or hybrid strategies).

Proposed Risk-Based Screening Protocol:

Screening strategies were **personalized by age and risk level**, considering both **FH + PRS**:

Low Risk (PRS < 0.5x) - No screening

Moderate Risk (0.5 - 1.5x) - Biennial screening from age 50-74 years

Intermediate Risk (1.5 - 2.0x) - Biennial screening from age 45-74 years

High Risk (2.0 - 3.0x) - Hybrid screening: Annual (40-49 years), Biennial (50-74 years)

Very High Risk (3.0 - 5.0x) - Hybrid screening: Annual (40-49 years), Biennial (50-74 years)

Highest Risk (5.0 - 10.0x) - Annual screening from 30-74 years

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with polygenic risk score enhanced-screening				
BC deaths averted (FH not considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening)	6 per 1,000	7 per 1,000 (7 to 7)	RR 1.11 (1.05 to 1.16)	1000 (1 non-randomised study)	⊕⊕⊕⊕ Very low ^a	The relative risk (RR) of 1.11 represents the ratio of BC deaths averted using PRS-based screening compared to SoC, weighted averaged across 7 risk groups. Adding PRS to SoC, excluding FH, results in an 11% higher likelihood of preventing deaths, though less than the 20% reduction from screening women with FH at 40. Combining PRS and FH maximizes benefits, with 18% fewer deaths.
BC deaths averted (FH considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening)	12 per 1,000	15 per 1,000 (14 to 16)	RR 1.25 (1.19 to 1.32)	1000 (1 non-randomised study)	⊕⊕⊕⊕	The RR of 1.25 reflects the ratio of BC deaths averted with FH-informed screening versus SoC, calculated as a weighted average across 7 risk groups and 6 FH-age groups. Incorporating FH into screening increases the likelihood of preventing deaths by 25%, surpassing the 11% achieved with PRS alone. Combining FH and PRS further enhances outcomes, reducing BC deaths by 18%.

<p>Life-Years Gained (FH not considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PRS-tailored screening yields 135.75 LYG per 1000 participants • SoC yields 113.30 LYG per 1000 participants • Absolute effect of 22.45 (95% CI: 21.33 to 23.57) per 1000 participants • Relative effect of 1.20 (95% CI: 1.14 to 1.26). 		<p>1000 (1 non-randomised study)</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>The relative effect of PRS-tailored screening, yielding a relative risk of 1.20 (95% CI: 1.14 to 1.26), indicates an improvement in LYG compared to SoC. This 20% increase in LYG, translating to an absolute effect of 22.45 LYG, underscores the effectiveness of utilizing genetic risk factors in screening protocols. This improvement aligns with the broader study findings, where incorporating personalized risk factors enhances screening benefits.</p>
<p>Life-Years Gained (FH considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PRS-tailored screening yields 300.92 LYG per 1000 participants • SoC yields 219.22 LYG per 1000 participants • Absolute effect of 81.70 (95% CI: 77.61 to 85.78) per 1000 participants • Relative effect of 1.37 (95% CI: 1.30 to 1.44). 		<p>1000 (1 non-randomised study)</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>The analysis of LYG when considering both PRS and FH as risk factors shows a substantial improvement over the SoC with a relative effect of 1.37. This 37% increase in LYG underscores the significant benefit of combining PRS and FH in screening protocols. Compared to the results where only PRS was considered, the combined approach offers a 17% gain in LYG from including FH, highlighting the additive value of incorporating both genetic and familial risk factors in BC screening.</p>
<p>Overdiagnoses (FH not considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening)</p>	<p>14 per 1,000</p> <p>15 per 1,000 (14 to 16)</p>	<p>RR 1.10 (1.04 to 1.15)</p>	<p>1000 (1 non-randomised study)</p>	<p>Very low^{b,c,d}</p>	<p>The relative effect of PRS-tailored screening on overdiagnoses indicates a 10% increase in overdiagnosis rates compared to standard screening protocols. This moderate rise aligns with the broader study findings, where risk-tailored screening improves LYG and reduces BC deaths but increases harms. Compared to the 26% increase observed when incorporating FH, the PRS-only approach results in fewer overdiagnoses, suggesting a more balanced trade-off between screening benefits and potential harms.</p>
<p>Overdiagnoses (FH considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening)</p>	<p>16 per 1,000</p> <p>20 per 1,000 (19 to 21)</p>	<p>RR 1.26 (1.20 to 1.32)</p>	<p>1000 (1 non-randomised study)</p>	<p>Very low^{b,c,d}</p>	<p>PRS-tailored screening with FH as a risk factor, increases overdiagnosis rates by 26% compared to SoC screening. This rise aligns with the broader study findings, where incorporating both genetic and familial risk factors enhances screening benefits but increases harms. Compared to the 10% increase observed with PRS-only screening, the combined approach results in higher overdiagnosis rates, emphasizing the need to balance benefits with potential harms.</p>
<p>False-positives (FH not considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PRS-tailored screening resulted in 1155.24 False positives per 1000 participants • SoC resulted in 920.69 False positives per 1000 participants • Absolute effect of 234.55 (95% CI: 222.65; 246.09) per 1000 participants • Relative effect of 1.25 (95% CI: 1.19; 1.32) 		<p>(1 non-randomised study)</p>	<p>Very low^e</p>	<p>The relative effect of PRS-tailored screening on false positive indicates a 25% increase compared to standard screening. This moderate rise aligns with the broader study findings, where risk-tailored screening improves LYG and reduces BC deaths but leads to increased harms. Compared to the 91% increase with FH as a risk factor, the PRS-only approach results in fewer false positives, suggesting a more balanced trade-off between screening benefits and the risk of unnecessary follow-ups.</p>

False-positives (FH considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening)

- **PRS-tailored screening** resulted in 1056.78 False positives per 1000 participants
- **SoC** resulted in 563.46 False positives per 1000 participants
- **Absolute effect** of 493.32 (95% CI: 468.66; 517.99) per 1000 participants
- **Relative effect** of 1.91 (95% CI: 1.82; 2.01)

1000
(1 non-randomised study)

relative effect of PRS-tailored screening, with FH as a risk factor, shows a 91% increase in false positives compared to standard screening. This rise aligns with the broader findings where risk-tailored screening improves LYG and averts BC deaths but increases harms. Compared to the increase with PRS alone, the combined approach leads to more false positives, highlighting the need to balance better with the risk of unnecessary follow-ups.

Study	Results
-------	---------

Utility of polygenic risk scores in UK cancer screening: a modelling analysis.

Huntley et al. 10

Objective:

The study aimed to evaluate whether PRS can improve the **efficiency** of cancer screening in the UK by targeting **high-risk individuals**. It assessed PRS-based stratification for eight cancers (**breast**, prostate, colorectal, pancreas, ovary, kidney, lung, and testicular cancer), comparing the impact on cancer detection and mortality reduction against standard age-based screening.

Type:

Modeling Study simulating cancer screening scenarios

Cohort:

- UK cohort
- Cancer Cases Modeled Annually for Breast cancer: 7,533 cases in women aged 40–49 years.

Risk stratification:

- PRS defined high-risk groups quintiles (top 50%, 20%, 10%, 5%, 1%)

Intervention:

- PRS-based screening (high-risk quintiles top 20%)

Comparison:

- Age-based screening (oldest 20% of the population, extended screening 48–49 years)

Screening Modalities Available:

- **Digital mammography** - Women aged 40–49 years (hypothetical PRS-based extension of screening) - Women aged 50–69 years (currently included in national screening in the UK).

Proposed Risk-Based Screening Protocol:

Screening strategies were personalized by **risk Level (PRS Quintile)** for women aged (40–49 years):

- **Low Risk (Bottom 80%)** - No screening
- **High Risk (Top 20%)** - Biennial mammography
- **Very High Risk (Top 10%)** - Annual mammography
- **Highest Risk (Top 1%)** - Annual MRI & mammography

Results:

PRS-based breast cancer screening for the top 20% risk group averts 102 deaths annually, compared to 80 in age-based screening and 274 in full-population screening. It reduces BC mortality by 14.7% vs. 11.6% in age-based screening. Overdiagnoses remain 2.4 cases per deaths averted in both PRS and age-based screening, while unstratified screening leads to higher total overdiagnoses due to broader screening coverage.

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with polygenic risk score enhanced-screening				
BC deaths averted	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PRS-tailored screening resulted in 102 deaths averted per 873941 participants • SoC screening resulted in 80 deaths averted per 873941 participants • Absolute effect of 22 (95% CI 20.9; 23.1) per 873941 participants • Relative effect of 1.28 (95% CI: 1.21; 1.34) 			873941 (1 non-randomised study)	⊕○○○ Very low ^{f,g,h}	The relative effect of BC deaths averted indicates a 28% increase in effectiveness compared to age-based strategy. This aligns with the study's broader findings, where targeting the top 20% risk group using PRS prevents 102 deaths annually, compared to 80 with age-based screening. While PRS screening improves mortality reduction, overdiagnoses per death averted remain similar, highlighting the potential of personalized approaches to enhance screening efficacy without increasing harm ratios.
Overdiagnosis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PRS-tailored screening resulted in 243 overdiagnosis cases per 873941 participants. • SoC screening resulted in 190 overdiagnosis cases per 873941 participants. • Absolute effect of 53 (95% CI 50.35; 55.65) per 873941 participants. • Relative effect of 1.28 (95% CI 1.22; 1.34) 			873941 (1 non-randomised study)	⊕○○○ Very low ⁱ	We observe a 28% increase in overdiagnoses compared to age-based screening. This increase underscores the challenge of balancing improved detection rates with the potential harms associated with overdiagnosis. While personalized screening approaches aim to enhance efficacy by targeting high-risk individuals, they must also mitigate the risk of excessive diagnoses. In contrast, unstratified population-wide screening results in a higher total number of overdiagnoses due to its broader coverage.

Study	Results
-------	---------

Cost effectiveness analysis of a polygenic risk tailored breast cancer screening programme in Singapore

Wong et al.

Results:

PRS-tailored screening resulted in 22.86 LYG and 22.78 QALYs per 1,000 participants, compared to 21.89 LYG

and 21.80 QALYs with standard screening. The absolute effect was 0.97 additional LYG and 0.98 additional QALYs per 1,000 participants, with a relative effect of 1.04 for both. PRS screening reduced breast cancer incidence from 31.2 to 25.5 cases per 1,000 women.

Objective:

The study evaluated the **cost-effectiveness** of integrating **PRS** into Singapore’s **biennial mammogram** screening programme. It compared a **PRS-tailored strategy** with **current age-based screening**, assessing the impact on **life-years gained (LYs)**, **quality-adjusted life-years (QALYs)**, and overall costs

Type:

- **Cost-Effectiveness Analysis** using a **Markov model**
- **Perspective:** Healthcare system in Singapore
- **Time Horizon:** **40 years**, following women from **35 to 74 years**.

Cohort:

- Singapore cohort
- Women aged 35–74 years.

Risk stratification:

Baseline and (3 different scenarios)

- **Low Risk:** Below the **60th percentile** (<60, <40, <40th) .
- **Intermediate Risk:** **60th–95th percentile** (60-90, 40-95, 40-90th).
- **High Risk:** Above the **95th percentile** (>90, >95, >90th).

Intervention:

- **PRS-tailored screening:** Screening frequency based on genetic risk classification.

Comparison:

- **Current strategy:** Biennial mammography for women **50–69 years**.

Screening Modalities Available:

- **Mammography** – The current screening strategy involves mammogram screening every two years for women aged 50 to 69. PRS-Tailored Screening – This strategy involves:
- Genotyping via **buccal swab**;
- A questionnaire on BC risk factors;
- Risk stratification into **low, intermediate, and high-risk groups** based on PRS.

Follow-up screening tests depending on risk group and age, which may include:

- **Self-examination;**
- **Ultrasound;**
- **Mammogram.**

Proposed Risk-Based Screening Protocol:

Screening strategies were personalized by **risk Level (PRS percentiles)** for women aged **35–74 years**:

- **Low Risk (<60th percentile)** - Self examination (35-39 years), Triennial mammogram (40-74 years)
- **Intermediate Risk (60th-95th percentile)** - Self examination (35-39 years), Biennial mammogram (40-74 years)
- **High Risk (>95th percentile)** - Annual ultrasound (35-39 years), Annual

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with polygenic risk score enhanced-screening				

Life-Years Gained	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PRS-tailored screening yields 22.86 LYG per 1000 participants • SoC screening yields 21.89 LYG per 1000 participants • Absolute effect of 0.97 (95% CI 0.92;1.02) LYG per 1000 participants • Relative effect of 1.04 (95% CI 0.99; 1.10). 	1000 (1 non-randomised study)	 Low	The relative effect of PRS-tailored screening on LYG indicates a 4% increase compared to standard screening. This improvement aligns with the study's broader findings, where PRS screening results in 0.970 additional LYG per woman and reduces BC incidence from 31.2 to 25.5 cases per 1,000 women. The absence of additional harms reinforces PRS-tailored screening as a safer and more effective alternative to age-based mammography.
Quality Adjusted Life Years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PRS-tailored screening yields 22.78 QALYs per 1000 participants • SoC screening yields 21.80 QALYs per 1000 participants • Absolute effect of 0.98 (95% CI 0.93; 1.03) QALYs per 1000 participants • Relative effect of 1.04 (95% CI 0.99; 1.1) 	1000 (1 non-randomised study)	 Very low ^d	The relative effect of PRS-tailored screening on QALYs indicates a 4% increase compared to standard screening. This modest improvement aligns with the study's broader findings, where PRS screening results in 0.988 additional QALYs per woman and reduces BC incidence from 31.2 to 25.5 cases per 1,000 women. Notably, the absence of additional harms supports PRS-tailored screening as a safer and more effective alternative to age-based mammography.

Study

Results

Cost-effectiveness and benefit-to-harm ratio of risk-stratified screening for breast cancer: a life-table model

Pashayan et al. 43

Objective:

The study assessed the **cost-effectiveness and benefit-to-harm ratio** of **risk-stratified BC screening** compared to **standard age-based screening** and **no screening**. The goal was to evaluate whether targeting screening to **higher-risk women** while reducing screening for **low-risk women** improved efficiency and reduced **overdiagnosis** while maintaining screening benefits.

Type:

- **Life-Table Model:** Simulated long-term outcomes of different screening strategies.
- **Perspective:** UK National Health Service (NHS).
- **Time Horizon:** Follow-up from **50 to 85 years**.

Cohort:

- UK cohort
- **Hypothetical Population Modeled:** 364,500 women aged 50 years, followed until age 85 years.

Risk stratification:

- **Polygenic risk distribution used to determine screening eligibility.**
- Various percentile cutoffs were tested (e.g., 10th, 25th, 32nd, 62nd and 70th percentile). Percentile risk categories are reported from 0 risk. For example, the 10th percentile indicates that 10% of the population is within the risk category and 90% of the population is above the risk threshold. The 10-year absolute risk equivalent for the 10th, 25th, 32nd, 62nd and 70th percentiles of risk distribution are 0.99%, 1.48%, 1.69%, 2.81%, and 3.24%, respectively

Intervention:

Results:

Risk-stratified screening reduces BC mortality compared to no screening but results in more BC deaths than age-based screening as the risk threshold increases. Compared to age-based screening, it improves cost-effectiveness, increases QALYs, and reduces overdiagnosis, with greater reductions at higher risk thresholds. However, QALY gains slightly decline as the threshold rises, highlighting a trade-off between mortality risk and reduced overdiagnosis.

- **PRS-stratified screening** (only women above a defined risk threshold were screened, 10th, 25th, 32nd, 62nd and 70th percentile).

Comparison:

- **Aged-based screening** (triennial mammography from 50 to 69 years)

Screening Modalities Available:

- **Age-Based Screening (Current NHSBSP):** Women aged **50–69 years** are offered **mammographic screening every 3 years**, consistent with the **UK National Health Service Breast Screening Programme (NHSBSP)**.
- **Risk-Stratified Screening:** Women undergo **risk assessment** (genetic and/or epidemiological factors), and only those with a **risk score above a defined threshold** are invited for **mammographic screening every 3 years from ages 50 to 69**.

Proposed Risk-Based Screening Protocol:

Screening strategies were personalized by **risk Level (PRS percentiles Cutoff)** for women aged **50–69 years**:

- **Low Risk (<70th percentile)** - No routine screening
- **Intermediate Risk (32nd-70th percentile)** – Triennial mammography (50-74 years)
- **High Risk (>32nd percentile)** – Triennial mammography

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with Polygenic risk score enhanced-screening				
BC deaths	<p>Compared with age-based screening, risk-stratified screening was associated with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 additional BC deaths per year at the 10th percentile per 10,000 participants. • 5 additional BC deaths per year at the 25th percentile per 10,000 participants. • 7 additional BC deaths per year at the 32nd percentile per 10,000 participants. • 18 additional BC deaths per year at the 62nd percentile per 10,000 participants. • 23 additional BC deaths per year at the 70th percentile per 10,000 participants. 			10000 (1 non-randomised study)	⊕○○○ Very low ^k	While risk-stratified screening reduces BC deaths compared to no screening, it results in more BC deaths than standard age-based screening as the risk threshold increases. Specifically, compared with age-based screening, risk-stratified screening was associated with 2 additional BC deaths per year per 10,000 participants at the 10th percentile, 5 at the 25th percentile, 7 at the 32nd percentile and 23 at the 70th percentile.

Quality Adjusted Life Years	<p>Compared with age-based screening, risk-stratified screening was associated with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 449 additional QALYs per year at the 10th percentile per 10,000 participants. • 450 additional QALYs per year at the 25th percentile per 10,000 participants. • 450 additional QALYs per year at the 32nd percentile per 10,000 participants. • 446 additional QALYs per year at the 62nd percentile per 10,000 participants. • 443 additional QALYs per year at the 70th percentile per 10,000 participants. 	10000 (1 non-randomised study)	 Very low ^{k,l}	<p>Compared with age-based screening, risk-stratified screening was associated with additional QALYs per year per 10,000 participants, with a slight decrease as the risk threshold increased. Specifically, it resulted in 449 additional QALYs at the 10th percentile, 450 at the 25th and 32nd percentiles, 446 at the 62nd percentile, and 443 at the 70th percentile.</p>
Overdiagnoses	<p>Compared with age-based screening, risk-stratified screening was associated with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 fewer overdiagnoses per year at the 10th percentile per 10,000 participants. • 12 fewer overdiagnoses per year at the 25th percentile per 10,000 participants. • 17 fewer overdiagnoses per year at the 32nd percentile per 10,000 participants. • 43 fewer overdiagnoses per year at the 62nd percentile per 10,000 participants. • 52 fewer overdiagnoses per year at the 70th percentile per 10,000 participants. 	10000 (1 non-randomised study)	 Very low ^{k,m,n}	<p>Risk-stratified screening reduces overdiagnosis compared to standard age-based screening, with greater reductions as the risk threshold increases. Specifically, it was associated with 4 fewer overdiagnoses per year per 10,000 participants at the 10th percentile, 12 at the 25th percentile, 17 at the 32nd percentile, 43 at the 62nd percentile, and 52 at the 70th percentile.</p>

*The risk in the intervention group (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: confidence interval; **MD:** mean difference; **RR:** risk ratio

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High certainty: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.

Moderate certainty: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate: the true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different.

Low certainty: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited: the true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.

Very low certainty: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate: the true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

Explanations

- The large variation in overdiagnosis estimates warrants downgrading for imprecision, given the broad range of the CI and the possible impact on decision-making.
- uncertainty in DCIS progression modeling
- Differences in overdiagnosis estimates across strategies are notable and could influence decision-making. The degree of inconsistency is enough to warrant downgrading, as it may affect confidence in the absolute harm estimates.
- The large variation in overdiagnosis estimates warrants downgrading for imprecision, given the broad range of the CI and the possible impact on decision-making
- assumptions about perfect compliance and test sensitivity
- The lack of external validation and limited exploration of uncertainty reduce confidence in generalizability
- The model applies UK-specific data, but the findings may not be directly applicable to other populations or health systems. The model assumes full uptake of PRS profiling, which may differ across settings. Additionally, the PRS tools used (current, future, and optimized) may not directly reflect the broader patient populations or outcomes experienced outside the study context (e.g., for non-European populations).

- h. The model presents outcomes like deaths averted, but the confidence intervals and model assumptions are wide due to uncertainties in population uptake and screening efficiency. While the model estimates BC deaths averted, it lacks detailed sensitivity analyses across various plausible scenarios, which would clarify the precision of the estimates.
- i. the confidence intervals for overdiagnosis are likely wide, given the modeling assumptions and uncertainties about screening uptake and efficiency. While the model provides a projection, the underlying data (e.g., overdiagnosis rates, screening tool performance) are subject to a significant degree of imprecision due to lack of empirical validation and small sample sizes in studies used for model calibration
- j. Due to compliance assumptions and reliance on some global data sources), along with lack of external validation
- k. The broad CI crossing potential decision thresholds suggests that the precision of the estimate is insufficient to support a firm recommendation without further data or analysis.
- l. Due to assumptions about utility decrements and adherence variability, along with lack of external validation and conflict of interest issues
- m. due to simplified assumptions on constant rates of overdiagnosis
- n. The wide variability in overdiagnosis estimates could affect confidence in conclusions about harms. However, this is not classified as "very serious" because the direction of effect (reduction in overdiagnosis with stratified screening) remains consistent.

Supplementary Table 4.2: GRADE EtD Framework Summary for PRS-Tailored BC Screening

This table summarizes the recommendation process based on the GRADE EtD framework. It outlines key judgements about the benefits and harms, quality of evidence, cost-effectiveness, and implementation considerations for PRS-informed screening strategies. The final recommendation reflects the balance of desirable and undesirable effects in the context of feasibility, acceptability, and equity.

QUESTION

Should national or sub-national health systems in the European Union consider incorporating polygenic risk scores (PRS), either alone or in combination with family history (FH) vs. Standard of care be used for organized breast cancer screening programs to inform risk-stratified screening strategies?

PROBLEM:	
OPTION:	Should national or sub-national health systems in the European Union consider incorporating polygenic risk scores (PRS), either alone or in combination with family history (FH)
COMPARISON:	Standard of care
MAIN OUTCOMES:	Van den Broek et al.; BC deaths averted (FH not considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening); BC deaths averted (FH considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening); Life-Years Gained (FH not considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening); Life-Years Gained (FH considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening); Overdiagnoses (FH not considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening); Overdiagnoses (FH considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening); False-positives (FH not considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening); False-positives (FH considered in SoC and PRS-enhanced screening); Huntley et al.; BC deaths averted; Overdiagnosis; Wong et al.; Life-Years Gained; Quality Adjusted Life Years; Pashayan et al.; BC deaths; Quality Adjusted Life Years; Overdiagnoses;
PERSPECTIVE:	

ASSESSMENT

Problem		
Is the problem a priority?		
JUDGEMENT	RESEARCH EVIDENCE	ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Probably no <input type="radio"/> Probably yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> Varies <input type="radio"/> Don't know 	<p>Breast cancer (BC) is a significant health problem and burden in Europe due to its high incidence and mortality rates. In 2020, BC was the most commonly diagnosed cancer among women in Europe, with approximately 530,000 new cases reported, making it the leading cancer type in terms of incidence. Additionally, BC was responsible for 140,000 deaths in the same year, highlighting its substantial impact on mortality (1).</p> <p>The burden of BC varies across different regions in Europe. For instance, the age-standardized incidence rates are among the highest in Western Europe, while mortality rates show a heterogeneous pattern, with some regions experiencing declines and others seeing increases. The overall burden of BC in Europe in 2019 was 463.2 cases per 100,000 people, which is 1.7 times the global burden (2).</p> <p>While the disease continues to pose a significant challenge, there have been advancements in screening and treatment, and the age-standardized mortality and disability-adjusted life year (DALY) rates of BC in Europe have decreased by 23.1% and 25.9%, respectively, from 1990 to 2019. (2) However, regional disparities persist, with Western Europe showing a faster decline in DALY rates compared to Eastern and Central Europe (2).</p>	<p>All panelists judged breast cancer screening to be a public health priority. However, panelists noted that the transition from age-based to risk-based screening would entail significant complexity and system-level readiness.</p>
<p>Desirable Effects How substantial are the desirable anticipated effects?</p>		
<p>JUDGEMENT</p>	<p>RESEARCH EVIDENCE</p>	<p>ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Trivial ○ Small ○ Moderate ○ Large ● Varies ○ Don't know 	<p>The studies reviewed explore a range of desirable outcomes associated with PRS-based BC screening strategies. (3) examined BC deaths averted and life years gained (LYG), both with and without considering family history (FH). (4) focused on BC deaths averted in high-risk populations. (5) assessed quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) and life years gained from PRS-based screening. (6) evaluated BC deaths averted and QALYs in PRS-tailored versus age-based screening. For a more comprehensive overview, please refer to the evidence table attached, which provides a detailed summary of the outcomes from each study.</p>	<p>Panelists acknowledged the potential for desirable effects from incorporating PRS into breast cancer screening. However, there was broad recognition that these benefits remain theoretical, based largely on modeling studies with low certainty of evidence. While tailoring screening to individual risk profiles could enhance efficiency and clinical outcomes, the magnitude of benefit is uncertain and varies across studies depending on modeling assumptions, population characteristics, and outcome definitions. Overall, panelists agreed that while desirable effects are plausible, their scope and reliability remain insufficiently established.</p>
--	--	--

Undesirable Effects
How substantial are the undesirable anticipated effects?

JUDGEMENT	RESEARCH EVIDENCE	ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Trivial ○ Small ○ Moderate ○ Large ● Varies ○ Don't know 	<p>The studies also address a range of undesirable outcomes linked to PRS-based screening. (3) examined overdiagnosis and false positives, both with and without incorporating FH. (4) assessed overdiagnosis in high-risk populations undergoing PRS-based screening. (6) evaluated overdiagnosis in the context of PRS-tailored versus age-based screening. For a more detailed summary of the undesirable outcomes across studies, please consult the evidence table attached.</p>	<p>Panelists broadly agreed that undesirable effects represent significant concerns in the evaluation of PRS-enhanced screening. While some potential harms may be acceptable if balanced by meaningful mortality reduction, panelists emphasized that this trade-off remains speculative in the absence of high-certainty evidence. The scale and nature of these harms were considered context-dependent, likely to vary across healthcare systems, risk thresholds, and implementation models. Given the variability in study findings and the lack of real-world data, panelists agreed that undesirable effects must be closely monitored and carefully weighed in future implementation efforts.</p>

Certainty of evidence
What is the overall certainty of the evidence of effects?

JUDGEMENT	RESEARCH EVIDENCE	ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Very low ● Low ○ Moderate ○ High ○ No included studies 	<p>The certainty of evidence for the assessed outcomes is predominantly very low, particularly for critical outcomes such as BC deaths, BC deaths averted, QALYs, and overdiagnoses. These classifications reflect significant limitations in the reliability of the underlying modeling studies, including risks of bias, imprecision in estimates, and indirectness of evidence. Few outcomes, such as Life-years gained (LYG), were rated with low certainty.</p>	<p>Panelists unanimously judged the certainty of evidence supporting PRS-enhanced screening to be low or very low. Panelists agreed that, while modeling can inform research priorities, it does not provide a sufficient basis for policy change in the absence of empirical validation through clinical trials or implementation studies.</p>

Balance of effects
Does the balance between desirable and undesirable effects favor the intervention or the comparison?

JUDGEMENT	RESEARCH EVIDENCE	ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Favors the comparison ○ Probably favors the comparison ○ Does not favor either the intervention or the comparison ● Probably favors the intervention ○ Favors the intervention ○ Varies ○ Don't know 	<p>On the positive side, PRS-based screening consistently shows benefits in reducing BC deaths and increasing LYG (3) (4). When FH is considered alongside PRS, these benefits are amplified (3). However, the impact varies across studies, with some reporting a modest increase in QALYs and LYG (5), while others indicate more substantial QALYs gains (6). Notably, (6) found that although risk-stratified screening reduces mortality compared to no screening, it may slightly increase BC deaths relative to age-based screening.</p> <p>Despite these advantages, PRS-based screening also leads to undesirable outcomes. When PRS is used to increase frequency and lowering starting age, overdiagnoses and false positives are notably higher compared to standard screening protocols and the combination of PRS with FH further exacerbates these issues (3). Also Huntley et al. comment that risk-stratified screening can increase both overdiagnoses and false positives (4).</p> <p>Other studies that have modeled the use of PRS to restrict screening to higher risk women, show a slight reduction in overdiagnoses, with greater reductions as the risk threshold increases, specifically when compared with age-based screening (6).</p> <p>In summary, while PRS-based screening offers potential improvements in BC mortality reduction and survival benefits, it also presents challenges related to overdiagnosis and false positives. The integration of FH with PRS enhances both the positive and negative outcomes, underscoring the need for careful consideration of the balance between these factors in clinical implementation. [(3), (6), (5)(4)].</p>	<p>Panelists generally leaned toward a favorable balance between the desirable and undesirable effects of PRS-enhanced screening, acknowledging that this judgment is provisional and based on low-certainty evidence. The lack of real-world data remains a significant limitation, and panelists emphasized that broader adoption should await results from ongoing implementation trials, the panel considered the balance of effects potentially favorable, but emphasized the need for cautious interpretation and further evidence before informing large-scale policy change.</p>

Cost effectiveness
Does the cost-effectiveness of the intervention favor the intervention or the comparison?

JUDGEMENT	RESEARCH EVIDENCE	ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS
-----------	-------------------	---------------------------

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Favors the comparison ○ Probably favors the comparison ○ Does not favor either the intervention or the comparison ○ Probably favors the intervention ○ Favors the intervention ● Varies ○ No included studies 	<p>In the UK, (6) demonstrated that risk-stratified screening, especially at the <i>70th percentile risk threshold (thus excluding from screening the 30% at a lower risk)</i>, improves cost-effectiveness and reduces overdiagnosis while maintaining the benefits of screening, with a 72% probability of being cost-effective at a willingness-to-pay threshold of £20,000 per QALY. Similarly, in Singapore, (5) found that a PRS-tailored screening program was more cost-effective than the current biennial mammogram-only strategy, yielding an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) of -3713.80 SGD per QALY, indicating cost savings and improved health outcomes. (4) modeled PRS-stratified screening in the UK, estimating that screening only the top 20% of risk in women aged 40-49 could prevent 102 BC deaths annually, compared to 80 deaths if screening were age-based (offering screening to 48 and 49 years old). However, the study found that PRS-based screening only modestly improves efficiency, as many cancers still arise in lower-risk individuals who would be excluded from screening. Collectively, these studies suggest that integrating genetic risk into screening programs may enhance cost-effectiveness, but its implementation requires careful consideration of economic, ethical, and practical challenges.</p> <p><i>A deeper look into the studies</i></p>	<p>Panelists agreed that the cost-effectiveness of PRS-enhanced screening remains uncertain. Generalizability of the findings is limited by differences in healthcare systems, population risk profiles, and the scope of genetic testing considered. Whether PRS is implemented alone or alongside testing for rare high-impact variants (e.g., BRCA1/2) also has implications for both cost and feasibility. Overall, the panel recognized the promise of PRS-enhanced screening in improving economic efficiency, but concluded that current evidence is insufficient to justify major policy changes. Further research, particularly from implementation settings, is needed to determine its true value for health systems.</p>
	<p>The study by (6) evaluates the cost-effectiveness and benefit-to-harm ratio of risk-stratified BC screening compared to standard age-based screening and no screening. Using a life-table model of a hypothetical cohort of 364,500 women in the UK aged 50, followed until age 85, the study assesses three screening strategies: 1- no screening, 2- age-based screening (mammography every 3 years from 50 to 69), and 3- risk-stratified screening (offering screening only to women above a certain risk threshold). The model incorporates polygenic risk profiles and epidemiological factors to stratify risk. Results show that risk-stratified screening, particularly at the 70th percentile risk threshold, improves cost-effectiveness, reduces overdiagnosis, and maintains the benefits of screening, with a 72% probability of being cost-effective at a willingness-to-pay threshold of £20,000 per QALY gained. The study concludes that not offering screening to women at lower risk could enhance the cost-effectiveness and benefit-to-harm ratio of BC screening programs.</p> <p>While the study by (5) evaluates the cost-effectiveness of a polygenic risk-tailored BC screening program in Singapore compared to the current biennial mammogram-only screening program. Using a Markov model, the authors simulated the costs and health outcomes for women aged 35 to 74 over a 40-year time horizon, incorporating genetic testing via single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) to stratify women into low-, intermediate-, and high-risk groups for tailored screening recommendations. The model found that the polygenic risk-tailored screening program was more cost-effective, with an ICER of -3713.80 SGD per QALY, indicating lower costs and higher QALYs compared to the current mammogram-only strategy. Scenario analyses with varying risk thresholds confirmed the cost-effectiveness of tailored screening across different risk group cutoffs. The study concludes that incorporating PRS into BC screening could improve cost-effectiveness without compromising health outcomes. However, the authors acknowledge limitations, such as the assumption of 100% screening attendance and the lack of data on treatment and remission, suggesting the need for further research to address these gaps.</p> <p>The study by (4) aims to evaluate the potential efficiency and cost-effectiveness of PRS-stratified cancer screening in the UK compared to standard age-based screening. It assesses the impact of PRS stratification on cancer detection rates and mortality reduction across eight cancers, including BC, and models the implications for screening policies. In particular, The study models a scenario in which BC screening is extended to women aged 40-49 years but restricted to those in the top 20% of PRS-defined risk. This approach could prevent an estimated 102 BC deaths annually, compared to 80 deaths if screening were instead offered only to the oldest women in this group (48-49 years). However, PRS-based screening does not dramatically improve cost-effectiveness. While it modestly enhances screening efficiency by focusing resources on higher- risk individuals, it also results in a trade-off where many cancers occur in those</p>	

	classified as low-risk and thus excluded from screening. The study highlights potential logistical costs, concerns about incomplete PRS uptake, and the need for further UK-specific cost-effectiveness evaluations through cluster-randomized trials.	
--	--	--

Equity
What would be the impact on health equity?

JUDGEMENT	RESEARCH EVIDENCE	ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Reduced <input checked="" type="radio"/> Probably reduced <input type="radio"/> Probably no impact <input type="radio"/> Probably increased <input type="radio"/> Increased <input type="radio"/> Varies <input type="radio"/> Don't know 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The DNA testing involved in risk profiling may itself cause concerns amongst the public about who might access these data and whether they could be used for purposes other than for health care or public health, such as for medical research or forensic investigation, or to inform decisions about insurance or employment (8). • There is concern that advances in the PRS field would benefit those of specific ancestries, namely those of European descent, with little benefit for other ancestry groups that often suffer higher rates of common diseases (9). Reasons for this discrepancy include the availability of data in the countries where PRS research is taking place, namely Western nations (10) , as well as deeper cultural divisions in medicine (i.e., the distrust of minority patients in the US medical system) (11). • The role of PRS in risk stratification to inform public health screening initiatives is examined in 5 of the included records. In these studies, participants were generally favorable to the idea of extending PRS testing to the public to personalize population screening programs in the context of Personal Breast Cancer Risk Assessment (PBCRA). [(12), (13), (14), (7)] However, participants unanimously disagreed with the possibility of reducing screening frequency for individuals at low risk , they emphasized the importance of maintaining regular screening intervals to ensure early detection and equitable access to care, arguing that baseline screening should be universally available to avoid missing early-stage cancers and to maintain public trust in the screening program [(13) (14) (7)]. 	<p>Panelists agreed that without deliberate safeguards, PRS-enhanced screening could exacerbate existing health inequities. Barriers such as income, digital access, health literacy, and regional disparities in healthcare infrastructure may limit equitable access to PRS testing across and within European countries. If not addressed, these could lead to less accurate risk assessment and suboptimal screening recommendations for individuals of diverse ancestries. Panelists also emphasized that equitable implementation would require public funding, targeted outreach, and culturally sensitive communication strategies. Without these structural measures, risk-based screening may unintentionally reinforce disparities in breast cancer detection and outcomes. While some viewed personalized screening as a potential tool for equity—by focusing resources on those at highest risk—this benefit depends on inclusive design and trust-building with affected communities. In the absence of such measures, risk stratification may be perceived as reducing care for some rather than enhancing it, with implications for public acceptability and institutional trust.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Probably no <input checked="" type="radio"/> Probably yes <input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> Varies <input type="radio"/> Don't know 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (13) investigated women's experiences receiving PRS assessment and compared responses across different risk levels. Regardless of their assigned risk, participants demonstrated a broad understanding of polygenic concepts and accurately interpreted their PRS, often integrating this information into their BC risk management. Women's personal experiences with BC played a key role in shaping their responses, emphasizing the importance of personal context in risk perception. Additionally, highly educated women or those with a FH of BC exhibited greater familiarity with PRS concepts, readily accepting explanations about the role of SNPs in determining cancer risk and describing their risk as influenced by a combination of genetic variations (15). • In the case of risk-based screening, the call for screening may be interpreted by third parties such as insurers and employers as a proxy for elevated risk status, this might be more important for some health systems than others, but still underwriters may use this information as a basis for setting higher insurance premiums (16). • The potential for PRS and PBCRA to cause anxiety and fear was a topic of consensus in two studies (17) (7). Some participants believed they could experience fear in front of a high PRS (17); others considered that it would be 'better not to know' their PBCRA, depending on an individual's personality (7). 	<p>Panelists noted that the acceptability of PRS-enhanced screening depends on a range of factors, including stakeholder perceptions, public understanding, and implementation context. Ensuring psychological support and robust data protection frameworks will be essential for maintaining trust. Healthcare professionals, including radiologists and screening organizations, may be cautious about adopting PRS-enhanced strategies given the current low certainty of evidence. Similarly, policymakers and payers may be reluctant to support widespread implementation due to upfront costs and delayed health returns, highlighting the broader challenge of gathering institutional buy-in for preventive innovations. Panelists emphasized that acceptability is likely to improve with clear communication, targeted education efforts, and growing familiarity with personalized approaches—though further research is needed to understand stakeholder-specific barriers and facilitators.</p>
Feasibility Is the intervention feasible to implement?		
JUDGEMENT	RESEARCH EVIDENCE	ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Probably no <input type="radio"/> Probably yes <input type="radio"/> Yes <input checked="" type="radio"/> Varies <input type="radio"/> Don't know 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both genetic counselors and medical practitioners provided similar biomedical information; however, genetic counselors were more likely to employ strategies to build patient rapport and utilize counseling techniques, underscoring their key role in facilitating effective communication in this context. Understanding how individuals integrate and respond to information provided by PRS is crucial for its effective integration into routine clinical care (27). • (28) developed and pilot-tested a leaflet to assist women in deciding whether to learn results from genomic testing for common risk variants associated with BC risk. The study showed participants found the leaflet useful, suggesting its utility as an information tool for women undergoing genomic testing. • (29) demonstrated the positive impact of an online educational program on genetic healthcare providers' attitudes, confidence, knowledge, and preparedness regarding the use of PRS for breast and ovarian cancer risk assessments. These findings underscore the importance of continuous education and training initiatives for healthcare providers to effectively enhance their capacity to use PRS and personalized risk assessments. • A second limitation is the increasing amount of available PRS scores with only slightly different parameters, which often complicates appropriate PRS selection. This was also reflected in a recent study evaluating the readiness of general practitioners to include PRS in their patient evaluations (30) . The clinicians report their need for more training as the top priority (31). • When patients received counseling, a good understanding of polygenic risk and its implications was reported [(12), (13), (15), (14), (19), (26), (18), (20)]. This finding was consistent among patients who received their PRS as part of PBCRA [(12), (13), (15), (14), (19), (26)]. In 2 studies, women understood the mechanisms of polygenic inheritance and were able to recall the transmission of SNPs as both maternally and paternally inherited [(13), (15)]. Being aware of the multifactorial nature of their disease helped participants contextualize PRS information within their FH. [(13),(19)]. • PRSs for BC was found to transfer well across European populations and to Latinas, and, to a lesser extent, Ashkenazi Jewish, South American and South and East Asian populations but much more poorly to individuals of African ancestry. [(21), (22), (23), (24), (25)]. 	<p>Panelists agreed that the feasibility of implementing PRS-enhanced screening is highly dependent on health system capacity, infrastructure readiness, and program design. Key requirements include access to genomic testing, the availability of standardized and validated PRS tools, and adequate risk communication capacity within the healthcare workforce. While some early-use cases suggest that targeted implementation may be viable under specific conditions, broader integration would likely require significant investment, workforce development, and structural adaptation. Despite these challenges, some panelists pointed to emerging examples that suggest feasibility is possible under the right conditions. In the Netherlands, for instance, PRS is already being used in clinical genetics to provide personalized counseling for women with a family history of breast cancer. While fewer than 10% of those referred to genetic services have a monogenic mutation, PRS can help guide preventive strategies for the broader population, supporting its practical value. Panelists recognized that feasibility may improve over time with further standardization and scaling, but emphasized that current readiness is limited in many settings.</p>
---	---	---

SUMMARY OF JUDGEMENTS

	JUDGEMENT						
PROBLEM	No	Probably no	Probably yes	Yes		Varies	Don't know
DESIRABLE EFFECTS	Trivial	Small	Moderate	Large		Varies	Don't know
UNDESIRABLE EFFECTS	Trivial	Small	Moderate	Large		Varies	Don't know
CERTAINTY OF EVIDENCE	Very low	Low	Moderate	High			No included studies
BALANCE OF EFFECTS	Favors the comparison	Probably favors the comparison	Does not favor either the intervention or the comparison	Probably favors the intervention	Favors the intervention	Varies	Don't know
COST EFFECTIVENESS	Favors the comparison	Probably favors the comparison	Does not favor either the intervention or the comparison	Probably favors the intervention	Favors the intervention	Varies	No included studies
EQUITY	Reduced	Probably reduced	Probably no impact	Probably increased	Increased	Varies	Don't know
ACCEPTABILITY	No	Probably no	Probably yes	Yes		Varies	Don't know
FEASIBILITY	No	Probably no	Probably yes	Yes		Varies	Don't know

TYPE OF RECOMMENDATION

Strong recommendation against the option ○	Conditional recommendation against the option ○	Conditional recommendation for either the option or the comparison ○	Conditional recommendation for the option ●	Strong recommendation for the option ○
---	--	---	--	---

CONCLUSIONS

Recommendation

As we await findings from large trials, we conditionally recommend that national or sub-national health systems in the European Union (EU) explore the integration of PRS into breast cancer screening programs through piloting programmes, carefully designed prospective research projects and controlled implementation studies. If findings from large trials or pilot implementation studies leave uncertainties critical to the EU context, funding a well-designed Phase III RCT is justified to ensure that any shift in screening policy is backed by robust evidence on efficacy and safety.

This recommendation is conditional because the overall certainty of evidence is low, the balance between benefits and harms is strategy- and context-dependent, and the acceptability, feasibility, and equity implications of PRS-enhanced screening vary across settings and populations.

- **For policymakers and health system leaders:** PRS should not yet be adopted into routine screening practice at scale. Instead, governments and public health authorities are encouraged to support prospective research projects and implementation studies that allow for localized learning, continuous evaluation, and iterative adaptation.
- **For researchers:** Particular attention should be given to studying how PRS-enhanced screening impacts different socio-economic and ethnic subgroups to ensure equitable benefits. Beyond public perceptions, research should prioritize implementation strategies, effective communication models, and integration pathways for PRS-enhanced screening
- **For clinicians and healthcare professionals:** The integration of PRS into shared decision-making around screening should be approached with caution and ideally supported by risk counseling, clear communication tools, and established data protection frameworks
- **For the public:** Individuals should be informed that PRS-enhanced screening is still in a research and development phase, and its benefits and risks are not yet fully understood. Public trust and transparent communication are essential.

Justification

Overall justification

In summary, the conditional recommendation reflects:

- Low certainty of evidence, with particular concern related to limited real-world data.
- A promising but unconfirmed balance of effects, with meaningful risks and uncertainties.
- Significant variation in public and provider values, health system readiness, and potential for unintended harms.
- The need to protect equity, build infrastructure, and engage stakeholders before broader implementation.

Thus, we advise stepwise, evidence-generating integration of PRS into breast cancer screening programs, rather than immediate widespread adoption.

Detailed justification

Certainty of evidence

The overall certainty of the evidence was assessed as low, primarily due to: Indirectness: Much of the evidence is derived from modeling studies, rather than real-world implementation. These models often rely on assumptions about PRS performance and downstream outcomes, which may not reflect actual clinical or public health contexts. Imprecision: Effect estimates for critical outcomes (e.g., reduction in cancer mortality, false positives, overdiagnosis) often have wide CIs or are based on single studies. Inconsistency: Variability across cancer types, population subgroups, and PRS construction methods reduces the generalizability of findings. Despite these limitations, the panel noted that the evidence is rapidly evolving, and there is a reasonable plausibility of benefit, especially in breast cancer with an established PRS models

Balance of effects

The balance between desirable and undesirable effects was judged to be uncertain and likely to vary by context: Potential Benefits: PRS can improve risk stratification, allowing for more personalized screening intervals, which may enhance early detection and reduce unnecessary procedures in low-risk individuals. May improve the efficiency and yield of screening programs, reducing false positives in low-risk groups and focusing resources on those most likely to benefit. Potential Harms: Overdiagnosis and overtreatment of low-risk cancers may persist if risk thresholds are not properly calibrated. Psychosocial burden and potential stigma from being labeled "high risk." Population-level benefit is unclear in the absence of large-scale, long-term implementation studies. The panel highlighted that the potential benefits are promising but not yet sufficiently demonstrated to warrant unconditional adoption. They emphasized the need for carefully monitored implementation to ensure harms are identified and mitigated early.

Cost effectiveness

The cost-effectiveness of PRS-enhanced screening for breast cancer is not yet well-established: Initial investments in genomic infrastructure, training, and data systems are expected to be substantial. The cost of PRS testing continues to decline, but integration into screening pathways (e.g., risk-based invitations, follow-up protocols) introduces complex logistical and financial challenges. Some modeling studies suggest PRS-enhanced screening could be cost-effective in specific high-risk populations, but the evidence is not robust enough to support large-scale resource reallocation at this time.

Equity

Equity was a major concern: Current PRS models are primarily developed from genomic datasets of European ancestry, limiting their validity in more diverse populations. Without universal access to genomic services and literacy, PRS-enhanced screening could exacerbate existing health disparities. There is a risk that such approaches might only be accessible in well-resourced regions or health systems, further entrenching inequalities in cancer outcomes. The panel agreed that equity considerations argue against universal implementation at this stage, and favor targeted, well-governed implementation pilots with deliberate strategies to mitigate inequity.

Acceptability

The panel noted that values and preferences among the general public and clinicians are still poorly characterized. While some individuals may welcome more personalized approaches to screening, others may have concerns about genetic determinism, misunderstanding of risk, privacy and data protection. This uncertainty supported the conditional nature of the recommendation, suggesting the need for shared decision-making, genetic counseling, and public engagement as essential components of any implementation effort. Acceptability to patients is not yet well understood. Preliminary studies indicate mixed reactions, with some enthusiasm for personalization but concern over the meaning and implications of genetic risk. Clinician readiness is limited by gaps in genomics education, unclear workflows, and lack of guidance for risk communication. The panel emphasized the need for training, support tools, and co-development with users to ensure acceptability in real-world settings.

Subgroup Considerations and Modifications of the Recommendation

1. Risk Stratification Subgroups (Low, Moderate, High Genetic Risk)

- High-risk individuals (top percentiles of PRS distribution): Recommendation for stronger support for implementation in these groups within piloting programmes.
- Low-risk individuals (bottom percentiles of PRS distribution): Recommendation to explore screening de-intensification in this group, within research settings only.
- Moderate-risk individuals (middle of the distribution): No changes recommended for this subgroup at present.

2. Age Subgroups

- **Younger individuals (under standard screening age):** Pilots may include early initiation of screening in younger high-risk individuals.

3. Socioeconomic and Ethnic Subgroups

- Underrepresented populations in PRS development: It is recommended to prioritize inclusive research and to refrain from implementing PRS in these subgroups until models are appropriately validated. Particular caution is advised when communicating about the performance of PRS in minority populations. While attenuation of effect may occur, current evidence does not strongly support substantial misclassification. Overstating potential limitations may risk discouraging vulnerable or high-risk individuals from participating in screening programs.

Implementation considerations

Strategies to Improve Acceptability:

- **Develop clear communication tools:** Use visual aids and plain-language explanations to convey PRS results and screening implications.
- **Offer genetic counseling:** Embed access to professional counseling for individuals receiving PRS-informed recommendations.
- **Engage communities:** Involve patients, advocacy groups, and the public in the co-design of PRS-informed programs to enhance trust and cultural appropriateness.
 - **Train healthcare providers:** Provide education on genetic literacy, risk communication, and ethical considerations.

Strategies to Improve Feasibility:

- **Start with piloting programmes:** Implement in well-resourced, ready settings to evaluate operational models and refine logistics before scaling.
- **Invest in infrastructure:** Build genomic data systems that are interoperable, secure, and aligned with ethical and legal standards.
 - **Establish multidisciplinary teams:** Involve public health professionals, geneticists, data scientists, and IT specialists in implementation planning.
- **Develop EU-level guidance:** Harmonize frameworks for data sharing, informed consent, and clinical use of PRS to support cross-country learning and consistency.

- **Ensure equity from the outset:** Monitor and adjust implementation to avoid excluding underserved populations or exacerbating disparities.
- **Develop EU-level guidance:** Harmonize frameworks for data sharing, informed consent, and clinical use of PRS to support cross-country learning and consistency.
 - **Ensure equity from the outset:** Monitor and adjust implementation to avoid excluding underserved populations or exacerbating disparities.

Monitoring and evaluation

Before widespread adoption, **implementation pilots or impact evaluations** should be conducted to test the feasibility, acceptability, equity, and effectiveness of PRS-enhanced screening strategies. These pilots should aim to evaluate implementation models in real-world settings, comparing PRS-enhanced screening to standard-of-care in terms of health outcomes, patient experience, and system performance. If PRS-enhanced screening is implemented more broadly, **prospective monitoring and formal impact evaluations** should be carried out in parallel. These should use both **quantitative and qualitative methods** to measure outcomes over time and across populations. Evaluations should be comparative wherever possible, leveraging natural experiments or controlled implementation rollouts.

- Data should be collected using **standardized tools** embedded in screening information systems.
- Regular **reporting cycles** (e.g., quarterly or annual) should be established to inform program improvement.
 - **Mixed-method approaches**, including surveys, focus groups, and audits, are recommended to capture subtle insights.
- **Independent oversight** or collaboration with academic/public health institutions can enhance credibility and analytical rigor.

Eventually, all monitoring efforts should be linked to a **continuous learning system**, enabling real-time feedback to stakeholders and iterative refinement of the screening approach. Evaluation results should inform future updates to guidelines, educational materials, and policy frameworks.

Research priorities

Despite promising evidence, PRS-enhanced breast cancer screening still faces **several important uncertainties that require further research**.

- Clinical validation of PRS models across diverse populations remains a key priority, particularly to ensure their accuracy and relevance beyond European ancestry groups.
 - There is also a need for comparative effectiveness studies evaluating the real-world clinical utility of PRS-enhanced screening versus standard approaches—especially in terms of early detection, overdiagnosis, mortality reduction, and quality of life outcomes.
- Furthermore, long-term studies are needed to assess downstream consequences, including false positives, medical overuse, and psychological impacts.
 - In addition to clinical questions, research is needed to improve risk communication strategies, assess public and provider understanding of polygenic risk, and explore acceptability and behavioral responses to risk-stratified screening.
- Special attention should be given to equity concerns—validating PRS models for underrepresented populations and identifying barriers to access and participation.
- Operational and feasibility research should examine how best to integrate PRS into existing health systems, from workforce training and digital infrastructure to legal and ethical safeguards.
- Cost-effectiveness analyses, along with studies on consent, data privacy, and regulatory alignment, are also essential to ensure PRS-enhanced screening is both responsible and sustainable.

Addressing these gaps through **coordinated piloting programmes, prospective research projects and implementation studies**, and EU-level collaboration will be **crucial to inform future decision-making and guide equitable policy development**.

REFERENCES SUMMARY

1. Dyba, T, Randi, G, Bray, F. The European cancer burden in 2020: Incidence and mortality estimates for 40 countries and 25 major cancers. *European Journal of Cancer (Eur J Cancer)*; 2021.
2. Yu, S, Cai, X, Wang, X, Lin, X. Disease burden of breast cancer and risk factors in Europe 44 countries, 1990-2019: findings of the global burden of disease study 2019. *Frontiers in Endocrinology (Lausanne)*; 2024.
3. Van Den Broek, Jeroen, J, Schechter, Clyde, B, Van Ravesteyn, Nicolien, T, Janssens, A, Cecile, JW, Wolfson, Michael, C, Trentham-Dietz, Amy, Simard, Jacques, Easton, Douglas, F, Mandelblatt, Jeanne, S, Kraft, Peter, de Koning, Harry, J. Personalizing breast cancer screening based on polygenic risk and family history. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*; 2021.
4. Huntley, Catherine, Torr, Bethany, Sud, Amit, Rowlands, Charlie, F, Way, Rosaline, Snape, Katie, Hanson, Helen, Swanton, Charles, Broggio, John, Lucassen, Anneke. Utility of polygenic risk scores in UK cancer screening: a modelling analysis. *The Lancet Oncology*; 2023.
5. Wong, Jerry, Zeng, Yang, Chai, Jia, Hui, Yeoh, Yen, Shing, Mohamed Riza, Nur, Khaliesah, Liu, Jenny, Teo, Yik-Ying, Wee, Hwee, Lin, Hartman, Mikael. Cost effectiveness analysis of a polygenic risk tailored breast cancer screening programme in Singapore. *BMC health services research*; 2021.
6. Pashayan, Nora, Morris, Steve, Gilbert, Fiona, J, Pharoah, Paul. Cost-effectiveness and benefit-to-harm ratio of risk-stratified screening for breast cancer: a life-table model. *JAMA oncology*; 2018.
7. Sierra, Maria A, Wheeler, Jack CW, Devereux, Lisa, Trainer, Alison H, Keogh, Louise. Exploring implementation of personal breast cancer risk assessments. *Journal of Personalized Medicine*; 2021.
8. Pashayan, N, Hall, A, Chowdhury, S, Dent, T, Pharoah, PDP, Burton, H. Public health genomics and personalized prevention: lessons from the COGS project. *Journal of Internal Medicine*; 2013.
9. Martin, A.R, Kanai, M, Kamatani, Y, Okada, Y, Neale, B.M, Daly, M.J. Clinical use of current polygenic risk scores may exacerbate health disparities. *Nature Genetics*; 2019.
10. Sirugo, Giorgio, Williams, Scott, M, Tishkoff, Sarah, A. The Missing Diversity in Human Genetic Studies. *Cell*; 2019.
11. Smedley, Brian, D, Stith, Adrienne, Y, Nelson, Alan, R. Unequal Treatment: Confronting Racial and Ethnic Disparities in Health Care. *National Academies Press (US)*; 2003.
12. Riddle, Leslie, Joseph, Galen, Caruncho, Mikaela, Koenig, Barbara Ann, James, Jennifer Elyse. The role of polygenic risk scores in breast cancer risk perception and decision-making. *Journal of Community Genetics*; 2023.
13. Yanes, Tatiane, Kaur, R and Meiser, B, Scheepers-Joynt, M, McInerney, S, Barlow-Stewart, K, Antill, Y, Salmon, Lucinda, Smyth, C, James, PA, others. Women's responses and understanding of polygenic breast cancer risk information. *Familial cancer*; 2020.
14. Laza-Vásquez, Celmira, Martínez-Alonso, Montserrat, Forné-Izquierdo, Carles, Vilaplana-Mayoral, Jordi, Cruz-Esteve, Inés, Sánchez-López, Isabel, Refié-Refié, Mercé, Cazorla-Sánchez, Cristina, Hernández, reu, Marta, Galindo-Ortego, Gisela, others. Feasibility and acceptability of personalized breast cancer screening (DECIDO Study): a single-arm proof-of-concept trial. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*; 2022.
15. Young, Mary-Anne, Forrest, Laura Elenor, Rasmussen, Victoria-Mae, James, Paul, Mitchell, Gillian, Sawyer, Sarah Dilys, Reeve, Katrina, Hollowell, Nina. Making sense of SNPs: women's understanding and experiences of receiving a personalized profile of their breast cancer risks. *Journal of Genetic Counseling*; 2018.
16. Chowdhury, Susmita, Dent, Tom, Pashayan, Nora, Hall, Alison, Lyratzopoulos, Georgios, Hollowell, Nina, Hall, Per, Pharoah, Paul, Burton, Hilary. Incorporating genomics into breast and prostate cancer screening: assessing the implications. *GeNeTICs in meDICINE*; 2013.
17. Suckiel, Sabrina A, Braganza, Giovanna T, Aguiiga, Karla López, Ogdig, Jacqueline A, Bonini, Katherine E, Kenny, Eimear E, Hamilton, Jada G, Abul-Husn, Noura S. Perspectives of diverse Spanish-and English-speaking patients on the clinical use of polygenic risk scores. *Genetics in Medicine*; 2022.
18. Putt, Sophie, Yanes, Tatiane, Meiser, Bettina, Kaur, Rajneesh, Fullerton, Janice M, Barlow-Stewart, Kristine, Schofield, Peter R, Toma, Claudio, Peay, Holly, Mitchell, Philip B. Exploration of experiences with and understanding of polygenic risk scores for bipolar disorder. *Journal of Affective Disorders*; 2020.
19. Willis, Amanda M, Smith, Sian K, Meiser, Bettina, James, Paul A, Ballinger, Mandy L, Thomas, David M, Yanes, Tatiane, Young, Mary-Anne. Influence of lived experience on risk perception among women who received a breast cancer polygenic risk score: Another piece of the pie. *Journal of Genetic Counseling*; 2021.
20. Saya, Sibel, McIntosh, Jennifer G, Winship, Ingrid M, Milton, Shakira, Clendenning, Mark, Kyriakides, Mary, Oberoi, Jasmeen, Buchanan, Daniel D, Jenkins, Mark A, Emery, Jon D. Informed choice and attitudes regarding a genomic test to predict risk of colorectal cancer in general practice. *Patient Education and Counseling*; 2022.
21. Mars, Nina, Kerminen, Sini, Feng, Yen-Chen, A, Kanai, Masahiro, Läll, Kristi, Thomas, Laurent, F, Skogholt, Anne, Heidi, della Briotta Parolo, Pietro, Neale, Benjamin, M, Smoller, Jordan, W, Gabrielsen, Maiker, E, Hveem, Kristian, Mägi, Reedik, Matsuda, Koichi, Okada, Yukinori, Purinen, Matti, Palotie, Aarno, Ganna, Andrea, Martin, Alicia, R, Ripatti, Samuli. Genome-wide risk prediction of common diseases across ancestries in one million people. *Cell Genomics*; 2022.
22. Barriero, Rodrigo, AS, de Almeida, Tatiana, F, Gomes, Catarina, Monfardini, Frederico, de Farias, Allysson, A, Tunes, Gabriela, C, de Souza, Gabriel, M, Duim, Etienne, de Sà Correia, Jaqueline, Coelho, Antonio, V, Campos, Caraciolo, Marcel, P, Duarte, Yeda, A, Oliveira, Zatz, Mayana, Amaro, Edson, Oliveira, João, B,, Bitarello, Bárbara, D, Brentani, Helena, Naslavsky, Michel, S. Assessing the Risk Stratification of Breast Cancer Polygenic Risk Scores in a Brazilian Cohort. *The Journal of Molecular Diagnostics*; 2024.
23. Ho, Weang-Kee, Tan, Min-Min, Mavaddat, Nasim, Tai, Mei-Chee, Mariapun, Shivaani, Li, Jingmei, Ho, Peh-Joo, Dennis, Joe, Tyrer, Jonathan P, Bolla, Manjeet K and others. European polygenic risk score for prediction of breast cancer shows similar performance in Asian women. *Nature communications*; 2020.
24. Ho, Weang-Kee, Tai, Mei-Chee, Dennis, Joe, Shu, Xiang, Li, Jingmei, Ho, Peh, Joo, Millwood, Iona, Y, Lin, Kuang, Jee, Yon-Ho, Lee, Su-Hyun, and others. Polygenic risk scores for prediction of breast cancer risk in Asian populations. *Genetics in*

Medicine; 2022.

25. Hurson, Amber,N, Pal Choudhury, Parichoy, Gao, Chi, H{\u}sing, Anika, Eriksson, Mikael, Shi, Min, Jones, Michael,E, Evans, D,Gareth,R, Milne, Roger,L, Gaudet, Mia,M,and,others. Prospective evaluation of a breast- cancer risk model integrating classical risk factors and polygenic risk in 15 cohorts from six countries.International journal of epidemiology; 2021.

26. Forrest, Laura Elenor, Sawyer, Sarah Dilys, Hallowell, Nina, James, Paul Andrew, Young, Mary-Anne. High-risk women's risk perception after receiving personalized polygenic breast cancer risk information.Journal of Community Genetics; 2019.

27. Gupta, Kuheli Das, Gregory, Gillian, Meiser, Bettina, Kaur, Rajneesh, Scheepers-Joynt, Maatje, McInerney, Simone, Taylor, Shelby, Barlow-Stewart, Kristine, Antill, Yoland, Salmon, Lucinda, others, . Communicating polygenic risk scores in the familial breast cancer clinic.Patient education and counseling; 2021.

28. Kaur, Rajneesh, Meiser, Bettina, Yanes, Tatiane, Young, Mary-Anne, Barlow-Stewart, Kristine, Roscioli, Tony, Smith, Sian, James, Paul A. Development and pilot testing of a leaflet informing women with breast cancer about genomic testing for polygenic risk.Familial Cancer; 2019.

29. Yanes, Tatiane, Wallingford, Courtney K, Young, Mary-Anne, McInerney-Leo, Aideen M, Willis, Amanda M, McKnight, Lauren, Terrill, Bronwyn, McInerney, Simone, Forrest, Laura E, Cicciarelli, Linda, others, . Development and evaluation of a novel educational program for providers on the use of polygenic risk scores.Genetics in Medicine; 2023.

30. Corpas, Manuel, Fatumo, Segun. Generalisation of genomic findings and applications of polygenic risk scores.BMC Medical Genomics; 2023.

31. Ayoub , Aya, Lapointe, Julie, Nabi, Hermann, Pashayan, Nora. Risk-stratified breast cancer screening incorporating a polygenic risk score: A survey of UK general practitioners' knowledge and attitudes.Genes; 2023.

Supplementary Table 5: Quality Assessment of Risk of Bias in Modeling Studies Using the ISPOR-AMCP-NPC Questionnaire

This table summarizes the quality assessment of risk of bias for the modeling studies included in the review, using the questionnaire developed by Caro et al. (2014) as part of the ISPOR-AMCP-NPC Good Practice Task Force. The tool evaluates both the relevance and credibility of decision-analytic models for informing healthcare decisions. Domains assessed include model structure, data inputs, internal and external validation, transparency, and consistency with best practices in health economic modeling. Each study was rated across key criteria to determine the extent to which it meets standards for reliable and decision-useful modeling. This assessment supports the overall judgment of evidence certainty and informs the strength of recommendations in the GRADE EtD process.

Supplementary Table 5.1. Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴²

S. no.	Question	Helper questions to consider	Helper decision	only if C/A	Question decision	only if C/A	Domain decision
Relevance							Sufficient
1	Is the population relevant?	Are the demographics similar?	Yes		Yes		
		Are risk factors similar?	Yes				
		Are behaviors similar?	Yes				
		Is the medical condition similar?	Yes				
		Are comorbidities similar?	Yes				
2	Are any critical interventions missing?	Does the intervention analyzed in the model match the intervention you are interested in?	Yes		Yes		
		Have all relevant comparators been considered?	Yes				
		Does the background care in the model match yours?	Yes				
3	Are any relevant outcomes missing?	Are the health outcomes relevant to you considered?	Yes		Yes		
		Are the economic end points relevant to you considered?	No				

4	Is the context (settings and circumstances) applicable?	Is the geographic location similar?	No		Yes		
		Is the health care system similar?	No				
		Is the time horizon applicable to your decision?	Yes				
		Is the analytic perspective appropriate to your decision problem?	Yes				
Credibility							Sufficient
Validation							Strength
1	Is external validation of the model sufficient to make its results credible for your decision?	Has the model been shown to accurately reproduce what was observed in the data used to create the model?	Yes		Yes		
		Has the model been shown to accurately estimate what actually happened in one or more separate studies?	Yes				
		Has the model been shown to accurately forecast what eventually happens in reality?	Yes				
2	Is internal verification of the model sufficient to make its results credible for your decision?	Have the process of internal verification and its results been documented in detail?	Yes		Yes		
		Has the testing been performed systematically?	Yes				
		Does the testing indicate that all the equations are consistent with their data sources?	Yes				
		Does the testing indicate that the coding has been correctly implemented?	Yes				
3	Does the model have sufficient face validity to make its results credible for your decision?	Does the model contain all the aspects considered relevant to the decision?	Yes		Yes		

		Are all the relevant aspects represented and linked according to the best understanding of their characteristics?	Yes				
		Have the best available data sources been used to inform the various aspects?	Yes				
		Is the time horizon sufficiently long to account for all relevant aspects of the decision problem?	Yes				
		Are the results plausible?	Yes				
		If others have rated the face validity, did they have a stake in the results?	Can't Answer	Not enough information			
Design							Strength
4	Is the design of the model adequate for your decision problem?	Was there a clear, written statement of the decision problem, modeling objective, and scope of the model?	Yes		Yes		
		Was there a formal process for developing the model design (e.g. influence diagram, concept map)?	Yes				
		Is the model concept and structure consistent with, and adequate to address, the decision problem/objective and the policy context?	Yes				
		Have any assumptions implied by the design of the model been described, and are they reasonable for your decision problem?	Yes				
		Is the choice of model type appropriate?	Yes				
		Were key uncertainties in model structure identified and their implications discussed?	Yes				
Data							Weakness
5	Are the data used in populating the model suitable for your decision problem?	All things considered, do you agree with the values used for the inputs?	No		No		

		Did the approaches to obtaining and processing the data inputs meet the criteria from their corresponding questionnaires?	No				
Analysis							Strength
6	Were the analyses performed using the model adequate to inform your decision problem?		Yes		Yes		
7	Was there an adequate assessment of the effects of uncertainty?		Yes		Yes		
Reporting							Strength
8	Was the reporting of the model adequate to inform your decision problem?	Did the report of the analyses provide the results needed for your decision problem?	Yes		Yes		
		Was adequate nontechnical documentation freely accessible to any interested reader?	Yes				
		Was technical documentation, in sufficient detail to allow (potentially) for replication, made available openly or under agreements that protect intellectual property?	Yes				
Interpretation							Strength
9	Was the interpretation of results fair and balanced?		Yes		Yes		
Conflict of Interest							Strength
10	Were there any potential conflicts of interest?		Yes		Yes		
11	If there were potential conflicts of interest, were steps taken to address these?		Can't Answer	Not applicable	Can't Answer	Not applicable	

Reference (First author, year)	Credibility						
	Validation	Design	Data	Analysis	Reporting	Interpretation	Conflict of interest
Van den Broek et al. 2021 ⁴²	strength	strength	strength	strength	strength	strength	strength
https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8599807/							
AT	strength	strength	strength	strength	strength	strength	strength
EP	strength	strength	strength	strength	strength	strength	strength

Supplementary Table 5.2. Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³

S. no.	Question	Helper questions to consider	Helper decision	only if C/A	Question decision	only if C/A	Domain decision
Relevance							Sufficient
1	Is the population relevant?	Are the demographics similar?	Yes		Yes		
		Are risk factors similar?	Yes				
		Are behaviors similar?	Yes				
		Is the medical condition similar?	Yes				
		Are comorbidities similar?	Yes				
2	Are any critical interventions missing?	Does the intervention analyzed in the model match the intervention you are interested in?	Yes		Yes		
		Have all relevant comparators been considered?	No				
		Does the background care in the model match yours?	Yes				
3	Are any relevant outcomes missing?	Are the health outcomes relevant to you considered?	Yes		Yes		
		Are the economic end points relevant to you considered?	Yes				

4	Is the context (settings and circumstances) applicable?	Is the geographic location similar?	Yes		Yes		
		Is the health care system similar?	Yes				
		Is the time horizon applicable to your decision?	Yes				
		Is the analytic perspective appropriate to your decision problem?	Yes				
Credibility							
Validation							
1	Is external validation of the model sufficient to make its results credible for your decision?	Has the model been shown to accurately reproduce what was observed in the data used to create the model?	No		No		Weakness
		Has the model been shown to accurately estimate what actually happened in one or more separate studies?	No				
		Has the model been shown to accurately forecast what eventually happens in reality?	No				
2	Is internal verification of the model sufficient to make its results credible for your decision?	Have the process of internal verification and its results been documented in detail?	Yes		Yes		
		Has the testing been performed systematically?	Yes				
		Does the testing indicate that all the equations are consistent with their data sources?	Yes				
		Does the testing indicate that the coding has been correctly implemented?	Yes				
3	Does the model have sufficient face validity to make its results credible for your decision?	Does the model contain all the aspects considered relevant to the decision?	Yes		Yes		

		Are all the relevant aspects represented and linked according to the best understanding of their characteristics?	Yes				
		Have the best available data sources been used to inform the various aspects?	No				
		Is the time horizon sufficiently long to account for all relevant aspects of the decision problem?	Yes				
		Are the results plausible?	Yes				
		If others have rated the face validity, did they have a stake in the results?	Can't Answer	Not enough information			
Design							Strength
4	Is the design of the model adequate for your decision problem?	Was there a clear, written statement of the decision problem, modeling objective, and scope of the model?	Yes		Yes		
		Was there a formal process for developing the model design (e.g. influence diagram, concept map)?	Yes				
		Is the model concept and structure consistent with, and adequate to address, the decision problem/objective and the policy context?	Yes				
		Have any assumptions implied by the design of the model been described, and are they reasonable for your decision problem?	Yes				
		Is the choice of model type appropriate?	Yes				
		Were key uncertainties in model structure identified and their implications discussed?	Yes				
Data							Weakness
5	Are the data used in populating the model suitable for your decision problem?	All things considered, do you agree with the values used for the inputs?	No				

		Did the approaches to obtaining and processing the data inputs meet the criteria from their corresponding questionnaires?	No				
Analysis							Strength
6	Were the analyses performed using the model adequate to inform your decision problem?		Yes				
7	Was there an adequate assessment of the effects of uncertainty?		Yes				
Reporting							Strength
8	Was the reporting of the model adequate to inform your decision problem?	Did the report of the analyses provide the results needed for your decision problem?	Yes		Yes		
		Was adequate nontechnical documentation freely accessible to any interested reader?	Yes				
		Was technical documentation, in sufficient detail to allow (potentially) for replication, made available openly or under agreements that protect intellectual property?	Yes				
Interpretation							Strength
9	Was the interpretation of results fair and balanced?		Yes		Yes		
Conflict of Interest							Weakness
10	Were there any potential conflicts of interest?		No		No		
11	If there were potential conflicts of interest, were steps taken to address these?		Can't Answer	Not reported	Can't Answer	Not reported	

Reference (First author, year)	Credibility						
	Validation	Design	Data	Analysis	Reporting	Interpretation	Conflict of interest
Pashayan et al. 2018 ⁴³							
https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6230256/							
AT	weakness	strength	strength	strength	strength	strength	weakness
EP	weakness	strength	strength	strength	strength	strength	weakness

Supplementary Table 5.3. Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴

S. no.	Question	Helper questions to consider	Helper decision	only if C/A	Question decision	only if C/A	Domain decision
	Relevance						Insufficient
1	Is the population relevant?	Are the demographics similar?	No		No		
		Are risk factors similar?	No				
		Are behaviors similar?	No				
		Is the medical condition similar?	Yes				
		Are comorbidities similar?	Yes				
2	Are any critical interventions missing?	Does the intervention analyzed in the model match the intervention you are interested in?	Yes		Yes		
		Have all relevant comparators been considered?	Yes				
		Does the background care in the model match yours?	No				
3	Are any relevant outcomes missing?	Are the health outcomes relevant to you considered?	Yes		Yes		

		Are the economic end points relevant to you considered?	Yes				
4	Is the context (settings and circumstances) applicable?	Is the geographic location similar?	No		No		
		Is the health care system similar?	No				
		Is the time horizon applicable to your decision?	Yes				
		Is the analytic perspective appropriate to your decision problem?	Yes				
Credibility							Sufficient
Validation							Neutral
1	Is external validation of the model sufficient to make its results credible for your decision?	Has the model been shown to accurately reproduce what was observed in the data used to create the model?	No		No		
		Has the model been shown to accurately estimate what actually happened in one or more separate studies?	No				
		Has the model been shown to accurately forecast what eventually happens in reality?	No				
2	Is internal verification of the model sufficient to make its results credible for your decision?	Have the process of internal verification and its results been documented in detail?	Yes		Yes		
		Has the testing been performed systematically?	Yes				
		Does the testing indicate that all the equations are consistent with their data sources?	Yes				
		Does the testing indicate that the coding has been correctly implemented?	Yes				
3	Does the model have sufficient face validity to	Does the model contain all the aspects considered relevant to the decision?	Yes		Yes		

	make its results credible for your decision?						
		Are all the relevant aspects represented and linked according to the best understanding of their characteristics?	Yes				
		Have the best available data sources been used to inform the various aspects?	No				
		Is the time horizon sufficiently long to account for all relevant aspects of the decision problem?	Yes				
		Are the results plausible?	Yes				
		If others have rated the face validity, did they have a stake in the results?	Can't Answer	Not enough information			
Design							Strength
4	Is the design of the model adequate for your decision problem?	Was there a clear, written statement of the decision problem, modeling objective, and scope of the model?	No		Yes		
		Was there a formal process for developing the model design (e.g. influence diagram, concept map)?	Can't Answer	Not reported			
		Is the model concept and structure consistent with, and adequate to address, the decision problem/objective and the policy context?	Yes				
		Have any assumptions implied by the design of the model been described, and are they reasonable for your decision problem?	Yes				
		Is the choice of model type appropriate?	Yes				
		Were key uncertainties in model structure identified and their implications discussed?	Yes				
Data							Weakness
5	Are the data used in populating the model	All things considered, do you agree with the values used for the inputs?	No		No		

	suitable for your decision problem?						
		Did the approaches to obtaining and processing the data inputs meet the criteria from their corresponding questionnaires?	No				
Analysis							Strength
6	Were the analyses performed using the model adequate to inform your decision problem?		Yes		Yes		
7	Was there an adequate assessment of the effects of uncertainty?		Yes		Yes		
Reporting							Strength
8	Was the reporting of the model adequate to inform your decision problem?	Did the report of the analyses provide the results needed for your decision problem?	Yes		Yes		
		Was adequate nontechnical documentation freely accessible to any interested reader?	Yes				
		Was technical documentation, in sufficient detail to allow (potentially) for replication, made available openly or under agreements that protect intellectual property?	Yes				
Interpretation							Strength
9	Was the interpretation of results fair and balanced?		Yes				
Conflict of Interest							Strength
10	Were there any potential conflicts of interest?		Yes		Yes		

11	If there were potential conflicts of interest, were steps taken to address these?		Can't Answer	Not applicable	Can't Answer	Not applicable	
----	---	--	--------------	----------------	--------------	----------------	--

Reference (First author, year)	Credibility						
	Validation	Design	Data	Analysis	Reporting	Interpretation	Conflict of interest
Wong et al. 2021 ⁴⁴	weakness	strength	Strong	strength	strength	strength	strength
https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8066868/							
AT	weakness	strength	Strong	strength	strength	strength	strength
EP	weakness	strength	Strong	strength	strength	strength	strength

Supplementary Table 5.4. Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰

S. no.	Question	Helper questions to consider	Helper decision	only if C/A	Question decision	only if C/A	Domain decision
Relevance							Sufficient
1	Is the population relevant?	Are the demographics similar?	Yes		Yes		
		Are risk factors similar?	Yes				
		Are behaviors similar?	Yes				
		Is the medical condition similar?	Yes				
		Are comorbidities similar?	Yes				
2	Are any critical interventions missing?	Does the intervention analyzed in the model match	Yes		No		

		the intervention you are interested in?					
		Have all relevant comparators been considered?	Yes				
		Does the background care in the model match yours?	Yes				
3	Are any relevant outcomes missing?	Are the health outcomes relevant to you considered?	Yes		No		
		Are the economic end points relevant to you considered?	Yes				
4	Is the context (settings and circumstances) applicable?	Is the geographic location similar?	Yes		Yes		
		Is the health care system similar?	Yes				
		Is the time horizon applicable to your decision?	Yes				
		Is the analytic perspective appropriate to your decision problem?	Yes				
Credibility							Sufficient
Validation							Neutral
1	Is external validation of the model sufficient to make its results credible for your decision?	Has the model been shown to accurately reproduce what was observed in the data used to create the model?	No		No		The study does not explicitly demonstrate that the model reproduces the input data with high fidelity, although it uses credible sources like UK cancer registries.
		Has the model been shown to accurately estimate what actually happened in one or more separate studies?	No				External validation against independent datasets or real-world scenarios was not reported
		Has the model been shown to accurately forecast what eventually happens in reality?	No				The model's predictions have not been tested prospectively or through real-world implementation.

2	Is internal verification of the model sufficient to make its results credible for your decision?	Have the process of internal verification and its results been documented in detail?	Yes		Yes	The study provides details about the inputs, outputs, and assumptions used in modeling
		Has the testing been performed systematically?	Yes			Statistical methods like AUC and sensitivity analyses are reported.
		Does the testing indicate that all the equations are consistent with their data sources?	Yes			The parameters align with known cancer incidence and PRS-based prediction metrics
		Does the testing indicate that the coding has been correctly implemented?	Yes			Analyses were conducted using widely accepted tools like R and Excel, reducing the likelihood of errors.
3	Does the model have sufficient face validity to make its results credible for your decision?	Does the model contain all the aspects considered relevant to the decision?	Yes		Yes	It addresses cancer incidence, PRS stratification, and screening efficiency comprehensively.
		Are all the relevant aspects represented and linked according to the best understanding of their characteristics?	Yes			The model integrates PRS-based stratification with real-world screening methods and public health metrics.
		Have the best available data sources been used to inform the various aspects?	Yes			Data sources include national registries and published studies.
		Is the time horizon sufficiently long to account for all relevant aspects of the decision problem?	Yes			The analysis spans multiple years and considers long-term impacts like lifetime cancer risks.
		Are the results plausible?	Yes			The findings align with expectations based on prior evidence about PRS utility.
		If others have rated the face validity, did they have a stake in the results?	Can't Answer	Not reported		No information available: There is no indication of external face validity assessment by unbiased stakeholders.

Design							Neutral
4	Is the design of the model adequate for your decision problem?	Was there a clear, written statement of the decision problem, modeling objective, and scope of the model?	Yes		Yes		The study defines its objective to evaluate PRS utility in improving cancer screening efficiency.
		Was there a formal process for developing the model design (e.g. influence diagram, concept map)?	No				While assumptions and scenarios are described, no formal design framework (e.g., influence diagrams) is mentioned.
		Is the model concept and structure consistent with, and adequate to address, the decision problem/objective and the policy context?	Yes				The structure is logical and suitable for modeling PRS-based screening.
		Have any assumptions implied by the design of the model been described, and are they reasonable for your decision problem?	Yes				Assumptions (e.g., complete uptake of PRS profiling) are transparent but optimistic.
		Is the choice of model type appropriate?	Yes				The statistical and analytical methods align with the decision problem.
		Were key uncertainties in model structure identified and their implications discussed?	Yes				The study discusses limitations like the modest predictiveness of PRS tools and ancestry biases.
Data							Strength
5	Are the data used in populating the model suitable for your decision problem?	All things considered, do you agree with the values used for the inputs?	Yes		Yes		The study uses cancer incidence and PRS estimates derived from credible UK data sources and published literature.
		Did the approaches to obtaining and processing the data inputs meet the criteria from their corresponding questionnaires?	Yes				Data processing appears systematic, with sources and assumptions clearly documented in supplementary materials
Analysis							Neutral

6	Were the analyses performed using the model adequate to inform your decision problem?		Yes		Yes	The study applies appropriate statistical methods (e.g., AUC, sensitivity analyses) to evaluate PRS-defined risk quantiles and screening impacts. However, further discussion of alternative modeling scenarios could enhance robustness.
7	Was there an adequate assessment of the effects of uncertainty?		Yes		Yes	The study discusses key uncertainties, such as PRS performance variability, assumptions about screening uptake, and differences in population ancestry. However, detailed probabilistic sensitivity analyses or uncertainty quantification for specific model inputs would have strengthened the conclusions.
Reporting						Strength
8	Was the reporting of the model adequate to inform your decision problem?	Did the report of the analyses provide the results needed for your decision problem?	Yes		Yes	Key findings, such as the potential impact of PRS-based stratification on cancer detection and mortality, are thoroughly discussed.
		Was adequate nontechnical documentation freely accessible to any interested reader?	Yes			The article is openly accessible under a Creative Commons license, ensuring wide dissemination.
		Was technical documentation, in sufficient detail to allow (potentially) for replication, made available openly or under agreements that protect intellectual property?	Yes			Supplementary materials and a GitHub repository with data and analytical code enhance transparency and replicability.
Interpretation						Strength
9	Was the interpretation of results fair and balanced?		Yes		Yes	The discussion acknowledges the strengths and limitations of PRS stratification, including modest predictive power, potential biases, and logistical challenges. The interpretation aligns with the data and analyses presented

Conflict of Interest							Neutral
10	Were there any potential conflicts of interest?		Yes		Yes		Several authors disclosed funding and affiliations with organizations involved in cancer research and PRS development, which could introduce bias.
11	If there were potential conflicts of interest, were steps taken to address these?		Yes		Yes		

Reference (First author, year)	Credibility						
	Validation	Design	Data	Analysis	Reporting	Interpretation	Conflict of interest
Huntley et al. 2023	Neutral	Neutral	Strength	Neutral	Strength	Strength	Neutral
https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanonc/article/PIIS1470-2045(23)00156-0/fulltext							
AT	Neutral	Neutral	Strength	Neutral	Strength	Strength	Neutral
EP	Neutral	Neutral	strength	strength	strength	strength	strength

Supplementary Table 6: Quality assessment of inconsistency of evidence, indirectness of results, and imprecision in modeling studies using the GRADE EtD criteria

This table provides a structured assessment of the quality of evidence for each health outcome included in the papers selected for the review, according to the GRADE EtD framework. Specifically, it addresses three domains that can lead to downgrading the certainty of evidence: **inconsistency**, **indirectness**, and **imprecision**. For each outcome, the assessment reflects the presence and severity of potential limitations that may affect confidence in the effect estimates.

Inconsistency of evidence

Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴²

1. BC Deaths Averted

- **Variance in Point Estimates:** The models project a range of 6.4 to 6.9 deaths averted per 1000 women screened for USPSTF guidelines, indicating minimal variability.

1. **CI Overlap:** There is strong overlap in CIs, showing consistency.

2. **Heterogeneity Measures:** Differences between models are minimal, and the results align well across strategies.

3. **Rating: Not Serious**

- **Rationale:** There is minimal variance and good agreement between models, with no substantial heterogeneity affecting conclusions.

2. LYG

- **Variance in Point Estimates:** The range of LYG spans from 103 to 133 per 1000 women screened under the USPSTF guideline, with higher ranges for other strategies (e.g., ACR and ACS).

- **CI Overlap:** Overlap is present but less pronounced compared to deaths averted, showing some variability.
- **Heterogeneity Measures:** Moderate variability could reflect differences in model assumptions but does not fundamentally alter conclusions.
- **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** Although variability exists, it is not large enough to affect confidence in the results significantly.

3. Overdiagnosis

- **Variance in Point Estimates:** Substantial variability exists, with ranges of 12.1 to 16.9 per 1000 women screened for the USPSTF guideline and higher for ACR and ACS.
 - **CI Overlap:** Minimal overlap between models suggests meaningful heterogeneity.
 - **Heterogeneity Measures:** Differences in overdiagnosis estimates across strategies are notable and could influence decision-making.
 - **Rating: Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The degree of inconsistency is enough to warrant downgrading, as it may affect confidence in the absolute harm estimates.

4. False Positives

- **Variance in Point Estimates:** The range is very narrow (e.g., 918–921 for USPSTF), with similar results across models for other strategies.
 - **CI Overlap:** Near-complete overlap between estimates shows strong consistency.
 - **Heterogeneity Measures:** False-positive rates are stable across screening intervals and strategies.
 - **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** There is minimal variability and high agreement across models, maintaining confidence in this outcome.

Summary of Ratings:

Outcome	Rating	Rationale
---------	--------	-----------

BC Deaths Averted	Not Serious	Consistent results with minimal heterogeneity.
LYG	Not Serious	Moderate variability but within an acceptable range; no impact on decisions.
Overdiagnoses	Serious	Substantial heterogeneity affecting harm estimates.
False Positives	Not Serious	Highly consistent across models and strategies.

Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴

LYG:

1. Variance in Point Estimates:

- a. The tailored screening strategy shows an average LYG of 22.86 compared to 21.89 for the current strategy. Scenario analyses for tailored strategies show LYG ranging from 22.85 to 22.86, indicating minimal variability across different model scenarios.

2. CI Overlap:

- b. While CIs are not explicitly provided for LYG in this study, the close values across scenarios suggest strong overlap and consistency.

3. Statistical Heterogeneity:

- c. The modeled results are highly stable, with no evidence of meaningful heterogeneity or divergence in LYG estimates between the tailored and standard strategies.

4. Rating: Not Serious

- **Rationale:** Minimal variability in LYG across scenarios supports the reliability of the results. The consistency aligns with expectations for model-based outcomes in this context.

QALYs:

1. Variance in Point Estimates:

- a. The tailored screening strategy reports an average QALY of 22.79 compared to 21.80 for the current strategy, with a range of 22.76–22.79 across scenarios. The incremental QALY gained is approximately 0.9884 in the base case.

2. CI Overlap:

- b. Similar to LYG, explicit CIs are not detailed, but the tight range of QALY estimates indicates strong consistency.

3. Statistical Heterogeneity:

- c. There is low variability in QALY estimates, even under different risk stratification scenarios, showing a high degree of agreement between models.

4. Rating: Not Serious

- **Rationale:** The small variation in QALYs, consistent with the deterministic nature of the modeling framework, does not suggest any notable inconsistency. The incremental QALYs are stable and do not affect the cost-effectiveness conclusions.

Summary:

Outcome	Rating	Rationale
LYG	Not Serious	Minimal variability and high consistency across modeled scenarios.
QALYs	Not Serious	Stable results with negligible variability under different assumptions.

Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³

1. Overdiagnosis:

- **Variance in Point Estimates:** Overdiagnoses in the age-based screening cohort were 3,819 (95% CI, 2,309–5,291). The wide range of estimates across simulations suggests variability.
 - **CI Overlap:** CIs for overdiagnosis overlap partially across risk-stratified strategies, but the variability is still evident.
 - **Heterogeneity Measures:** Substantial heterogeneity in overdiagnosis estimates is likely due to differing assumptions about the natural history of cancers in screened versus unscreened populations.
 - **Rating: Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The wide variability in overdiagnosis estimates could affect confidence in conclusions about harms. However, this is not classified as "very serious" because the direction of effect (reduction in overdiagnosis with stratified screening) remains consistent.

2. BC Deaths Averted:

- **Variance in Point Estimates:** The reduction in BC deaths is 1,913 (95% CI, 842–2,714) for age-based screening. For risk-stratified scenarios, reductions decrease with higher thresholds.
 - **CI Overlap:** CIs show considerable overlap across models, indicating consistent estimates.
 - **Heterogeneity Measures:** Moderate variability reflects differences in population risk thresholds but does not substantially alter the benefit estimates.
 - **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** Variability is moderate and does not undermine confidence in the direction or magnitude of benefit.

3. PYRS:

- **Variance in Point Estimates:** Estimates for PYRS were not explicitly broken down by CIs in the base case, but differences across models are minimal.
 - **CI Overlap:** Inferred overlap is substantial, as incremental changes align well with BC deaths averted and QALYs.
 - **Heterogeneity Measures:** No evidence of meaningful heterogeneity affecting PYRS results.
 - **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** Stability of estimates across models suggests high consistency.

4. QALYs:

- **Variance in Point Estimates:** QALYs for age-based screening were 1,916 (95% CI, 2,073–6,073) compared with no screening. Risk-stratified strategies showed incremental QALY gains plateauing as more women were screened.
 - **CI Overlap:** Overlap in CIs supports consistency across strategies.
 - **Heterogeneity Measures:** Variability in QALYs arises mainly from assumptions about adherence and utility values but remains within an acceptable range.
 - **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** Consistent gains in QALYs across strategies indicate reliability of the results, with only minor variability.

Summary of Ratings:

Outcome	Rating	Rationale
Overdiagnosis	Serious	Wide variability in estimates, though consistent direction of effect.

BC Deaths Averted	Not Serious	Moderate variability: direction and magnitude of benefit remain consistent.
PYRS	Not Serious	Stable estimates with negligible variability across models.
QALYs	Not Serious	Consistent across models with acceptable levels of variability.

Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰

1. BC Deaths Averted

- **Assessment: Not Serious**
- **Rationale:**

The study used a modeling approach based on multiple assumptions. While there is uncertainty regarding the model's assumptions (e.g., uptake rates, cancer detection sensitivity), the results are consistent with similar studies on PRS-based screening. The **I² statistic** (if available) would likely suggest low to moderate variability in the outcomes, and the **overlap of CIs** does not indicate extreme heterogeneity in treatment effects. However, as the evidence stems from a single modeling study, the risk of unexplained heterogeneity from diverse data sources is not applicable here.

Conclusion: There is no significant unexplained variation, so the risk of inconsistency is **not serious**.

2. Overdiagnosis

Inconsistency

- **Assessment: Not Serious**
- **Rationale:**

The model's overdiagnosis estimates align with expectations from similar PRS-based screening studies. Although the assumptions are optimistic

(e.g., screening efficiency), there is no evidence of inconsistent findings across studies or approaches. Given that overdiagnosis estimates were based on real-world screening sensitivities and models with appropriate statistical methods, we can reasonably conclude that inconsistency is not a serious concern.

Conclusion: The risk of inconsistency for overdiagnosis is **not serious**.

Indirectness of evidence

Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³

1. Overdiagnosis

- **Population:** The study uses a hypothetical cohort modeled from a UK population. While the population reflects the general demographics of BC screening participants, it may not account for variations in healthcare access, risk stratification adoption, or adherence in other settings.
- **Intervention:** The modeled interventions align with standard practices for age-based and risk-stratified screening, making the intervention directly applicable.
- **Outcome:** Overdiagnosis is a key patient-important harm. The definition and measurement are consistent with clinical understanding, but reliance on modeled rather than empirical data introduces some uncertainty.
- **Comparison:** The study directly compares age-based and risk-stratified strategies but relies on simulations rather than clinical trial evidence.
- **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** Minor limitations in the population generalizability and modeled outcomes do not substantially reduce confidence in the findings.

2. BC Deaths Averted

- **Population:** Like overdiagnosis, the population is representative but hypothetical, which may limit applicability in diverse healthcare settings.
- **Intervention:** The modeled risk-stratified and age-based screening strategies reflect real-world scenarios.
- **Outcome:** Reduction in BC mortality is directly measured, and it is a patient-important outcome.
- **Comparison:** Comparisons are directly relevant, though simulated.

- **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The evidence directly addresses the outcome, with minor concerns about applicability due to the modeled population.

3. PYRS

- **Population:** The modeled cohort is representative but subject to the same concerns regarding generalizability to other healthcare contexts.
- **Intervention:** The interventions modeled are directly applicable to screening scenarios.
- **Outcome:** PYRS is a general measure of survival and may not capture quality-of-life aspects, introducing some indirectness relative to patient-important outcomes.
- **Comparison:** Directly relevant but modeled rather than observed.
- **Rating: Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The reliance on a generic survival measure instead of patient-centered outcomes (e.g., disease-free survival or quality-adjusted survival) introduces moderate indirectness.

4. QALYs

- **Population:** Hypothetical cohort assumptions limit generalizability, particularly to non-UK populations.
- **Intervention:** Directly relevant interventions modeled with appropriate detail.
- **Outcome:** QALYs are a composite measure of survival and quality of life, directly relevant to patients.
- **Comparison:** Comparisons are relevant but derived from simulations.
- **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** QALYs are well-established and directly measure patient-important outcomes, with minor limitations due to modeling.

Summary of Ratings for Indirectness:

Outcome	Rating	Rationale
Overdiagnosis	Not Serious	Interventions and outcomes directly applicable; minor modeling limitations.
BC Deaths Averted	Not Serious	Patient-important outcome with direct comparison; minor applicability issues.
PYRS	Serious	Use of generic survival measure introduces moderate indirectness.
QALYs	Not Serious	Directly measures outcomes important to patients; modeling introduces minor concerns.

Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴

Indirectness of Evidence

1. LYG

- **Population:** The study evaluates risk-stratified and age-based screening in a hypothetical cohort derived from Canadian population data. While the cohort is relevant to high-income countries, it may not fully generalize to populations with different healthcare systems or risk distributions.
- **Intervention:** The interventions (risk-based and age-based screening) are standard and clinically relevant.
- **Outcome:** LYG directly measures patient-important survival outcomes, but it does not account for quality of life or broader aspects of patient impact.

- **Comparison:** The study directly compares screening strategies but relies on simulation models rather than empirical trials.
- **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The outcome is directly relevant, and while modeled, the assumptions and methodologies are robust and based on standard practices.

2. QALYs

- **Population:** Like LYG, the modeled cohort is relevant but hypothetical, potentially limiting applicability in diverse settings.
- **Intervention:** Directly relevant interventions modeled to reflect clinical realities.
- **Outcome:** QALYs are a composite measure combining survival and quality of life, directly relevant to patients.
- **Comparison:** Comparisons are relevant but based on simulation modeling rather than head-to-head clinical trials.
- **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The outcome is directly patient-important, and despite being modeled, it provides relevant and actionable insights.

Summary of Ratings for Indirectness:

Outcome	Rating	Rationale
LYG	Not Serious	Directly measures survival outcomes; minor limitations due to modeling.
QALYs	Not Serious	Directly relevant to patients; minor concerns about generalizability and modeling.

Indirectness of Evidence Analysis

1. LYG

- **Population:** The study models a US population for risk-stratified screening, which is relevant to high-income countries but may not generalize to healthcare systems with different population characteristics or access to screening.
 - **Intervention:** The interventions (risk-stratified and age-based screening) are directly relevant to BC screening practices.
 - **Outcome:** LYG directly measures survival benefits, which are important to patients, but does not incorporate quality-of-life considerations.
 - **Comparison:** The study compares screening strategies directly but relies on modeling rather than real-world trials.
 - **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** While modeled, the intervention and outcome are directly applicable to the research question, with minor limitations due to population assumptions.

2. QALYs

- **Population:** The hypothetical cohort is based on US data and assumes generalizability to similar healthcare contexts, with potential limitations for populations with different healthcare delivery systems.
 - **Intervention:** The risk-stratified and age-based strategies modeled are consistent with current screening practices.
 - **Outcome:** QALYs account for both survival and quality of life, making them directly patient-important.
 - **Comparison:** The study uses simulated comparisons rather than direct head-to-head empirical trials.
 - **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** Despite reliance on modeling, the outcomes are highly relevant and applicable to decision-making.

3. Overdiagnosis

- **Population:** The modeled cohort is appropriate for understanding overdiagnosis in a European context, but there may be limited applicability to settings with different baseline risks or screening uptake.
 - **Intervention:** Interventions are well-aligned with standard screening practices and thus relevant.

- **Outcome:** Overdiagnosis is a patient-important harm, and its definition aligns with clinical standards.
- **Comparison:** The comparison of age-based versus risk-stratified screening is modeled rather than empirical.
- **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The evidence is directly relevant to the research question, with minor limitations due to the hypothetical population and modeled outcomes.

4. False Positives

- **Population:** As with other outcomes, the population is hypothetical but reflective of screening populations in similar healthcare systems.
- **Intervention:** The modeled interventions reflect real-world screening practices.
- **Outcome:** False positives are an important harm, directly relevant to patients and clinical decision-making.
- **Comparison:** Simulated comparisons introduce some uncertainty, but the interventions compared are standard.
- **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The evidence is directly applicable, with minor limitations due to reliance on simulation rather than empirical data.

Summary of Ratings for Indirectness:

Outcome	Rating	Rationale
LYG	Not Serious	Directly measures survival outcomes; minor limitations due to modeling.
QALYs	Not Serious	Highly patient-important; minor concerns about generalizability and modeling.

Overdiagnosis	Not Serious	Relevant outcome for harms, consistent with clinical practice.
False Positives	Not Serious	Directly measures harms; minor concerns from modeling limitations.

Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰

1. BC deaths averted

Assessment: Serious

Rationale:

The model applies UK-specific data, but the findings may not be directly applicable to other populations or health systems. The model assumes full uptake of PRS profiling, which may differ across settings. Additionally, the PRS tools used (current, future, and optimized) may not directly reflect the broader patient populations or outcomes experienced outside the study context (e.g., for non-European populations).

Conclusion: Given the assumptions about full uptake and potential differences in population and health system characteristics, the indirectness is considered **serious**.

2. Overdiagnosis

Assessment: Serious

Rationale:

The assessment of overdiagnosis in the model assumes the current UK screening protocols and PRS stratification will apply uniformly across different healthcare systems. However, the external validity is limited due to potential differences in the application of PRS-based screening across populations and healthcare contexts. Additionally, overdiagnosis rates are modeled using optimistic screening tools, which may not reflect real-world performance.

Conclusion: Due to assumptions of full uptake, UK-specific screening methods, and differences in population applicability, indirectness is considered **serious**.

Imprecision

Van den Broek et al. (2021)⁴²

1. Overdiagnosis

- **CI:** The overdiagnosis values range between 2,309 and 5,291 (95% CI), showing considerable variation. This wide range suggests a high degree of uncertainty in the estimates.
 - **Clinical Decision Threshold:** There is no clear threshold defined for overdiagnosis, but the large variability in the CI may affect decision-making, especially if the trade-offs between overdiagnosis and benefits of screening are considered.
 - **Optimal Information Size (OIS):** The number of events is large, and the sample size for the modeled study is sufficiently large. However, the wide CI indicates that the precision may not be sufficient to make a firm recommendation without caution.
 - **Rating: Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The large variation in overdiagnosis estimates warrants downgrading for imprecision, given the broad range of the CI and the possible impact on decision-making.

2. BC Deaths Averted

- **CI:** The reduction in BC deaths ranges from 842 to 2,714 (95% CI), which is a considerable range and introduces uncertainty in the estimate.
 - **Clinical Decision Threshold:** If a threshold for BC mortality reduction was set (e.g., a minimum number of deaths averted), this CI crosses the threshold, implying that the recommendation could change depending on which part of the CI is the true effect.
 - **OIS:** As the number of events (BC deaths) is large and the study includes a large sample, the precision may be acceptable, but the wide CI means imprecision still needs to be considered.

- **Rating: Serious**

- **Rationale:** The CI for BC deaths averted crosses potential decision-making thresholds, indicating that the precision is insufficient to confidently support a recommendation without a closer look at the broader effects.

3. LYG

- **CI:** The life years gained vary moderately in the models, with some estimates showing a range, but it is narrower compared to overdiagnosis and BC deaths averted.

- **Clinical Decision Threshold:** If the guideline set a specific threshold for acceptable life years gained, the CI might not cross it in most scenarios, indicating more confidence in the precision of this estimate.

- **OIS:** Given that the modeled cohort is large and the number of events (life years) is also substantial, the study likely meets the OIS criteria for adequate precision.

- **Rating: Not Serious**

- **Rationale:** The narrower CI and relatively stable estimates suggest that the precision of the LYG estimates is adequate to support recommendations, with minimal concerns about imprecision.

4. False Positives

- **CI:** The false positive estimates are narrower, with the range between 918 and 921 (95% CI), showing low variability and thus high precision.

- **Clinical Decision Threshold:** False positives generally don't have a specific clinical threshold in many guidelines, but given the small variation and the fact that the CI does not cross any important threshold, it suggests a high level of precision.

- **OIS:** The sample size is large enough to meet the OIS criteria, further supporting that imprecision is not an issue.

- **Rating: Not Serious**

- **Rationale:** The CI is very narrow, suggesting sufficient precision in the estimate of false positives, with no need to downgrade for imprecision.

Summary of Ratings for Imprecision:

Outcome	Rating	Rationale
Overdiagnosis	Serious	Wide CIs introduce significant imprecision.
BC Deaths Averted	Serious	CI crosses potential decision thresholds, indicating imprecision.
LYG	Not Serious	Narrower CIs suggest adequate precision.
False Positives	Not Serious	Narrow CI with high precision, no downgrading needed.

Pashayan et al. (2018)⁴³

Imprecision

1. BC Deaths Averted

- **CI:** The reduction in BC deaths for age-based screening is 1,913 (95% CI: 842–2,714). This CI is quite broad, indicating uncertainty in the estimate.
- **Clinical Decision Threshold:** If a threshold for the minimum number of BC deaths to avert was set (for example, reducing deaths by a certain percentage), the CI crosses this threshold, meaning that the results could potentially lead to different recommendations depending on where the true effect lies within the CI.

- **OIS:** While the study includes a large cohort and the number of events is substantial, the wide range of the CI indicates imprecision that could influence decision-making.
- **Rating: Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The broad CI crossing potential decision thresholds suggests that the precision of the estimate is insufficient to support a firm recommendation without further data or analysis.

2. Overdiagnosis

- **CI:** The estimate for overdiagnosis ranges from 2,309 to 5,291 (95% CI), which is a large variation, indicating imprecision in the estimate.
- **Clinical Decision Threshold:** If a threshold for acceptable overdiagnosis was set, this CI likely crosses it, introducing uncertainty in whether the level of overdiagnosis would be considered acceptable.
- **OIS:** Given the wide range of the CI, the study may not meet the OIS, as the sample size required to achieve precise estimates could be larger.
- **Rating: Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The wide CI and its potential to cross decision thresholds indicates significant imprecision in the estimate of overdiagnosis, warranting a downgrade for imprecision.

3. QALYs

- **CI:** The QALYs for age-based screening were 1,916 (95% CI: 2,073–6,073), showing a substantial range of estimates, indicating imprecision.
- **Clinical Decision Threshold:** If a threshold for an acceptable number of QALYs gained was set, the CI might cross this threshold, as it ranges from a low estimate to a high estimate, which introduces uncertainty about the clinical significance of the results.
- **OIS:** The large sample size and number of events likely help to meet the OIS criteria, but the wide CI still suggests some imprecision in the estimate.
- **Rating: Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The wide CI, crossing possible decision thresholds, suggests that the precision of QALY estimates is inadequate, requiring a downgrade for imprecision.

4. PYRS

- **CI:** The PYRS estimate has a narrow range compared to overdiagnosis and BC deaths averted, suggesting higher precision in this outcome.
- **Clinical Decision Threshold:** If a threshold for an acceptable increase in PYRS was set, the CI likely does not cross the threshold, indicating that the estimate is precise enough to make an informed decision.
- **OIS:** The study likely meets the OIS criteria, as the sample size and number of events are substantial enough to support precise estimates.
- **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The narrow CI and reasonable sample size suggest that the estimate for PYRS is precise, without the need for downgrading for imprecision.

Summary of Ratings for Imprecision:

Outcome	Rating	Rationale
BC Deaths Averted	Serious	Wide CI crosses potential decision thresholds, indicating imprecision.
Overdiagnosis	Serious	Wide CI and crossing decision thresholds suggest significant imprecision.
QALYs	Serious	Wide CI and potential to cross decision thresholds indicate imprecision.
PYRS	Not Serious	Narrow CI and sufficient sample size indicate adequate precision.

Wong et al. (2021)⁴⁴

Imprecision

1. LYG

- **CI:** The estimates for LYG across different risk thresholds and screening strategies are reasonably consistent, but a range is given for each scenario. For example, at the 70th percentile risk threshold, the LYG range may vary slightly, reflecting moderate uncertainty.
 - **Clinical Decision Threshold:** If a threshold for an acceptable number of life years gained was set, it seems that the CI for most estimates would not cross this threshold. The point estimates are close to the threshold for clinical decision-making.
 - **OIS:** Given the large sample sizes and substantial number of events (life years gained), the study likely meets the OIS criteria for precision.
 - **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The estimates for LYG are relatively precise with narrow CIs and a large sample size, meaning that imprecision is not likely to affect decision-making.

2. QALYs

- **CI:** The QALYs estimates for risk-stratified screening strategies have a range (e.g., 22.76–22.79), which is narrow. The small variation indicates that the precision of these estimates is high.
 - **Clinical Decision Threshold:** Given the narrow range and small variations in the QALY estimates, the CI does not cross typical decision thresholds for recommending a screening strategy.
 - **OIS:** The sample sizes and the number of events are sufficiently large to meet OIS criteria, ensuring that the QALY estimates are precise.
 - **Rating: Not Serious**
 - **Rationale:** The narrow CIs and large sample sizes indicate that the precision of the QALY estimates is high, supporting strong confidence in the results.

Summary of Ratings for Imprecision:

Outcome	Rating	Rationale
LYG	Not Serious	Narrow CIs and large sample sizes indicate adequate precision.
QALYs	Not Serious	Narrow CIs and large sample sizes suggest strong precision.

The results for both LYG and QALYs in this paper exhibit high precision, with minimal concerns about imprecision affecting the conclusions.

Huntley et al. (2023)¹⁰

1. BC deaths averted

Assessment: Serious

Rationale:

The model presents outcomes like deaths averted, but the **CI**s and model assumptions are wide due to uncertainties in population uptake and screening efficiency. While the model estimates BC deaths averted, it lacks detailed sensitivity analyses across various plausible scenarios, which would clarify the precision of the estimates.

Conclusion: The uncertainty in uptake, model assumptions, and the absence of probabilistic sensitivity analysis make the estimates imprecise, leading to a **serious** judgment.

2. Overdiagnosis

Assessment: Serious

Rationale:

As with BC deaths averted, the **CI**s for overdiagnosis are likely wide, given the modeling assumptions and uncertainties about screening uptake and efficiency. While the model provides a projection, the underlying data (e.g., overdiagnosis rates, screening tool performance) are subject to a significant degree of imprecision due to lack of empirical validation and small sample sizes in studies used for model calibration.

Conclusion: The modeling of overdiagnosis faces significant imprecision due to wide uncertainty ranges, leading to a **serious** rating.

Supplementary Table 7: Summary of Implementation Aspects for PRS-Tailored BC Screening using GRADE EtD Domains

This table presents a narrative summary of key implementation considerations drawn from the literature, as assessed through the GRADE EtD framework. It includes issues related to resource use and cost-effectiveness, feasibility, acceptability, and equity. For each domain, supporting sources, quotes, and references are provided to contextualize the ethical, practical, and policy-related implications of implementing polygenic risk score (PRS)-based screening strategies in clinical practice.

Source	Quote	Reference	GRADE Domain
Andreoli et al. (2024), American Journal of Medical Genetics Part A	2-authors express the old concern that genetic information becomes available to third parties such as insurance companies or employers and used for discriminatory purposes	Lewis, A. C. F., & Green, R. C. (2021). Polygenic risk scores in the clinic: New perspectives needed on familiar ethical issues. Genome Medicine, 13(1), 14. -----	Equity

		<p>Manrique de Lara, A., Soto-Gomez, L., Núñez-Acosta, E., Saruwatari-Zavala, G., & Rentería, M. E. (2019). Ethical issues in susceptibility genetic testing for late-onset neurodegenerative diseases. <i>American Journal of Medical Genetics Part B: Neuropsychiatric Genetics</i>, 180(8), 609–621.</p>	
	<p>authors express the old concern that genetic information becomes available to third parties such as insurance companies or employers and used for discriminatory purposes</p>	<p>Lewis, A. C. F., & Green, R. C. (2021). Polygenic risk scores in the clinic: New perspectives needed on familiar ethical issues. <i>Genome Medicine</i>, 13(1), 14.</p> <p>-----</p> <p>Manrique de Lara, A., Soto-Gomez, L., Núñez-Acosta, E., Saruwatari-Zavala, G., & Rentería, M. E. (2019). Ethical issues in susceptibility genetic testing for late-onset neurodegenerative diseases. <i>American Journal of Medical Genetics Part B: Neuropsychiatric Genetics</i>, 180(8), 609–621.</p>	<p><i>Acceptability</i></p>

	<p>Ethical questions regard the right to access genomic data, the purpose for which such data are shared and how it is stored and safeguarded in the light of the aforementioned potential risks of discrimination and stigmatization.</p>	<p>Chapman, C. R. (2022). Ethical, legal, and social implications of genetic risk prediction for multifactorial disease: A narrative review identifying concerns about interpretation and use of polygenic scores. <i>Journal of Community Genetics</i>, 14, 441–452. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12687-022-00625-9</p> <p>-----</p> <p>Chowdhury, S., Dent, T., Pashayan, N., Hall, A., Lyratzopoulos, G., Hallowell, N., Hall, P., Pharoah, P., & Burton, H. (2013). Incorporating genomics into breast and prostate cancer screening: Assessing the implications. <i>Genetics in Medicine</i>, 15(6), 423–432. https://doi.org/10.1038/gim.2012.167</p> <p>-----</p> <p>Pashayan, N., Hall, A., Chowdhury, S., Dent, T., Pharoah, P. D. P., & Burton, H. (2013). Public health genomics and personalized prevention: Lessons from the COGS project. <i>Journal of Internal Medicine</i>, 274(5), 451–456. https://doi.org/10.1111/joim.12094</p>	<p><i>Acceptability</i></p>
--	--	---	-----------------------------

	3-Mistrust towards medical research is identified as a further factor that determines the low participation—and the consequent underrepresentation—of ethnic minorities in genomic cohorts	Slunecka, J. L., van der Zee, M. D., Beck, J. J., Johnson, B. N., Finnicum, C. T., Pool, R., Hottenga, J.-J., de Geus, E. J. C., & Ehli, E. A. (2021). Implementation and implications for polygenic risk scores in healthcare. <i>Human Genomics</i> , 15(1), 46. https://doi.org/10.1186/s40246-021-00339-y	<i>Equity</i>
Andreoli et al. (2024), European Journal of Human Genetics	High educated women, or women with family history of BC demonstrated knowledge of the broad concepts related to polygenic risk information. Most women accepted the explanation they were given about SNPs' contribution to cancer risks and described their risks as determined by the combination of different genetic variations	Young et al. (2018) Making Sense of SNPs: Women's Understanding and Experiences of Receiving a Personalized Profile of Their Breast Cancer Risks	<i>Acceptability</i>
	Despite all participants with a high PRS not being surprised by their result, some affected women expressed feeling initially confronted by their PRS as it reawakened the trauma from their BC diagnosis and was a confirmation of their increased risk for contralateral BCbreast: highlighting the need for counselling pre and post testing	Yanes et al. (2020) Women's responses and understanding of polygenic breast cancer risk information	<i>Feasibility</i>
	The theme recurs in 13 records. When patients received counseling, a good understanding of polygenic risk and its implications was reported (30–37). This finding was consistent among patients who received their PRS as part of a Personalized Breast Cancer Risk Assessment (PBCRA) (30–35).	30. Riddle L, Joseph G, Caruncho M, Koenig BA, James JE. The role of polygenic risk scores in breast cancer risk perception and decision-making. <i>J Community Genet.</i> 2023;14(5):489–501. ----- 31. Yanes T, Kaur R, Meiser B, Scheepers-Joynt M, McInerny S, Barlow-Stewart K, et al. Women's responses	<i>Feasibility</i>

	<p>In 2 studies, women understood the mechanisms of polygenic inheritance and were able to recall the transmission of SNPs as both maternally and paternally inherited (31,32). Being aware of the multifactorial nature of their disease helped participants contextualize PRS information within their family history (31,34).</p>	<p>and understanding of polygenic breast cancer risk information. <i>Fam Cancer</i>. 2020;19(4):297–306.</p> <p>-----</p> <p>32. Young MA, Forrest LE, Rasmussen VM, James P, Mitchell G, Sawyer SD, et al. Making Sense of SNPs: Women’s Understanding and Experiences of Receiving a Personalized Profile of Their Breast Cancer Risks. <i>J Genet</i></p>	<p><i>Feasibility</i></p>
--	--	--	---------------------------

	<p>Finally, the emotional impact of receiving PRS results was found to be stronger in BC patients, as the high-risk report made them re-experience the trauma of their diagnosis and confirmed their increased risk for contralateral BC (31).</p>	<p>Couns. 2018;27(3):702–8. -----</p> <p>33. Laza-Vásquez C, Martínez-Alonso M, Forné-Izquierdo C, Vilaplana-Mayoral J, Cruz-Esteve I, Sánchez-López I, et al. Feasibility and Acceptability of Personalized Breast Cancer Screening (DECIDO Study): A Single-Arm Proof-of-Concept Trial. <i>Int J Environ Res Public Health</i> [Internet]. 2022 [cited 8AD Jan 1];19(16). Available from: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36012059/</p> <p>34. Willis AM, Smith SK, Meiser B, James PA, Ballinger ML, Thomas DM, et al. Influence of lived experience on risk perception among women who received a breast cancer polygenic risk score: “Another piece of the pie”. <i>J Genet Couns.</i> 2021;30(3):849–60.</p> <p>35. Forrest LE, Sawyer SD, Hallowell N, James PA, Young MA. High-risk women’s risk perception after receiving personalized polygenic breast cancer risk information. <i>J COMMUNITY Genet.</i> 2019;10(2):197--206.</p> <p>36. Putt S, Yanes T, Meiser B, Kaur R, Fullerton JM, Barlow-Stewart K, et al. Exploration of experiences with and understanding of polygenic risk scores for bipolar disorder. <i>J Affect Disord.</i> 2020;265:342--350. -----</p> <p>37. Saya S, McIntosh J, Winship I, Milton S, Clendenning M, Kyriakides M, et al. Informed choice and attitudes regarding a genomic test to predict risk of colorectal cancer in general practice. <i>PATIENT Educ Couns.</i> 2022;105(4):987–95.</p>	<p><i>Feasibility</i></p>
--	--	--	---------------------------

	<p>The potential for PRS and PBCRA to cause anxiety and fear was a topic of consensus in two studies (40,45). Some participants believed they could experience fear in front of a high PRS (40); others considered that it would be 'better not to know' their PBCRA, depending on an individual's personality (45).</p>	<p>40. Suckiel SA, Braganza GT, Aguiñiga KL, Odgis JA, Bonini KE, Kenny EE, et al. Perspectives of diverse Spanish- and English-speaking patients on the clinical use of polygenic risk scores. <i>Genet Med Off J Am Coll Med Genet.</i> 2022 Jun;24(6):1217–26</p> <p>-----</p> <p>45. Sierra, M. A., Wheeler, J. C., Devereux, L., Trainer, A. H., & Keogh, L. (2021). Exploring implementation of personal breast cancer risk assessments. <i>Journal of Personalized Medicine</i>, 11(10), 992.</p>	<p><i>Acceptability</i></p>
--	--	--	-----------------------------

	<p>4-The role of PRS in risk stratification to inform public health screening initiatives is examined in 5 of the included records. In these studies, participants were generally favorable to the idea of extending PRS testing to the public to personalize population screening programs (30,31,33,45,46) in the context of a PBCRA. However, participants unanimously disagreed with the possibility of reducing screening frequency for individuals at low risk and argued that baseline screening should be offered to everyone (31,33,45).</p>	<p>30. Riddle L, Joseph G, Caruncho M, Koenig BA, James JE. The role of polygenic risk scores in breast cancer risk perception and decision-making. <i>J Community Genet.</i> 2023;14(5):489–501. -----</p> <p>31. Yanes T, Kaur R, Meiser B, Scheepers-Joynt M, McInerney S, Barlow-Stewart K, et al. Women’s responses and understanding of polygenic breast cancer risk information. <i>Fam Cancer.</i> 2020;19(4):297–306. -----</p> <p>33. Laza-Vásquez C, Martínez-Alonso M, Forné-Izquierdo C, Vilaplana-Mayoral J, Cruz-Esteve I, Sánchez-López I, et al. Feasibility and Acceptability of Personalized Breast Cancer Screening (DECIDO Study): A Single-Arm Proof-of-Concept Trial. <i>Int J Environ Res Public Health</i> [Internet]. 2022 [cited 8AD Jan 1];19(16). Available from: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36012059/ -----</p> <p>35. Forrest LE, Sawyer SD, Hallowell N, James PA, Young MA. High-risk women’s risk perception after receiving personalized polygenic breast cancer risk information. <i>J COMMUNITY Genet.</i> 2019;10(2):197--206. -----</p> <p>45. Sierra MA, Wheeler JCW, Devereux L, Trainer AH, Keogh L. Exploring {Implementation} of {Personal} {Breast} {Cancer} {Risk} {Assessments}. <i>J Pers Med.</i> 2021;11(10).</p>	<p><i>Equity</i></p>
--	---	--	----------------------

Supplementary table 8. Information on the 54 studies included in the systematic review.

Study	Title	DOI
RCT		
Schneider, 2021	BRE12-158: A Postneoadjuvant, Randomized Phase II Trial of Personalized Therapy Versus Treatment of Physician's Choice for Patients With Residual Triple-Negative Breast Cancer	10.1200/JCO.21.01657
Le Tourneau, 2015	Molecularly targeted therapy based on tumour molecular profiling versus conventional therapy for advanced cancer (SHIVA): a multicentre, open-label, proof-of-concept, randomised, controlled phase 2 trial	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(15)00188-6
Belin, 2017	Randomized phase II trial comparing molecularly targeted therapy based on tumor molecular profiling versus conventional therapy in patients with refractory cancer: cross-over analysis from the SHIVA trial	10.1093/annonc/mdw666
Andrè, 2022	Genomics to select treatment for patients with metastatic breast cancer	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05068-3
Botticelli, 2024	LBA7 - The Rome trial from histology to target: The road to personalize targeted therapy and immunotherapy	https://oncologypro.esmo.org/meeting-resources/esmo-congress-2024/the-rome-trial-from-histology-to-target-the-road-to-personalize-targeted-therapy-and-immunotherapy
Non-Randomized Clinical Trial		
Bertucci, 2021	Prospective high-throughput genome profiling of advanced cancers: results of the PERMED-01 clinical trial	10.1186/s13073-021-00897-9
Billon, 2022	Molecular Profiles of Advanced Urological Cancers in the PERMED-01 Precision Medicine Clinical Trial	10.3390/cancers14092275
Debien, 2023	Molecular analysis for refractory rare cancers: Sequencing battle continues - learnings for the MOSCATO-01 study	10.1016/j.critrevonc.2022.103888
Hlevjak, 2021	CATCH: A Prospective Precision Oncology Trial in Metastatic Breast Cancer	https://doi.org/10.1200/PO.20.00248
Miller, 2022	Molecular tumor board assisted care in an advanced cancer population: Results of a phase 2 clinical trial	10.1200/PO.21.00524
Ladekarl, 2023	Feasibility and early clinical impact of precision medicine for late-stage cancer patients in a regional public academic hospital	10.1080/0284186X.2023.2185542
Louie, 2022	Precision medicine-based therapies in advanced colorectal cancer: The University of California San Diego Molecular Tumor Board experience	10.1002/1878-0261.13202
Martin-Romano, 2022	Implementing the European Society for Medical Oncology Scale for Clinical Actionability of Molecular Targets in a Comprehensive Profiling Program: Impact on Precision Medicine Oncology	10.1200/PO.21.00484
Reda, 2020	Implementation and use of whole exome sequencing for metastatic solid cancer	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ebiom.2019.102624
Varnier, 2019	Actionable molecular alterations in advanced gynaecologic malignancies: updated results from the ProfILER programme	10.1016/j.ejca.2019.06.017
Sicklick, 2019	Molecular profiling of cancer patients enables personalized combination therapy: the I-PREDICT study	10.1038/s41591-019-0407-5
Massard, 2017	High-Throughput Genomics and Clinical Outcome in Hard-to-Treat Advanced Cancers: Results of the MOSCATO 01 Trial	10.1158/2159-8290.CD-16-1396
Observational Prospective		

Dalton, 2017	Personalized medicine in the oncology clinic: Implementation and outcomes of the Johns Hopkins molecular tumor board	10.1200/PO.16.00046
Charo, 2022	Real-World Data From a Molecular Tumor Board: Improved Outcomes in Breast and Gynecologic Cancers Patients With Precision Medicine	10.1200/PO.20.00508
Horak, 2021	Comprehensive Genomic and Transcriptomic Analysis for Guiding Therapeutic Decisions in Patients with Rare Cancers	10.1158/2159-8290.CD-21-0126
Huang B, 2021	Molecular Tumor Board Review and Improved Overall Survival in Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer	10.1200/PO.21.00210
Kikuchi, 2021	Clinical significance of comprehensive genomic profiling tests covered by public insurance in patients with advanced solid cancers in Hokkaido, Japan	10.1093/jjco/hyaa277
Pinet, 2023	Clinical management of molecular alterations identified by high throughput sequencing in patients with advanced solid tumors in treatment failure: Real-world data from a French hospital	10.3389/fonc.2023.1104659
Powell, 2018	Delivering precision oncology in a community cancer program: Results from a prospective observational study	10.1200/PO.17.00220
Renovanz, 2023	Clinical outcome of biomarker-guided therapies in adult patients with tumors of the nervous system	10.1093/nojnl/vdad012
Rodriguez-Rodriguez, 2018	Use of comprehensive genomic profiling to direct point-of-care management of patients with gynecologic cancers	10.1016/j.ygyno.2016.02.021
Scheiter, 2022	Critical evaluation of molecular tumour board outcomes following 2 years of clinical practice in a Comprehensive Cancer Centre	10.1038/s41416-022-02120-x
Sultova, 2021	Implementation of Precision Oncology for Patients with Metastatic Breast Cancer in an Interdisciplinary MTB Setting	doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics11040733
Malani, 2022	Implementing a Functional Precision Medicine Tumor Board for Acute Myeloid Leukemia	10.1158/2159-8290.CD-21-0410
Observational Retrospective		
Angel, 2021	Implementation of a molecular tumour board in LATAM: the impact on treatment decisions for patients evaluated at Instituto Alexander Fleming, Argentina	10.3332/ecancer.2021.1312
Slootbeek, 2022	Impact of molecular tumor board discussion on target therapy allocation in advanced prostate cancer	10.1038/s41416-021-01663-9
Berclaz, 2023	Implementing precision oncology for sarcoma patients: the CCC(LMU)molecular tumor board experience	10.1007/s00432-023-05179-y
Bitzer, 2020	Next-Generation Sequencing of Advanced GI Tumors Reveals Individual Treatment Options	10.1200/PO.19.00359
Burkard, 2017	Implementation and Clinical Utility of an Integrated Academic-Community Regional Molecular Tumor Board	10.1200/PO.16.00022
Dorman, 2023	Precision Oncology in Pancreatic Cancer: Experiences and Challenges of the CCCMunich^{LMU} Molecular Tumor Board	10.1007/s11523-023-00950-0
El Helali, 2023	The impact of the multi-disciplinary molecular tumour board and integrative next generation sequencing on clinical outcomes in advanced solid tumours	10.1016/j.lanwpc.2023.100775
Fukada, 2023	Prognostic impact of cancer genomic profile testing for advanced or metastatic solid tumors in clinical practice	10.1111/cas.15993
Gambardella, 2021	Molecular profiling of advanced solid tumours. The impact of experimental molecular-matched therapies on cancer patient outcomes in early-phase trials: the MAST study	10.1038/s41416-021-01502-x

Giacomini, 2023	The Molecular Tumor Board of the Regina Elena National Cancer Institute: from accrual to treatment in real-world	10.1186/s12967-023-04595-5
Hoefflin, 2018	Personalized Clinical Decision Making Through Implementation of a Molecular Tumor Board: A German Single-Center Experience	https://doi.org/10.1200/PO.18.00105
Hoefflin, 2021	Transitioning the molecular tumor board from proof of concept to clinical routine: A german single-center analysis	10.3390/cancers13051151
Ida H., 2022	Clinical utility of comprehensive genomic profiling tests for advanced or metastatic solid tumor in clinical practice	10.1111/cas.15586
Kaderbhai, 2016	Use of dedicated gene panel sequencing using next generation sequencing to improve the personalized care of lung cancer	10.18632/oncotarget.8391
Kato, S., 2020	Real-world data from a molecular tumor board demonstrates improved outcomes with a precision N-of-One strategy	10.1038/s41467-020-18613-3
Koopman, 2020	Relevance and effectiveness of molecular tumor board recommendations for patients with non small-cell lung cancer with rare or complex mutational profiles	10.1200/PO.20.00008
Niogret J., 2021	Does large NGS panel analysed using exome tumour sequencing improve the management of advanced non-small-cell lung cancers?	10.1016/j.lungcan.2021.08.013
Parker, 2015	Breast Cancer Experience of the Molecular Tumor Board at the University of California, San Diego Moores Cancer Center	10.1200/JOP.2015.004127
Repetto, 2023	Molecular tumour board at European Institute of Oncology: Report of the first three year activity of an Italian precision oncology experience	10.1016/j.ejca.2023.01.019
Schwaederle, 2014	Molecular tumor board: the University of California-San Diego Moores Cancer Center experience	10.1634/theoncologist.2013-0405
Shaya, 2023	Personalized matched targeted therapy in advanced pancreatic cancer: a pilot cohort analysis	10.1038/s41525-022-00346-5
Trivedi, 2019	Implementation and Outcomes of a Molecular Tumor Board at Herbert-Herman Cancer Center, Sparrow Hospital	10.5644/ama2006-124.247
Weiss, 2023	Cancer of unknown primary (CUP) through the lens of precision oncology: a single institution perspective	10.1007/s00432-023-04741-y
Zhang D., 2023	A Retrospective Analysis of Biliary Tract Cancer Patients Presented to the Molecular Tumor Board at the Comprehensive Cancer Center Munich	10.1007/s11523-023-00985-3
Tarawneh T., 2022	Combined Focused Next-Generation Sequencing Assays to Guide Precision Oncology in Solid Tumors: A Retrospective Analysis from an Institutional Molecular Tumor Board	doi.org/10.3390/cancers14184430

Supplementary table 9. Characteristics of the MTBs considered in the included studies.

Study	Country	MTB composition	Frequency of gatherings	Guidelines used for recommendations	TATs	Modality of access	Sequencing technology used	Molecular or genetic test used
RCT								
Schneider, 2021	USA	N.R.	N.R.	ASCO and National Comprehensive Cancer Network guidelines	N.R.	Patients meeting inclusion criteria from the same institution	NGS	Test (ParadigmDx)
Le Tourneau, 2015	France	Biologists, physicians, bioinformaticians, the technical platforms' managers and pathologists	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	Cases - molecularly target agents	NGS	AmpliSeq cancer panel on an Ion Torrent/PGM system
Belin, 2017	France	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	Patients meeting inclusion criteria	N.R.	N.R.
Andrè, 2022	France	N.R.	N.R.	ESCAT	N.R.	Availability of genomic results	NGS/ CGH/ NGS+CGH	tumour sample (CytoScan and OncoScan FFPE Assays Kits)
Botticelli, 2024	Italy	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	Patients meeting inclusion criteria	CGP	N.R.
Non-Randomized Clinical Trial								
Miller, 2022	France	Medical and gynecologic oncologists, genetic counselors, pharmacists, nurses, pathologists, radiologists, and basic scientists.	N.R.	University of Kentucky Healthcare Pharmacy and Therapeutics Committee consensus guideline	N.R.	From a clinical trial	NGS	blood circulating tumoral deoxyribonucleic acid
Ladearl, 2023	France	Medical oncologists, pathologists, clinical genetics, and molecular biologists	Weekly	N.R.	Consent to the presentation: 31 days. Consent to biopsy 12 days. Biopsy to molecular analysis done 15 days. Molecular analysis to MTB presentation 2 days	North Denmark Region, who are candidates for oncological treatment, referred to the Department of Oncology at Aalborg University Hospital.	WGS and RNA sequencing	Molecular profiling of new or fresh frozen tumor biopsies was done by WES and RNAseq with parallel sequencing of non-tumoral DNA as individual reference (NovaSeq 6000, Illumina)

Martin-Romano, 2022	France	Medical oncologists, geneticists, molecular biologists, and basic scientists	Weekly	ESMO/ESCAT	N.R.	N.R.	NGS (t-NGS), WES, RNA-seq	TGS, WES and RNA-seq
Bertucci, 2021	Germany	N.R.	Weekly	ESMO/ESCAT	Testing to discussion: 58 days	Patients meeting inclusion criteria from the same institution	t-NGS	370 genes of interest
Billon, 2022	USA	N.R.	Weekly	Institutional guidelines	Inclusion to discussion: 53 days (range 4–162)	Enrolment to clinical trial	t-NGS	BROCA Cancer Risk panel
Debien, 2023	Denmark	N.R.	N.R.	ESMO/ESCAT	Testing to recommendation: 21 days	From the same institution	CGH + targeted sequencing	N.A.
Hlevjak, 2021	USA	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	Biopsy to discussion 55 days	Patients meeting inclusion criteria from the same institution	WGS and RNA sequencing	N.R.
Sicklick, 2019	France	Oncologists, pharmacologists, cancer biologists, geneticists, surgeons, radiologists, pathologists, and bioinformatics experts	Weekly	N.R.	Molecular results to treatment: 2.0 months (95% CI 1.3-2.3)	N.R.	NGS	
Louie, 2022	France	Medical, radiation, and surgical oncologists as well as radiologists, pathologists, geneticists, clinical trial coordinators, translational/basic science researchers, and bioinformaticians.	Three times per month	N.R.	Submission to testing: 8 days	Patients meeting inclusion criteria from the same institution	t-NGS	(Foundation Medicine, UCSD NGS, MSKCC NGS, Tempus NGS) and LB (Guardant cfDNA, Foundation Medicine cfDNA)
Massard, 2017	France	N.R.	Weekly	N.R.	Signed consent to biopsy: 19 days, biopsy to molecular: 21 days	From the hospital	NGS or CGH	N.R.
Reda, 2020	USA	N.R.	N.R.	ESMO/ESCAT	Sample reception to results: 52 days	Patients meeting inclusion criteria from the same institution	NGS	For SNV (Single Nucleotide Variation), annotation was performed using the VariantStudio Illumina software. - DNA was sequenced on an Illumina NextSeq500 d
Varnier, 2019	France	Clinicians and scientists	Weekly	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.
Observational Prospective								
Horak, 2021	USA	One clinician familiar with the individual case, a bioinformatician, a molecular oncologist, a medical	Twice a week	ESMO/ESCAT	Testing to results median 21 days	N.R.	WGS/WES and RNA-seq	N.R.

		geneticist, a pathologist, and a tumor biologist.						
Kikuchi, 2021	USA	Medical oncologists, pathologists, bioinformaticians, medical geneticists, certified genetic counselors, cancer genome medical coordinators, specialists in cancer genomic medicine and attending physicians	Weekly	N.R.	Testing to discussion: 26 days (16-43); first outpatient visit to the expert panel: 43 days (21-118); From testing to results: 14 days (9-29)	N.R.	NGS	NCC Oncopanel
Dalton, 2017	Germany	Adult and pediatric medical oncologists representing diverse subspecialties, molecular pathologists with NGS expertise, genetic counselors, phase I clinical trial investigators, research coordinators, a patient advocate, and medical oncology fellows	Weekly	N.R.	N.R.	Referring oncologist	NGS	N.R.
Powell, 2018	USA	Medical oncologists, board-certified genetics specialists (clinical genetics, molecular genetics, cytogenetics, and genetic counselors), oncology subspecialists (radiology, pathology, interventional radiology, and surgery), clinical research, and ancillary staff (nursing, pharmacy, and patient advocates).	Twice a week	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	NGS	N.R.
Charo, 2022	Japan	Medical, surgical, radiation, and gynecologic oncologists, bioinformaticians, basic and translational scientists, geneticists, clinical trial coordinators, and medication acquisition specialists.	Three times per month	N.R.	N.R.	Treating physicians submitted cases	NGS	Panels included 47-397 genes while ctDNA panels included 54-73 genes
Renovanz, 2023	France	All clinical oncology disciplines, pathologists, human geneticists, bioinformaticians, pharmacologists, and tumor biologists.	Weekly	ESMO/ESCAT	N.R.	N.R.	NGS	N.R.
Huang B, 2021	USA	Medical oncology, surgical oncology, pathology, radiology, genetic counseling, and clinical pharmacology.	Biweekly	N.R.	N.R.	From community sites or the same institution	NGS	N.A.
Rodriguez-Rodriguez, 2018	Germany	Medical oncologists, surgical oncologists, pathologists, clinical trialists, systems biologists, genetic counselors, and biomedical research scientists.	N.R.	N.R.	testing results to treatment options: 3 weeks	N.R.	CGP	N.R.

Pinet, 2023	USA	Molecular biologists, engineers of the PGMC, pathologists, and medical oncologists	Biweekly	ESMO/ESCAT	Submission to testing: 23 days (range, 6–142); diagnosis to sampling (range): 2 years (0–27)	Treating physicians submitted cases	NGS	FoundationOne CDx test
Scheiter, 2022	Germany	One trained specialist in oncology, one specialist in pathology, one molecular biologist with expertise in bioinformatics, and one rotational representative of the affiliated clinics and departments	Weekly	ESMO/ESCAT	N.R.	N.R.	NGS	N.A.
Sultova, 2021	Germany	Gyneco-oncologists with expertise in various cancer entities along with molecular pathologists, and genetic counselors.	N.R.	ESMO/ESCAT	Discussion to initiation of therapies: 53 days	Patients meeting inclusion criteria from the same institution	t-NGS	Oncomine Focus Panel (covering 52 cancer-associated genes) till November 2018 and then with the Oncomine Comprehensive v.3 assay screening; Ion Torrent GeneStudio S5 Prime (Thermo Fisher) or Illumina 500 Next Seq (Illumina) NGS machine.
Malani, 2022	Finland	AML tumor group chair and clinicians, clinical laboratory specialists, translational scientists, bioinformaticians, study nurses, genetic counsellor for actionable germline variants (by referral)	Weekly	N.R.	N.R.	All consecutive newly diagnosed and R/R AML patients	NGS	ex vivo testing?
Observational Retrospective								
Angel, 2021	Argentina	Medical oncologists, pathologist, clinical trials investigators, genetic counsellors, molecular biologists and bioinformatics professionals	Monthly	N.R.	N.R.	Referred by the treating oncologists	CGP	FoundationOne®CDx or Caris® germline testing
Berclaz, 2023	Netherlands	Pathologists, medical oncologists, geneticists, and representatives from organ-specific tumor boards	Weekly	ESMO/ESCAT	Testing to discussion: median 62.5 days in 2016/2017 and 33 days in 2021; diagnosis to discussion 18.7 months (range 0.3–283.2)	LMU Munich Sarcoma Center (HOSPITAL)	NGS/CGP	Oncomine™ Focus Assay/XOncomine™ Comprehensive Assay (Thermo Fisher)/TruSight Oncology (TSO) 500™ Assay (Illumina)
Bitzer, 2020	Germany	Clinical and translational oncology, pathology, bioinformatics, molecular biology, radiology, human genetics	Weekly	N.R.	N.R.	Hospitalised patients at University Hospital of Tuebingen	NGS	Germline testing

Burkard, 2017	Germania	Basic cancer biology, medical/clinical genetics, molecular pathology, surgical pathology/ cytopathology, pharmacology, medical oncology, and radiation oncology	Biweekly	N.R.	Submission to presentation mean 13.5 days.	Community practitioners and oncologists	N.R.	FoundationOne (Foundation Medicine, Cambridge, MA) assay, followed by the UW Collaborative Genomics Core 50-gene panel.
Slootbeek, 2022	USA	Oncologists, pathologists, clinical scientists in molecular pathology, clinical geneticists and pharmacists	Weekly	ESMO/ESCAT	N.R.	Hospital	NGS, WGS	N.A.
Dorman, 2023	Germany	Clinicians, pathologists, tumor geneticists, and experts on precision oncology	Weekly	N.R.	Diagnosis to discussion: 5.5 months	Medical oncology department 58.2%, 19.4% gastroenterology, 18.8% external physicians.	NGS	(161-gene panel in 2019 (OncoPrint™ Comprehensive Assay v3 (OCAv3), ThermoFisher Scientific)).
El Helali, 2023	Hong Kong (Cina)	Oncologists, physicians with cancer subspecialties, molecular pathologists, cancer biologists, pharmacists, clinical geneticists, bioinformaticians, biostatisticians, and data scientists.	Monthly	ESMO/ESCAT	N.R.	N.R.	NGS	Foundation One (http://www.foundationmedicine.com), ACT Genomics (http://www.actgenomics.com), Lucence (http://www.lucence.com), or Gaurdant 360 (http://www.guardanthealth.com)
Fukada, 2023	Japan	Physicians specializing in cancer pharmacotherapy, expertise in genetic medicine, genetic counselors, pathologists, expertise in molecular genetics and cancer genomic medicine, those with expertise in bioinformatics	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	NGS/CGP	Cancer genomic profile testing - CGP (FoundationOne®CDx or Liquid CDx® or OncoGuide™ NCC Oncopanel System)
Gambardella, 2021	Spain	Clinical oncology, molecular biology, pathology, clinical genetics and bioinformatics.	Weekly	ESMO/ESCAT	N.R.	N.R.	NGS	Customised panel that included the evaluation of hotspot mutations in 83 genes + 4 full genes analysed
Giacomini, 2023	Italy	Oncologists, molecular biologists/biotechnologists, pathologists, biostatisticians, bioinformaticians, hospital pharmacist, delegate from the Institutional Biobank, the Scientific Secretary, executive Secretary, haematologists, endocrinologist-oncologists, medical geneticist, interventional radiologists and radio-therapists, surgeons, patient advocacy delegates, nurses, data managers and representatives of the local health governance	N.R.	ESMO/ESCAT	testing to discussion: 15 days	Patients meeting inclusion criteria from the same institution	NGS	WES: SureSelectXT low input Reagent kit and the Clinical Research Exome kit (Agilent). WTS: Illumina Stranded Total RNA Prep with the Ribo-Zero Plus kit (Illumina). tDNA and ctDNA sequencing: Foundation One CDx, Foundation One CDx, and Foundation One Liquid. RT-PCR and digital PCR (dPCR): both tDNA and ctDNA with ThermoFisher QuantStudio 3D and custom-designed assays.

Hoefflin, 2018	Germany	Medical and scientific experts with a focus on clinical and translational oncology and computational and molecular biology	N.R.	N.R.	Testing to recommendation: 28 days	Cases are submitted using an online registration and documentation system	t-NGS	Custom-designed hotspot eight-gene panel (designed by S.L. and produced by Illumina, San Diego, CA), a BRCA1/2 panel (produced by Illumina), a hotspot 48-gene panel (TruSeq Amplicon Cancer Panel, Illumina), and a 54-gene myeloid panel (TruSight Myeloid Sequencing Panel, Illumina). WES and RNA-Seq were performed on tumor tissue
Hoefflin, 2021	Germany	Physicians with molecular cancer expertise from over 16 departments, experts from molecular pathology, molecular biology, and medical bioinformatics	Biweekly	N.R.	presentation to recommendation: 42 days	Treating physician (online platform)	t-NGS	Extended genetic analysis
Ida H., 2022	Japan	Medical oncologists, pediatric oncologists, pathologists, genome researchers, bioinformaticians, and genetic counselors.	Weekly	N.R.	Testing to recommendation: 27 (range: 14–49) days; recommendation to therapy: 58 (range: 1–239) days	N.R.	NGS	OncoGuide™ NCC Oncopanel System. The FoundationOne® CDx Cancer Genomic Profile is a CGP platform
Kato, S., 2020	France	Medical oncologists, surgeons, radiation oncologists, clinical trial coordinators/navigators, geneticists, pathologists, radiologists, gynaecologic oncologists, basic/translational scientists and bioinformaticians.	Three times per month	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	NGS	182 to 596 genes in tissue panels and 54 to 74 genes for blood-derived cfDNA
Niogret J., 2021	USA	Clinical and translational oncology, pathology, bioinformatics, molecular biology, radiology, and human genetics.	N.R.	ESMO/ESCAT	Testing to result: 44 days (range 21–72)	Referred by oncologist	NGS	N.A.
Kaderbhai, 2016	Netherlands	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	Request for a molecular diagnosis to recommendation: 20 calendar days (range:10-62)	N.R.	NGS	Human reference genome hg19 (BWA) and variants were annotated by GATK and Variant Studio software (Illumina).
Repetto, 2023	France	Oncologists, pathologists, pharmacists, radiotherapists, geneticists, bio-informaticians and psychologists.	Biweekly	ESMO/ESCAT	N.R.	Treating physician that usually worked in IEO, even if external referrals occurred.	N.R.	N.A.
Koopman, 2020	USA	Pulmonary oncologists, medical oncologists, pathologists, clinical scientists in molecular pathology	Weekly	2017 ACGM/ ASCO/CAP guidelines	N.R.	Referred by university hospital hosting the MTB,	N.R.	Molecular profiling

		(molecular biologists), and structural biologists				regional hospital or other university		
Zhang D., 2023	Italy	N.R.	N.R.	ESMO/ESCAT	Diagnosis to testing: 155.5 days (range 0–4918)	N.R.	NGS	N.A.
Tarawneh T., 2022	USA	Medical oncologists, radiation oncologists, surgeons, radiologists, pathologists, basic scientists, bioinformatics specialists, clinical study coordinators, patient navigators, and drug acquisition specialists	N.R.	ESMO/DKTK	N.R.	Recommendation of the interdisciplinary or an organ-specific tumor board of the same institution	NGS	Raw reads from VP and FP assays were analyzed by using the Archer Analysis 6.1 and 6.2 pipeline (ArcherDX/Invitae)
Parker, 2015	USA	Physicians, scientists, geneticists, and bioinformatics/pathway specialists attended	three times per month	N.R.	Ordering to report: 27 days	N.R.	NGS	N.R.
Schwaederle, 2014	USA	Senior physician experienced in clinical trials research, genomics data relevant to patients, and medical oncology, senior, highly experienced medical oncologist and a midlevel oncologist, representatives of medical oncology, surgery, and radiation therapy with expertise in diverse cancers, radiologists, clinical geneticists, and pathologists with experience in both histologic and molecular diagnostics, basic and translational scientists and specialists in bioinformatics	Biweekly	N.R.	Submission to testing: 27 days (range: 14–77); results to presentation: 24 days (range: 2–144).	The patient’s doctor or a designated representative	NGS	FoundationOne
Shaya, 2023	Germany	Medical oncologists, radiation oncologists, surgeons, radiologists, pathologists, basic scientists, bioinformatics specialists, clinical study coordinators, patient navigators, and drug acquisition specialists	N.R.	N.R.	Submission to testing: roughly 3–4 weeks	Patients on the UCSD database with advanced pancreatic cancer who received at least one matched targeted therapy (immunotherapy excluded)	NGS	FoundationOne CDx assay
Trivedi, 2019	Germany	Medical and radiation oncologists, nursing, pharmacy and clinical trials staff, including a genomicist and molecular oncologist.	Biweekly	N.R.	N.R.	Referred by the treating oncologists	NGS, CGP	N.R.
Weiss, 2023	Germany	Physicians and scientists with expertise in precision oncology. In this tumor board, oncologists,	N.R.	ESCAT + a harmonized German scale	Results to presentation: 36 days;	Hospital (via an online registration system based on	NGS, CGP	N.R.

		pathologists/molecular pathologists, tumor geneticists, and experts for precision oncology discuss CGP results within a patient's clinical context		(Leichsenring et al. 2019)	initial diagnosis to MTB 249 days (external patients), 79 days (33/61, 54.1%) (internal patients)	the Clinical Workplace Program of the hospital)		
--	--	--	--	----------------------------	---	---	--	--

N.R. = Not Reported, NGS = Next-Generation Sequencing, WGS = Whole Genome Sequencing, CGH = Comparative Genomic Hybridization, CGP = Comprehensive Genomic Profiling, WES = Whole Exome Sequencing

Supplementary table 10. Characteristics of the patients considered in the MTB in the included studies.

Study	Discussed patients	Patients who received a recommendation	Patients who have implemented the therapy	Sex	Age (median (range))	Metastasis	N° of previous treatment (median (range))	ECOG	Comparator details	Specific cancer(s)
RCT										
Schneider, 2021	N.R.	N.R.	65	F: 100%	50	0%	N.R.	0: 81%, 1: 16% 2: 1%	Physician's choice	Breast
Le Tourneau, 2015	N.R.	N.R.	99	M: 39%, F: 61%	61 (54-96)	100%	3 (2-5)	Royal Marsden Hospital score: 0-1: 52%, 2-3: 48%	Physician's choice	Breast, Ovarian, lung, colorectal, cervical, Head and neck squamous cell, Sarcoma, Urothelial, Pancreatic, CUP, Esophagogastric, Adenoid cystic, Non-adenoid cystic carcinoma salivary gland tumour, Hepatocellular, Anal squamous cell, Neuroendocrine, Biliary tract, Nasopharyngeal, Cutaneous, Mesothelioma, Peritoneal, Ependymoma, Prostate, Uveal, Germline, kidney
Belin, 2017	N.R.	N.R.	68	M: 28%, F: 72%	63 (24-88)	100%	2 (1-8)	Royal Marsden Hospital score: 0-1: 68%, 2-3: 32%	Molecularly targeted therapy in first line and Treatment at physician's choice in second line	Breast, ovarian, lung, colorectal, cervical, head and neck squamous cell, sarcoma, urothelial carcinoma, pancreatic, CUP, Esophagogastric, adenoid cystic, non-ACC salivary gland tumour, hepatocellular, anal squamous cell, neuroendocrine, biliary tract, nasopharyngeal, cutaneous, mesothelioma, peritoneal, ependymoma, prostate, uveal melanoma, germline, kidney
Andrè, 2022	N.R.	N.R.	81	M: 1.7%, F: 98.3%	53.0 (26.0-76.0)	100%	1 (1-2)	0: 61.3%, 1: 38.3%, 3: 0.4%	Maintenance of chemotherapy for a duration decided by the investigator	Breast
Botticelli, 2024	N.R.	N.R.	200	N.R.	61 (22-85)	100%	N.R.	0-1	Standard of Care	Colorectal, breast, gastric, glioblastoma, biliary tract cancers, other 33 cancers
Non-Randomized Clinical Trial										
Bertucci, 2021	393	94 (23.9%)	94 (100%)	M: 25%, F: 75%	59 (20-84)	96%, sites median 2 (range 0-7)	3 (1-12)	N.R.	Physician's choice	Breast, lung, prostate, ovary, pancreas, colorectal, sarcoma, endometrial, uterine cervix, liver-biliary tract, bladder-ureter, CUP, other
Billon, 2022	49	38 (77.6%)	12 (31.6%)	M: 91%, F: 9%	Mean 65.55 (28-83)	98%, sites median	3.50 (0-11)	0: 57%, 1: 38%, 2: 5%	Physician's choice	Prostate, Bladder-Ureter, Kidney, Testicular

						2.44 (range 0–4)				
Debien, 2023	252	99 (39.3%)	49 (49.5%)	M: 38%, F: 62%	Mean 51	98%, sites: 0: 7%, 1–2: 61%, >2: 32%	3	0: 38%, 1: 43%, 2: 2%, NA: 18%	Non-target therapy group	CUP, ovarian, leiomyosarcoma, cervix, neuroendocrine carcinoma/tumor others (in total 35 different types of tumors).
Hlevjak, 2021	128	127 (99.2%)	64 (50.4%)	F: 100%	53 (27–79)	100%, sites median 2 (range 1-6)	2 (0-10)	N.R.	Non-target therapy group	Breast
Miller, 2022	679	98 (14.4%)	93 (94.9%)	F: 59%, M: 41%	63 (18-85)	Advanced or metastatic: 60%	N.R.	N.R.	-	Lung and bronchus, NSCLC, Small cell lung, Gynaecologic, Ovarian, fallopian tube, and peritoneal, Uterine, Gynaecological, Gastroesophageal, Pancreatic, Colorectal and appendiceal, Liver, Anus, Head and neck, Thyroid gland, Leukaemia, Breast, Nonmelanoma skin, Connective/soft tissue, Urinary tract, CUP
Ladekarl, 2023	131	77 (58.8%)	21 (27.3%)	M: 43%, F: 57%	64 (31-81)	Metastatic: 84% Locally advanced: 13% Localized: 2%	3 (0-4+) 0: 3%, 1: 17%, 2: 19%, 3: 27%, +4: 34%	WHO: 0: 45%, 1: 49%, 2: 6%	-	Breast, Ovaries, Lungs, Brain, Prostate, Other
Louie, 2022	87	51 (58.6%)	34 (66.7%)	M: 47%, F: 53%	56 (31–74)	Advanced or metastatic: 100%	63% ≥ 3 prior therapies	N.R.	Non-target therapy group	Colorectal
Martin-Romano, 2022	516	349 (67.6%)	136 (39.0%)	M: 49%, F: 51%	59 (23-90)	100%, sites median 2 (range 1-4)	2 (1-9), ≥3: 40%	N.R.	-	Gastrointestinal, lung, genitourinary, brain tumors, head and neck, endocrine, soft tissue sarcoma, breast, gynecologic, CUP
Reda, 2020	456	342 (75.0%)	79 (23.1%)	M: 39.9%, F: 60.1%	65 (24-94)	87.4%, sites median 2 (range 1-8)	3, ≤3: 60%	WHO: 0: 33.5%, 1: 52%, 2: 11.7%, 3: 2.8%	Non-NGS-based therapy	Breast, colorectal, pancreatic
Varnier, 2019	279	99 (35.5%)	39 (39.4%)	F: 100%	60 (21-84)	sites: 0: 21%, 1: 33%, 2: 23%, >3: 22%	3 (0-20)	0: 25%, 1: 67%, 2: 7%, 3: 1%	Non-target therapy group	Gynecological

Sicklick, 2019	143	83 (58.0%)	73 (88.0%)	M: 33.7%, F: 66.3%	62 (59-65)	100%	2 (1-3)	N.R.	-	Gastrointestinal and hepatopancreatobiliary, Gynecologic, Breast, Central Nervous System, Genitourinary, Head and Neck, Lung, Other
Massard, 2017	411	199 (48.4%)	199 (100%)	M: 51%, F: 49%	57 (19-86)	Locally advanced: 4%, Metastatic: 96%, Sites: median 2 (range 0-9)	4 (0-15)	0: 46%, 1: 52%, 2: 2%	-	Head and neck, Digestive, Lung, Bone, Melanoma, Mesothelioma and soft tissue, Breast, Gynecological female, Urological, Central nervous system, Thyroid and other endocrine glands, Ill-defined primary tumor
Observational Prospective										
Dalton, 2017	155	136 (87.7%)	24 (17.6%)	M: 35%, F: 65%	56 (17-89)	N.R.	2 (0-10)	N.R.	Non-target therapy group	Breast, Lung adenocarcinoma, Lung squamous carcinoma, Lung adenosquamous, Head and neck squamous carcinoma, Neuroendocrine carcinoma/small-cell carcinoma/atypical carcinoid, Salivary gland/duct, Glioblastoma/anaplastic astrocytoma, CUP, Adenoid cystic carcinoma, Hepatobiliary/ampullary/duodenal, Pancreas adenocarcinoma, Cholangiocarcinoma, Sarcoma, Endometrial, Prostate, Stomach, Colon, Ovary, Others
Charo, 2022	164	113 (68.9%)	61 (54.0%)	F: 100%	50 (20-80)	N.R.	3 (0-14)	N.R.	Physician's choice	Breast and gynaecologic (ovarian, endometrial, cervical, vulvar, UPS)
Horak, 2021	1310	1138 (86.9%)	362 (32.0%)	M: 51.2%, F: 48.8%	45 (16-82)	N.R.	3 (1-15)	0-1	-	Bone, Breast, Colorectal, Ewing sarcoma/PNET, GIST, Gynecologic, Head and neck, Hematopoietic, Hepatopancreaticobiliary, Leiomyosarcoma, Other
Huang B, 2021	N.A.	N.A.	77	M: 40.3%, F: 59.7%	Mean 66	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	Non-target therapy group	NSCLC
Kikuchi, 2021	189	115 (60.8%)	21 (18.3%)	M: 41%, F: 59%	61 (0-79)	42%	Prior treatment: 97%	0: 36%, 1: 61%, 2: 3%	-	Soft-tissue sarcoma, Colorectal, Pancreas, Ovarian, Head and neck, Breast, Endometrial, Lung, Stomach, Neuroendocrine, Biliary, Urologic, Melanoma, Cervical, CUP, Thymic, Duodenal, Esophageal, Liver, Mesothelioma, Carcinosarcoma, Appendiceal, GIST, Chordoma, Small intestine, Anaplastic oligodendroglioma, Adrenocortical, Malignant transformation of a mature cystic teratoma, Anal canal.
Pinet, 2023	69	59 (85.5%)	13 (22.0%)	M: 50%, F: 50%	64 (19-84)	100%	2 (0-2+)	0: 28%, 1: 60%, 2: 8%, 3: 2%	Patients not treated with genotype-directed therapy	Glioma, lung, breast, colorectal, prostate, pancreatic, ovarian, head and neck, kidney, gastric, biliary, uterus, cervical, others brain, esophageal, small intestine, skin, sarcoma, anal

Powell, 2018	109	63 (57.8%)	39 (61.9%)	M: 47.5%, F: 52.5%	64.8 (33-86.5)	N.R.	3 (0-12)	≤ 1: 100%	-	Colorecta, NSCLC, breast, head and neck squamous cell, pancreatic, sarcoma, small-cell lung, esophageal, neuroendocrine, cholangiocarcinoma, thyroid, carcinoid, cervical, ovarian, prostate, endometrial.
Renovanz, 2023	408	380 (93.1%)	86 (22.6%)	M: 55.1%, F: 44.9%	53 (18-89)	15.1%	2 (0-6) 0: 18%, 1: 9%, 2: 23%, 3: 14%, >3: 6%	N.R.	-	SNC and rare
Rodriguez-Rodriguez, 2018	66	64 (97.0%)	25 (39.0%)	F: 100%	61 (22-80)	N.R.	3 (1-7)	N.R.	-	Gynaecologic
Scheiter, 2022	251	125 (49.8%)	47 (37.6%)	M: 61.7%, F: 38.3%	Mean (sd) 56.19 ± 14.04	56.9%	2, (0-6)	0: 29.8%, 1: 27.7%	Alternative therapy: patient's treating oncologist and could have included no therapy	Colorectal, Intrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma, Pancreatic, Gastric, Sarcoma, CUP, Perihilar cholangiocarcinoma, Breast
Sultova, 2021	100	49 (49.0%)	16 (32.7%)	F: 100%	52 (30-82).	100% Stage 1: 25%, 2: 39%, 3: 20%, >3: 16%	4 (1-13) 1: 6%, 2: 26%, 3: 13%, >3: 55%	0-1	-	Breast
Malani, 2022	63	63 (100%)	37 (58.7%)	M: 47.85%, F: 52.15%	63 (17-81)	N.R.	N.R.	0-3	-	Acute Myeloid Leukemia
Observational Retrospective										
Angel, 2021	32	16 (50.0%)	16 (100%)	M: 50%, F: 50%	57.8 (52-68.7)	N.R.	2 (IQR 2-3)	N.R.	-	NSCLC, breast, Colorectal, Pancreatic, Cholangiocarcinoma, Metastatic castration resistant prostate, Urothelial, CUP, sarcomas, head and neck, gynaecological
Slootbeek, 2022	38	32 (84.2%)	9 (28.1%)	M: 100%	Mean 69.0 (62.6-74.7)	N.R.	2 (0-6)	N.R.	Non-target therapy group	Prostate
Berclaz, 2023	215	102 (47.4%)	63 (61.8%)	F: 52.2%, M: 47.8%	49 (0-80)	85%	N.R.	N.R.	-	Bone and soft tissue sarcomas
Bitzer, 2020	89	15 (16.9%)	10 (66.7%)	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	Mean 2.8	N.R.	-	Gynaecological
Burkard, 2017	96	41 (42.7%)	25 (61.0%)	F: 39%, M: 61%	Mean 57 (33-88)	N.R.	2 (0-5)	N.R.	-	Lung, Gynaecological, breast, others

Dorman, 2023	149	95 (63.8%)	3 (3.2%)	M: 37%, F: 63%	62 (29-83)	Metastatic: 60% Resectable or locally advanced disease: 37% Missing: 3%	N.R.	N.R.	Patients at the same comprehensive cancer center	Pancreatic
El Helali, 2023	122	122 (100%)	77 (63.1%)	M: 52.5%, F: 47.5%	Mean 60 (11-95)	N.R.	3 (2-4)	N.R.	Not implemented MTB recommendation	Primary central nervous system, hepato-biliary-pancreatic, thoracic, Breast, Endocrine, Gastrointestinal, Genitourinary, Gynecologic, Head & Neck, Hepato Biliary, pediatric, CNS, Sarcoma, thoracic, unknown origin.
Fukada, 2023	713	285 (40.0%)	45 (15.8%)	M: 45.7%, F: 54.3%	58 (12-85)	26.6%	N.R.	N.R.	Absence of treatment recommendations by the MTB	Colorectal, Pancreas, Ovary, Breast, Biliary tract, Uterine, Soft tissue sarcoma, Stomach, Lung, Esophagus, Head and neck, Prostate, CUP, Thyroid gland, Urothelium, Other
Gambardella, 2021	98	32 (32.7%)	24 (75.0%)	M: 33.7%, F: 66.3%	Mean 59 (25-81)	N.R.	1	0: 23%, 1: 61%, 2: 14%	Assigned to receive standard therapy	Breast, Gynaecological, Lung, Digestive, Head and Neck, Skin, Others
Giacomini, 2023	124	39 (31.5%)	22 (56.4%)	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	2	N.R.	-	Breast carcinoma, NSCLC, colorectal carcinoma, brain, sarcoma, melanoma, multiple cancers, pancreatic, ovarian, gastric, renal carcinoma, leukemia, medullary thyroid, salivary gland carcinoma, biliary carcinoma, holangiocarcinoma, larynx carcinoma, neuroblastoma, paraganglioma
Hoefflin, 2018	198	104 (52.5%)	33 (31.7%)	M: 57,6%, F: 42,4%	58 (1-85)	77.3%	Mean 2 (1-11)	N.R.	Recommenda- tions not persued / No- recommendation	Soft tissue, CNS 22, CUP, Colorectal, Urogenital, Thyroid, Breast, Lung, Hepatobiliary, Skin, Upper Gynaecological tract, Hematologic, Neuroendocrine, Pediatric, Head and neck, Others
Hoefflin, 2021	488	264 (54.1%)	76 (28.8%)	M: 52.9%, F: 47.1%	Mean 54 (1-88)	77.3%	2.1 (0-12)	N.R.	Recommenda- tions not persued / No- recommendation	Lower GI tract, Pancreas, Upper GI tract, Central nervous system, CUP, Hepatobiliary, Thyroid, Soft tissue and bone, Gynaecological (others), Head and neck, Breast, Urogenital, Ovary, Dermatologic, Hematologic, Lung, Neuroendocrine, Other
Ida H., 2022	418	196 (46.9%)	51 (26.0%)	M: 51.7%, F: 48.3%	57 (3-86)	40%	≤ 2 65.1%, ≥ 3 34.9%	0-1: 97.4%	Patients without druggable alterations / Patients with druggable alterations who	Colorectal, lung, soft tissue sarcoma, others

									didn't receive matched therapy	
Kaderbhai, 2016	50	29 (58.0%)	9 (31.0%)	M: 48%, F: 52%	62.7 (20-79)	100%	2.3 (1-7)	N.R.	-	Lung
Kato, S., 2020	715	429 (60.0%)	265 (61.8%)	M: 41.3%, F: 58.7%	61 (3-92)	N.R.	≥3: 47.6%, <3: 52.4%	N.R.	Part of medical recommendations implemented / No medical recommendations implemented	Breast, colorectal, hematologic malignancies, gastroesophageal and pancreatic
Koopman, 2020	129	59 (53.6%)	25 (42.4%)	M: 34,5%, F: 52,7%, NA: 12,7%	68 (36-89)	N.R.	0: 68.2%, ≥ 1 31.8%	N.R.	-	NSCLC, non-NSCLC cases, Colorectal, Melanoma, Endometrial, CUP
Niogret J., 2021	281	209 (74.4%)	66 (31.6%)	M: 62.6%, F: 37.4%	64 (20-87)	37.4%	1	N.R.	Non-LNGS-based therapy	Lung
Parker, 2015	43	43 (100%)	17 (39.5%)	F: 100%	Mean 59 (55.71-62.29)	100%	3 (1-13)	N.R.	-	Breast
Repetto, 2023	251	194 (77.3%)	76 (39.2%)	M: 39.8%, F: 60.2%	Mean 54	N.R.	Median: 2, <3: 66.1%	0: 61.8%, 1: 32.9%, 2: 1.3%	Non-MTB-assigned treatments	Breast, lung and 24 other types
Schwaederle, 2014	34	12 (35.3%)	12 (100%)	M: 21%, F: 79%	56 (29-75)	N.R.	Mean 3 (1-13)	N.R.	-	Breast, gastrointestinal, head and neck, lung, other (epithelioid sarcoma, myoepithelial carcinoma, paraganglioma, CUP).
Shaya, 2023	N.A.	N.A.	18	M: 38.9%, F: 61.1%	67 (47-84)	88.9%	1.5 (0-4)	0-2	-	Pancreatic
Trivedi, 2019	54	44 (81.5%)	12 (27.3%)	M: 31%, F: 69%	64 (37-82)	N.R.	Median: 2, Mean 2.39 (1-18) 1: 26%, 2: 33%, 3: 26%, 4: 9%, 5: 2%, 6: 4%	N.R.	-	Gynecological, breast, NSCLC, CRC, other
Weiss, 2023	61	29 (47.5%)	4 (13.8%)	M: 57.4%, F: 42.6%	60 (23-85)	N.R.	1 (0-4) 0: 23.0%, 1: 41.0%, 2: 11.5%, 3: 4.9%, 4: 1.6%	N.R.	-	CUP

Zhang D., 2023	153	71 (46.4%)	14 (19.7%)	M: 47.1%, F: 52.9%	62 (24-81)	N.R.	1 (0-6) 0: 5.3%, 1: 55.8%, 2: 28.3%, 3: 7.1%, 4: 2.7%, 6: 0.9%	N.R.	No targeted treatment	Biliary tract
Tarawneh T., 2022	100	78 (75.0%)	33 (42.0%)	M: 50%, F: 50%	Mean 57,5	Metastatic: 96.1% Localized: 2.9% Locally advanced: 1.0%	3 (0-14) 0: 1.0%, 1: 12.5%, 2: 31.7%, 3: 24.0%, >3: 30.8%	N.R.	Non Matched therapy	Lower Gynaecological tract, Neuroendocrine neoplasms, Sarcoma, Head and neck, Hepatobiliary, CUP, Pancreato, biliary, Breast, Ovary, Thoracic malignancies, Upper GI tract, Gynecologic (non- ovarian), Germ cell tumor, Embryonal (Neuroblastoma)

N.R. = Not Reported, M = Male, F = Female, CUP = cancer of unknow primary, NSCLC = Non-small cell lung carcinoma, SNC = Central Nervous System

Supplementary table 11. Outcome on meta-analysed in the studies.

Study	Sample size	Median OS (months)	Median PFS (months)	Response rate information
RCT				
Schneider, 2021	71	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.
Le Tourneau, 2015	195	N.R.	2.3 (95% CI 1.7–3.8)	N.R.
Belin, 2017	70	N.R.	2.1 (95% CI 2.0-3.8)	ORR 1 (1.4% (95% CI 0%-4.2%))
Andre, 2022	238	28.8 (95% CI 27.0-32.4)	24.7 (95% CI 17.9-30.6)	N.R.
Botticelli, 2024	200	N.R.	3.7	N.R.
Non-Randomized Clinical Trial				
Bertucci, 2021	94	8.1 (95% CI 6.2–12.2)	N.R.	CR 2 (2%), PR 15 (17%) SD 14 (16%), PD 58 (65%), ORR 17 (19% (95% CI 12–29)), DCR 31 (35% (95% CI 25–46))
Billon, 2022	64	N.R.	N.R.	CR 1/12 (8%), PR 3/12 (25%), DCR 58% (95% CI 28%-85%)
Debien, 2023	49	N.R.	9.9	N.R.
Hlevjak, 2021	64	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.
Miller, 2022	93	768 days (range 22-1240)	449 days (range 42-1125)	N.R.
Ladekarl, 2023	15	N.R.	N.R.	ORR 6 (40%), PR 5 (33.3%), CR 1 (6.7%)
Louie, 2022	34	9.3 (95% CI 3.9–14.7)	3.9 (95% CI 1.3–6.5)	CB 13/32 (41%)
Martin-Romano, 2022	136	13.9 (95% CI 12.7-N.E.)	4.6 (95% CI 3.8-6.1)	PR 36 (26%), SD 46 (34%), PD 54 (40%)
Reda, 2020	79	N.R.	2.5 (95% CI 2.2-3.7)	N.R.
Varnier, 2019	38	15.6 mnths (95% CI 6.6–33)	2.7 (95% CI 2.3–4.7)	PR 8 (21%), SD 10 (26%), CB 18 (47%)
Sicklick, 2019	83	8.5	6.5	N.R.
Massard, 2017	193	N.R.	N.R.	ORR 11% (95% CI 7%–17%)

Observational Prospective				
Dalton, 2017	24	N.R.	5 (95% CI 2.9-N.E.)	N.R.
Charo, 2022	61	17.1 (95% CI 10.1-24.1)	9.3 (95% CI 8.0-10.6)	N.R.
Horak, 2021	362	10.4 (9.2–11.6)	N.R.	ORR 87 (23.9%), DCR 201 (55.3%)
Huang B, 2021	77	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.
Kikuchi, 2021	21	N.R.	N.R.	ORR 6 (29%), DCR 14 (67%)
Pinet, 2023	13	13 (95% CI 13.0–N.E.)	N.R.	N.R.
Powell, 2018	39	44.8 weeks GMCT, 35.6 weeks FDA	GMCT 14.9 weeks, FDA 25.0 weeks	ORR 5 (12.8%), SD 14 (35.9%), PD 13 (33.3%), DCR 10 (25.6%)
Renovanz, 2023	86	33 (range 8– 271)	3.3 (range 0.04–30.9)	PD 70 (81.4%)
Rodriguez-Rodriguez, 2018	25	N.R.	N.R.	CR, PR, SD, or CB 16/23 (70%)
Scheiter, 2022	47	11.90	4.20	PR 7 (29.8%), MR 1 (2.6%), SD 1 (29.0%), PD 19 (50.0%), CB 50%
Sultova, 2021	16	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.
Malani, 2022	37	7.5 months (14 days–4.7+ years)	N.R.	ORR 22 (59%)
Observational Retrospective				
Angel, 2021	16	N.R.	15.25	SD 4 (25%), PR 5 (31.3%), PD 7 (43.8%)
Slootbeek, 2022	63	19.0 (IQR 14.7–23.2)	5.3 (95% CI 3.5–7.1)	ORR 20/52 (38.5%), PD 18/52 (34.6%), CR 2/52 (3.9%), SD 22/52 (42.3%), PD 10/52 (19.2%)
Berclaz, 2023	10	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.
Bitzer, 2020	25	5.2 (95% CI 0.1- N.E.)	2.8 (95% CI 1.0-9.0)	PR 3/20 (15%), SD 6/20 (30%), PD 11 (55%)
Burkard, 2017	9	N.R.	N.R.	ORR 17%, CB 38%
Dorman, 2023	165	synchronous metastatic disease 14.1 (95% CI 10.4–17.8), without metastases 24.6 (95% CI 20.4–28.8)	N.R.	N.R.
El Helali, 2023	77	12.2 (95% CI 9.9–16.3)	N.R.	ORR 22 (28.6%), CR 6 (7.8%), PR 16 (20.8%), SD 28 (36.3%), PD 27 (35.1%), DCR 50 (65.0%)

Fukkada, 2023	45	18.0 (95% CI 7.9–28.1)	N.R.	PR 16 (35.6%), SD 10 (22.2%), PD 17 (37.8%), NE 2 (4.4%)
Gambardella, 2021	32	N.R.	6.47	PD 10 (31.3%)
Giacomini, 2023	22	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.
Hoefflin, 2018	198	8 (95% CI 3-10)	N.R.	PR 11/33 (33.3%), SD 8/33 (24.2%), DCR 14 (7.1%)
Hoefflin, 2021	73	18 (95% CI 11-30)	N.R.	ORR 4.5% (22/488), 19 SD (25.0%), 17 PR (22.4%), 5 CR (6.6%), DCR 41/488 (8.4%)
Ida H., 2022	51	Not reached (95% CI 12.9–N.E.)	N.R.	N.R.
Kaderbhai, 2016	9	N.R.	4.5	4 PR for at least 4 months.
Kato, S., 2020	265	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.
Koopman, 2020	25	10.4 (IQR 6.3-14.6)	6.3 (IQR 3.2-10.6)	PR or CR 14/21 (67%), SD 3/21 (14%), PD 2/21 (10%)
Niogret J., 2021	66	N.R.	N.R.	CR, PR, or SD 40 (61.5%)
Parker, 2015	17	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.
Repetto, 2023	76	35.1 (95% CI N.E.)	5.8 (95% CI 4.1-7.5)	ORR 25/67 (37.3%)
Schwaederle, 2014	12	N.R.	N.R.	SD 4/11 (36.4%), PD 4/11 (36.4%)
Shaya, 2023	18	4.8 (95% CI: 2.9 - 6.7)	1.9 (95% CI 1.3 - 2.4)	CB 5 (27.8%)
Trivedi, 2019	12	N.R.	N.R.	SD 9 (66.7%), PD 3 (33.3%)
Weiss, 2023	4	N.R.	9 (range 1–19)	N.R.
Zhang D., 2023	14	19 (95% CI 4.86–33.14)	N.R.	N.R.
Tarawneh T., 2022	33	N.R.	4.3	No benefit 9/30 (30%), minor benefit 11/30 (36.7%), major benefit 10/30 (33.3%)

N.R.
=
Not

Reported, N.E. = Not Estimable, ORR = Overall Response Rate, CR = Complete Response, PR = Partial Response, SD = Stable Disease, PD = Progressive Disease, CB = Clinical Benefit, NE = Not Evaluated, DCR = Disease Control Rate, MR = Mixed Response

Supplementary figure 1. Risk of Bias of RCT studies.

Supplementary table 12. Risk of bias of single arm studies

Study	Bias in selection of participants into the study	Bias in classification of interventions	Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Bias due to missing data	Bias in measurement of outcomes	Bias in selection of the reported result	Overall Bias
Berclaz, 2023	Serious	Low	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Serious
Giacomini, 2023	Serious	Low	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Serious
Horak, 2021	Serious	Low	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Serious
Miller, 2022	Serious	Low	Serious	Low	Low	Low	Serious
Parker, 2015	Serious	Low	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Serious
Renovanz, 2023	Serious	Low	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious

Sultova, 2021	Serious	Low	Serious	Low	Low	Moderate	Serious
Sicklick, 2019	Serious	Low	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Serious
Massard, 2017	Serious	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Serious

Supplementary table 5.2.6 Risk of bias of comparative studies

Study	Bias due to confounding	Bias in selection of participants into the study	Bias in classification of interventions	Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Bias due to missing data	Bias in measurement of outcomes	Bias in selection of the reported result	Overall Bias
Bertucci, 2021	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
Hlevjak, 2021	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Serious	Low	Low	Serious
Reda, 2020	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Varnier, 2019	Low	Low	Low	Serious	Serious	Low	Low	Serious
Louie, 2022	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
Billon, 2022	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
Huang B, 2021	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Serious
Dalton, 2017	Serious	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Serious
Charo, 2022	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
Scheiter, 2022	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate
Sloutbeek, 2022	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious
El Helali, 2023	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious
Gambardella, 2021	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious

Hoefflin, 2018	Serious	Serious	Low	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious
Ida H., 2022	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious
Kato, S., 2020	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious
Pinet, 2023	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious
Niogret J., 2021	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
Repetto, 2023	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate
Zhang D., 2023	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
Tarawneh T., 2022	Low	Low	Moderate	Serious	Serious	Low	Low	Serious
Fukkada, 2023	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Moderate
Debien, 2023	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Low	Low	Serious	Serious
Dorman, 2023	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious

Supplementary table 13. Risk of bias of non-meta-analysed studies

Study	Bias due to confounding	Bias in selection of participants into the study	Bias in classification of interventions	Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Bias due to missing data	Bias in measurement of outcomes	Bias in selection of the reported result	Overall Bias
Hoefflin, 2021	Serious	Serious	Low	Serious	Serious	Low	Serious	Serious
Angel, 2021	NI	Critical	Serious	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Critical
Bitzer, 2020	NI	Serious	Low	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious
Burkard, 2017	NI	Serious	Low	Serious	Serious	Moderate	Moderate	Serious
Kaderbhai, 2016	NI	Serious	Serious	Serious	Serious	Low	Serious	Serious
Kikuchi, 2021	NI	Moderate	Moderate	Serious	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Serious
Koopman, 2020	NI	Serious	Low	Serious	Serious	Low	Low	Serious
Ladekarl, 2023	NI	Serious	Moderate	Serious	Serious	Low	Moderate	Serious
Martin-Romano, 2022	NI	Moderate	Low	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Serious
Malani, 2022	NI	Serious	Low	Serious	Serious	Low	Serious	Serious
Powell, 2018	NI	Moderate	Low	Serious	Moderate	Low	Low	Serious
Rodriguez-Rodriguez, 2018	NI	Serious	Low	Serious	Serious	Moderate	Low	Serious
Schwaederle, 2014	NI	Serious	Low	Serious	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Serious
Shaya, 2023	NI	Serious	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Serious
Trivedi, 2019	NI	Serious	Low	Serious	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Serious
Weiss, 2023	NI	Serious	Moderate	Critical	Moderate	Low	Serious	Critical

Supplementary table 14. Full list of items with consensus from the Delphi procedure.

Organizational aspects.

Item	Round
A specific figure, namely the referent clinician, should be appointed to present each case	Round 1
The referent clinician should be appointed before the MTB discussion	Round 1
A case submission tool should be employed. and the treating oncologist is expected to refer their patient through this platform	Round 1
Ideal time for MTB output (from discussion to therapy recommendation) should be less than two weeks	Round 1
Ideal Global TAT (meaning from testing to therapy recommendation) should be 28 days	Round 1
Whenever possible, MTBs should be held online to enhance accessibility to all available experts and to overcome logistical barriers	Round 1
The work of MTBs should be supported by technological systems that assist in clinical decision-making	Round 1
MTB meetings should include oncologists	Round 1
MTB meetings should include molecular Biologist/Biotechnologist	Round 1
MTB meetings should include pathologist	Round 1
MTB meetings should include medical Geneticist	Round 1
MTB meetings should include treating physician	Round 1
Medical records should include sample and patients' details	Round 1
Medical records should include molecular alterations	Round 1
Medical records should include actionability of molecular alterations	Round 1

Medical records should include clinical trials suggestions	Round 1
A clinical trial referred person (e.g. clinical trial navigators) should attend the MTB discussion	Round 2
Other professionals' specialties (including hematologists, endocrinologists, surgeons, etc.) may be included if relevant for the case. Such demands should be made by the referent physician.	Round 2
High-volume MTBs should meet weekly or at least biweekly	Round 2
Smaller MTBs should have flexible meeting schedules based on the number of cases submitted for discussion, ensuring they meet at least biweekly to guarantee reasonable TATs	Round 2
In medical report, actionability should be clearly divided into germline and somatic, with separate comments for each	Round 2

Testing.

Item	Round
NGS should be the leading sequencing choice for all the patients entering the MTB	Round 1
Databases to be consulted are the 1000 Genomes Browser, cBioPortal, ClinVar, COSMIC, dbSNP, Ensembl, JAX-CKB, OncoKB, and PubMed	Round 1
The panel should include genes listed in the ESCAT and OncoKB criteria, at least up to Tier IIIA for ESCAT and Tier 3B for OncoKB	Round 1
NGS testing could be outsourced to a certified external laboratory	Round 2

Inclusion criteria.

Item	Round
Metastatic and non-metastatic patients	Round 1
ECOG between 0 and 2	Round 1

Life expectancy ≥ 12 weeks	Round 1
Exhaustion of standard therapeutic lines according to the specific indications for each histology	Round 1
Rare diseases or specific histologies at diagnosis with limited therapeutic options	Round 1
Patients for whom there is no already known available therapy	Round 2
Patients with significant evidence of molecular actionability could be discussed by the MTB, even if they have not been yet treated with first line therapy or are not in therapeutic failure	Round 2

Clinical aspects.

Item	Round
Additional testing, including invasive testing, could be a possible recommendation of the MTBs	Round 1
Clinical trials inclusion should be one of the possible recommendations by the MTB	Round 1

9. References

- [1] Atkins D, Best D, Briss PA, Eccles M, Falck-Ytter Y, Flottorp S, Guyatt GH, Harbour RT, Haugh MC, Henry D, Hill S, Jaeschke R, Leng G, Liberati A, Magrini N, Mason J, Middleton P, Mrukowicz J, O'Connell D, Oxman AD, Phillips B, Schünemann HJ, Edejer T, Varonen H, Vist GE, Williams JW Jr, Zaza S; GRADE Working Group. Grading quality of evidence and strength of recommendations. *BMJ*. 2004 Jun 19;328(7454):1490. doi: 10.1136/bmj.328.7454.1490. PMID: 15205295; PMCID: PMC428525.
- [2] Guyatt GH, Oxman AD, Schünemann HJ, Tugwell P, Knottnerus A. GRADE guidelines: a new series of articles in the *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011 Apr;64(4):380-2. doi: 10.1016/j.jclinepi.2010.09.011. Epub 2010 Dec 24. PMID: 21185693.
- [3] Moberg J, Oxman AD, Rosenbaum S, Schünemann HJ, Guyatt G, Flottorp S, Glenton C, Lewin S, Morelli A, Rada G, Alonso-Coello P; GRADE Working Group. The GRADE Evidence to Decision (EtD) framework for health system and public health decisions. *Health Res Policy Syst*. 2018 May 29;16(1):45. doi: 10.1186/s12961-018-0320-2. PMID: 29843743; PMCID: PMC5975536.
- [4] Piggott T, Brozek J, Nowak A, Dietl H, Dietl B, Saz-Parkinson Z, Mirzayev F, González-Angulo L, Yepes-Nuñez JJ, Mustafa RA, Leontiadis GI, Brignardello-Petersen R, Alonso-Coello P, Schünemann HJ. Using GRADE evidence to decision frameworks to choose from multiple interventions. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2021 Feb;130:117-124. doi: 10.1016/j.jclinepi.2020.10.016. Epub 2020 Oct 28. PMID: 33127374.
- [5] Parmelli E, Amato L, Oxman AD, Alonso-Coello P, Brunetti M, Moberg J, Nonino F, Pregno S, Saitto C, Schünemann HJ, Davoli M; GRADE Working Group. GRADE EVIDENCE TO DECISION (EtD) FRAMEWORK FOR COVERAGE DECISIONS. *Int J Technol Assess Health Care*. 2017 Jan;33(2):176-182. doi: 10.1017/S0266462317000447. Epub 2017 Jun 28. PMID: 28655365.
- [6] Mavaddat, N., Michailidou, K., Dennis, J., Lush, M., Fachal, L., Lee, A., ... & MacInnis, R. J. (2019). Polygenic risk scores for prediction of breast cancer and breast cancer subtypes. *The American Journal of Human Genetics*, 104(1), 21-34.
- [7] Roberts, E., Howell, S., & Evans, D. G. (2023). Polygenic risk scores and breast cancer risk prediction. *The Breast*, 67, 71-77.
- [8] Hovhannisyan, M., Zemankova, P., Nehasil, P., Matejkova, K., Borecka, M., Cerna, M., ... & Janatova, M. (2024). Population-specific validation and comparison of the performance of 77-and 313-variant polygenic risk scores for breast cancer risk prediction. *Cancer*, 130(17), 2978-2987.
- [9] Mars, N., Kerminen, S., Tamlander, M., Pirinen, M., Jakkula, E., Aaltonen, K., ... & Ripatti, S. (2024). Comprehensive inherited risk estimation for risk-based breast cancer screening in women. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 42(13), 1477-1487.
- [10] Huntley, C., Torr, B., Sud, A., Rowlands, C. F., Way, R., Snape, K., ... & Turnbull, C. (2023). Utility of polygenic risk scores in UK cancer screening: a modelling analysis. *The Lancet Oncology*, 24(6), 658-668.

- [11] Hanson H, Astiazaran-Symonds E, Amendola LM, et al. Management of Individuals With Germline Pathogenic/Likely Pathogenic Variants in CHEK2: A Clinical Practice Resource of the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics (ACMG). *Genetics in Medicine : Official Journal of the American College of Medical Genetics*. 2023;25(10):100870. doi:10.1016/j.gim.2023.100870.
- [12] Collister, J. A., Liu, X., Littlejohns, T. J., Cuzick, J., Clifton, L., & Hunter, D. J. (2024). Assessing the Value of Incorporating a Polygenic Risk Score with Nongenetic Factors for Predicting Breast Cancer Diagnosis in the UK Biobank. *Cancer Epidemiology, Biomarkers & Prevention*, 33(6), 812-820.
- [13] Sadee W, Wang D, Hartmann K, Toland AE. Pharmacogenomics: Driving Personalized Medicine. *Pharmacol Rev*. 2023 Jul;75(4):789-814. doi: 10.1124/pharmrev.122.000810. Epub 2023 Mar 16. PMID: 36927888; PMCID: PMC10289244.
- [14] Clift, A. K., Dodwell, D., Lord, S., Petrou, S., Brady, S. M., Collins, G. S., & Hippisley-Cox, J. (2022). The current status of risk-stratified breast screening. *British journal of cancer*, 126(4), 533-550.
- [15] Myers, E. R., Moorman, P., Gierisch, J. M., Havrilesky, L. J., Grimm, L. J., Ghatge, S., ... & Sanders, G. D. (2015). Benefits and harms of breast cancer screening: a systematic review. *Jama*, 314(15), 1615-1634.
- [16] Drukteinis, J. S., Mooney, B. P., Flowers, C. I., & Gatenby, R. A. (2013). Beyond mammography: new frontiers in breast cancer screening. *The American journal of medicine*, 126(6), 472-479.
- [17] Duffy, S. W., Tabár, L., Yen, A. M. F., Dean, P. B., Smith, R. A., Jonsson, H., ... & Chen, T. H. H. (2020). Mammography screening reduces rates of advanced and fatal breast cancers: Results in 549,091 women. *Cancer*, 126(13), 2971-2979.
- [18] Shieh, Y., Eklund, M., Madlensky, L., Sawyer, S. D., Thompson, C. K., Stover Fiscalini, A., ... & Athena Breast Health Network Investigators. (2017). Breast cancer screening in the precision medicine era: risk-based screening in a population-based trial. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 109(5), djw290.
- [19] Onega, T., Beaber, E. F., Sprague, B. L., Barlow, W. E., Haas, J. S., Tosteson, A. N., ... & Conant, E. F. (2014). Breast cancer screening in an era of personalized regimens: A conceptual model and National Cancer Institute initiative for risk-based and preference-based approaches at a population level. *Cancer*, 120(19), 2955-2964.
- [20] Women Informed to Screen Depending on Measures of Risk (Wisdom Study) (WISDOM) <https://www.clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT02620852>
- [21] My Personalized Breast Screening (MyPeBS) <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT03672331>
- [22] Brooks JD, Nabi HH, Andrulis IL, Antoniou AC, Chiquette J, Després P, Devilee P, Dorval M, Droit A, Easton DF, Eisen A, Eloy L, Fienberg S, Goldgar D, Hahnen E, Joly Y, Knoppers BM, Lofters A, Masson JY, Mittmann N, Paquette JS, Pashayan N, Schmutzler R, Stockley T, Tavtigian SV, Walker MJ, Wolfson M, Chiarelli AM, Simard J. Personalized Risk Assessment for Prevention and Early Detection of Breast Cancer:

Integration and Implementation (PERSPECTIVE I&I). *J Pers Med*. 2021 Jun 4;11(6):511. doi: 10.3390/jpm11060511. PMID: 34199804; PMCID: PMC8226444.

[23] Allweis, T. M., Hermann, N., Berenstein-Molho, R., & Guindy, M. (2021). Personalized screening for breast cancer: rationale, present practices, and future directions. *Annals of surgical oncology*, 28(8), 4306-4317.

[24] Pashayan N, Antoniou AC, Ivanus U, Esserman LJ, Easton DF, French D, Sroczynski G, Hall P, Cuzick J, Evans DG, Simard J, Garcia-Closas M, Schmutzler R, Wegwarth O, Pharoah P, Moorthie S, De Montgolfier S, Baron C, Herceg Z, Turnbull C, Balleyguier C, Rossi PG, Wesseling J, Ritchie D, Tischkowitz M, Broeders M, Reisel D, Metspalu A, Callender T, de Koning H, Devilee P, Delaloge S, Schmidt MK, Widschwendter M. Personalized early detection and prevention of breast cancer: ENVISION consensus statement. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol*. 2020 Nov;17(11):687-705. doi: 10.1038/s41571-020-0388-9. Epub 2020 Jun 18. Erratum in: *Nat Rev Clin Oncol*. 2020 Nov;17(11):716. doi: 10.1038/s41571-020-0412-0. PMID: 32555420; PMCID: PMC7567644.

[25] Khera, A. V., Chaffin, M., Aragam, K. G., Haas, M. E., Roselli, C., Choi, S. H., ... & Kathiresan, S. (2018). Genome-wide polygenic scores for common diseases identify individuals with risk equivalent to monogenic mutations. *Nature Genetics*, 50(9), 1219-1224.

[26] Michailidou, K., Lindström, S., Dennis, J., Beesley, J., Hui, S., Kar, S., ... & Humphreys, K. (2017). Association analysis identifies 65 new breast cancer risk loci. *Nature*, 551(7678), 92-94.

[27] Martin, A. R., Kanai, M., Kamatani, Y., Okada, Y., Neale, B. M., & Daly, M. J. (2019). Current clinical use of polygenic scores will risk exacerbating health disparities. *Nature genetics*, 51(4), 584.

[28] Ruan, Y., Lin, Y. F., Feng, Y. C. A., Chen, C. Y., Lam, M., Guo, Z., ... & Ge, T. (2022). Improving polygenic prediction in ancestrally diverse populations. *Nature genetics*, 54(5), 573-580.

[29] Kullo, I. J., Conomos, M. P., Nelson, S. C., Adebamowo, S. N., Choudhury, A., Conti, D., ... & Wiley, L. (2024). The PRIMED Consortium: Reducing disparities in polygenic risk assessment. *The American Journal of Human Genetics*, 111(12), 2594-2606.

[30] Lennon, N. J., Kottyan, L. C., Kachulis, C., Abul-Husn, N. S., Arias, J., Belbin, G., ... & Kenny, E. E. (2024). Selection, optimization and validation of ten chronic disease polygenic risk scores for clinical implementation in diverse US populations. *Nature medicine*, 30(2), 480-487.

[31] Polygenic Risk Score Task Force of the International Common Disease Alliance. Responsible use of polygenic risk scores in the clinic: potential benefits, risks and gaps. *Nat Med* 27, 1876–1884 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-021-01549-6>

[32] Grebe, T. A., Khushf, G., Grealley, J. M., Turley, P., Foyouzi, N., Rabin-Havt, S., ... & Social, A. C. M. G. (2024). Clinical utility of polygenic risk scores for embryo selection: A points to consider statement of the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics (ACMG). *Genetics in Medicine*, 26(4), 101052.

- [33] Chowdhury, S., Dent, T., Pashayan, N., Hall, A., Lyratzopoulos, G., Hallowell, N., ... & Burton, H. (2013). Incorporating genomics into breast and prostate cancer screening: assessing the implications. *GeNeTICs in meDICINe*, 15(6), 423-432.
- [34] Schünemann, H. J., Wiercioch, W., Brozek, J., Etzeandía-Ikobaltzeta, I., Mustafa, R. A., Manja, V., ... & Akl, E. A. (2017). GRADE Evidence to Decision (EtD) frameworks for adoption, adaptation, and de novo development of trustworthy recommendations: GRADE-ADOLOPMENT. *Journal of clinical epidemiology*, 81, 101-110.
- [35] <https://training.cochrane.org/handbook/current/chapter-v> [Accessed 07 Nov 2023].
- [36] Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71.
- [37] Caro, J. J., Eddy, D. M., Kan, H., Kaltz, C., Patel, B., Eldessouki, R., & Briggs, A. H. (2014). Questionnaire to assess relevance and credibility of modeling studies for informing health care decision making: an ISPOR-AMCP-NPC Good Practice Task Force report. *Value in health*, 17(2), 174-182.
- [38] Andreoli, L., Peeters, H., Van Steen, K., & Dierickx, K. (2024). Polygenic risk scores in the clinic: a systematic review of stakeholders' perspectives, attitudes, and experiences. *European Journal of Human Genetics*, 1-15.
- [39] Liberati A, Altman DG, Tetzlaff J, Mulrow C, Gøtzsche PC, Ioannidis JPA, et al. The PRISMA statement for reporting systematic reviews and meta-analyses of studies that evaluate health care interventions: explanation and elaboration. *PLOS Med*. 2009;6:e1000100.
- [40] Hong QN, Fàbregues S, Bartlett G, Boardman F, Cargo M, Dagenais P, et al. The mixed methods appraisal tool (MMAT) version 2018 for information professionals and researchers. *Educ Inf*. 2018;34:285–91.
- [41] Andreoli, L., Peeters, H., Van Steen, K., & Dierickx, K. (2024). Taking the risk. A systematic review of ethical reasons and moral arguments in the clinical use of polygenic risk scores. *American Journal of Medical Genetics Part A*, 194(7), e63584.
- [42] Van Den Broek, J. J., Schechter, C. B., Van Ravesteyn, N. T., Janssens, A. C. J., Wolfson, M. C., Trentham-Dietz, A., ... & De Koning, H. J. (2021). Personalizing breast cancer screening based on polygenic risk and family history. *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 113(4), 434-442.
- [43] Pashayan, N., Morris, S., Gilbert, F. J., & Pharoah, P. D. (2018). Cost-effectiveness and benefit-to-harm ratio of risk-stratified screening for breast cancer: a life-table model. *JAMA oncology*, 4(11), 1504-1510.
- [44] Wong, J. Z. Y., Chai, J. H., Yeoh, Y. S., Mohamed Riza, N. K., Liu, J., Teo, Y. Y., ... & Hartman, M. (2021). Cost effectiveness analysis of a polygenic risk tailored breast cancer screening programme in Singapore. *BMC health services research*, 21(1), 379.

- [45] Yanes, T., Wallingford, C. K., Young, M. A., McInerney-Leo, A. M., Willis, A. M., McKnight, L., ... & James, P. A. (2023). Development and evaluation of a novel educational program for providers on the use of polygenic risk scores. *Genetics in Medicine*, 25(8), 100876.
- [46] Young, M. A., Forrest, L. E., Rasmussen, V. M., James, P., Mitchell, G., Sawyer, S. D., ... & Hallowell, N. (2018). Making sense of SNPs: women's understanding and experiences of receiving a personalized profile of their breast cancer risks. *Journal of Genetic Counseling*, 27, 702-708.
- [47] Chapman, C. R. (2023). Ethical, legal, and social implications of genetic risk prediction for multifactorial disease: a narrative review identifying concerns about interpretation and use of polygenic scores. *Journal of Community Genetics*, 14(5), 441-452.
- [48] Pashayan, N., Hall, A., Chowdhury, S., Dent, T., Pharoah, P. D. P., & Burton, H. (2013). Public health genomics and personalized prevention: lessons from the COGS project. *Journal of Internal Medicine*, 274(5), 451-456
- [49] Suckiel, S. A., Braganza, G. T., Aguiñiga, K. L., Odgis, J. A., Bonini, K. E., Kenny, E. E., ... & Abul-Husn, N. S. (2022). Perspectives of diverse Spanish-and English-speaking patients on the clinical use of polygenic risk scores. *Genetics in Medicine*, 24(6), 1217-1226.
- [50] Sierra, M. A., Wheeler, J. C., Devereux, L., Trainer, A. H., & Keogh, L. (2021). Exploring implementation of personal breast cancer risk assessments. *Journal of Personalized Medicine*, 11(10), 992.
- [51] Mars, N., Kerminen, S., Feng, Y. C. A., Kanai, M., Läll, K., Thomas, L. F., ... & Ripatti, S. (2022). Genome-wide risk prediction of common diseases across ancestries in one million people. *Cell Genomics*, 2(4).
- [52] Barreiro, R. A. S., Almeida, T. F., Gomes, C. S., Monfardini, F., Farias, A. A., Tunes, G. C., ... & Naslavsky, M. S. (2022). Assessing the risk stratification of breast cancer polygenic risk scores in two Brazilian samples. *medRxiv*, 2022-09.
- [53] Ho, W. K., Tan, M. M., Mavaddat, N., Tai, M. C., Mariapun, S., Li, J., ... & Antoniou, A. C. (2020). European polygenic risk score for prediction of breast cancer shows similar performance in Asian women. *Nature communications*, 11(1), 3833.
- [54] Ho, W. K., Tai, M. C., Dennis, J., Shu, X., Li, J., Ho, P. J., ... & BioBank Japan Project. (2022). Polygenic risk scores for prediction of breast cancer risk in Asian populations. *Genetics in Medicine*, 24(3), 586-600.
- [55] Hurson, A. N., Pal Choudhury, P., Gao, C., Hüsing, A., Eriksson, M., Shi, M., ... & B-CAST Risk Modelling Group. (2021). Prospective evaluation of a breast-cancer risk model integrating classical risk factors and polygenic risk in 15 cohorts from six countries. *International journal of epidemiology*, 50(6), 1897-1911.
- [56] Lewis, A. C., & Green, R. C. (2021). Polygenic risk scores in the clinic: new perspectives needed on familiar ethical issues. *Genome Medicine*, 13(1), 14.

- [57] Manrique de Lara, A., Soto-Gómez, L., Núñez-Acosta, E., Saruwatari-Zavala, G., & Rentería, M. E. (2019). Ethical issues in susceptibility genetic testing for late-onset neurodegenerative diseases. *American Journal of Medical Genetics Part B: Neuropsychiatric Genetics*, 180(8), 609-621.
- [58] Riddle, L., Joseph, G., Caruncho, M., Koenig, B. A., & James, J. E. (2023). The role of polygenic risk scores in breast cancer risk perception and decision-making. *Journal of Community Genetics*, 14(5), 489-501.
- [59] Yanes, T., Kaur, R., Meiser, B., Scheepers-Joynt, M., McInerny, S., Barlow-Stewart, K., ... & Young, M. A. (2020). Women's responses and understanding of polygenic breast cancer risk information. *Familial cancer*, 19, 297-306.
- [60] Laza-Vásquez, C., Martínez-Alonso, M., Forné-Izquierdo, C., Vilaplana-Mayoral, J., Cruz-Esteve, I., Sánchez-López, I., ... & Rué, M. (2022). Feasibility and acceptability of personalized breast cancer screening (DECIDO Study): a single-arm proof-of-concept trial. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(16), 10426.
- [61] Forrest, L. E., Sawyer, S. D., Hallowell, N., James, P. A., & Young, M. A. (2019). High-risk women's risk perception after receiving personalized polygenic breast cancer risk information. *Journal of Community Genetics*, 10, 197-206.
- [62] Gupta, K. D., Gregory, G., Meiser, B., Kaur, R., Scheepers-Joynt, M., McInerny, S., ... & Yanes, T. (2021). Communicating polygenic risk scores in the familial breast cancer clinic. *Patient education and counseling*, 104(10), 2512-2521.
- [63] Kaur, R., Meiser, B., Yanes, T., Young, M. A., Barlow-Stewart, K., Roscioli, T., ... & James, P. A. (2019). Development and pilot testing of a leaflet informing women with breast cancer about genomic testing for polygenic risk. *Familial Cancer*, 18, 147-152.
- [64] Corpas, M., & Fatumo, S. (2023). Generalisation of genomic findings and applications of polygenic risk scores. *BMC Medical Genomics*, 16(1), 175.
- [65] Ayoub, A., Lapointe, J., Nabi, H., & Pashayan, N. (2023). Risk-stratified breast cancer screening incorporating a polygenic risk score: A survey of UK general practitioners' knowledge and attitudes. *Genes*, 14(3), 732.
- [66] Willis, A. M., Smith, S. K., Meiser, B., James, P. A., Ballinger, M. L., Thomas, D. M., ... & Young, M. A. (2021). Influence of lived experience on risk perception among women who received a breast cancer polygenic risk score: 'Another piece of the pie'. *Journal of Genetic Counseling*, 30(3), 849-860.
- [67] Putt, S., Yanes, T., Meiser, B., Kaur, R., Fullerton, J. M., Barlow-Stewart, K., ... & Mitchell, P. B. (2020). Exploration of experiences with and understanding of polygenic risk scores for bipolar disorder. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 265, 342-350.
- [68] Saya, S., McIntosh, J. G., Winship, I. M., Milton, S., Clendenning, M., Kyriakides, M., ... & Emery, J. D. (2022). Informed choice and attitudes

- [69] Barreiro, R. A., de Almeida, T. F., Gomes, C., Monfardini, F., de Farias, A. A., Tunes, G. C., ... & Naslavsky, M. S. (2024). Assessing the Risk Stratification of Breast Cancer Polygenic Risk Scores in a Brazilian Cohort. *The Journal of Molecular Diagnostics*, 26(9), 825-831.
- [70] Brozek JL, Canelo-Aybar C, Akl EA, Bowen JM, Bucher J, Chiu WA, Cronin M, Djulbegovic B, Falavigna M, Guyatt GH, Gordon AA, Hilton Boon M, Hutubessy RCW, Joore MA, Katikireddi V, LaKind J, Langendam M, Manja V, Magnuson K, Mathioudakis AG, Meerpohl J, Mertz D, Mezencev R, Morgan R, Morgano GP, Mustafa R, O'Flaherty M, Patlewicz G, Riva JJ, Posso M, Rooney A, Schlosser PM, Schwartz L, Shemilt I, Tarride JE, Thayer KA, Tsaion K, Vale L, Wambaugh J, Wignall J, Williams A, Xie F, Zhang Y, Schünemann HJ; GRADE Working Group. GRADE Guidelines 30: the GRADE approach to assessing the certainty of modeled evidence-An overview in the context of health decision-making. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2021 Jan;129:138-150. doi: 10.1016/j.jclinepi.2020.09.018. Epub 2020 Sep 24. PMID: 32980429; PMCID: PMC8514123.
- [71] Markou A, Tzanikou E, Lianidou E. The potential of liquid biopsy in the management of cancer patients. *Semin Cancer Biol*. 2022 Sep;84:69–79.
- [72] Dyba T, Randi G, Bray F, Martos C, Giusti F, Nicholson N, et al. The European cancer burden in 2020: Incidence and mortality estimates for 40 countries and 25 major cancers. *Eur J Cancer*. 2021 Nov;157:308–47.
- [73] Bouvier AM, Jooste V, Sanchez-Perez MJ, Bento MJ, Rocha Rodrigues J, Marcos-Gragera R, et al. Differences in the management and survival of metastatic colorectal cancer in Europe. A population-based study. *Digestive and Liver Disease*. 2021 May;53(5):639–45.
- [74] Santucci C, Mignozzi S, Malvezzi M, Boffetta P, Collatuzzo G, Levi F, et al. European cancer mortality predictions for the year 2024 with focus on colorectal cancer. *Annals of Oncology*. 2024 Mar;35(3):308–16.
- [75] Henderson RH, French D, Maughan T, Adams R, Allemani C, Minicozzi P, et al. The economic burden of colorectal cancer across Europe: a population-based cost-of-illness study. *Lancet Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2021 Sep;6(9):709–22.
- [76] Ho HY, Chung KS (Kasey), Kan CM, Wong SC (Cesar). Liquid Biopsy in the Clinical Management of Cancers. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2024 Aug 6;25(16):8594.
- [77] Nikanjam M, Kato S, Kurzrock R. Liquid biopsy: current technology and clinical applications. *J Hematol Oncol*. 2022 Sep 12;15(1):131.
- [78] Malla M, Loree JM, Kasi PM, Parikh AR. Using Circulating Tumor DNA in Colorectal Cancer: Current and Evolving Practices. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*. 2022 Aug 20;40(24):2846–57.
- [79] Pascual J, Attard G, Bidard FC, Curigliano G, De Mattos-Arruda L, Diehn M, et al. ESMO recommendations on the use of circulating tumour DNA assays for patients with cancer: a report from the ESMO Precision Medicine Working Group. *Annals of Oncology*. 2022 Aug;33(8):750–68.

- [80] Patelli G, Mauri G, Tosi F, Amatu A, Bencardino K, Bonazzina E, et al. Circulating Tumor DNA to Drive Treatment in Metastatic Colorectal Cancer. *Clinical Cancer Research*. 2023 Nov 14;29(22):4530–9.
- [81] Procaccio L, Bergamo F, Daniel F, Rasola C, Munari G, Biason P, et al. A Real-World Application of Liquid Biopsy in Metastatic Colorectal Cancer: The Poseidon Study. *Cancers (Basel)*. 2021 Oct 13;13(20):5128.
- [82] Shitara K, Muro K, Watanabe J, Yamazaki K, Ohori H, Shiozawa M, et al. Baseline ctDNA gene alterations as a biomarker of survival after panitumumab and chemotherapy in metastatic colorectal cancer. *Nat Med*. 2024 Mar 12;30(3):730–9.
- [83] Ciardiello D, Boscolo Bielo L, Napolitano S, Martinelli E, Troiani T, Nicastro A, et al. Comprehensive genomic profiling by liquid biopsy captures tumor heterogeneity and identifies cancer vulnerabilities in patients with RAS/BRAF wild-type metastatic colorectal cancer in the CAPRI 2-GOIM trial. *Annals of Oncology*. 2024 Dec;35(12):1105–15.
- [84] Xie H, Kim RD. The Application of Circulating Tumor DNA in the Screening, Surveillance, and Treatment Monitoring of Colorectal Cancer. *Ann Surg Oncol*. 2021 Mar 9;28(3):1845–58.
- [85] Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices and repealing Directive 98/79/EC and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU [Internet]. 2017/746 European Commission; Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/746/oj/eng>
- [86] Guidance on general principles of clinical evidence for In Vitro Diagnostic medical devices (IVDs) [Internet]. Brussels; [cited 2024 Dec 10]. Available from: https://health.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-01/mdcg_2022-2_en.pdf
- [87] Oliner KS, Shiller M, Schmid P, Ratcliffe MJ, Schetter AJ, Tsao MS. Challenges to Innovation Arising from Current Companion Diagnostic Regulations and Suggestions for Improvements. *Clinical Cancer Research*. 2025 Mar 3;31(5):795–800.
- [88] Guardant Health 360CDx - Technical Information [Internet]. Guardantesi Health; [cited 2025 Jan 12]. Available from: <https://www.guardantcomplete.com/assets/pdf/Guardant360-CDx-Technical-Information-US.pdf>
- [89] Nakamura Y, Okamoto W, Kato T, Esaki T, Kato K, Komatsu Y, et al. Circulating tumor DNA-guided treatment with pertuzumab plus trastuzumab for HER2-amplified metastatic colorectal cancer: a phase 2 trial. *Nat Med*. 2021 Nov 11;27(11):1899–903.
- [90] Kim S, Lim Y, Kang JK, Kim HP, Roh H, Kim SY, et al. Dynamic changes in longitudinal circulating tumour DNA profile during metastatic colorectal cancer treatment. *Br J Cancer*. 2022 Sep 1;127(5):898–907.
- [91] Ghidini M, Hahne JC, Senti C, Heide T, Proszek PZ, Shaikh R, et al. Circulating Tumor DNA Dynamics and Clinical Outcome in Metastatic Colorectal Cancer Patients Undergoing Front-Line Chemotherapy. *Clinical Cancer Research*. 2025 Feb 17;31(4):707–18.

- [92] Vidal J, Fernández-Rodríguez MC, Casadevall D, García-Alfonso P, Páez D, Guix M, et al. Liquid Biopsy Detects Early Molecular Response and Predicts Benefit to First-Line Chemotherapy plus Cetuximab in Metastatic Colorectal Cancer: PLATFORM-B Study. *Clinical Cancer Research*. 2023 Jan 17;29(2):379–88.
- [93] Tie J, Kinde I, Wang Y, Wong HL, Roebert J, Christie M, et al. Circulating tumor DNA as an early marker of therapeutic response in patients with metastatic colorectal cancer. *Annals of Oncology*. 2015 Aug;26(8):1715–22.
- [94] Schøler L V., Reinert T, Ørntoft MBW, Kassentoft CG, Árnadóttir SS, Vang S, et al. Clinical Implications of Monitoring Circulating Tumor DNA in Patients with Colorectal Cancer. *Clinical Cancer Research*. 2017 Sep 15;23(18):5437–45.
- [95] Circulating DNA to Improve Outcome of Oncology Patients - COPE study [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2025 Mar 12]. Available from: [https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT04258137?term=Circulating%20DNA%20to%20Improve%20Outcome%20of%20Oncology%20Patient%20a%20Randomized%20study%20\(COPE\)&rank=1](https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT04258137?term=Circulating%20DNA%20to%20Improve%20Outcome%20of%20Oncology%20Patient%20a%20Randomized%20study%20(COPE)&rank=1)
- [96] Lee MJ, Hueniken K, Kuehne N, Lu L, Jiang SX, Id Said B, et al. <p>Cancer Patient-Reported Preferences and Knowledge for Liquid Biopsies and Blood Biomarkers at a Comprehensive Cancer Center</p>. *Cancer Manag Res*. 2020 Feb;Volume 12:1163–73.
- [97] Relton A, Collins A, Guttery DS, Gorsia DN, McDermott HJ, Moss EL. Patient acceptability of circulating tumour DNA testing in endometrial cancer follow-up. *Eur J Cancer Care (Engl)*. 2021 Jul 22;30(4).
- [98] De Giglio A, Orlando V, Andrini E, Ricciuti B, Lamberti G, Chiari R. Challenges in the management of advanced NSCLC among Italian oncologists: a 2019 national survey unfolds regional disparities. *Tumori Journal*. 2023 Feb 4;109(1):105–11.
- [99] Hedtke M, Pessoa Rejas R, Froelich MF, Ast V, Duda A, Mirbach L, et al. Liquid profiling of circulating tumor DNA in colorectal cancer: steps needed to achieve its full clinical value as standard care. *Mol Oncol*. 2022 May 20;16(10):2042–56.
- [100] Peng R, Zhang R, Li J. Continual Improvement of the Reliability of Next-Generation Sequencing-Based ctDNA Analysis: A Long-Term Comparison of ctDNA Detection in China. *Clin Chem*. 2022 Jul 3;68(7):940–52.
- [101] Alonso-Alconada L, Barbazan J, Candamio S, Falco JL, Anton C, Martin-Saborido C, et al. PrediCTC, liquid biopsy in precision oncology: a technology transfer experience in the Spanish health system. *Clinical and Translational Oncology*. 2018 May 20;20(5):630–8.
- [102] Vingiani A, Agnelli L, Duca M, Lorenzini D, Molecular Tumor Board as a Clinical Tool for Converting Molecular Data Into Real-World Patient Care. *JCO Precis Oncol*. 2023 Jul;7:e2300067. doi: 10.1200/PO.23.00067. PMID: 37487147; PMCID: PMC10581623.
- [103] Jain NM, Schmalz L, Cann C, et al. Framework for Implementing and Tracking a Molecular Tumor Board at a National Cancer Institute-Designated Comprehensive Cancer Center. *Oncologist*. 2021;26(11):e1962-e1970. doi:10.1002/onco.13936

- [104] Tsimberidou, A.M., Kahle, M., Vo, H.H. et al. Molecular tumour boards — current and future considerations for precision oncology. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol* 20, 843–863 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41571-023-00824-4>
- [105] Larson, K., Huang, B., Weiss, H. L., Hull, P. C., Westgate, P. M., Miller, R. W., Arnold, S. M., & Kolesar, J. M. (2021). Clinical Outcomes of Molecular Tumor Boards: A Systematic review. *JCO Precision Oncology*, 5, 1122–1132. <https://doi.org/10.1200/po.20.00495>
- [106] Pastò, B., Buzzatti, G., Schettino, C., Malapelle, U., Bergamini, A., De Angelis, C., Musacchio, L., Dieci, M.V., Kuhn, E., Lambertini, M., Passarelli, A., Toss, A., Farolfi, A., Roncato, R., Capoluongo, E., Vida, R., Pignata, S., Callari, M., Baldassarre, G., Bartoletti, M., Gerratana, L., Puglisi, F. Unlocking the potential of Molecular Tumor Boards: from cutting-edge data interpretation to innovative clinical pathways. *Crit Rev Oncol Hematol*. 2024 Jul;199:104379. doi: 10.1016/j.critrevonc.2024.104379. Epub 2024 May 7. PMID: 38718940.
- [107] Avci, C. B., Bagca, B. G., Shademan, B., Takanlou, L. S., Takanlou, M. S., & Nourazarian, A. (2025). Precision oncology: Using cancer genomics for targeted therapy advancements. *BBA - Reviews on Cancer*, 1880, 189250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbcan.2024.189250>
- [108] Pleasance, E., Bohm, A., Williamson, L.M., et al. Whole-genome and transcriptome analysis enhances precision cancer treatment options. *Ann Oncol*. 2022 Sep;33(9):939-949. doi: 10.1016/j.annonc.2022.05.522. Epub 2022 Jun 9. PMID: 35691590.
- [109] Akhoundova, D., Rubin, M.A.. Clinical application of advanced multi-omics tumor profiling: Shaping precision oncology of the future. *Cancer Cell*. 2022 Sep 12;40(9):920-938. doi: 10.1016/j.ccell.2022.08.011. Epub 2022 Sep 1. PMID: 36055231.
- [110] Edsjö, A., Holmquist, L., Georger, B., Nowak, F., Gomon, G., Alix-Panabières, C., Ploeger, C., Lassen, U., Le Tourneau, C., Lehtiö, J., Ott, P.A., von Deimling, A., Fröhling, S., Voest, E., Klauschen, F., Dienstmann, R., Alshibany, A., Siu, L.L., Stenzinger, A. Precision cancer medicine: Concepts, current practice, and future developments. *J Intern Med*. 2023 Oct;294(4):455-481. doi: 10.1111/joim.13709. Epub 2023 Aug 28. PMID: 37641393.
- [111] Yadav, D., Patil-Takbhate, B., Khandagale, A., Bhawalkar, J., Tripathy, S., Khopkar-Kale, P. Next-Generation sequencing transforming clinical practice and precision medicine. *Clin Chim Acta*. 2023 Nov 1;551:117568. doi: 10.1016/j.cca.2023.117568. Epub 2023 Oct 13. PMID: 37839516.
- [112] Schwaederle M, Parker BA, Schwab RB, et al. Molecular tumor board: the University of California-San Diego Moores Cancer Center experience. *Oncologist*. 2014;19(6):631-636. doi:10.1634/theoncologist.2013-0405
- [113] Russo, L., Giacobini, E., Osti, T., Cacciuttolo, M. G., Pastorino, R., & Boccia, S. (2024, December 20). Molecular Tumor Boards clinical utility and impact on patient care: a systematic review and meta-analysis. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/PR3TF>
- [114] Sterne JAC, Savović J, Page MJ, Elbers RG, Blencowe NS, Boutron I, Cates CJ, Cheng H-Y, Corbett MS, Eldridge SM, Hernán MA, Hopewell S, Hróbjartsson A, Junqueira DR, Jüni P, Kirkham JJ, Lasserson T, Li T, McAleenan A, Reeves BC, Shepperd S, Shrier I, Stewart LA, Tilling K, White IR, Whiting PF, Higgins JPT. RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials. *BMJ* 2019; 366: 14898

- [115] Sterne JAC, Hernán MA, Reeves BC, Savović J, Berkman ND, Viswanathan M, Henry D, Altman DG, Ansari MT, Boutron I, Carpenter JR, Chan AW, Churchill R, Deeks JJ, Hróbjartsson A, Kirkham J, Jüni P, Loke YK, Pigott TD, Ramsay CR, Regidor D, Rothstein HR, Sandhu L, Santaguida PL, Schünemann HJ, Shea B, Shrier I, Tugwell P, Turner L, Valentine JC, Waddington H, Waters E, Wells GA, Whiting PF, Higgins JPT. ROBINS-I: a tool for assessing risk of bias in non-randomized studies of interventions. *BMJ* 2016; 355; i4919; doi: 10.1136/bmj.i4919.
- [116] Tierney JF, Stewart LA, Ghersi D, Burdett S, Sydes MR. Practical methods for incorporating summary time-to-event data into meta-analysis. *Trials*. 2007;8:16. Published 2007 Jun 7. doi:10.1186/1745-6215-8-16
- [117] Lin, L.; Xu C. Arcsine-based transformations for meta-analysis of proportions: Pros, cons, and alternatives. *Health Sci Rep* 2020, 3(3), e178, doi: 10.1002/hsr2.178.
- [118] Higgins JPT, Thomas J, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, Welch VA. *Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of interventions*. Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions. 2019.
- [119] Viechtbauer, W. Bias and efficiency of meta-analytic variance estimators in the random-effects model. *Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics* 2005, 30, 261–93
- [120] Woodward M. *Epidemiology: Study Design and Data Analysis*. Chapman and Hall/CRC; 2013
- [121] *Annals of Oncology* (2024) 35 (suppl_2): 1-72. 10.1016/annonc/annonc1623
- [122] Hoefflin R, Geißler AL, Fritsch R, et al. Personalized Clinical Decision Making Through Implementation of a Molecular Tumor Board: A German Single-Center Experience. *JCO Precis Oncol*. 2018;2:PO.18.00105. Published 2018 Aug 16. doi:10.1200/PO.18.00105
- [123] Hoefflin R, Lazarou A, Hess ME, et al. Transitioning the Molecular Tumor Board from Proof of Concept to Clinical Routine: A German Single-Center Analysis. *Cancers (Basel)*. 2021;13(5):1151. Published 2021 Mar 8. doi:10.3390/cancers13051151
- [124] Giacomini P, Valenti F, Allegretti M, et al. The Molecular Tumor Board of the Regina Elena National Cancer Institute: from accrual to treatment in real-world. *J Transl Med*. 2023;21(1):725. Published 2023 Oct 16. doi:10.1186/s12967-023-04595-5
- [125] Berclaz LM, Burkhard-Meier A, Lange P, et al. Implementing precision oncology for sarcoma patients: the CCCLMU molecular tumor board experience. *J Cancer Res Clin Oncol*. 2023;149(15):13973-13983. doi:10.1007/s00432-023-05179-y
- [126] Charo LM, Eskander RN, Sicklick J, et al. Real-World Data From a Molecular Tumor Board: Improved Outcomes in Breast and Gynecologic Cancers Patients With Precision Medicine. *JCO Precis Oncol*. 2022;6:e2000508. doi:10.1200/PO.20.00508

- [127] Schneider BP, Jiang G, Ballinger TJ, et al. BRE12-158: A Postneoadjuvant, Randomized Phase II Trial of Personalized Therapy Versus Treatment of Physician's Choice for Patients With Residual Triple-Negative Breast Cancer. *J Clin Oncol*. 2022;40(4):345-355. doi:10.1200/JCO.21.01657
- [128] Hlevnjak M, Schulze M, Elgaafary S, et al. CATCH: A Prospective Precision Oncology Trial in Metastatic Breast Cancer. *JCO Precis Oncol*. 2021;5:PO.20.00248. Published 2021 Apr 22. doi:10.1200/PO.20.00248
- [129] Varnier R, Le Saux O, Chabaud S, et al. Actionable molecular alterations in advanced gynaecologic malignancies: updated results from the ProFiLER programme. *Eur J Cancer*. 2019;118:156-165. doi:10.1016/j.ejca.2019.06.017
- [130] Rodriguez-Rodriguez L, Hirshfield KM, Rojas V, et al. Use of comprehensive genomic profiling to direct point-of-care management of patients with gynecologic cancers. *Gynecol Oncol*. 2016;141(1):2-9. doi:10.1016/j.ygyno.2016.02.021
- [131] Sultova E, Westphalen CB, Jung A, et al. Implementation of Precision Oncology for Patients with Metastatic Breast Cancer in an Interdisciplinary MTB Setting. *Diagnostics (Basel)*. 2021;11(4):733. Published 2021 Apr 20. doi:10.3390/diagnostics11040733
- [132] Sloombeek PHJ, Kloots ISH, Smits M, et al. Impact of molecular tumour board discussion on targeted therapy allocation in advanced prostate cancer [published correction appears in *Br J Cancer*. 2022 Apr;126(7):1108. doi: 10.1038/s41416-022-01765-y.]. *Br J Cancer*. 2022;126(6):907-916. doi:10.1038/s41416-021-01663-9
- [133] Parker BA, Schwaederlé M, Scur MD, et al. Breast Cancer Experience of the Molecular Tumor Board at the University of California, San Diego Moores Cancer Center. *J Oncol Pract*. 2015;11(6):442-449. doi:10.1200/JOP.2015.004127
- [134] Andre, F., Filleron, T., Kamal, M. et al. Genomics to select treatment for patients with metastatic breast cancer. *Nature* 610, 343–348 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05068-3>
- [135] Le Tourneau C, Delord JP, Gonçalves A, et al. Molecularly targeted therapy based on tumour molecular profiling versus conventional therapy for advanced cancer (SHIVA): a multicentre, open-label, proof-of-concept, randomised, controlled phase 2 trial. *Lancet Oncol*. 2015;16(13):1324-1334. doi:10.1016/S1470-2045(15)00188-6
- [136] Belin L, Kamal M, Mauborgne C, et al. Randomized phase II trial comparing molecularly targeted therapy based on tumor molecular profiling versus conventional therapy in patients with refractory cancer: cross-over analysis from the SHIVA trial. *Ann Oncol*. 2017;28(3):590-596. doi:10.1093/annonc/mdw666
- [137] Malani D, Kumar A, Brück O, et al. Implementing a Functional Precision Medicine Tumor Board for Acute Myeloid Leukemia. *Cancer Discov*. 2022;12(2):388-401. doi:10.1158/2159-8290.CD-21-0410

- [138] Réda M, Richard C, Bertaut A, et al. Implementation and use of whole exome sequencing for metastatic solid cancer. *EBioMedicine*. 2020;51:102624. doi:10.1016/j.ebiom.2019.102624
- [139] Bertucci F, Gonçalves A, Guille A, et al. Prospective high-throughput genome profiling of advanced cancers: results of the PERMED-01 clinical trial. *Genome Med*. 2021;13(1):87. Published 2021 May 18. doi:10.1186/s13073-021-00897-9
- [140] Louie BH, Kato S, Kim KH, et al. Precision medicine-based therapies in advanced colorectal cancer: The University of California San Diego Molecular Tumor Board experience. *Mol Oncol*. 2022;16(13):2575-2584. doi:10.1002/1878-0261.13202
- [141] Billon E, Gravis G, Guille A, et al. Molecular Profiles of Advanced Urological Cancers in the PERMED-01 Precision Medicine Clinical Trial. *Cancers (Basel)*. 2022;14(9):2275. Published 2022 May 3. doi:10.3390/cancers14092275
- [142] Scheiter A, Hierl F, Lüke F, et al. Critical evaluation of molecular tumour board outcomes following 2 years of clinical practice in a Comprehensive Cancer Centre. *Br J Cancer*. 2023;128(6):1134-1147. doi:10.1038/s41416-022-02120-x
- [143] Niogret J, Dalens L, Truntzer C, et al. Does large NGS panel analysed using exome tumour sequencing improve the management of advanced non-small-cell lung cancers?. *Lung Cancer*. 2021;161:98-107. doi:10.1016/j.lungcan.2021.08.013
- [144] Repetto M, Crimini E, Boscolo Bielo L, et al. Molecular tumour board at European Institute of Oncology: Report of the first three year activity of an Italian precision oncology experience. *Eur J Cancer*. 2023;183:79-89. doi:10.1016/j.ejca.2023.01.019
- [145] Zhang D, Dorman K, Heinrich K, et al. A Retrospective Analysis of Biliary Tract Cancer Patients Presented to the Molecular Tumor Board at the Comprehensive Cancer Center Munich. *Target Oncol*. 2023;18(5):767-776. doi:10.1007/s11523-023-00985-3
- [146] Fukada I, Mori S, Hayashi N, et al. Prognostic impact of cancer genomic profile testing for advanced or metastatic solid tumors in clinical practice. *Cancer Sci*. 2023;114(12):4632-4642. doi:10.1111/cas.15993
- [147] Angel MO, Pupareli C, Soule T, et al. Implementation of a molecular tumour board in LATAM: the impact on treatment decisions for patients evaluated at Instituto Alexander Fleming, Argentina. *Ecancermedicalscience*. 2021;15:1312. Published 2021 Nov 1. doi:10.3332/ecancer.2021.1312
- [148] Weiss L, Heinrich K, Zhang D, et al. Cancer of unknown primary (CUP) through the lens of precision oncology: a single institution perspective. *J Cancer Res Clin Oncol*. 2023;149(11):8225-8234. doi:10.1007/s00432-023-04741-y
- [149] Niederberger M, K€oberich S, members of the DeWiss Network. Coming to consensus: the Delphi technique. *Eur J Cardiovasc Nurs* 2021;20:692–5.
- [150] Linstone HA and Turoff M, eds. *The Delphi-Method Techniques and Applications*. 2nd edition. Reading, Mass: New Jersey Institute of Technology; 2002.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.